

IDIMT-2025 ICT in Business: AI Everywhere? Glory and Disgrace of AI

33rd Interdisciplinary Information Management Talks

With pride we present the proceedings of the 33rd annual IDIMT Conference.

Artificial Intelligence continues to make impressive advances and almost every month a new system is presented. But does this translate into a proportionate use in business – and as a second step, business advantages? In this conference we investigate various aspects of new developments to ICT itself as well as its use for management and business processes and their transformation. Ethical and security aspects as well as specific application areas (teaching, autonomous vehicles, supply chain management, social media) are touched too, to obtain an encompassing view of the topic.

We have chosen the following 10 topics for 2025:

- Early Career & Student Showcase (Sonntag)
- AI in Crisis Management (Neubauer, Rainer)
- Cyber Security vs AI (Sonntag)
- Ethical Aspects of AI: Research and Usage (Lisnik)
- Data, AI and Digital-Driven Transformation: Shaping Sustainable Digital Futures (Pucihar)
- AI and Autonomous Systems (Schoitsch, Abdelkader)
- Business Information Systems and Digitalization (Doucek, Maryška)
- Social Media and AI: Contributor, Selector, ...? (Pavlíček)
- AI in Supply Chain Management (Delina)
- University-Industry Collaboration (Pitner)

Based on a double-blind two-step review process we have selected 43 of the submitted papers with a totality of more than 107 co-authors. The program ran in two parallel streams.

The authors come from 11 different countries: Armenia, Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Greece, Israel, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Ukraine.

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Hradec Králové, Czech Republic

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AI IN CRISIS MANAGEMENT

POTENTIALS AND CHALLENGES OF AI IN CRISIS MANAGEMENT ACROSS AUSTRIA AND EUROPE

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Artificial Intelligence; crisis management; responsible AI; AI literacy; AI governance

Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) holds great promise for improving how societies prepare for and respond to crises. Yet real-world implementation is far from straightforward. It is shaped by structural, regulatory, and ethical considerations that can constrain both AI's functionality and its adoption in high-stakes contexts. Drawing on recent Austrian research projects, this paper examines recurring challenges in AI-supported communication and decision-making in public health and crisis management. These include data fragmentation, lack of model interpretability, regulatory uncertainty, and insufficient stakeholder alignment. While rooted in the Austrian context, these challenges reflect broader patterns seen across Europe, particularly in light of evolving regulatory frameworks such as the EU AI Act. Addressing them requires more than technical innovation. It necessitates inclusive design, long-term institutional strategies, and strong ethical governance to align technological development with societal needs. The paper further positions AI literacy as a foundational capability for sustainable deployment, enabling informed engagement, accountability, and trust across all levels of adoption. When grounded in human-centred principles, AI systems can become a meaningful support in building resilience and responsiveness to future crises.

1. Introduction

Understanding how we engage with artificial intelligence begins with how well we understand it. Consequently, AI literacy forms the foundation for enabling individuals and institutions to critically engage with AI systems, fostering trust and informed decision-making (Kumar & Sangwan, 2024). This competence becomes particularly vital in high-stakes contexts, where its absence can lead to misinterpretation, misplaced trust, or missed opportunities, illustrating how AI may either support or undermine human judgement depending on how it is implemented (Eubanks, 2018).

Artificial intelligence is neither inherently good nor bad: its glory and disgrace are two sides of the same coin, shaped by how it is developed, governed, and applied. This perspective reflects broader academic discussions on aligning AI with societal goals while addressing ethical and operational risks (Vinuesa et al., 2020; Leslie, 2019). Research on AI during the COVID-19 pandemic (Rainer et al., 2024) illustrated its potential to enhance decision-making and public health coordination, while also exposing critical concerns around trust, transparency, and systemic fragility.

In a future public health crisis, an AI-based voice assistant might be deployed to support overloaded health hotlines. Designed to handle high call volumes and offer initial guidance, such a system could ease pressure on emergency response teams. Yet in stressful moments involving emotional or dialect-heavy speech, the AI may struggle to interpret inputs accurately or provide adequate support.

Drawing on insights from two Austrian research projects, KRISAN and ROADS, and prospective follow-up initiatives, this paper explores recurring technical, legal, ethical, and organisational challenges in applying AI. These project-level tensions reflect broader structural issues within Austria's research and policy landscape and serve to contextualise current European debates on AI in critical infrastructure and public health. AI literacy is introduced as a cross-cutting concern that fundamentally shapes understanding, trust, and the sustainable use of AI across sectors.

2. Applied AI in crisis management: lessons from Austrian research

Europe is increasingly at risk of future health crises due to global interconnectedness, demographic changes and climate change. Effective crisis management requires proactive coordination, data-informed decisions, and the integration of diverse systems and actors. AI has emerged as a promising tool to support these efforts, yet its application in practice reveals persistent limitations.

Recent Austrian research projects illustrate these challenges. KRISAN highlighted the technical complexity of deploying AI in real-time crisis communication (Hagendorn et al., 2024). ROADS, while not implementing AI directly, identified barriers to future applications, including fragmented data, limited model transparency, and unresolved legal and ethical issues (Rainer et al., 2023).

From concept to implementation, both projects demonstrate recurring frictions in AI application for crisis management. Anticipated follow-up approaches aim to mitigate these risks by addressing data fragmentation, algorithmic bias, limited model transparency, and regulatory misalignment. The aim is to establish the conditions for trustworthy, legally compliant, and socially responsive AI systems within Austria's public health and emergency infrastructures.

2.1 Crisis situations supported by an AI voice dialogue system: the KRISAN project

To support the health system in crises such as infectious outbreaks, the KRISAN project (<https://www.joanneum.at/digital/en/projects/krisan>) developed a conversational AI system designed to manage high call volumes while generating a dynamic situational overview, particularly in support of triage and call centre operations. The project covered two use cases: emergency transport coordination and pandemic-related call response (Hagendorn et al., 2024).

Built on the Cognigy conversational AI framework, the system integrated speech-to-text and text-to-speech (via Microsoft Azure) and accessed a medical facility database via a WebAPI. Large language model (LLM)-driven dialogue flows extracted caller intent and guided adaptive question pathways. Usability testing was conducted in multiple cycles with simulated users to iteratively improve the system. User feedback and call evaluations helped refine speech recognition and dialogue handling, particularly to address challenges such as dialects and limited digital literacy.

The project highlighted critical challenges in AI application. Although testing was not conducted in live emergencies, realistic scenarios exposed limitations in training data, operational readiness, and speech recognition reliability, particularly under conditions of dialect, urgency, and emotional stress. Legal and ethical obligations, including GDPR compliance and AI Act transparency, had to be addressed from the outset. Trust in the system depended on its explainability, fallback mechanisms, and operational resilience under uncertain conditions.

Future work will focus on enhancing explainability, multimodal robustness, and interoperability with emergency systems, aiming to develop adaptive AI agents grounded in trust-by-design principles and suited to high-stakes communication environments.

2.2 Evidence-based planning and AI potential for pandemic management: the ROADS project

While KRISAN focused on AI-supported communication in crisis management, the ROADS project (<https://www.ages.at/en/roads>) developed a demonstrator concept to support pandemic planning by aligning public health objectives with corresponding social measures.

Although AI was not yet applied, ROADS laid essential groundwork for future integration. The Austrian Ministry of Health and relevant stakeholders expressed interest in advancing the ROADS system into an AI-supported solution, recognising its potential to manage complex, high-volume data and strengthen evidence-based decision-making. The project also underscored the necessity of expert validation for any AI-supported outputs (Rainer et al., 2024). Based on legal, strategic, and policy analyses, ROADS introduced an expert-driven matching process to link strategic objectives to interventions, exposing challenges such as unclear strategic mandates, fragmented data sources, and limited institutional coordination (Rainer et al., 2023).

Two follow-up directions are under consideration: one targets adaptive AI integration for dynamic alignment of policy goals and real-time data, building on automated knowledge synthesis and cross-institutional data harmonisation (Fontes et al., 2023). The other addresses usability and stakeholder alignment, aiming to strengthen trust and legitimacy through co-design, interpretability, and iterative feedback loops (Rainer et al., 2023). Both directions prioritise expert validation and contextual sensitivity, ensuring that AI augments, rather than replaces, human judgement in future crisis response systems (Shneiderman, 2020).

3. Challenges in AI application across Austria and Europe

National projects such as KRISAN and ROADS illustrate recurring challenges in applying AI to crisis management. These include fragmented data environments, siloed research funding, and limited alignment between research capacities and regulatory demands in Austria. Similar difficulties persist across Europe, where short-term project cycles and low institutional readiness continue to obstruct long-term AI adoption (Gao & Janssen, 2022).

Regulatory frameworks within the European Union, especially the AI Act, are increasingly seen as a global benchmark for responsible AI governance (Stix, 2021). However, a growing gap remains between regulatory ambition and the practical implementation of research outcomes, particularly within public infrastructure. While research activity is accelerating globally, the institutional conditions required to translate AI innovation into sustainable public-sector applications are still maturing across much of Europe.

3.1 Common challenges at the national and European level

Strengthening alignment between institutional capacity, governance, and innovation strategies will be crucial for ensuring that AI systems contribute effectively and responsibly to crisis management. Table 1 outlines core implementation challenges from KRISAN and ROADS, alongside recurring patterns across the European AI landscape.

Source: (authors)

Table 1. Clustered challenges in AI implementation across Austria and Europe

challenge type	Austria (projects KRISAN and ROADS)	Europe (literature review)
technical	low explainability and interpretability limited reliability due to data instability limited speech recognition accuracy	fragmented innovation strategies lack of scalable, robust solutions (Serger et al., 2023)
legal and regulatory	real-time GDPR and AI Act compliance (see also GDPR, 2016; AI Act, 2024) unclear legal responsibilities in emergency use (Hagendorn et al., 2024)	gap between high-level AI principles and concrete, implementable policy actions misalignment in health and technological governance structures (Van Noordt & Medaglia, 2023)
ethical and organisational	gaps in transparency, trust, and accountability widen global inequalities lack of consistent organisational guidelines (BMKOES, 2023) inconsistent integration of ethics presence of gender bias	difficulty in translating ethical principles into actionable guidelines (Bird et al., 2020; González & Rampino, 2024; Kiseleva et al., 2022) siloes sectors prevent coordinated AI development (Starke et al., 2025)
systemic and environmental	short-term project funding vs. long-term application and adaptation needs lack of AI policy coherence unaddressed environmental impacts (Rainer et al., 2023)	structural funding constraints similar to Austrian issues intensive energy-use and high carbon emissions (Strubell et al., 2019)

3.2 Opportunities and risks of AI in crisis-related applications

The challenges summarised in Table 1, along with growing awareness among AI users of the need to address them proactively and holistically, form the basis for unlocking AI's potential in health-related crisis management. When such limitations are actively mitigated, artificial intelligence can support more responsible and context-sensitive applications. Conversely, overlooking these issues, or lacking the literacy to recognise them, may amplify existing risks.

Figure 1 presents a simplified overview of these opportunities and risks, drawing on insights from academic and institutional sources (Kelly et al., 2022; EPRS, 2023; WHO, 2023).

Figure 1. Core opportunities and risks of AI applicable to crisis management and decision support

Source: (authors, figure generated using napkin.ai)

These factors are relevant not only for technological development but also for regulatory coherence and institutional adoption across Europe. Opportunities such as increased operational efficiency, targeted automation, and system-level responsiveness have the potential to enhance decision-making and resource coordination in dynamic scenarios (Vinuesa et al., 2020). While AI can accelerate insights and support timely action, it also raises concerns about overreliance on automated outputs, reduced critical oversight, and the risk of human deference to system recommendations, particularly under time pressure or in emotionally charged situations (Leslie, 2019). Uneven implementation of data protection continues to affect public trust. Similarly, the impact of AI on labour markets remains contested, with debates ranging from role transformation to potential displacement.

4. Understanding and strengthening AI literacy

As AI systems become increasingly integrated into public life, AI literacy has emerged as a foundational competence for individuals and institutions navigating an increasingly automated world. It encompasses the ability to understand, evaluate, and interact meaningfully with AI systems. As defined by Long and Magerko (2020), this includes interpreting how algorithms function, assessing their outputs, and engaging critically with their limitations and potential biases. Building on this, Kumar and Sangwan (2024) conceptualise AI literacy as a prerequisite for responsible AI use, particularly in domains where trust, accountability, and societal impact are at stake.

In high-stakes environments such as crisis management and public health, AI literacy enables informed oversight and mitigates overreliance on opaque “black box” systems whose outputs might otherwise be accepted without question. Yet a persistent competence gap is evident among practitioners, including emergency responders and healthcare professionals, who often lack the training required to interpret or supervise AI tools effectively (Hassan et al., 2024).

This unmet need extends beyond institutional actors. As noted by Sun and Medaglia (2019) and Wolniak and Stecula (2024), limited AI awareness also affects the general public, including those directly impacted by crises, whose capacity to understand or challenge automated decisions remains

minimal. This lack of comprehension compounds existing digital divides, especially in vulnerable population groups (Saka, Hormiga, & Valls-Pasola, 2024). An important aspect of AI literacy is transparency in human-AI interaction. In public-facing systems such as crisis helplines or digital health triage systems, it is essential that users are explicitly informed when they are interacting with an AI rather than a human agent. Disclosure protocols and opt-out mechanisms help preserve user agency and trust. The consequences of low AI literacy extend beyond individual misunderstanding. It can weaken public trust (Aoki, 2020), reduce institutional transparency, and undermine ethical governance frameworks (Kuziemski & Misuraca, 2020). As Kholov and Mamarasulov (2025) argue, long-term AI deployment in public administration depends on sustained awareness and competence. Educational and embedded training programmes are essential to closing these competency gaps (Achanta, 2025).

Beyond formal training, everyday practices can help foster AI literacy among both professionals and the general public. One such practice is AI prompting – the act of interacting with systems through tailored inputs and queries. Prompting encourages exploration, facilitates gradual competence development, and fosters critical engagement with AI tools. While prompting was not a central concept in KRISAN, its structured dialogue flows illustrate how interaction design can foster user agency and foundational prompting skills, such as phrasing questions clearly, interpreting responses, and managing expectations. Moreover, normalising such interaction helps destigmatise AI use, reframing it not as a threat or novelty but as a tool that, when well understood, can empower individuals and support decision-making. Ultimately, strengthening AI literacy is not an optional add-on but a structural prerequisite for responsible, inclusive, and effective AI use in crisis management and beyond.

5. Conclusion and outlook

Despite promising advances in research and demonstrators, the broader-scale application of artificial intelligence in crisis management, particularly in public health, continues to face significant challenges. Technical opacity, fragmented data ecosystems, legal uncertainties, and low institutional readiness impair the responsible deployment of AI in high-stakes domains such as public health. These concerns underscore the need for more mature, adaptive, and transparent AI systems. At the same time, AI offers considerable potential to transform decision-making through faster data analysis, predictive modelling, and dynamic coordination. While KRISAN demonstrates applied use cases, ROADS provides strategic foundations for understanding how AI could be embedded into pandemic management. Together, they underscore the complexity of aligning AI with operational and strategic demands. Addressing these systemic and technical challenges also requires investment in human capabilities. Responsible innovation in AI depends on broad-based literacy that enables high-level decision-makers, practitioners, and citizens to understand, question, and apply AI systems effectively. Strengthening AI literacy across disciplines and institutions is vital. Structured prompting and hands-on engagement can provide accessible opportunities to build this capacity. Future efforts should prioritise interdisciplinary collaboration, long-term investment strategies, and cross-border coordination to address shared challenges.

With deliberate, context-sensitive governance and inclusive engagement, AI can become a powerful enabler rather than a risk factor in building resilient and equitable crisis response systems. Ultimately, the glory or disgrace of AI in crisis management is not intrinsic to the technology itself, but a reflection of the choices we make in how we develop, regulate, and apply these technologies in service of the public good.

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FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO SOCIAL VULNERABILITY TO VARIOUS HAZARDS IN EUROPEAN METROPOLITAN AREAS

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Abstract

Disasters tend to disproportionately impact individuals and communities with pre-existing social vulnerabilities. Assessing social vulnerability of areas, communities, or individuals, is not only essential for providing effective protection and care during disasters, but also for reducing vulnerabilities and enhancing resilience. In the context of the EU-funded project PANTHEON, a study was conducted which resulted in a list of possible social vulnerability indicators to assess the vulnerability of a community or of individuals to various hazards. These factors were specifically tailored to the European metropolises Paris, Athens, and Vienna. This paper will present the identified indicators and discuss their benefits for disaster risk management (DRM). Besides an extensive literature review, the development of the list was informed by expert interviews and expert surveys. The research resulted in a non-exhaustive list of 16 social vulnerability factors, covering life-stage-, health-, social-connection-, resource-, exposure-and-protection-, and knowledge-and-awareness-related vulnerabilities. This list of social vulnerability indicators could be used by researchers, disaster risk managers, and other stakeholders to evaluate social vulnerability at both individual and community levels to support targeted risk reduction and resilience-building efforts, potentially also using artificial intelligence (AI).

1. Introduction

This publication was adapted from the publicly available Deliverable D2.3 (Kainz et al., 2024) of the EU-funded project PANTHEON. The indicators were adapted and revised for the scope of this publication, which focuses on social vulnerability factors to disasters. PANTHEON aims to develop a community-based Smart City Digital Twin Platform for optimised DRM operations and enhanced community disaster resilience. Further information on the project can be found on the website (<https://pantheon-project.eu/>).

1.1 Vulnerability to hazards in the European context

Vulnerability is one of the key concepts in disaster research. It is defined by the United Nations as “conditions determined by physical, social, economic and environmental factors or processes which increase the susceptibility of an individual, a community, assets or systems to the impacts of hazards” (United Nations General Assembly, 2016, p. 24). When disasters occur, the extent of damage, casualties, and recovery capacity is heavily influenced by these factors (Choo & Yoon, 2024; Cutter, 1996). While there are many aspects that increase vulnerability, like physical, economic, or environmental factors, this study focuses on **social vulnerability** factors that make certain individuals and communities more susceptible to disaster impacts.

Disasters disproportionally affect those who are already in vulnerable situations, while also exacerbating existing vulnerabilities by disrupting livelihoods, healthcare access, or social support networks. In the past, DRM strategies have often overlooked the needs of vulnerable groups, but awareness of this issue has increased in recent years. The Council of Europe, for instance, emphasizes the need to address social vulnerabilities as part of DRM (Prieur, 2012). Several social groups are frequently listed in the literature as particularly vulnerable to disasters, including people with

disabilities, migrants, asylum seekers and refugees, children, the elderly, people living in poverty, and women (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2022; Council of Europe, n.d.; Dearden, 2017; Flanagan et al., 2011; Painter et al., 2024). However, vulnerability is context-dependent; for instance, while women are often at greater risk in hazard situations, there are cases where men may be more vulnerable, e.g. flooding (due to increased risk-taking behaviour) or road accidents (European Commission, 2022; Jonkman & Kelman, 2005).

1.2 Vulnerability indicators

Indicators are functions that map observable variables, such as the number of elderly residents in an area, to broader theoretical concepts, such as vulnerability to disasters. Generally, indicators are simple linear functions with monotonous increase or decrease. Since vulnerability is a theoretical concept that cannot be measured directly, vulnerability indicators make the concept operational instead of measuring it (Hinkel, 2011). Vulnerability indicators can be used to identify particularly vulnerable people, regions or sectors on a local scale (summarized in Hinkel, 2011). In the literature, different indices for measuring the social vulnerability to hazards can be found. For instance, Jublee and Saikat Kumar (2016) used principal component analysis to identify socioeconomic and infrastructure-related vulnerabilities in India, including the degree of homelessness and marginalization and the access to basic services. Similarly, Scheuer et al. (2011), who examined vulnerability to flooding in Leipzig, Germany, divided vulnerability into economic, social, and ecological factors. These categories included elements such as the number of children and elderly people, social and health care related infrastructure, and unemployment rate, in a particular area. Streifeneder et al. (2024) on the other hand, focusing on the COVID-19 pandemic in Austria, identified four categories: Biological susceptibility (health condition), generic susceptibility (including factors like age and living conditions), lack of capacity to anticipate (level of formal education), and lack of capacity to cope (including e.g. their access to health facilities).

Building on a combination of prior existing frameworks and expert opinions, this study aims to develop a list of **social vulnerability indicators** applicable to European metropolitan areas, based largely on data from **Athens, Paris, and Vienna**. These areas were chosen since they are the focus areas of the project PANTHEON.

2. Material and Methods

The indicators were derived through a methodology comprised of expert interviews, expert surveys, and an extensive literature review. To comply with the focus regions within the project PANTHEON, we focused on the areas of Athens, Paris, and Vienna, with some participants being from other areas in Greece, France, and Austria. Participants were recruited from two groups, namely *DRM Stakeholders* (Civil Protection Authorities, First Responders and emergency services, utilities and infrastructure providers, private companies, media, donors, governmental and policy making authorities) and *Community and citizen stakeholders* (local communities and citizens, NGOs/associations, charities, informal groups, particularly those working with vulnerable groups).

Based on literature research, a preselection was made of certain hazards that were considered relevant for the areas: Earthquake; Volcanic Eruption; Tsunami; Landslide; Heatwave; Storm; Blizzard; Flood; Drought; Wildfire; Epidemics/Pandemics; Technological accident; Cyber threat; Terrorist attack; and Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear and Explosive (CBRNe) malicious act.

Data collection for the survey and interviews took place between February and November 2023 using convenience sampling. Informed consent forms were signed before the interviews and integrated into

the questionnaire. In respect of ethics, the online survey, the interview guideline and the informed consent for participation were translated into Greek, French and German. Furthermore, most of the interviews were conducted in the native language of the interview partners. Answers were analysed in anonymous form using qualitative content analysis (Mayring, 2002) and descriptive statistics in IBM SPSS V 28.0.0.0 and Microsoft Excel 2016.

An online questionnaire was created in Greek, French, and German, and the link was sent to experts active in these regions via email. A total of 71 participants responded to the online questionnaire (19 partly, 52 fully filled out; 26 were from Greece, 13 from France, and 32 from Austria). Nearly half of the respondents (49.3%) were female, and the mean age was 44.8 years (SD = 11.8). Most participants (60.6%) were working in disaster management, with a majority working for an NGO or other social organisation (28.2%), in first response (21.1%), or academia and research (16.9%). Relevant questions for social vulnerability factors aimed to collect expert opinions on socially vulnerable groups, their vulnerability in different hazard situations as well as the status of and the potential for their involvement in disaster management and education. For instance, participants were asked to identify the top five hazards in their regions (using the preselected list of hazards mentioned before), and to list the groups they considered most vulnerable to these hazards and why.

In order to collect qualitative in addition to the quantitative survey data, eleven semi-structured interviews were conducted with three experts in Greece, four in France, and four in Austria. Almost half of the interview partners were female, and their age ranged between 31 and 66 years. Their expertise spanned diverse fields ranging from social sciences over work with the homeless to disaster management. The interview guideline included questions about the most relevant hazards in the interviewees' respective regions, the most relevant vulnerable groups to these hazards according to their experience, the reasons they considered them vulnerable, as well as whether they thought gender played a role in vulnerability. Seven interviews were conducted in oral form (online, via telephone, or in person) and four in written form via email.

3. Results

As a result of the literature research, the expert interviews and survey, a list of 16 possible factors covering social vulnerability to a wide range of hazards was created (see Table 1). In addition to reasons for why these groups are particularly vulnerable, the table also includes possible methods of quantification or operationalization of vulnerability for a certain area or community. The list was retrospectively clustered into six categories: life-stage-, health-, social-connection-, resource-, exposure-and-protection-, and knowledge-and-awareness-related vulnerabilities.

Table 1. Vulnerability indicators devised for Paris, Athens, and Vienna, in no particular order

Vulnerability Indicator	Reasons for vulnerability	Potential measurement
<i>Life-stage-related</i>		
Advanced age	Lack of capacity to respond to disasters, dependency on others, mobility problems	% of people over 65 years of age in the population (see e.g. Chou, 2004)
Young age	Lack of capacity to respond to disasters, dependency on others, mobility problems	% of people under 15 years of age in the population (see e.g. Chou, 2004)

Vulnerability Indicator	Reasons for vulnerability	Potential measurement
Family status	Care-giving responsibilities Financial resources	% of families with minor children in the population
<i>Health-related</i>		
Mental health	Lack of capacity to respond to disasters, dependency on others, possible problems with medication	% of people with mental disorder/disability/illness in the population
Physical health	Lack of capacity to respond to disasters, dependency on others, mobility problems, possible problems with medication	% of people with physical disorder/disability/illness in the population
Reduced Mobility	Complications during evacuation or concerning self-protection, can be a result of e.g. physical disability or a lack of means of transportation	% of people in the population with known mobility problems
Pregnancy	Mobility problems, possible health complications, teratogens	% of known pregnant persons in the population
<i>Social-connection-related</i>		
Migration background	Language barriers, possible insufficient social integration and awareness of local disaster management plans, living conditions and financial resources	% of first generation immigrant households, refugees and asylum seekers in the population
Language/communication barriers	Problems with communication between emergency services/official bodies and locals, vulnerability to misinformation	% of people with insufficient skills in the local language or the need of specific communication tools in the population
Social isolation	Lack of social network, lack of possible aid in case of problems	% of single-person households in the area
<i>Resource-related</i>		
Financial resources	Individual financial resources are needed to prepare for disasters as well as recover and rebuild after	Median income/inhabitants of households in the area
<i>Exposure- and protection-related</i>		
Increased exposure	Increased exposure of e.g., healthcare workers to pathogens, first responders to aftershocks, or homeless persons to the elements puts them at increased risk	% of population working and living in increased exposure (including people living in top-floor apartments for heatwaves, in basements and ground floors for floods, people living next to forests for wildfires, and homeless persons)

Vulnerability Indicator	Reasons for vulnerability	Potential measurement
Poor housing quality	Increased risk of collapse or damage, e.g., during earthquakes or floods, lack of protection, increased exposure	% of population living in houses with poor structural integrity and/or insufficient regulations
Special accommodations	Dependency on others, possible problems with mobility and evacuation, possible problems with heating and cooling, dependence on working infrastructure, electricity	% of people living or staying in special accommodations in the area (hospitals, prisons, care homes, homeless shelters and women's shelters...)
<i>Knowledge-and-awareness-related</i>		
Lack of disaster awareness or disaster education	Lack of knowledge about how best to behave in a disaster situation puts people at risk. Lack of awareness may also cause hazards, e.g in the case of man-made wildfires or other man-made hazards	Qualitative/Number of disaster preparedness trainings/education programs available per 1,000 inhabitants
Lack of familiarity with the environment/Local knowledge	E.g. tourists or new residents may be vulnerable due to unfamiliarity with the terrain, the local safety measures, and the local language	Qualitative/% of people without familiarity with the environment in the area during a typical day

Source: Sarah Kainz

4. Discussion

Social vulnerability is a complex topic. In this study, we attempted to provide an overview of different factors that lead to increased vulnerability for individuals and communities in a disaster situation, focusing on three European capital cities. These factors span various socioeconomic aspects, categorized into aspects of life stage, health, social connectedness, available resources, exposure and available protection, and knowledge and awareness. They can be used by researchers, disaster risk managers, and other stakeholders to support targeted risk reduction and resilience-building efforts.

All of these aspects should be taken into account in DRM processes, especially for groups experiencing multiple vulnerabilities and compounded risks, such as homeless persons. Many of these vulnerabilities can be reduced, increasing the resilience of individuals as well as of a community as a whole. For instance, exposure can be limited, protection can be improved, and knowledge and awareness can be increased through education and awareness campaigns. Other vulnerability factors, such as poverty, require systemic change independent of DRM processes in order to be reduced. In general, it is important to keep in mind that while vulnerabilities can be mitigated, they will never be completely eradicated. It will always be important to pay special attention to the needs of vulnerable groups in disaster situations to reduce their risks, e.g. by using inclusive language and communication channels, or by providing special accommodations and support in evacuation and recovery efforts (see e.g. Prieur, 2012). Vulnerabilities can be reduced by e.g. providing education and raising awareness (Muttarak & Lutz, 2014), or implementing disaster prevention measures tailored to the needs of vulnerable groups (Prieur, 2012). Multiple projects apart from PANTHEON tackle social

vulnerabilities by raising awareness and empowering communities., e.g. the EU-funded projects BuildERS (<https://buildersproject.eu/>) and C2IMPRESS (<https://www.c2impress.com/home>).

In the context of AI based models, vulnerability indicators are already used to influence the modelling of simulation systems. A recent example is the usage of vulnerability indicators in Spatial Dependency Risk Analysis, where it has already been shown to be of great value (Stergiopoulos et al., 2025). One implementation of this concept is the correlation of Heat Risk maps with data like population density and different vulnerabilities of citizens (e.g., age group below 14 and above 60, as per the IPCC recommendations; Kazerani & Winter, 2009). This analysis can be used to identify the most at-risk city blocks during heatwaves, proposing routing paths and efficient station points for first responders to aid in planning and preparedness of their deployments. For this purpose, it is crucial that the training data is unbiased and the people using the technology are well trained in its use.

While this study provides a broad overview on social vulnerability, it has several limitations. First, it must be noted that the list of factors is in no way exhaustive. Rather, it is a selection derived from an extensive literature review, expert interviews, and surveys, focusing on vulnerabilities most relevant to hazards in Athens, Paris, and Vienna. Some factors may be missing, particularly for hazards not covered in this study. Since we attempted to provide a general overview of vulnerabilities to a wide range of hazards, additional vulnerabilities to specific hazards, e.g. specific health vulnerabilities to epidemics, are not covered. In general, in order to be applicable to individual hazards, these indicators have to be adapted – e.g. not every factor in this leads to increased vulnerability to cyber attacks. It must be further noted that many of these factors overlap and interact, such as migration background and language barriers, or health-related issues and age. However, it is important to treat them as distinct factors to ensure that no critical aspects of vulnerability are overlooked.

One often-listed aspect not included in our list of indicators is gender. This decision resulted from the answers from our interview and survey partners and from the conflicting results from the literature. While women are often considered more vulnerable to disaster, sometimes the roles are reversed (European Commission, 2022; Jonkman & Kelman, 2005), which was also mentioned by our expert participants. Gender is therefore a complex aspect of vulnerability and cannot be adequately covered by a single index. Other groups, such as LGBTQIA+ persons, homeless persons, or unemployed persons, are also known to be more vulnerable, however this comes as a result of other factors like increased exposure or lack of resources (see e.g. Mann et al., 2024). Our list covers the underlying factors for vulnerability, and other groups may be vulnerable *because* of these factors. In order to expand on this list or verify its contents, we recommend systematic literature reviews, meta-analyses or analyses of data on past disasters. For use in other regions (e.g. within Europe), these factors should also be consolidated with further data collection like additional expert interviews.

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MATCHING NEEDS AND CAPABILITIES FOR PANDEMIC MANAGEMENT

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Pandemic management, matching, capability gaps, solutions, measures

Abstract

Whenever a disaster hits, it is imperative that practitioners and other involved stakeholders have access to the best possible capabilities when mastering the event. This is equally crucial for pandemic management. The systematic three tier approach presented in this paper – taxonomy, expert knowledge and metrics – enables systematic matching of gaps and potential solutions both on national as well as international level. This methodology offers several advantages, including reproducibility, comparability of solutions, and the potential to close capability gaps. This approach also allows for the expansion of the matching concept based on evolving end-user requirements. However, continuous involvement of practitioners and stakeholders is necessary to update needs and adapt the description of proposed capabilities. The dynamic nature of pandemics poses scalability challenges due to the limited availability of human resources to update and extend the knowledge base. This highlights the need for automated or semi-automated approaches, such as AI applications, to maintain a dynamic knowledge base.

1. Introduction

In the domain of crisis and disaster management (CDM), one of the central challenges is to find the best possible solutions for practitioners to bridge their capability gaps (DRIVER+, 2025). This challenge is closely related to how to best match the solutions with the capability gaps and associated needs. Depending on the type of challenge, a solution can be any tool or a combination of tools such

as hardware, IT tools or systems, concepts, methodologies or measures, whereas a gap reflects requirements from actors involved in crisis and disaster management acting at the operational, tactical or strategic level as well as from society or parts of the society.

In general terms, there are different potential approaches on how to combine gaps and solutions. Specific requirements and challenges can be identified case-by-case through direct questioning and involvement of stakeholders. Based on their feedback solutions can then be iteratively developed and adapted. This is a valid approach but has the shortcoming that knowledge about gaps of stakeholders might be lost after the development of a very use case specific solution. Moreover, this approach makes the comparison of different solutions difficult because the specified description of user requirements will vary considerably from case to case, even when the underlying capability gaps are quite similar. Collaborative platforms and networking organisations, such as CMINE (CMINE, 2025) or DCNA (DCNA, 2025) provide a test environment for the identification of practitioners needs and specification of requirements on solutions, but the arising concepts for matching of solutions and gaps are loose and only partially systematic. In a similar way, search engines as well as different AI applications can be applied to identify solutions for specific gaps (Roy et al, 2025). However, there is a lack of a unified methodology enabling reproducibility and comparability of solutions as well as gap – solution matching.

Several initiatives were made to ensure that crisis and disaster management stakeholders get the most suitable capabilities for their requirements. A common approach is the provision of repositories with descriptions of solutions such as the Disaster Risk Stakeholder Hub (DRSH, 2025), the Knowledge Hub from Emerging Planning College (EPC, 2025) or the CORDIS website with results from European projects (CORDIS, 2025). All these platforms have their merits, but they do not explicitly link gaps and solutions. To address this specific challenge, the Portfolio of Solution (PoS, 2025) was developed in the frame of the European project DRIVER+. The PoS is a platform designed as a knowledge management service enabling solution owners to present their solutions and compare them with other solutions. The system is mainly used to present solutions for operative practitioners with the potential to support them in tasks such as information exchange, management of resources, modelling, or provision of Common Operational Picture for decision support. A central feature of the platform is the possibility to describe use cases for the application of the solutions including one or more elements of a taxonomy of crisis management functions (Tagarev, 2020). Another module of the system is the Gaps Explorer enabling different types of crisis managers to describe their requirements in a similar way as the solutions also using the same taxonomy of crisis management functions. The use of the same elements of a common taxonomy makes it possible to identify potentially suitable solutions to close specific gaps specified by crisis managers and other stakeholders (for more details on matching using taxonomies see chapter 2.1).

Pandemic management and CDM are closely related. Similar to CDM, different types of stakeholders are involved in pandemic management such as first responders, employees of health care facilities, authorities and related agencies. In case of epidemics and pandemics these stakeholders are mandated to protect the society. For that purpose, different types of targets need to be reached, such as lowering of the infection rate, protecting vulnerable parts of the population or maintenance of medical services. The question arises what kind of measures or bundles of measures are best suited to reach the different types of targets on the strategic, tactical as well as operational levels of pandemic management (Rainer et al, 2023 & 2024). This question goes hand in hand with the need to assess the ability of measures such as lockdowns to fulfil requirements like the lowering of the reproduction rate. Within this paper we focus on decision support concepts for pandemic management, supporting stakeholders in the selection of adequate measures for targets arising during the management of epidemics or pandemics. This encompasses the analysis of different matching concepts as well as the description of a concept of a platform for decision support in pandemic management.

2. Matching concepts

In the frame of this paper, we discuss three concepts to match measures and targets of pandemic management that were applied within the Austrian national security project ROADS on decision support for pandemic management (Rainer et al, 2024, ROADS, 2025):

- Taxonomies
- Expert knowledge
- Metrics

The solutions tackled in ROADS are pandemic management measures that can be used at the operational, tactical, or strategic level, depending on the selected targets. The gaps intended to be closed are represented by single targets or bundles of targets arising during the management of pandemics such as protection of the vulnerable population.

2.1 Matching using taxonomies

An option for matching the needs and measures of national pandemic management is the development of a taxonomy of pandemic management functions. The matching process is very much based on the concept of the Portfolio of Solutions (PoS) (DRIVER+, 2025). In the PoS, the matching process links solutions (i.e. tools, software, processes, etc.) with one or more Crisis Management Functions (CMFs). This method was largely adapted in ROADS, with a key difference, namely

- The integration of (usually detrimental) secondary effects and necessary framework conditions are presented for each measure; a comparison of measures is also possible here.

Because it turned out that existing international taxonomies for crisis management as well as pandemic management were only partially suitable for the developed demonstrator, new pandemic management functions were developed to build a specific taxonomy of pandemic management functions.

The principle of matching relies on using the same taxonomy of pandemic management functions (PMFs) to describe both measures and objectives. Table 1 provides selected examples from the taxonomy of pandemic functions.

Table 1. Examples of elements of the taxonomy of pandemic functions from ROADS

Pandemic Management Function elements
Detection of pathogens
Assessment of the Reproduction Rate
Identification of the transmission path of diseases

Source: (authors)

Pandemic management functions aim to achieve effects in a pandemic response system (e.g. coordination, alignment of efforts, shared awareness). The ‘function’ focuses on what is to be achieved, not how or by whom. Individual tools, systems, building blocks, can each fulfil a specific function – either independently or in combination. Conversely, a single element may also support multiple functions. (DRIVER+ Terminology, 2025). There are different approaches on how to develop a taxonomy of pandemic management functions. In ROADS, so-called pandemic characteristics were developed based on expert knowledge and the taxonomy of pandemic management functions was derived from them. The development of pandemic management functions

from pandemic characteristics is demand-orientated and correspondingly ambiguous. For this reason, it is also necessary for a taxonomy to be expandable at any time and therefore, it is dynamic by nature. Elements of the taxonomy can only be reduced if it is ensured that the removed element has not been used in any description of a measure (solution) or target.

The number of identical pandemic management functions assigned to both a target and a possible corresponding measure can be used to rank how well different measures address that target.

2.2 Matching based on expert knowledge

In addition to algorithmic matching based on a taxonomy, a knowledge base maintained by experts can be used. Experts define specific relations between objectives and measures. Some examples of such relations are given in Table 2 for illustration purposes. These recommendations are based on scientific findings and practical experience, typically captured in workshops and interviews. However, the expert assessments need to be regularly updated to reflect new scientific findings.

Table 2. Examples of target – measures relations as basis for expert based matching

Strategic target	Tactical target	Operational target	Measures
Containment	Reduction of morbidity & mortality	Reduction of virus spread	Hygienic measures: e.g. hand washing
Containment	Reduction of morbidity & mortality	Reduction of virus spread	Quarantine
Protection by medical counter measures: vaccination and medication	Minimising severe disease progression	Contribution to development of medical countermeasures	Vaccination (if available)

Source: (authors, CAVE (2021))

The expert knowledge management approach has some advantages:

- Greater precision through qualified assessments compared to taxonomy matching
- Measures can be prioritised

On the other hand, there is need for continuous maintenance of the knowledge base, in particular during the dynamic evolution of a pandemic like COVID-19, the scientific basis changed almost on a daily rate. Moreover, as with all not- or only semi-automated approaches, the scalability is limited in case of manual interventions. If large volumes of new information need to be integrated in the knowledge base, experts may be hindered by limited resources. Expert systems are highly dependent on the selection of panel members and thus prone to bias. In general terms, lack of standardised definitions of the requested expert status as well as of harmonised good practices are limiting factors (see e.g. Langfeldt, 2001, Hossain et al 2018).

2.3 Metric based matching

Both the taxonomy- and expert knowledge-based matching approaches allow to establish qualitative relations between measures and targets. By extending the expert knowledge approach towards metric-based matching, quantitative matching relations can be established. For that purpose, it is necessary

to have scientific information available that provides a link between measures and metrics. In Table 3, examples are shown illustrating the potential use of metrics for matching.

Table 3. Example of specific measures and associated metrics

Measure	Focus of measure	Impact on metric
Lockdown	Store closure	Reduction of reproduction rate by 35% (95% CI: 29-41%)
Lockdown	Closing of gastronomy business	Reduction of reproduction rate by 12% (95% CI: 8-17%)
Lockdown	Leisure and entertainment facilities closure	Reduction of reproduction rate by 3% (95% CI: -1-10%)

Source: (Sharma et al 2021)

These are examples of measure – metric relations based on a systematic literature search. Such metrics have the potential to be used for quantitative matching of e.g. the operational target to reduce the virus spread and specific measures within the categories of lockdowns. It becomes evident that this approach enables a quantifiable comparison between store closure and the closure of gastronomy business. Nevertheless, this type of matching should be based on the outcome of a large body of evidence – not a single study, encompassing aspects such as type of pathogen, regional occurrence, type of affected population, among others. A shortcoming of this approach was that only a limited number of studies were found that provided this type of information. At this stage, quantifiable indicators are used instead of elements of a taxonomy.

2.4 Alternative matching concepts

The three matching concepts discussed in the previous chapters all have limitations because of their rather static data collection and aggregation processes. The decision support based on this type of non-dynamic, common operational picture aggregation hampers the optimised selection of measures to tackle the dynamic changing situation during a pandemic such as COVID-19. There is need for dynamic collection, structuring, evaluation, aggregation, and finally provision of knowledge. This encompasses AI-based allocation of measures to expected impacts. Such approaches must be grounded in a detailed evaluation of existing workflows of pandemic management, encompassing analysis of mandates and roles. It is also worth considering why vectorisation approaches were not used in the proposed approach. Their lack of transparency, challenges in reproducibility, and limited suitability for small datasets make them less appropriate for contexts requiring clear, accountable decision-making. A structured, taxonomy-based method offers a more interpretable and reliable alternative.

3. Demonstrator for pandemic knowledge management

To support evidence-based decision-making in crisis contexts, a web-based demonstrator system has been developed for structured mapping between strategic goals and corresponding measures. The core of the demonstrator is implemented using Drupal 10 as a content management system, enhanced with a multi-layer architecture to ensure scalability, usability, and extensibility:

- *Presentation Layer:* Drupal 10 with a Bootstrap-based frontend provides an accessible user interface for domain experts.

- *Data Storage Layer:* A relational database (MariaDB) is used to model structured content types for goals and measures. This choice supports well-defined relationships and maintains consistency in complex metadata structures. While NoSQL or graph databases offer benefits in highly dynamic or relationship-heavy domains, the current use case favours relational consistency and integration with Drupal's entity system.
- *Search and Indexing Layer:* The Apache Solr integration is a critical component of the demonstrator. Solr enables advanced full-text search, faceted filtering, and dynamic ranking of results. Content from both targets and measures is indexed along key taxonomic fields such as thematic classification, expected impact, and entry probability. This facilitates the retrieval of relevant matches in near real-time, even as the dataset grows. For example, a decision-maker can filter all measures related to "Containment" with an "Impact = 5" and "Probability ≥ 3 " within milliseconds. The Apache Solr is configured to support semantic mapping. Measures and goals are both tagged with hierarchical taxonomy terms (e.g., "Containment > Lockdown" or "Mitigation > Public Awareness"). Solr indexes these terms in flat and hierarchical forms, enabling both exact and fuzzy matching.

4. Discussion and outlook

The systematic approach of matching gaps and solutions that was demonstrated both on the international level in DRIVER+ as well as in the national project ROADS has several advantages, encompassing reproducibility of the matching approach, comparability of solutions, as well as their potential to close capability gaps and the possibility to expand the matching concept based on evolving end user requirements. On the other hand, it turned out that there is need for continuous involvement of practitioners and other stakeholders to update their requirements as well as the various solutions to adapt the description of their capabilities. Moreover, when looking at the dynamic changing knowledge base in the course of a pandemic, scalability quickly reaches its limits due to frequently reaching of the maximum of available human capacities to continuously update and extend the knowledge base needed for the description of gaps, measures, as well as metrics. These limitations hamper the success of existing approaches considerably. This highlights the need to explore the potential of automated or semi-automated approaches, e.g. by AI applications to have a dynamic knowledge base available reflecting the dynamic evolution in complex scenarios such as pandemics.

A web-based system was developed to support decision-makers in efficiently identifying appropriate measures based on predefined criteria. Implemented in Drupal 10, the system uses taxonomies and modules, for example, Entity Views Attachment (EVA) to dynamically visualise relationships between objectives and measures.

The three matching concepts presented in this paper have specific properties:

- *Taxonomies* enable a structured and systematic matching of measures to objectives. By developing a specific taxonomy for pandemic management functions, a clear and consistent description of both measures and objectives can be achieved. This facilitates the comparability and evaluation of measures
- *Expert knowledge* provides a more precise and informed mapping of measures to objectives based on scientific evidence and practical experience. This method enables prioritisation of measures and takes into account the latest scientific developments, as long as the knowledge can be continuously updated
- *Metrics-based approaches* extend the qualitative categorisation by introducing quantitative relationships between measures and objectives. This enables an objective evaluation and

comparability of the measures based on measurable criteria. However, this method is heavily dependent on the availability of comprehensive scientific data, which is often limited.

Using the three approaches - taxonomies, expert knowledge and metrics – individually or in combination, provides a robust foundation for identifying appropriate measures for pandemic management. Each approach has its own strengths and weaknesses, and their integration has the potential to significantly improve the effectiveness and efficiency of the selection of measures. However, the dynamic nature of pandemics requires flexible and adaptable systems that can be continuously updated and expanded. Future developments should focus on the automated extraction, structuring and semantic linking of knowledge of heterogeneous information sources (e.g. text-based documents) using artificial intelligence (AI) and graph databases. First, content is extracted and converted into structured semantic units, such as “solutions”, “gaps”, or “capabilities”. These entities and their semantic relations are then mapped in a graph database, creating a flexible, relational knowledge base. Generative Large Language Models (LLMs) have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in text understanding and generation, enabling the extraction of structural knowledge from plain natural language texts (Xu et al, 2023). A central element is the automatic generation of a taxonomy, which hierarchically structures the extracted concepts along thematic and functional dimension. The semantic grouping will then be integrated into the graph structure.

Next an intelligent matching engine will be developed that automatically correlates solutions with identified gaps and vice versa. The matching is based on several dimensions like semantic similarity (via embedding comparison), taxonomic proximity (same or related categories) and contextual weighting based on metrics such as relevance, effort or technical fit.

Another important component will be a feedback mechanism through which user can provide feedback on the quality of the suggested matches. These evaluations are transferred into a learning process to iteratively improve the matching logic – e.g. through re-ranking models or reinforcement learning.

This could further improve decision-making and enable a faster and more precise response to changing pandemic situations.

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THE USE OF AN AI-SUPPORTED TOOL FOR THE DEPLOYMENT OF INFORMAL VOLUNTEERS IN CRISIS AND DISASTER MANAGEMENT ON THE BASIS OF THEIR COMPETENCIES

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Abstract

Volunteers play an important role in crisis and disaster management in Austria. However, the competence-based integration of informal, spontaneous volunteers in crisis situations remains a major challenge for public safety organisations. The CERTIFIER (Certificate for CERTificate For Integrated Emergency Response) project addresses this issue by developing a digital, competency-based system, providing a basis to efficiently and securely integrate informal volunteers into emergency operations. The core innovation of the project is a digital proof of competence system that allows individuals to present verifiable qualifications through interoperable digital credentials. CERTIFIER allows targeted deployment based on validated skills, supported by ontology-based competence matching and a user-friendly chatbot interface. A mixed-methods requirements elicitation and tabletop-exercises showed a strong interest in automated registration, documentation of skills and certification of engagement. The results highlight the potential of the system to optimise human resource allocation and improve operational efficiency. Key design considerations support the registration process and the development of an ontology for matching skills and competences, as well as transparent handling of data. CERTIFIER addresses current gaps in coordination and resource allocation and demonstrates how digital and AI technologies can promote responsive and effective volunteer engagement in disaster management.

1. Background and Introduction

Volunteering is one main pillar of crisis and disaster management in Austria, with emergency response organisations ensuring the effective and professional handling of emergency and disaster operations (BMI, 2009). Organisations managing disasters are used to working with trained, formal and professionalised volunteers. Recent findings from the CIVolunteer (KIRAS, AT) research project highlight a trend to shortcomings in the volunteer sector: a decline or shortage of volunteers could lead to supply bottlenecks and make effective coordination in crises difficult (Schönböck et al., 2024a, Schönböck et al. 2024b, Fritz & Mathewson, 1957; Quarantelli & Dynes, 1977; Skar et al., 2016; Strandh & Eklund, 2018). However, the coordination of spontaneous, informal volunteers, who spontaneously offer support in a crisis situation is a major challenge for authorities and public safety organisations. Emergency services are also confronted with informal volunteers who form self-

organised groups and take actions (Quarantelli & Dynes, 1977; Stallings & Quarantelli, 1985; Strandh & Eklund, 2018). These persons or groups can provide valuable resources and make important contributions to disaster management (Barsky et al., 2007; Helshloot & Ruitenberg, 2004; Scanlon et al., 2014; Whittaker et al., 2015). They offer benefits such as reduced bureaucracy, greater flexibility and closer proximity to those affected (Stallings & Quarantelli, 1985; Whittaker et al., 2015). When it comes to managing a collaborative emergency response, public safety organisations face the challenge of how to appropriately involve informal volunteers. These actors typically do not use standardised systems and are only loosely integrated into official coordination structures. Emergency response organisations are challenged by the situation to use the potential of informal volunteers while addressing concerns that often prevent their full integration. These concerns include safety risks due to insufficient information, lack of protective equipment, limited risk awareness (Harris et al., 2017), logistical challenges, overstretch of critical resources (Harris et al., 2017; Whittaker et al., 2015), inadequate planning (Skar et al., 2016) and legal uncertainties such as liability issues (Barsky et al., 2007). This results in informal volunteers being involved only in minor tasks, while their specific skills and competencies remain unused.

This is where the KIRAS funded project CERTIFIER (FFG, AT, 2023-2025) comes in. The aim of the project is to develop a comprehensive concept for the competence-based involvement of informal volunteers. A central objective is the creation of a digital solution to record and document the skills and qualifications of informal volunteers through a digital competence certificate, integrating a formal confirmation of their activities as foreseen in national law by using the digital volunteer passport, provided by the Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health, Care and Consumer Protection in Austria. Overall, CERTIFIER offers the following added value:

- Documentation and validation of competences of informal volunteers
- Basis for efficient and targeted involvement of informal volunteers in acute crisis situations
- Needs-driven technology development to ensure greater stakeholder acceptance
- In-depth understanding of the challenges associated with the participation of informal volunteers

2. Concept and Approach

2.1 CERTIFIER-Concept

The proof of concept developed in the CERTIFIER project enables informal volunteers with existing skills to identify their qualifications to emergency services without compromising privacy or data security. This allows emergency services to make informed decisions for involvement of individuals in disaster management tasks by relying on a validated digital record of volunteers' competencies, thereby avoiding lengthy verification procedures. This approach helps to manage disasters more effectively and with greater resource efficiency.

CERTIFIER supports disaster management in the following ways:

- Volunteers register via (diverse) volunteer platforms or using the AI-driven chatbot of CERTIFIER and confirm their general willingness to support tasks. Existing qualifications will be listed on the platform and can be validated by digital certificates
- Volunteers, which hold digital certificates in interoperable formats (e.g. European Digital Identity, ISO/IEC 18013.5, W3C Verifiable Credential Model) received during

education and training (e.g. professional qualifications, driving licences, etc.) are able to share them easily using the CERTIFIER platform.

- In the back end of the system, tasks are matched to their required competences, and crisis managers are informed about the available volunteer resources.
- Platform operators from emergency services can notify relevant volunteers with the required skill profiles. If special qualifications are required, the chatbot serves as an interface for verifying credentials.

In line with security and privacy-by-design principles, volunteers use CERTIFIER to prove that they hold the required digital credentials. The chatbot provides information about the deployment and potential areas of activity for volunteers to support emergency services. If certain qualifications are missing, the system can suggest alternative suitable fields of activity. If the validation was successful, volunteers receive a signed token (e.g. visualized in the form of a QR code) confirming their qualification and active registration. This token can be verified, e.g. through an app-based scan, by emergency services and grants permission to access the disaster area and perform specific tasks on site.

CERTIFIER supports emergency services in the targeted and demand-driven allocation of volunteers. Commanders can search for specific tasks (e.g. "set up lighting") and receive AI-based suggestions of verified, qualified volunteers (e.g. electricians). Final task assignments always remain with human decision-makers.

Key Innovations of CERTIFIER:

- AI-supported registration of spontaneous volunteers with validated skills — privacy-friendly through verifiable credentials (SSI).
- Immediate access to relevant competencies — no manual checks required.
- Compatible with established digital ID standards (e.g. EUDI, W3C VCs, ISO/IEC 18013.5).
- Intelligent backend enables competence-based task allocation in real time.
- Volunteers retain control over their digital identity while enabling coordination transparency.
- Modular and interoperable — adaptable to various disaster types and organizations.
- Early registration boosts preparedness, resilience, and sustainable volunteer engagement.

In case of power outages, token authenticity can still be verified offline; with internet access, additional information becomes available.

Figure 1. The CERTIFIER system (by CERTIFIER consortium)

2.2 Skills and Competence Matching

In CERTIFIER, a volunteer is considered competent for a task if the required skills and competences are fulfilled. These requirements are divided into two types: self-claimed competences, such as physical fitness or psychological resilience, and competences that must be proven through formal certifications, such as the ability to drive a specific vehicle or provide first aid. Each competence is linked to one or more certifications, and a single certification can validate multiple skills. Similarly, a skill can be proven by different certifications, any one of which is sufficient. Only certifications issued by authorized and recognized issuers are accepted by the system. Currently, the relationships between tasks, competences, and certifications are defined manually based on existing skill catalogs like ESCO (2020), RebeKa (2018), and KatHelferPro (2024). Since these catalogs are not fully aligned, manual mapping is necessary. However, there is strong potential to use large language models (LLMs) to assist in parsing and improving these matchings. For legal reasons, LLMs are not currently used in the live system for automated competence-task matching. All user and business data is encrypted both at rest and in transit, following established security standards. System access is secured through JWT bearer tokens issued via OpenID Connect. Role-based access control and strict data separation reduce the likelihood and impact of data breaches. In the event of a breach, trust revocation, secret rotation, and additional mitigation measures will be implemented promptly.

2.3 AI Concept

The core AI concept driving this initiative is to facilitate efficient and effective deployment of skilled volunteers by leveraging an AI-based chatbot system. This system functions as both a communicative interface for informal volunteers and a sophisticated decision-making tool for emergency services, thereby enhancing the coordination and management of volunteer resources in crisis situations.

The CERTIFIER project comprises two distinct yet complementary chatbots: “Chatbot fwH” designed for informal volunteers, and “Chatbot BOS” intended for use by public safety organisations - each tailored to meet specific user needs and operational contexts. The Chatbot fwH is designed primarily to assist skilled volunteers with the registration process including the competency validation. This involves guiding users through the necessary steps to establish their credentials,

ensuring that emergency services have accurate information regarding each volunteer's competencies. Concurrently, the Chatbot BOS focuses on identifying and allocating suitable fwH based on the specific requirements of tasks at hand, thereby streamlining the matching process between volunteers' skills and situational demands. To achieve these objectives, both chatbots are developed using advanced conversational AI design methods. These methods involve a detailed modelling of domain-specific entities (e.g. competencies, locations, tasks, etc.) and dialogue flows to facilitate natural and intuitive interactions. Also the CERTIFIER project investigates the utilization of modern Generative AI methods (large language models, AI agents etc.) for powering these two chatbots.

The ONDEWO Call Center AI Platform (2025) supports the full AI conversation lifecycle, from modelling to managing automated dialogues. It ensures responsive chatbot performance and maintains conversation histories for quality assurance. Users can rate chatbot responses, enabling continuous improvement based on real-time feedback. Voice input and output make interactions more natural, allowing users to communicate as they would with a person. These features enhance both functionality and user experience.

2.3 Requirements elicitation

To inform the design of the CERTIFIER system, a desk study was first carried out to map public authorities, security organisations, and volunteer networks in Austria. This was followed by 16 qualitative expert interviews with crisis managers, operational leads, staff, and technical specialists from state and municipal bodies, first responder organisations (such as fire brigades and emergency services like the Red Cross and Johanniter), and NGOs working with informal volunteers. The interviews explored how volunteers are integrated into regular operations and how spontaneous volunteers are engaged during crises. Participants also provided input on the requirements for a volunteer registration tool that includes an AI-based chatbot. Building on these insights, a quantitative online survey was conducted to assess the chatbot's potential. To further understand the registration and motivation of informal volunteers, an additional survey among spontaneous volunteers (61 respondents) and a focus group with four individuals who had previously participated in disaster relief efforts were conducted. These findings shaped the analysis of system and chatbot requirements and formed the basis for the CERTIFIER design concept.

2.4 Tabletop-exercise

A tabletop exercise was used to test the preliminary CERTIFIER system in a simulated refugee crisis scenario. Two groups participated: spontaneous volunteers and an emergency management organisation. Participants completed key tasks such as registration, chatbot use, deployment, and validation of qualifications. The exercise was evaluated through observations, short questionnaires, and phase-end discussions. Insights from this mixed-methods evaluation informed the refinement of system components and processes.

3. Results of the requirements elicitation and tabletop-exercise

3.1 Results of the requirements elicitation

Findings show that in non-crisis situations, volunteer management relies on personal interviews, collection of basic data, and task assignments based on qualifications and coordinator judgment. In crises, managing informal volunteers is more difficult due to inconsistent digital registration, limited resources, and lack of standardised competence tracking. Volunteer coordinators see potential in using an AI chatbot to support registration and matching, enabling faster and more efficient

deployment. To be effective, the chatbot must be simple, transparent in data handling, and tailored to user needs. While coordinators prioritise privacy, integration, and documentation, volunteers seek quick registration, task access, and recognition of their skills. Concerns about data privacy and technical reliability may hinder adoption. Despite the limited sample size, the mixed-method approach offers useful insights for further development and testing of the CERTIFIER system.

3.2 Results of the tabletop-exercise

The tabletop exercise offered valuable insights for refining CERTIFIER, especially regarding chatbot use and AI-assisted decision-making. Participants viewed chatbots as helpful tools to simplify registration and data entry, provided they are one of several input options. Natural, conversational language and voice interaction were seen as key to improving usability and trust. Skills-based matching based on verified qualifications was identified as a core strength, with transparent communication - such as updates via an EU digital ID wallet - seen as essential for user trust. Matching and search functions should be intuitive and easy to use. While the concept was generally well received, concerns were raised about digital infrastructure, and trust in digital credentials. Furthermore, user acceptance might be different under stress. Inclusive, accessible design remains critical to broad adoption.

4. Conclusion

Findings from the requirements analysis and tabletop exercise offer clear direction for further development of CERTIFIER's AI-based chatbot and decision-support tools. The technologies show strong potential to improve volunteer coordination, particularly in registration, task matching, and documentation of skills. The chatbot was valued for its ability to collect data automatically, support transparent data handling, and offer user-friendly interactions. Integrating skill-based matching can enhance decision-making by enabling precise volunteer allocation. Key design needs include a flexible matching taxonomy, transparent validation, modular architecture, mobile access, and intuitive interfaces. Features like feedback tools and push notifications support adaptability and informed decisions. To ensure adoption, privacy, technical reliability, and trust in digital credentials must be addressed - especially in settings with limited digital infrastructure. Offline functionality and cybersecurity are also essential. Overall, the results confirm the potential of AI tools to reduce workload, improve accuracy, and promote transparent, inclusive volunteer management. Ongoing user-driven development and testing remain crucial for real-world success.

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AI IN CRISIS MANAGEMENT: BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This paper presents a bibliometric analysis of research on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in crisis management, based on the PRISMA diagram methodology and the Web of Science database. The PRISMA methodology facilitates transparent systematic reviews and reporting on what has been done, how it has been done, and what the findings are. The results show that the main research directions follow three lines - technological, crisis management itself and preparation for it, and crisis communication. The central countries working on the issue have also been identified. Particular attention is given to the potential benefits for both public institutions and private-sector organisations involved in emergency preparedness and response. Rather than emphasizing competition, the results suggest that AI primarily improves coordination, efficiency, and decision-making during crises.

1. Introduction

Bibliometric analysis is a very useful tool for literature analysis. It allows a few things, such as finding linked citations or detecting clusters of trends. It tends to be very useful in the first step of the process of creating an overview of a field (Greener, 2022). Öztürk et al. (2024) then point out that this approach is often applied in the field of management as well. Researchers can use this method of analysis to uncover current trends, which is often a common source of motivation to undertake this analysis. In addition, different databases, software or approaches can be used for it - identifying lead authors, countries, universities, keywords or co-authors (Hassan & Duarte, 2024).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a transformative field of computer science that enables machines to emulate human intelligence and perform complex tasks. AI encompasses various subfields, including

machine learning, natural language processing, and data analytics (Shrivastava, 2024). Its applications span multiple sectors, such as healthcare, education, agriculture, and autonomous systems (Kulkarni, 2024). The foundation of modern AI is supported by cutting-edge technologies such as big data processing, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things (Mian, 2022). While AI holds promising prospects for industrial applications, its widespread adoption faces challenges from both internal and external perspectives (Mukhamediev et al., 2022).

Crisis management is critical for organisations to prevent, mitigate, and resolve crises (Nteka, 2021). It involves multiple phases, such as risk assessment, preparedness, and response strategies. Regular reviews of crisis plan, and employee training are essential to maintain readiness (Ciekanowski et al., 2023). Effective crisis management requires proactive planning, scenario development, and business continuity strategies. Key elements include transparent and timely communication with stakeholders, collaboration with external partners, and integration of technology and innovation (Tiwari, 2024). Various techniques and approaches have been proposed to address different aspects of crisis management (Abdalla et al., 2021).

AI is crucial in crisis management, enabling faster and more accurate decision-making. However, ethical considerations associated with AI use in crisis management must be addressed (Vladu, 2023). AI offers more advanced simulation capabilities, offering a faster and more dynamic workflow for the entire crisis management process (Karinshak, 2024). Some positions state that AI can create a proactive system from a conventional reactive approach to disaster management (Cao, 2023). AI applications in disaster management include predicting and mitigating disasters, analysing social media for real-time information, and providing insights for decision-making (Wong, 2021). AI integration in disaster management spans all phases, from prevention to recovery, incorporating tracking, mapping, or geospatial analysis (Pang, 2022). This study focuses primarily on sub symbolic approaches to AI (e.g., machine learning or predictive modelling), while symbolic AI does not play a significant role.

2. Methodology

The main aim of this paper is to provide a bibliometric analysis with a focus on identifying the main topics in the field of “AI in crisis management”. The Web of Science scientific database was used to compile the literature review. This database was chosen because of several reasons. Firstly, it is the easiest tool for bibliometric analysis (AlRyalat et al., 2019). As Cantrell et al. (2022) point out, it is a more efficient tool than other databases (like Google Scholar). Singh et al. (2021) then point out that WoS is the most selective database, ensuring high relevance and quality. The research is based on the PRISMA 2020 Methodological Guide for Literary Reviews, as shown in Figure 1. The main advantage is that it reflects recent developments in systematic review methodology (Sohrabi et al., 2021). It provides clear reporting guidelines for systematic reviews to ensure complete and transparent reporting (Brennan & Munn, 2021).

The search itself was conducted on 20th April 2025. The leading search focus was “Topic”, defined by the sentence “AI” OR “Artificial Intelligence” OR “Intelligent Systems” OR “Machine Learning” OR “Data-Driven” AND “Crisis” OR “Disaster” OR “Crisis Management” OR “Emergency Management” OR “Disaster Management” OR “Disaster Response” OR “Emergency Response” OR “Crisis Response” OR “Disaster Recovery”. Defined in this way, the introductory sentence is entirely in line with the objective of this paper, as it defines the field focused on artificial intelligence and its relationship to crises, crisis management, disasters, or critical infrastructure. At this point, 8 500 posts have been found.

Figure 1. PRISMA diagram

Source: authors according to PRISMA (2021)

First, all papers that are not available in “Open Access” have been excluded. This criterion was included on the grounds that the scientific debate identified is mainly to help future research identify the main tools for using AI within corporate practice. Another exclusion criterion was the year of publication of the paper. As this is an assessment of the current situation, all papers with a publication date before 2023 were excluded. Besides the fact that AI is constantly evolving and improving, so keeping an eye on the current literature is necessary (Grewal et al., 2024), other research on this topic also used a 3-year time period (Woo & Choi, 2021). Other researchers, like Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019), show that the limitation of the time period can be due to some significant change, invention, or technology introduced. Therefore, the year 2023 was chosen as the starting point because it introduced the generative AI model ChatGPT for public use (Thompson et al., 2023), which is the most famous and well-known AI of current time.

Subsequently, all papers that are not in the “Article” or “Proceeding Paper” category have been excluded. This step ensures a higher scientific relevance of the articles. Finally, those contributions that are not written in English have been excluded. This criterion was applied because English is the main language used in scientific publications (Bahji et al., 2023) and analyses are often made on for English written papers, as reported by Mishra et al. (2024). Subsequently, a reduction was made in terms of specific areas. The contribution aims to evaluate the given topic in business practice. Therefore, several areas within the Web of Science Categories were selected, namely “Business”, “Management”, “Operations Research Management Science” and “Computer Science Artificial Intelligence.” This step ensured a targeted focus of the research on businesses and their practices. To ensure coverage of the business management field, the “Research Area” specification was used, namely “Business Economics”, “Operations Research Management Science”, “Public Administration”, and “Engineering”. After applying all the specified criteria, 82 contributions were found. Subsequently, a manual screening of the remaining contributions was carried out, during which abstracts, titles, and keywords were analysed. The final number of papers was 66. These papers were further analysed in VOSviewer. This tool enables the construction and visualisation of bibliometric networks, such as co-authorship, keyword co-occurrence, and country collaboration maps. The tool is widely used in bibliometric research (van Eck & Waltman, 2010).

The second cluster focuses on crisis management itself and on building resilience. Keywords such as crisis management, disaster management, disaster relief operations, resilience, coordination, and crisis communication show that this area deals with the practical management of crises. Research in this area focuses on how to structure decision-making processes in times of crisis, how to effectively coordinate multiple actors (e.g., government agencies, non-profit organisations, businesses), how to ensure fluid communication in chaotic environments, and how to systematically strengthen the ability of organisations to cope with unpredictable events. The practical implication of this cluster is that AI systems are used not only to detect crises but also to directly support the management of crisis teams, optimize interventions on the ground, and model future scenarios to minimize damage. This area can consider a few specific applications and situations, such as using AI systems to manage incidents during cyber-attacks, testing the resilience of operations through AI simulations of personnel outages, or simulating the impact of a supply chain outage and designing alternatives.

The third cluster focuses on the social and communication dimensions of crisis management. It includes keywords such as crisis communication, social media, information, or behaviour. This cluster reflects that crisis management is impossible without effective information management in today's digital age. The research here explores, for example, how social networks influence the spread of information and misinformation during crises, what communication strategies are most effective in alerting the public, and how social media data analysis can be used to identify problems quickly. In practical terms, this means that AI is being used to process large volumes of data and analyse public sentiment, monitor crisis responses, and support decision-making based on how public opinion is evolving in real-time. Again, several specific use cases can be considered, such as using social media analytics to disseminate crisis information, automating the sending of personalized alerts to the population via chatbots, or monitoring customer reaction when products are unavailable.

3. Discussion

The first finding was that the link between AI and crisis management lies in technology. AI is revolutionizing crisis management through various technological applications. It improves decision-making, information management, and communication during crises. Key technologies include machine learning, social network analysis, big data analytics, and geographic information systems. However, challenges remain, including managing disparate information, supporting different platforms, or data set limitations (Bukar et al., 2022). Artificial intelligence applications, such as drone technology or robotics, contribute to more effective disaster response and mitigation. Overall, the role of AI in crisis management is crucial for faster responses in all phases of disaster management (Arfan et al., 2019). The above facts support the finding that it is necessary to emphasize this issue and help businesses overcome this obstacle.

Subsequently, the area of crisis management itself was observed, with the concepts of resilience, communication, or coordination identified as important. Crisis management and resilience are crucial for organisations facing major disruptions. Effective crisis response involves shared sensemaking, issue identification, and strategic adaptation (Parker, 2023). Organisational resilience is characterized by preparedness, response effectiveness, and recovery capabilities (Almufarji & Husin, 2022). Building long-term organisational resilience requires integrating crisis management and resiliency theories and embedding innovations introduced during emergencies (Donelli et al., 2022).

Finally, crisis communication was identified as an important area. Crisis communication has emerged as a crucial aspect of crisis management in the digital age, with social media playing a pivotal role (Kuipers et al., 2023). Effective communication and social media usage are the most significant factors influencing crisis management, followed by leadership and knowledge management (Hazaa

et al., 2021). Future research should focus on leveraging AI-based technologies to improve crisis communication practices and establish shared situational awareness (Abboodi et al., 2023).

To safely use AI in crisis management, the necessary ethical and legal standards must first be in place. These will establish accountability for AI systems' decision-making (Gevaert et al., 2021). Ghaffarian et al. (2023) then add that openness is crucial to ensure interpretability so that AI decisions can be tracked and explained. Equally important is the collaboration between government institutions and companies, and hence research organisations, which will support the development of reliable systems while enabling rapid real-time response (Kapucu et al., 2024).

Although the paper was intended to emphasize timeliness, it is important to consider the research barriers and limitations. There has been a focus on sources available in English, which reflects a desire for practical applicability to a broader professional and corporate audience, but at the same time, may lead to, but may also lead to, the omission of some specific approaches published in other languages or regions. Similarly, the choice of a timeframe of 2023 onwards responds to the dynamic developments in the field but may have overlooked older yet relevant studies. Finally, bibliometric analysis should be seen as a tool for identifying significant trends and directions, not as a means of deep content analysis of individual publications. However, these aspects do not diminish the value of the findings; on the contrary, they provide a solid basis for follow-up research and further refinement. Further research may focus on a deeper analysis of AI's effectiveness in crisis management, for example, in the form of comparative studies or other systematic reviews. There is also scope for looking at AI's role in decision-making processes or coordination of actors during a crisis. The role of AI in information and communication flows within organisations can also be explored.

4. Conclusion

The main aim of this paper was to provide a bibliometric analysis with a focus on identifying the main topics in the field of “AI in crisis management”. This study has shown that (AI) plays a key role in modern crisis management and significantly influences how organisations respond to emergencies. The literature analysis revealed three main areas of interest - technology tools, building organisational resilience, and crisis communication, all complementary and reinforcing. AI enables faster threat detection, more effective decision-making, and better coordination of crisis interventions.

At the same time, however, several challenges have been identified that hinder the full implementation of AI in crisis management. These include the limited availability of quality data, ethical issues, problems with integrating technology into existing structures, and the need for greater awareness of AI's potential among managers, both for managers of private companies and those working in the public sphere, as crisis management affects both spheres. In conclusion, the future success of AI in crisis management depends not only on technological advances but also on the ability of organisations to systematically incorporate new approaches and strengthen their ability to withstand crises.

In addition to managers of private and public enterprises who can use the results to optimize decision-making processes, plan scenarios, or improve communication, the study results also have important implications for the academic and research community working to develop theoretical frameworks and practical applications of AI in crisis management. The bibliometric analysis provides an overview of current trends, research directions, and potential areas for further study. From the perspective of technology companies or developers, the results of this study provide a source of inspiration for the development of AI-based tools that will reflect the specific needs of practice.

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CYBER SECURITY VS AI

A SECURE SCHEME FOR CHAINED AUTHENTICATION COMBINED WITH ATTESTATION

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Abstract

It may be desirable to split computation into several parts and perform them on remote systems, see e.g. microservices. However, not always are these services directly and publicly available. For instance, if the calculation is performed at home, no public IP address may be available. Or the exact location of the computation should remain hidden. In these cases, the remote party may be identified solely as a Tor onion service or some anonymous cloud provider. It is then desirable to pass on the work only if the recipient can still be identified as trustworthy, e.g. by remote attestation (guaranteeing a specific calculation via the actual executable and its secure environment). Even if the location and identity of the operator is known, this is very desirable. Moreover, each entity in a chain of calculation should remain oblivious of all non-directly connected steps and any authentication information for those, including any additional data or the exact work instructions. This paper proposes a scheme to pass on work packages in a secure manner to a verified next step, while keeping all non-directly involved data hidden.

1. Introduction

If intelligent agents, e.g. AI systems, cannot perform some task immediately, they may decide on whom to pass it to for further processing. The same obviously is possible manually. In many cases the actual counterpart may be of little interest, and e.g. be selected solely based on the price: it is “merely” necessary that a specific computation is performed. This might require identification of the owner so that the work performed can be invoiced (deducted from the “points” in an account, billed in some currency etc). If this happens several times in a sequence it is necessary that e.g. a task does know whom to contact next and how to securely identify it (or at least verify their computation; see below), but none of the information used for payment – else it could submit other tasks under the identity of someone else who would be billed for it – or simply steal that data and use it a second time/somewhere else.

The scheme presented here draws on the ideas implemented in Tor, specifically layered encryption.

1.1 Related work

A somewhat similar approach is described in (Sollins, 1988) as “Cascaded authentication” but there no attestation is included and it work more as a delegation of rights. It is based on a “passport” signed at each stage, which includes limits each stage may perform on behalf of the issuer.

The system described by (Bela/Piroska 2009) consists of a central “coordinator” node, which shares passwords with each node. However, if many requests come in, the load on this central node might be too large, so a stage may authenticate to another stage before passing the work on, i.e. stage i assures stage $i+1$ that it did validate the origin. Therefore, a trust relationship between all those stages in required (and attestation is not included either).

Attempting to achieve less authentication than documentation is the scheme proposed by (Pattaranantakul et al 2021). Here the way a packet traverses multiple stages of work (e.g. firewall, load balancer, NAT) is verified through chained signatures. I.e., there the path is verifiable, but no authentication takes place and no data is kept secret.

1.2 Usage scenario

When training an AI system, outsourcing calculation is often unavoidable, especially for additional company-specific training, as the necessary specialized hardware will neither be available nor cost-effective to purchase. Additionally, several stages may be required, e.g. pretraining, adding pre- and/or post-filters, combining it with other systems and libraries, integration into a web-system (e.g. chatbot), testing & publishing it etc. Each stage obviously needs its own information to be able to perform its work. However, it does not need information and instructions for any other steps. Instructions for previous and the current stage can obviously be removed before passing the work package onward, but those for latter ones must invariably be present. Similar, but not identical, authentication information for the next stage is required. For the next stage it must be available in a “useful” format so authentication can succeed, but further stages should remain unknown and any other authentication data unavailable. Note that this approach assumes a direct hand-off between the stages (\rightarrow sequence model), i.e. not returning it to the initiator (\rightarrow star model) after each step. This is especially important in AI, as models may be huge and transfer bandwidth and time is an issue – less between professional services but much more so with a single central hub at a private company.

In this scenario attestation is slightly less important, as each stage is likely known in advance. But small price differences per hour for training might result in a large end prices; cheaper alternatives may be useful. If the operator of a stage is not perfectly trustworthy (perhaps because until then little known/no previous experience/...), it is important to prove the actual computation performed. Note that especially with AI models it may be practically impossible to determine whether a model was trained correctly or not afterwards – the result could mostly perform as expected but still fail for some inputs, because not all input data provided was used in training or additional malicious input was inserted. So process attestation through the software executed is then useful.

A prime example for attestation being imperative is, if the operator of a stage remains anonymous and the authentication information includes some valuable consideration (directly, pre-paid etc). That information should only be disclosed to a stage if that stage can prove that it actually will perform the work and do this completely as advertised. Note that while we cannot prevent a DoS attack by e.g. carefully timed crashing/powering off the system, the system as a whole (OS, libraries, calculation program etc) cannot be modified maliciously or attestation will fail.

2. System description

The proposed system consists of two parts: the first is responsible for securely “identifying” the next element in the sequence and its composition/state. This is performed via remote attestation (Prünster 2019). This means we might not actually obtain the identity of the partner, but we can rely on the program that is running, including the whole boot process, the OS as well as the application. If the software is closed source or no inspection is available, at least it can be verified that the claimed version (not known in any more detail) is executed. This prevents not only any software modification (e.g. using less computation and producing worse results), but also any malicious modifications unknown to the operator of the services, e.g. via malware if the system is hacked.

The second part passes data through the chain of systems encrypted. This requires the initiator to know the exact sequence of systems in advance. It starts with the information for the last system, which is encrypted with the public key of that system. Then the data for the last-but-one system is appended and the whole encrypted with the public key of that system, and so on. Consequently, each system can decrypt the package intended for itself, which contains “its” information as well as an opaque blob to pass on. The latter is still encrypted, so no information can be gleaned from it.

The data for a system consists of multiple elements:

- Data directly encrypted with its own private key: This encompasses parameters, work instructions etc, but also the information which next system to contact and how to authenticate there (might be anonymous at this stage), including a nonce to be sent to the next stage.
- It also includes a second set of authentication data for the next stage (the first e.g. being anonymous). This data is encrypted with the private key of the next system and a derivative of the attestation. Also included is a checksum: if the next system attests successfully, the data can be decrypted, the checksum matches, and correct authentication data can be transferred and decrypted by the next stage. If the checksum is incorrect, it does not run the correct software and might accept any authentication (to obtain possession of all other data). But because of the wrong checksum the current stage knows that the decrypted data is actually garbage and should not be used. In this way the current stage does not even have to know the actual value expected from the next stage before it receives it and cannot access the authentication data for the next stage irrespectively whether attestation fails or succeeds.

Note that the attestation value cannot be expected to be any kind of cryptographic key, especially not a valid private/public key of an asymmetric cryptosystem. However, it can easily serve as (or as the basis for using a key derivation function) a symmetric key. This is why the initiator of the whole scheme needs to know the expected value, so it can encrypt the data appropriately.

However, as soon as a stage has encountered a specific next stage at least once, it would know the attestation value that it is expected to return and could decrypt the data, obtaining authentication information (still encrypted, but useable e.g. for other work). This is prevented through the nonce: it is sent initially to the next stage, which then includes it in its “attestation” reply, e.g. calculating a hash of the actual attestation value and the nonce and returning the result. The initiator knows the actual value and can therefore calculate the expected value, which is used for encryption. The current stage however, even if having had successful contact with the next stage before, will be unable to identify the actual attestation value (meaning it cannot know the computation to be performed too, not even if it is the same as some time before!) and therefore the expected reply. Any authentication information for the next stage is therefore masked by the nonce – which the recipient knows and therefore can easily remove, obtaining the actual authentication data to verify.

Definitions:

- $WorkData_i$ = Work data for stage i , i.e. instructions
- $Address_i$ = “Address” of stage i , e.g. domain name or IP address
- $AuthFirst_i$ = Authentication info for first part of authentication at stage i (known to stage $i-1$)
- $AuthSecond_i$ = Second authentication info for stage i (not to be known by stage $i-1$)
- $Nonce_i$ = Nonce to be sent to stage i
- ATT_i = Attestation value of stage i
- $PrivK_i$ = Private Key of stage i
- $PubK_i$ = Public Key of stage i
- DP_i = Data package for stage i ; contains information for later stages (secret from stage $i-1$)
- $Result_i$ = Result of work of stage i

$$\begin{aligned}
 DP_i = & WorkData_i \mid Address_{i+1} \mid AuthFirst_{i+1} \mid Nonce_{i+1} \mid \\
 & Enc(Enc(AuthSecond_{i+1}, Sign(Nonce_{i+1} \mid Nonce_{i+1}, PrivK_{i+1})), \\
 & \quad Hash(ATT_{i+1} \mid Sign(Nonce_{i+1}, PrivK_{i+1}))) \mid \\
 & CRC(Enc(AuthSecond_{i+1}, Sign(Nonce_{i+1} \mid Nonce_{i+1}, PrivK_{i+1}))) \mid \\
 & Enc(DP_{i+1} \mid Nonce_{i+1}, PubK_{i+1})
 \end{aligned}$$

After working on $WorkData_i$ combined with $Result_{i-1}$ to create $Result_i$, stage i performs:

1. Send to stage $i+1$ at $Address_{i+1}$: $Nonce_{i+1}, AuthFirst_{i+1}$
2. Receive as answer from stage $i+1$: $Hash(ATT_{i+1} \mid Sign(Nonce_{i+1}, PrivK_{i+1}))$; this is calculated based on ATT (it knows the value itself through retrieving it from its secure element, employing $Nonce_{i+1}$; most attestations need some nonce). Through $AuthFirst_{i+1}$ it can decide whether it wants to perform this work for that entity and then signs the $Nonce_{i+1}$, appends the attestation value and hashes the result. The final outcome is returned to stage i .
3. Decrypt with the answer the value $Enc(AuthSecond_{i+1}, Sign(Nonce_{i+1} \mid Nonce_{i+1}, PrivK_{i+1}))$ and compare CRC of that result against the expected known value. If it does not match, stop.
4. Send the decrypted $Enc(AuthSecond_{i+1}, Sign(Nonce_{i+1} \mid Nonce_{i+1}, PrivK_{i+1}))$ and $Enc(DP_{i+1} \mid Nonce_{i+1}, PubK_{i+1})$ as well as $Result_i$ to the stage $i+1$. Hand-off from the current stage i is now complete and this stage can stop execution. Optionally it can wait for a confirmation from stage $i+1$ so it can notify the initiator in case of a problem (and return the intermediate result to it). It can now delete all data of this task.

Stage $i+1$ performs:

5. Using its own $PrivK_{i+1}$ and remembering the nonce from before (step 1) it can decrypt $AuthSecond_{i+1}$ and verifies this. If the check succeeds, it decrypts $DP_{i+1} \mid Nonce_{i+1}$ and checks whether the $Nonce_{i+1}$ in there is the same as used in this communication before. Optionally it informs the previous stage about the result (success and take-over/ rejection).
6. Start the work on DP_{i+1} together with $Result_i$ from the previous stage(s).

The Initiator performs a setup procedure for each stage, starting with itself as the final stage and an empty WorkData, then continuing back through the chain of stages:

1. Assemble/gather WorkData_i, Adress_{i+1}, AuthFirst_{i+1}
2. Created a random Nonce_{i+1} and sends it securely to the system at stage i+1 for signing it (in two configurations). Note that the stage i+1 system can also (and for security maybe should) create the nonces themselves, but must disclose it to the requesting party. These values can also be created/obtained in advance.
3. It takes the second signature and uses it to encrypt its own AuthSecond credentials for stage i+1 with it and stores the value.
4. It calculates the CRC of the value from step three. The CRC could also be replaced by a hash algorithm if desired. The prerequisite here is that this must be a one-way function (i.e. no recreation of the encrypted value based on the output – this may only become available to stage i after being received from the next stage).
5. It hashes the expected ATT (perhaps performing an attestation itself with the nonce and expecting this to not change if the same nonce is used again later) together with the first signature and uses this to encrypt the result from the step three a second time.
6. It appends the nonce to the data package for the next (i+1) stage and encrypts it with the public key of that stage.

3. Security analysis

Potential attacks against security targets from various actors are investigated in this section.

3.1 Third parties

Communication takes place encrypted, so third parties won't see anything useful and can't use it. This especially applies to all authentication data, which is (even though encrypted by an outer layer) not accessible even to the sending stage itself. Replay is further impossible through the nonce – preventing any “replay” of a communication even if unknown, e.g. to exhaust resources (but this is likely already addressed through transport encryption too).

However, depending on the number of tasks being processed simultaneously by a system, it may be possible to trace a task through its individual stages. This can be based on timing or on the size of the task (more difficult, as the added results/removed inputs may vary significantly). Such information disclosure is practically unavoidable, but can be reduced e.g. by employing Tor for communication between the stages. As this is exactly one of the use cases – an “unknown” operator – this problem is solved at least in those cases.

3.2 Analysis by stage i

Note that stage i is assumed to run only attested software and therefore not behave undesirably. As this includes the OS, even being executed inside a container includes the execution environment, so attacks through hypervisors are (absent bugs or hidden functionality when verifying the code for attestation) impossible too. However, as physical control by its owner cannot be prevented, external (hardware) access to the data and potentially also modification remains possible, although unlikely.

As stage i doesn't know the private key of the next stage, it is unable to access the AuthSecond credentials it uses for the actual authentication at it. So even if it knows ATT (which is probably known publicly and therefore must be assumed to be available), it cannot calculate the outer key and is therefore unable to decrypt the AuthSecond $_{i+1}$ information. After it received the correct reply, it can decrypt the outer layer, but still cannot get at the inner content as the private key of the recipient is still unknown: AuthSecond $_{i+1}$ remains secret. The authentication information is only available to the original initiator of the request, as well as the entity verifying it (stage $i+1$).

Regarding publicly available attestation: note that most protocols require a nonce (see e.g. Coker et. al 2011. – “Sailer protocol”), so the output value cannot be determined without that nonce and the actual device. So while the nonce is known to stage i , it would have to perform an attestation itself with the recipient on its own, using the known nonce and an assumption of the calculation intended, to obtain verification that actually that calculation will take place at the next stage.

The instructions and any additional data for the next stage DP $_{i+1}$ are encrypted with the public key of the next stage too, so these remain secret as well. From this follows that any authentication info or data even further down the stages of the work pipeline remain secret too, including the nonces (see before) and which and how many further stages exist at all. Through the encryption they cannot be modified undetected too. Note that these can be (blindly) sabotaged through modifications, but then stage i cannot be forced to send anything to stage $i+1$ anyway – it can simply stop execution (but note that this should not be the case “inside” the software as this stage was verified through attestation!). And through logging it can be detected, whether “original” (=decryptable) data was transferred to the next stage or “damaged” (=not decryptable) one.

A potential information disclosure that cannot be avoided by this scheme is, that stage i will see previous results as well as the data this stage is expected to work on. This could be addressed by homomorphic encryption, but that is out of the scope of this approach.

3.3 Reuse by stage i

A stage can perform exactly the same transaction a second time (which may be desirable, e.g. if an error occurs), i.e. receive work once and send it on multiple times. This could alternatively be used e.g. for DoS attacks or resource exhaustion. This can be addressed through the nonce: if a stage keeps track of the nonces it has issued but already seen, it can accept an unfinished hand-off/task again, respectively reject it if it was already completed.

A stage could in a similar way potentially reuse the encrypted data including the nonce for the next stage for a different workload (i.e. attaching the authentication data for work package A to package B, ensuring that A has to pay additionally for the work performed for B). This is again easily detected (and refused) by keeping track of used nonces by stage $i+1$. Substituting different work for stage $i+1$ (i.e. not reusing but switching it between tasks) or any of the following stages is impossible, as both encrypted package as well as authentication information include the nonce, so the (opaque for stage i because of encryption) block cannot be copied to different data. The only possible attack is lying about the own results and passing on falsified data. This is theoretically possible for own work, but here includes previous results. This runs counter to a stage executing only attested, and therefore trusted, code; but see above regarding external modifications.

3.4 Impersonation of stage $i+1$

An impersonator might know the correct value of ATT (but see above: if a/the nonce is incorporated it will not be available), but it must be assumed for any kind of security guarantees that it will not know the private key of the stage it attempts to impersonate. Therefore, when receiving the nonce,

the correct reply cannot be calculated by an impersonator and even should access to the work package be obtained, it cannot be decrypted. At that stage only AuthFirst has been disclosed (i.e. no work results of the previous stage and no instructions/data for the next stage), which cannot be used for any authentication, as the (additionally encrypted) AuthSecond is needed for that. The previous stage can try again, hoping to reach the correct target this time, abandon the work, or send some information back to the initiator (perhaps combined with the current intermediate results).

4. Evaluation

This approach has some specific drawbacks and advantages. Drawbacks include:

- Each stage needs to keep track of expired nonces. This can be reduced if the nonces used are more complex and include an expiry timestamp. To improve security, these would have to be added to the long and secure random value; a single timestamp should pose no problem and can use any syntax desirable. Before use, conversion to a canonical form and perhaps hashing might be required. Also, each stage must pre-create these nonces and the two signed variants of them. While these can be created in advance, this somewhat clashes with the reduction of risk approach outlined: if created long in advance, a longer expiry time must be set and more nonces will have to be tracked (as either unused up to now or already used but not yet expired).
- Availability (or traceability) is not handled in this approach: any stage can always accept data for processing and then not do anything or simply not pass the result on further. This is addressed through the attestation and can be further reduced through logging and e.g. a signed “receipt” returned to the previous stage. Then it will be traceable at which point in the pipeline a work task disappeared through influences outside of attestation. So crashing/stopping a system can only be detected, but not avoided.

Distinct advantages of this scheme include:

- Through the attestation each stage knows that the next stage is not only claiming to be as trustworthy as required by the originator of the request, but actually configured/ performing as expected. This is not an absolute guarantee as it depends on the assessment at the start; later modifications through malware, bad operators, reconfiguration etc remain possible.
- A stage does not get access to the actual (=second part) identifying information for the next stage; these remain secret. This applies independently whether the next stage passes the checks (attestation) or not. The same applies to a stage receiving such information incorrectly (e.g. because of impersonation), as they remain securely encrypted.
- The authentication information is hidden from all (including the one using it) previous stages and therefore can be anything: a password, a cryptographic key, a token etc. This lack of disclosure converts any kind of authentication into an opaque bearer token usable only once (because of the nonce) and simplifies implementation.
- No additional trusted third party is needed and no further party is contacted during hand-off to the next stage. Every communication takes place directly and solely between initiator and all stages (before starting), respectively between adjacent work chain stages.

For an implementation of the scheme, one more difficulty might occur: attestations of systems may not be a simple single value, however long. These may in reality take the form of a (long) list of hashes, each attesting to a single stage in the boot/loading process. While these obviously can be reduced to a single value, the problem might be that several (or even many) valid variants may exist.

E.g. when a (for this task irrelevant) security update is performed, the previous as well as the current value of a stage should be acceptable. Additionally, some systems might not always be predictable in their load sequence. This means, that a specific attestation can be verified to be valid, but cannot be determined deterministically and uniquely in advance: e.g. drivers may be loaded in varying sequence, which could be irrelevant regarding security. So a list of “every process running” combined with an “original OS+HW+...” should be seen as acceptable and can be verified, but cannot easily be boiled down to a single value in advance. This can be ameliorated by introducing canonicalization: creating a predetermined order for all values involved, thereby ignoring any sequence (e.g. sorting of hashes by their value). But variants, where multiple values are valid, are more difficult to handle, especially if multiple stages/layers of attestation exist: two possible values for the BIOS, three for the OS etc. A countermeasure could be that the attestation is checked inside a trusted subsystem (e.g. a TPM [TCG]) on stage $i+1$), i.e. by the system itself. If this succeeds, the system could replace the complete and verified list by a single (e.g. random stored nonce) value to be used instead. Attestation then does not directly attest the state of a system, but that this state has been securely and in a trustworthy way been verified. However, this requires the trusted subsystem to perform a potentially complex check and trust that subsystem to perform it correctly.

5. Summary and outlook

A system for chaining work instructions, including authentication information, was described and analysed regarding its security properties. This allows to combine a sequence of tasks into a single work package to be handed over consecutively to multiple stages, while simultaneously keeping as much information secret as possible. Additionally, the next stage only then receives the data (its own instructions as well as previous results) if it can prove through attestation that it runs a pre-approved system, i.e. is unmodified and will perform its work as expected.

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AI, CYBERSECURITY AND THE REAL VALUE PROPOSITION FOR BUSINESS: MOVING BEYOND THE HYPE

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Abstract

In today's digital world, cybersecurity is a major concern for businesses everywhere. This paper looks at how artificial intelligence (AI) can help improve cybersecurity measures in nowadays organizations. Through a systematic review, the author identified eight particular use cases where cybersecurity might benefit from AI. Among these use cases belong e.g. enhanced threat detection, automated incident response, user behavior analysis, or application security. By combining AI with human expertise, businesses can better handle cybersecurity challenges and make smarter decisions. While AI has great potential, the technology is often hyped up, being often rather a buzzword in vendor's marketing campaigns. This vendors' pressure then leads to unrealistic expectations of organizations. The goal is to provide a systematic view of AI's role in cybersecurity, helping companies use its strengths while being aware of its limitations.

1. Introduction

In today's digital age, cybersecurity has become a significant concern for organizations across all sectors. The escalating reliance on digital infrastructure, coupled with the increasing sophistication of cyber threats, has made traditional security measures insufficient. Consequently, organizations are driven to explore innovative solutions to protect their assets and operations. Among the emerging technologies, artificial intelligence (AI) stands out for its potential to fortify cybersecurity defenses (Raval et al., 2024). AI components, such as machine learning, natural language processing, and predictive analytics, promise more efficient and effective cybersecurity mechanisms by enabling proactive threat detection and automated response systems.

However, the cybersecurity industry has seen inaccuracy in AI-branded solutions, with vendors often overstating the capabilities and benefits of their products (Content Engine LLC, 2023). This trend has led to AI being frequently used as a marketing buzzword, obscuring the actual value these technologies bring. Organizations must approach AI-driven cybersecurity solutions with caution, ensuring they understand the underlying technologies and their relevance to their specific contexts.

The effectiveness of AI in cybersecurity depends on several factors, including the quality of data used for training algorithms and the sophistication of the AI models (ENISA, 2023).

This paper presents the initial findings of a long-term research initiative focused on the materialization of cybersecurity value for businesses. Given AI's significant influence across organizations and various domains, the starting point of this research is dedicated to the use of AI, specifically identifying security risks associated with deploying AI solutions within organizations. Through extensive research of published studies, the author has already identified eight primary security concerns (Zbořil, 2024):

1. Adversarial attacks - AI models can be manipulated through adversarial attacks, compromising their reliability and safety in critical applications (Raval, 2024).
2. Insufficient data governance leading to data leakage - Poor data governance can result in data leakage, exposing sensitive information and undermining data privacy (Kalodanis, 2023).
3. Data privacy and integrity: Unauthorized access and manipulation of data used by AI systems can lead to privacy breaches and biased outcomes (Nigro, 2023).
4. Model theft and reverse engineering: Unauthorized replication or analysis of AI models can lead to intellectual property theft and expose security vulnerabilities (Mirsky, 2023).
5. Bias and fairness: AI systems may be affected by biases from training data, leading to unfair or discriminatory outcomes (Jia, 2022).
6. Lack of explainability and transparency: The "black box" nature of AI can limit understanding and trust in AI-driven decisions (ENISA, 2023).
7. Compliance and regulatory risks: AI deployments must comply with evolving regulations to avoid legal penalties and operational disruptions (Nature, 2023).
8. Robustness and physical harm: AI systems must be robust to prevent failures that could result in physical harm or financial losses (Zaman et al., 2021).

Organizations must incorporate these risks into their decision-making processes regarding the adoption and implementation of AI. Failure to consider these potential risks exposes organizations to potential business disruptions (Nigmatov & Pradeep, 2023). Nevertheless, AI is simultaneously highlighted for its potential to enhance cybersecurity mechanisms.

To realize the tangible benefits of AI in cybersecurity, organizations must adopt a balanced perspective, recognizing both the potential and limitations of these technologies. By investing in robust data governance frameworks, adversarial training, explainable AI research, and continuous compliance monitoring, organizations can enhance the security posture of their AI-driven cybersecurity solutions (Hannecke, 2023). This approach enables businesses to make informed decisions regarding the integration of AI into their security strategies, moving beyond the hype to leverage AI's true value in protecting against evolving cyber threats.

This paper critically reviews the usage of AI in cybersecurity, identifying areas where AI can contribute to enhancing security postures while also highlighting the limitations and risks associated with its deployment. By adopting a balanced perspective, this research aims to provide insights that enable businesses to make more informed decisions regarding the integration of AI into their cybersecurity strategies.

2. Methodology

This research employs a comprehensive literature review methodology, including analysis of academic studies, industry reports and case studies, with the objective to synthesize current knowledge on the real security benefits of integrating AI into cybersecurity mechanisms.

The data gathering was primarily conducted based on research on Scopus and Web of Science databases joint with leveraging AI for research through the ResearchRabbit platform. The most searches were directed to the keywords related to the combinations of „AI“, „cybersecurity/IT security“, „benefits“. Due to the fact that AI is very progressive topic, the searches were limited to the publications from last 5 years. By integrating findings from both academic and industry sources, this research offers a comprehensive view of the security challenges tied to AI integration in cybersecurity. The gathered data analysis is conducted through a structured thematic approach, designed to uncover recurring themes and insights from the literature.

3. Research

This section is split into two subsequent parts where the first one introduces the particular use cases (areas of usage) where AI is proclaimed that it brings benefits to cybersecurity measures, whereas the second one critically reviews the real benefit of AI solutions for cybersecurity practise.

3.1 Security Areas with Potential for AI

The integration of AI into cybersecurity practices has markedly transformed the landscape of organizational defense mechanisms, promising enhanced efficiency and innovation. This section explores the primary usage of AI for the cybersecurity purposes. However, the real impact of AI for cybersecurity does not always meet the benefits proclaimed by technology vendors. Below is an overview of the proclaimed security benefits connected with the deployment of AI-driven cybersecurity solutions within organizations. Simultaneously, the author also analyzed the benefits from more critical perspective, looking also on the weak points, security risks and overpromising solutions that are impressive when during their promotion, however, the reality looks different.

Use case 1 – Enhanced Threat Detection and Response:

AI boosts the accuracy and speed of threat detection by analyzing vast amounts of data in real-time, identifying patterns, and spotting anomalies that might signal cyber threats. It can process and correlate data from various sources, like network traffic, user behavior, and system logs, to uncover sophisticated threats that traditional methods might miss. This capability helps organizations reduce the risk of data breaches and cyber attacks, protecting sensitive information and maintaining customer trust. Faster threat detection leads to quicker response times, minimizing potential damage and downtime. Unlike traditional security systems that rely on predefined rules and signatures, AI can learn and adapt to new patterns, making it more effective in identifying unknown threats and reducing false positives. (Dhanushkodi & Thejas, 2024; Sharma, 2024; Thapaliya & Bokani, 2024)

One special area is detection network anomalies. By establishing baseline patterns of normal network behavior, AI systems can identify deviations like unusual data transfers, unauthorized access attempts, or abnormal traffic patterns. Early detection of network anomalies prevents potential attacks and minimizes the impact on business operations, maintaining network integrity and ensuring the availability of critical services. Non-AI systems may rely on static rules and thresholds, which can be ineffective in detecting dynamic and evolving threats. (Alin et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2022)

Use case 2 –Automated Incident Response:

AI automates the incident response process, cutting down the time needed to identify and mitigate threats. It can analyze security events, prioritize incidents based on severity, and initiate predefined response actions, like isolating affected systems or blocking malicious traffic. This automation reduces the workload on security teams, allowing them to focus on more complex tasks and strategic initiatives. Faster incident response minimizes the impact of cyber attacks, reducing recovery costs and maintaining business continuity. Manual incident response can be time-consuming and prone to human error, but AI-driven automation ensures consistent and rapid responses, improving overall efficiency and effectiveness. While conventional systems already offer certain automation, AI significantly enhances this by leveraging machine learning to detect new threats, adapt to evolving attack patterns, and make real-time decisions that are based on contextual analysis. Unlike rule-based systems, AI can learn from past incidents and continuously improve its response mechanisms. (Ismail, 2024; Bisht, 2024)

Use case 3 – Predictive Analytics:

AI uses predictive modeling techniques to anticipate potential cyber threats based on historical data and patterns. By analyzing past incidents and identifying trends, AI can forecast future threats and recommend proactive measures to strengthen defenses. This helps organizations stay ahead of cyber threats by implementing preventive measures before attacks occur, reducing the likelihood of successful attacks and enhancing overall security posture. Traditional methods often react to threats after they occur, leaving organizations vulnerable to new attacks. AI's predictive capabilities enable a forward-looking approach, improving readiness and resilience, not only by integrating real-time threat intelligence, allowing for dynamic risk prioritization and faster decision-making. This helps security teams stay focused on the most critical vulnerabilities, optimize resource allocation, and improve incident readiness. (Samia et al., 2024; Madala et al., 2023)

Use case 4 – User Behavioral Analysis:

AI algorithms analyze user behavior and network activity to identify deviations from normal patterns, helping detect insider threats and advanced persistent threats (APTs) that might bypass traditional security systems. AI can continuously monitor and learn from user interactions, adapting its detection mechanisms over time. AI enhances threat detection by correlating behavioral anomalies with contextual data – such as time of access, device type, or location – enabling more accurate risk assessments. It can also reduce false positives by distinguishing between legitimate unusual behavior and actual threats, improving alert quality and reducing alert fatigue among analysts. Over time, AI builds a dynamic behavioral baseline for each user, allowing for personalized security monitoring that evolves with organizational changes. Early detection of insider threats and APTs prevents significant damage and data loss, safeguarding intellectual property and sensitive information, and maintaining operational integrity and compliance with regulations. Non-AI systems may struggle to detect behavioral anomalies, especially in large and complex networks. AI's ability to learn and adapt to user behavior makes it more effective in identifying suspicious activities. (Olabanji et al., 2024; Nasir et al., 2021)

Use case 5 – Vulnerability Management:

AI helps identify and prioritize vulnerabilities in systems and networks by scanning and analyzing vast amounts of data. It can assess the severity of vulnerabilities and recommend remediation actions, helping organizations allocate resources effectively. Efficient vulnerability management reduces the risk of exploitation and ensures timely patching of critical vulnerabilities, maintaining a robust security posture and avoiding costly breaches. Traditional vulnerability management relies on manual processes and predefined rules, which can be slow and inefficient. AI's ability to analyze large

datasets and prioritize vulnerabilities enhances accuracy and speed. (Nath, 2024; Komaragiri & Edward, 2022)

Use case 6 – Application Security:

AI significantly enhances application security by continuously monitoring and analyzing application behavior to detect and prevent vulnerabilities and malicious activities. AI systems can identify unusual patterns and anomalies in application usage, such as unauthorized access attempts, data exfiltration, or code injection attacks. By leveraging machine learning algorithms, AI can predict potential security threats and recommend proactive measures to mitigate risks. This capability helps organizations protect their applications from exploitation, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of data. AI-driven application security reduces the likelihood of successful attacks, minimizes downtime, and maintains user trust. Traditional application security methods often rely on static rules and manual monitoring, which can be insufficient in detecting dynamic and evolving threats. AI's ability to learn and adapt to new attack vectors makes it more effective in safeguarding applications against sophisticated threats. (Bhimanapati et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2021)

Use case 7 – Compliance & Information Security Management (ISM):

AI plays a crucial role in enhancing compliance and ISM by automating the monitoring and enforcement of security policies and regulatory requirements. AI systems can analyze vast amounts of data to improve compliance with industry standards, such as GDPR, HIPAA, and ISO 27001. By continuously monitoring security controls and identifying deviations from compliance requirements, AI helps organizations maintain a robust security posture and avoid costly penalties. AI-driven ISM improves the accuracy and efficiency of compliance audits, reducing the burden on security teams and ensuring timely remediation of vulnerabilities. Traditional compliance and ISM methods often involve manual processes and periodic audits, which can be time-consuming and prone to human error. AI's ability to automate and streamline compliance monitoring enhances overall security management, ensuring organizations stay compliant with regulatory standards and protect sensitive information. (Alevizos & Ta, 2024; Reddy, 2024)

3.2 Critical Review of Real Value Proposition for Business

While artificial intelligence has been researched since the mid-20th century, the recent hype surrounding AI has led to its usage as a buzzword, often overshadowing its real value proposition for businesses (Wojnar & Zbořil, 2024). Even though AI has the potential to enhance cybersecurity measures, it is often marketed as a silver bullet solution, creating unrealistic expectations (Taddeo et al., 2019).

AI solutions are not plug-and-play technologies. They often require significant customization and additional training to adapt to the specific environment of an organization. Without this adaptation, AI tools may underperform or fail to address the organization's actual security needs.

Furthermore, the hype surrounding AI in cybersecurity often leads to unreasonable expectations. Marketing campaigns and media coverage tend to exaggerate AI's capabilities, presenting it as a cure-all for cybersecurity challenges. This can lead to disappointment when AI systems fail to deliver on these promises. AI systems require high-quality data to function effectively. In cybersecurity, data can be noisy, incomplete, or biased, affecting the accuracy of AI predictions. AI algorithms can inherit biases present in training data, leading to discriminatory outcomes. Implementing AI solutions in cybersecurity requires significant expertise and resources, which may not be available to all organizations (Mmaduekwe, 2024; Mohammed, 2024). An example is the Use Case 7 - Compliance & Information Security Management (ISM) – where the people who create the AI solution might not

have experience in ISM and thus, the solution might not be trained for the traditional burdens in development of information security system (ISMS) / security governance in organizations.

Moreover, over-reliance on AI can introduce new vulnerabilities. Organizations may depend heavily on AI for cybersecurity, assuming it will provide comprehensive protection. However, AI lacks human intuition, business context, and ethical awareness. It can create blind spots in defenses, as automated systems may fail to adapt to nuanced threats or understand intent (Taddeo et al., 2019). This over-reliance can undermine security efforts, as AI systems are only as good as the data they learn from and the algorithms they use. When AI is treated as unmistakable, it can lead to complacency and reduced human readiness, ultimately weakening cybersecurity measures. (Zbořil, 2024)

While AI holds promise for enhancing cybersecurity measures, it is not a panacea. Businesses must approach AI with realistic expectations and understand its limitations. A balanced approach that combines human expertise with AI tools is essential for effective cybersecurity. Over-reliance on AI can lead to negative feedback, as organizations may depend on it without achieving the promised value, ultimately compromising their security posture (Enholm, 2021).

4. Conclusion

The idea that companies can simply activate AI and trust it to automatically protect their systems from any threat is overly simplistic and potentially hazardous. This approach can foster a false sense of security and lead to the neglect of other vital components of a robust security strategy. The truth is, AI isn't perfect – it can be tricked, exploited, or bypassed by clever attackers. If companies depend too much on AI and ignore basic security principles and the human element, they are opening themselves up to new cyber threats. Plus, using AI without carefully considering the risks and ethical implications can lead to problems like privacy breaches or biased algorithms. Organizations need to be cautious, integrating AI into a broader security strategy rather than replacing it.

AI systems further require additional training and fine-tuning to adapt to the specific use-cases and context in which they are deployed. This adaptation process can be technically complex, resource-demanding, and may require skilled specialists with expertise in both cybersecurity and AI. These factors can significantly increase the cost and complexity of implementation, which organizations must take into consideration when planning AI integration.

It's important for organizations to avoid falling for marketing hype and really think about what AI can and can't do. Before embracing AI, they should evaluate the specific issues AI can address, its limitations, and how to effectively incorporate it into a holistic security framework that includes technological, procedural, and human elements. In the end, while artificial intelligence can truly transform cybersecurity, organizations should be careful not to get caught up in promises that cannot be delivered in real.

As follow up on this paper, the author will use the results as part of the long-term research aimed to materialization of cybersecurity value for business. Moreover, a potential extension of this research lies in analyzing the gap between the marketing claims of AI-powered security technologies and their actual performance and usage.

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APPLYING PROTECTION MOTIVATION THEORY TO ENHANCE ADHERENCE TO ONLINE SECURITY PRACTICES

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Keywords

Protection motivation theory; online security; threat appraisal; coping appraisal

Abstract

With the increasing frequency and sophistication of cyber threats, individual compliance with online security practices has become a critical factor in organizational and societal cybersecurity. This article explores the application of Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) as a theoretical framework for understanding and influencing user behavior in the context of online security. We examine the core components of PMT—threat appraisal and coping appraisal—and their predictive power in shaping security-related intentions and behaviors. By synthesizing findings from empirical studies and incorporating original survey-based research, we highlight determinants of user motivation to engage in following online security measures. We also explore how these findings can be translated into actionable strategies.

1. Introduction

As digital technologies permeate nearly all aspects of life, individuals face growing exposure to online security threats. Despite the availability of advanced technical solutions—such as intrusion detection systems, firewalls, automation, artificial intelligence and encryption protocols—human behavior continues to represent a significant point of vulnerability (Moustafa et al., 2021), (Kim & Kim, 2024). Even well-informed users sometimes bypass security mechanisms for the sake of convenience, creating an ongoing challenge for security professionals and policymakers. Research in behavioral cybersecurity has emphasized the need to account for psychological, emotional, and social variables that influence individuals' compliance with recommended practices.

In this context, Protection Motivation Theory (PMT), developed by Rogers (1975) and revised in 1983 (Rogers et al., 1983) to explain individual health behavior, offers a compelling framework for understanding how users evaluate cyber threats and determine whether to engage in protective actions. The theory's emphasis on cognitive appraisal processes aligns well with the decision-making challenges posed by cybersecurity behavior, making PMT a relevant model in the digital age. Its adaptability across diverse domains of behavior—including health, environment, and now cybersecurity—demonstrates its conceptual strength. Moreover, PMT allows for nuanced

understanding of motivational and deterrent factors, providing a diagnostic lens for designing personalized security interventions.

While this article includes several recommendations for improving online security behavior based on PMT, it is important to clarify that not all of them emerge directly from our survey data. Some proposed interventions are supported by the correlations identified in our findings, particularly those related to coping appraisal constructs. Others are theoretically grounded in PMT or derived from related literature in behavioral science and information security.

2. Theoretical Background: Protection Motivation Theory

Protection Motivation Theory posits that individuals are motivated to protect themselves from harm when they cognitively appraise both the nature of the threat and their ability to cope with it. These appraisals are broken down into two core dimensions:

Threat Appraisal, which assesses the danger posed by a cyber threat and includes:

- Perceived severity: an individual's judgment regarding the seriousness of the consequences if the threat materializes.
- Perceived vulnerability: an individual's belief about their likelihood of being personally affected.
- Rewards of non-compliance: benefits associated with not taking protective action, such as convenience or saved time.

Coping Appraisal, which evaluates one's ability to deal with the threat, consisting of:

- Response efficacy: the perceived effectiveness of the recommended protective behavior.
- Self-efficacy: the individual's confidence in their ability to carry out the behavior.
- Response costs: the perceived barriers or drawbacks to engaging in the behavior, such as time, effort, or financial resources.

Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) suggests that individuals are more likely to engage in protective behaviors when they perceive a threat as both severe and personally relevant, when they do not expect to gain any rewards from non-compliance, and when they believe that taking protective action is both effective and affordable.

3. PMT and Online Security Compliance

Over the past two decades, PMT has been applied in a range of contexts including health communication (Floyd et al., 2000), environmental behavior (McCaughey et al., 2017), and increasingly, information security. Digitalisation and advancements of technologies triggered the wide employment of the protection motivation theory in the information systems management field over the last two decades. Considering the debates about the threats that technology could pose for users (e.g. pretexting, phishing, targeted malware, cyberattacks) and organisations (Verkijika, 2018), (Ifinedo, 2012), (Thompson et al., 2017), the theory was useful in understanding the factors that make individuals avoid technology-related threats (Crossler, 2010). Numerous empirical studies support the theory's utility in explaining user behavior in online environments. In the realm of cybersecurity, PMT has been used to investigate behaviors such as password hygiene, email safety, and software maintenance. The modular nature of PMT also allows integration with other behavior change theories

such as the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) or the Health Belief Model (Janz & Becker, 1984), offering rich potential for interdisciplinary inquiry. The motivation to follow an adaptive behaviour is supported by perceived threats and individuals' appeal for avoiding the negative consequences of not engaging in the behaviour (Weinstein, 1993). The importance of volitional processes— that is, the deliberate decision and commitment to follow through on protective intentions despite possible distractions or effort—highlighted by Milne et al. (2002), complements PMT's distinction between wanting to act (motivation) and being capable of acting (coping).

A foundational study by Chenoweth et al. (2009) applied PMT to understand adoption behavior regarding anti-spyware software. Through a rigorous structural equation modelling approach, the study confirmed that perceived vulnerability, perceived severity, response efficacy, and response cost significantly influenced users' intention to adopt protective technologies. Notably, self-efficacy was found to be less influential, suggesting context-specific variance in PMT variables. Their results are further reinforced by cross-study comparisons that confirm PMT's applicability to diverse forms of cybersecurity behaviors.

Additionally, (Woon et al., 2005) extended PMT to home wireless security, identifying response efficacy and self-efficacy as significant predictors of secure behavior. Workman et al. (2008) used PMT to explain security lapses and found that perceived threat and coping appraisal factors influenced compliance with security protocols. These studies illustrate the model's versatility across multiple cybersecurity domains.

However, no study has addressed the motivation to adopt personal information security measures in general.

4. Survey-Based Research on PMT and Online Security

To further examine the explanatory power of PMT in the context of online security, we conducted a survey among 120 young individuals (20-33 years). The aim was to assess how PMT constructs predict online security behavior and to validate the framework's relevance in practical cybersecurity scenarios. In addition, we aimed to investigate the effects of socio-demographic factors (age, gender) on security behavior and intention.

4.1 Methodology

A structured, self-administered questionnaire was disseminated through online platforms and university networks, especially the networks of Prague University of Economics and Business. This means that the participants were not exclusively IT students, although it can be assumed that most of them were university students. Participants were asked to respond using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The items measured constructs derived from PMT. Questions were informed by previous PMT applications, including those used by Chenoweth et al. (2009). Since students were instructed to distribute the questionnaire beyond their own circles, the results reflect a broader range of perspectives, not just their own. The survey also collected demographic data (age, gender).

4.2 Questionnaire Structure

The questionnaire included seven items:

Behavioral Intention: I intend to follow the principles of online security.

Perceived Severity: A cyber attack on my personal accounts could lead to identity theft or financial loss.

Perceived Vulnerability: It is likely that I will become a victim of an online security breach.

Reported Behavior: I follow the principles of online security.

Response Cost: Following online security practices takes too much time or effort.

Response Efficacy: Protecting my devices and accounts significantly reduces the chances of a successful cyber attack.

Self-Efficacy: I feel capable of recognizing and avoiding online security threats.

We excluded the rewards of non-compliance, as this aspect is already covered by the concept of response cost.

5. Results

Table 1. PMT factors

PMT factor	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Behavioral_Intention	120	3,58	1,18
Perceived_Severity	120	3,70	0,97
Perceived_Vulnerability	120	2,79	1,31
Reported_Behavior	120	3,25	1,29
Response_Cost	120	3,07	1,32
Response_Efficacy	120	3,91	1,13
Self_Efficacy	120	3,55	1,20

Table 2. PMT factors correlations (indicates significance at the 1% level.)**

		Beh. Int.	Rep. Beh.	Perc. Severity	Perc. Vuln.	Response Cost	Response Efficacy	Self Efficacy
Beh. Int.	r_s	1,00	0,83**	0,34**	0,34**	-0,34**	0,61**	0,54**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
Rep. Beh.	r_s	0,83**	1,00	0,25**	0,27**	-0,27**	0,54**	0,49**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0,00		0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00

5.1 Key Findings

The descriptive analysis indicates that perceived response efficacy was rated the highest ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 1.13$), followed by perceived severity ($M = 3.70$, $SD = 0.97$), and moderate to high levels of self-reported behavioral intention ($M = 3.58$, $SD = 1.18$) and self-efficacy ($M = 3.55$, $SD = 1.20$).

Reported security behavior was somewhat lower ($M = 3.25$, $SD = 1.29$), while perceived vulnerability was notably the lowest ($M = 2.79$, $SD = 1.31$), suggesting that many users do not consider themselves likely targets of cyberattacks.

Key correlational findings (Spearman's r_s) include:

Behavioral intention and reported behavior were strongly correlated ($r_s = 0.83$, $p < .001$), supporting the theoretical assumption that intention is a primary predictor of action. Response efficacy was the strongest individual predictor of both behavioral intention ($r_s = 0.61$, $p < .001$) and reported behavior ($r_s = 0.54$, $p < .001$), confirming its central role in coping appraisal as posited by PMT. Self-efficacy also showed substantial effects, correlating with behavioral intention ($r_s = 0.54$, $p < .001$) and reported behavior ($r_s = 0.49$, $p < .001$), although its effect was somewhat weaker than that of response efficacy. Response cost showed a negative correlation with both intention ($r_s = -0.34$, $p < .001$) and behavior ($r_s = -0.27$, $p < .001$), in line with the theoretical prediction that perceived barriers reduce motivation to engage in protective actions. Perceived severity and perceived vulnerability were moderately correlated with both behavioral intention (severity: $r_s = 0.34$; vulnerability: $r_s = 0.34$) and behavior (severity: $r_s = 0.25$; vulnerability: $r_s = 0.27$), suggesting a meaningful but less dominant role of threat appraisal in explaining security behavior.

The average age of respondents was 24,98 years ($SD=2,82$), 57% males, 43% females. Neither age, nor gender was correlated with the PMT questions.

These findings reinforce the core structure of PMT. Coping appraisal constructs (particularly response efficacy and self-efficacy) demonstrated the strongest relationships with cybersecurity behavior, while threat appraisal variables contributed more modestly. The data suggest that interventions should prioritize boosting users' confidence and reducing friction in security-related tasks, rather than relying solely on fear-based messaging.

6. Designing Effective Interventions

The following interventions are suggested in light of both our findings and established research in the PMT literature. Where direct empirical support from our survey is limited, we note that the proposal is based on theoretical assumptions or prior studies.

Focus on Response Efficacy in Awareness Campaigns: Our data show that response efficacy was the strongest predictor of both behavioral intention ($r_s = 0.61$, $p < 0.001$) and reported behavior ($r_s = 0.54$, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that awareness efforts should primarily highlight the effectiveness of protective actions. While perceived severity also showed some correlation ($r_h = 0.34$ with intention), its effect was comparatively weaker. Therefore, although messaging about threat severity may be helpful, emphasis should be placed on efficacy to maximize motivational impact.

User-Centric Training to Enhance Self-Efficacy: Self-efficacy was another strong correlate of both behavioral intention ($r_h = 0.54$) and reported behavior ($r_h = 0.49$), indicating that users' confidence in their own abilities plays a central role. While our survey did not directly evaluate the effects of training, prior PMT-based studies (e.g., Khan et al., 2023) have shown that interactive learning and simulations can foster self-efficacy. Hence, we recommend user-centric formats such as gamified learning or scenario-based tutorials, especially for individuals with lower prior experience.

Streamlining Security Tasks to Reduce Response Costs: Although response cost demonstrated a negative correlation with both intention ($r_h = -0.34$) and behavior ($r_h = -0.27$), its predictive power was weaker than efficacy-related factors. Nonetheless, this still supports the notion that reducing

friction—e.g., via automation or preconfigured defaults—can support behavior change, especially when paired with stronger efficacy messaging.

Behavioral Nudges: Our data do not provide direct evidence for the efficacy of nudges. However, drawing on the broader behavioral science literature, small cues (e.g., reminders or progress tracking) are often effective in sustaining behavior where motivation is present but inconsistent. This recommendation is therefore extrapolated from theoretical alignment with volitional processes in PMT (Milne et al., 2002).

Policy Framing: While our data did not include questions about organizational policies, PMT suggests that supportive environments reduce response costs and increase perceived control. Therefore, this suggestion stems from the conceptual framework rather than from our dataset, and we acknowledge it as a theoretically motivated extension.

Feedback Mechanisms: We did not test this empirically, but the idea that warning messages or success confirmations might enhance perceived response efficacy is supported by user experience studies outside of PMT. We cite this as a potential area for future empirical validation.

Future research should empirically test these intervention types using experimental or longitudinal designs to evaluate their causal effectiveness in enhancing security behavior in real-world settings.

7. Limitations and Future Research

While this study contributes to a growing body of literature validating PMT in cybersecurity contexts, it is not without limitations. The use of self-reported data introduces potential biases, including social desirability and recall errors. Additionally, the study captures intended or claimed behaviors rather than actual observed ones, which may differ in practice. The sample, although somewhat diverse, consisted predominantly of individuals with some level of IT affinity, such as students. As such, it may not adequately represent the broader or global population, particularly older users or those working in non-IT occupations. Future research should explore:

- Longitudinal studies to assess behavior over time,
- Experimental designs testing the causal impact of PMT-based interventions,
- Integration of complementary frameworks such as the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB),
- Cross-cultural comparisons to examine the influence of sociocultural context on PMT constructs,
- Inclusion of emotional and affective components beyond cognitive appraisals,
- Investigation of organizational variables such as management support, policy enforcement, and training availability.

8. Conclusion

Protection Motivation Theory offers a robust and flexible framework for understanding the cognitive and motivational factors that influence cybersecurity behavior. This paper extends prior work by applying PMT to a contemporary survey of digital users and validates its constructs in a cybersecurity context. The inclusion of findings from other studies enhances the theoretical foundation and illustrates the versatility of the model.

As cyber threats continue to proliferate in complexity and scale, integrating PMT into awareness campaigns, training programs, and system design will be vital for fostering a culture of security. Policymakers, developers, and educators should consider the multifaceted insights PMT provides to better align security solutions with human behavior. A theory-driven approach, grounded in psychological science, holds great promise for advancing both research and practice in cybersecurity. Ultimately, a deeper understanding of the cognitive mechanisms underlying security behavior is essential for promoting resilient digital ecosystems.

In addition, the growing role of artificial intelligence in both cybersecurity defenses and social engineering attacks calls for renewed attention to user behavior. AI-powered systems can support behaviorally adaptive security interfaces, personalized alerts, and real-time detection of risky actions. However, they also raise new challenges, such as deepfake-driven phishing or AI-assisted fraud, which may alter perceived threats and coping capacities.

Ultimately, a deeper understanding of the cognitive mechanisms underlying security behavior—especially in interaction with intelligent systems—is essential for promoting resilient digital ecosystems.

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**ETHICAL ASPECTS OF AI:
RESEARCH AND USAGE**

SELECTED ETHICAL ASPECTS OF AUTHORSHIP OF THE USE OF AI PRODUCTS

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Abstract

The use of AI brings with it many conveniences and advantages for every AI user. However, information processing is associated with the quantity and quality of resources and the ways in which artificial intelligence learns. Therefore, there are many new questions and challenges in scientific work. Among them are text authorship and bias. The article deals with these two phenomena in connection with scientific practice.

1. Introduction.

The development of the use of AI in many areas has become an integral part of scientific work and scientific research.

In this article, I will discuss the two most debatable threats to the use of AI in science, which are bias and privacy protection.

AI is most often used in the creation of science to process large volumes of data, perform simulations and predictions that would be unfeasible for traditional research methods. With the development of artificial intelligence (AI), new horizons are opening up in the field of science, from medicine to astrophysics to biotechnology. AI technologies allow scientists to process huge amounts of data, perform simulations and predictions that would be unfeasible for traditional research methods. However, with this technological revolution also come significant ethical challenges that deserve attention to ensure that the use of AI in science is not only effective, but also responsible. (Katrencik, 2023)

2. Selected references for ethical principles for the use of artificial intelligence in scientific research

The use of artificial intelligence in scientific research should be guided by broad ethical principles and guidelines. Various international and national frameworks provide an important basis for the responsible and ethical use of AI. The UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence (UNESCO, 2021) presents ten core principles that emphasize a human rights-based

approach to the ethics of AI. These principles include proportionality and non-harmfulness, safety and security, the right to privacy and data protection, multi-stakeholder and adaptive governance and collaboration, responsibility and accountability, transparency and explainability, human oversight and determination, sustainability, information and literacy, and equity and non-discrimination (UNESCO, 2021). Together, these principles form the basis for the ethical use of AI systems, always keeping in mind the importance of human oversight. (UNESCO, 2021)(Fjelland, 2020)

In addition, the Belmont Report (IBM, 2024) (Giroux, 2022), originally developed for human research, is proposed as a historical precedent for ethical research in AI. The three core principles of the Belmont Report – respect for persons, beneficence and justice – could be directly applied to AI research involving human subjects, thereby promoting more trustworthy and responsible uses of AI. Respect for persons would require informed consent from individuals whose data is used to train AI systems. Beneficence would mean designing studies to minimize risks to participants, and justice would require fair selection of subjects, avoiding inappropriate exclusion that can lead to bias in the data. (IBM, 2024)(Giroux, 2022)

IBM has set out three guiding principles for the development of data and AI: the purpose of AI is to augment human intelligence, data and knowledge belong to their creators, and AI systems must be transparent and explainable (IBM, 2024). These principles emphasize collaboration between humans and AI, ownership of data, and the importance of transparency in AI recommendations (IBM, 2024). Similarly, the Principles for the Ethical Use of AI in the United Nations System (CEB, 2024) are based on UNESCO recommendations and highlight ten principles rooted in ethics and human rights.

2.1. Bias

One of the biggest risks when using AI in scientific research is the potential presence of bias. Algorithms are built on historical data, and if that data contains biases (such as discrimination against certain groups or unfair representations), AI can carry them into its decisions. This can be particularly dangerous in medicine, where incorrect or unfair decisions can lead to serious consequences for individuals or even entire populations.

An example would be an algorithm that helps diagnose diseases but has been trained on data that only includes certain ethnic groups, which may lead to lower diagnostic accuracy in patients from other ethnic groups. The solution to this challenge is to ensure that algorithms are trained on diverse and representative data and that they are regularly monitored and updated.

Bias can seriously affect the veracity of information in relation to investing. (Katrenčík, 2018)

Three categories of bias in computer systems have been developed from real-world case studies: pre-existing, technical, and emergent. Pre-existing bias has its roots in social institutions, practices, and attitudes. Technical bias arises from technical constraints on reasoning. Emergent bias arises in the context of use. Although other authors have pointed to bias in specific computer systems and have pointed to a general problem, one solution is to examine the extent of bias and consider how to deal with the presence of bias, and it should be included among a selected set of criteria—including reliability, accuracy, and efficiency—by which the quality of systems used in society should be judged. (Friedman, 1996)

“Respect for persons”, which includes autonomy, refers to the right of an individual to make decisions regarding their physical body and its derivatives (e.g., tissue samples) and their personal information. Autonomy is usually respected through the practice of informed consent. In the context of artificial intelligence, autonomy must be taken into account when using personal health data for the development, training and validation of artificial intelligence systems and when applying artificial intelligence systems in patient care. Many individuals expect transparency and control over their

identified and even anonymised data. In the European Union, the enforcement of means of arbitrary deletion has been demonstrated through their “right to erasure (to be forgotten)”. This could help balance people’s autonomy and the development of artificial intelligence. (Rocher, 2019) Furthermore, as artificial intelligence technologies become increasingly widespread in many areas, concerns may also arise regarding people’s awareness of and consent to AI-assisted diagnostics.

Type bias:

AI bias can manifest in various ways, affecting different demographic groups and societal sectors. Some common types of AI bias include:

1. **Data Bias:** This occurs when the data used to train AI models is not representative of the real world or reflects existing societal biases. For example, if a hiring algorithm is trained on historical data where men were predominantly in leadership roles, it might unfairly favour male candidates. Different types of data bias include:
 - a) Historical bias: Arises from past prejudices reflected in the data.
 - b) Sample bias: Occurs when the training data doesn't accurately represent the population the AI will interact with.
 - c) Label bias: Happens when data labelling is inconsistent or reflects subjective opinions.
 - d) Measurement bias: Occurs due to inaccuracies or incompleteness in data collection and recording.
 - e) Exclusion bias: Arises when certain groups or information are left out of the training data.
 - f) Selection bias: Occurs when the data collection process favours certain groups.
 - g) Coverage bias: A type of selection bias where some groups are underrepresented in the dataset.
 - h) Non-response bias: Another form of selection bias where certain individuals or groups are less likely to participate in data collection.
2. **Algorithmic Bias:** Even with unbiased data, the design of algorithms can introduce bias. This can happen through the choice of features, how different variables are weighted, or the inherent assumptions in the algorithm's structure.
3. **Human Bias:** The biases and preconceived notions of the people involved in creating, training, and deploying AI systems can unintentionally seep into the technology. This can occur during data labelling, feature selection, or even in how the problem itself is framed. Different types of human bias that can affect AI include:
 - a) Prejudice bias: When societal stereotypes and faulty assumptions are included in the data.
 - b) Recall bias: Occurs during data labelling when labels are applied inconsistently due to subjective observations.
 - c) Confirmation bias: When developers or the AI system itself favours information that confirms pre-existing beliefs.
 - d) Automation bias: The tendency to over-rely on AI systems and disregard contradictory information.
 - e) In-group bias: Favouring individuals or data from groups one identifies with.
 - f) Out-group homogeneity bias: Perceiving members of other groups as more similar than they actually are.
4. **Representation Bias:** This occurs when certain groups are underrepresented or overrepresented in the training data, leading to skewed results for those groups.

5. **Interaction Bias:** Arises from the way users interact with the AI system, where different groups might use the system in ways that lead to biased outcomes.

Causes of AI bias are multifaceted and often interconnected:

- **Biased Training Data:** As mentioned, if the data used to train AI reflects existing societal biases or doesn't represent the diversity of the real world, the AI will likely perpetuate and even amplify these biases. This can stem from historical inequalities, skewed representation, or flawed data collection processes.
- **Flawed Algorithm Design:** The way an algorithm is designed, including the features it prioritizes and how it weighs different factors, can inadvertently introduce bias, even with seemingly neutral data.
- **Human Oversight (or Lack Thereof):** While human review can help catch biases, if the humans involved hold their own biases (conscious or unconscious), these can still influence the AI system. Additionally, a lack of sufficient human oversight can allow biases to go unnoticed and uncorrected.
- **Lack of Diversity in Development Teams:** When AI systems are developed by teams lacking diverse perspectives, unconscious biases are more likely to be embedded in the technology.

Mitigating AI bias is a complex but crucial endeavour. Some strategies include:

- **Ensuring Diverse and Representative Data:** Carefully curating training datasets to accurately reflect the population the AI will serve is essential. This includes actively seeking out and incorporating data from underrepresented groups.
- **Algorithmic Auditing and Transparency:** Regularly testing and evaluating AI systems for bias is crucial. Explainable AI (XAI) techniques can help understand how AI models make decisions, making it easier to identify potential sources of bias.
- **Diverse Development Teams:** Building AI systems with diverse teams can bring a wider range of perspectives to the development process, helping to identify and mitigate potential biases.
- **Feature Engineering and Selection:** Carefully selecting and engineering the features used by the AI model can help avoid proxies for sensitive attributes that might lead to bias.
- **Bias Detection and Correction Techniques:** Various technical methods are being developed to detect and mitigate bias in AI models during training and deployment.
- **Establishing Ethical Guidelines and Governance:** Organizations should prioritize the ethical and responsible use of AI and establish clear guidelines and oversight mechanisms to address bias.
- **Human-in-the-Loop Systems:** Incorporating human review and feedback in the AI development and deployment process can help identify and correct biases. (Rocher, 2019).

2.2 Privacy and data security

All data that is part of the content of the virtual space is always associated with the personalization of the creator of the information, or the person making the information available to the viral space. In fact, every activity is associated with a trace that can be used to trace the author and also trace all data

about the author and also about the place, time of creation of the publication and identification of the device, access point from where these changes to the information occurred.

A special ethical challenge is also the use of AI in scientific research, especially in areas such as genetics or personalized medicine, which often requires access to sensitive personal data. It is essential to ensure the protection of this data to prevent its misuse or leakage. Researchers must adhere to strict ethical and legal standards to protect the privacy of research participants and at the same time ensure that their research does not lead to the creation of algorithms that could encounter privacy problems, such as unauthorized tracking or profiling of individuals.

The phenomenon of anonymity and the investigation of authorship

The phenomenon of anonymity is, as the Internet has grown, so have questions of privacy and authorship. Ensuring anonymity and authorship allows individual Internet users to carry out their online activities in comfort and privacy (Kambourakis, 2014). According to Burkell (Anonymity in Behavioural Research: Not Being Unnamed, But Being Unknown, 2006), anonymity is at one level synonymous with the impossibility of identifying an individual. After all, the word anonymous itself means “without a name”. However, if we interpret the term in a slightly broader sense, we realize that it also includes a meaning reflecting social distance and at the same time a lack of distinguishableness from those around us. In the first sense, anonymity contrasts with the condition of being named, and in the second with the state of being known (Burkell, 2006). When considering how anonymity affects user behavior on the Internet, according to Burkell (2006), it is useful to look at it from three main perspectives: 1. Name anonymity, defined as the non-disclosure of identifying information, has relatively clear behavioral consequences: people are willing to provide sensitive information and are more likely to be honest (Burkell, 2006). 2. Visual anonymity, mainly related to facial unrecognition, can lead to a reduced perception of interpersonal obligations, a greater willingness to reveal oneself, higher levels of aggression and a lower willingness to help in interpersonal interactions (Burkell, 2006). 3. Anonymity of actions consists in the fact that an individual’s actions are either not seen or cannot be attributed to him. The consequence of this anonymity is a great sense of freedom and independence associated with the lowest possible level of responsibility (Burkell, 2006).

In some areas, information about the authorship (ownership) of information is even required. For example, when we are looking for information about the originator or owner of a thing or statement. (Compare Zatrochová, 2021)

In the scientific field, anonymity is an unwanted phenomenon. Authors want to be identified with their ideas by authorship, because it is their property.

The use of AI is problematic in relation to the anonymization of the author. The way in which AI creates content information, despite the method of traceability, it is impossible to fully identify authorship, and so what was supposed to serve the development becomes a direct threat to the values for which online repositories and platforms for sharing information, knowledge and processes in science were created.

There are still areas in which we want to maintain anonymity, it is even required, because it concerns personal information such as health, social status, origin and even opinions and ideas. Building ethics is necessary from the beginning of education. (Osvaldová, 2022)

3. Methodology

In the research, we selected the most commonly perceived threats to the use of AI in scientific practice. We identified the most common threats: autonomy, bias, transparency, privacy protection

and employment outflow. We evaluated selected aspects among academics in Slovakia at the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava.

We conducted the research on a sample of 100 academic respondents in various academic positions and in various years of study. The main distribution of the sample was 50 academics and 50 students.

The research was conducted in the months of December 2024 - January 2025.

A maximalist scale of 1-5 was chosen.

As the first research task, we dealt with the arrangement of threats. In the research, I will deal with the most perceived threats and these are the ones identified in the first places from the research: bias and text authorship.

We investigated how respondents perceive the importance of truth or error in statements found using AI and how they perceive the principles of authorship in content creation.

4. Research

We have established the following hypothesis:

H0: Respondents in the monitored sets have comparable perceptions of bias.

H1: Respondents in the monitored sets do not have comparable perceptions of bias.

To test the hypotheses, the Anova test was used at a significance level of 0.05. The test results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 - ANOVA program output

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Students	50	276	3,65	0,7875
Academics	50	290	3,83	0,7050

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	23,89776	8	2,98722	4,081064	9,55E-05	1,954029
Within Groups	433,3269	592	0,731971	H1		
Total	457,2246	600				

Source: own processing

Based on the values of F and Fcrit, we recommend accepting the alternative hypothesis H1.

H1: Respondents in the monitored sets do not have comparable perceptions of bias. Student respondents show significant differences in perceptions of bias threat.

Using the correlation coefficient, they examined the degree of agreement between perceptions of bias threat and authorship (anonymity).

Table 2- Corelations

	Score Q1	Average Q	r
Students	75,2	67,64706	0,30443
Academics	75,2	68,72941	0,70058

Source: own processing

The correlation shows that academics are more concerned about the loss of the relationship between information and authorship than students.

5. Conclusion

We can assume that students do not place as much emphasis on attribution and do not fear the loss of authorship to the same extent as academics.

This is a natural consequence of the importance of consequences. We can therefore assume that these things arose on the basis that the threat to the existence of students in relation to the results of their work is not as great as for academics. The use of AI in science offers great potential for accelerating discoveries and progress in various fields. However, like any new technology, it also brings with it a number of ethical challenges. It is essential that scientists, developers and regulators work together to create frameworks that ensure the responsible and ethical use of AI. Only in this way can we avoid potential negative consequences and maximize the benefits of this technology for society.

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PERCEPTIONS AND ATTITUDES OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS TOWARDS ETHICAL ASPECTS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Artificial intelligence (AI); survey research; ethics; higher education

Abstract

As artificial intelligence (AI) becomes increasingly integrated into higher education, understanding how students perceive, use, and evaluate AI tools is important for future responsible educational practices. This study investigates university students' self-perceived knowledge of AI, frequency of use of AI tools, acceptance of AI in academic contexts, and ethical concerns about AI technologies. A total of 103 undergraduate students participated in an online survey, distributed to technical (STEM) and non-technical universities. Our findings showed that students in STEM programs reported significantly higher levels of self-assessed AI knowledge than their non-STEM peers, although there was no significant difference in the actual frequency of use between these groups. Frequent users were more accepting of AI-assisted academic tasks, especially in the generation of outlines for the final thesis. In particular, students expressing stronger ethical concerns, particularly about data privacy, regulation, and bias - were significantly less likely to support the use of AI in formal academic assessments. This negative correlation emphasizes the importance of ethical awareness in shaping student attitudes toward AI. Overall, the study highlights the need for higher education institutions to not only teach technical competencies related to AI but also to promote critical and ethical engagement with these technologies across all fields of study.

1. Introduction

The accelerated advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) technology has brought to the forefront critical ethical discussions. University students, representing the next generation of professionals and decision-makers across various fields such as information technology, economics, education, and the humanities, offer invaluable perspectives on these emerging AI-driven phenomena. Equipped not only with theoretical insights but also positioned to practically implement AI solutions, these students will directly shape the future trajectory and societal integration of such technologies. It is therefore particularly important, that the society understand these students and make them ready to face these evolving challenges ethically responsible. The goal of this research is to found out, whether the type of study program and frequency of use of AI influence the ethical views of students.

Within the context of higher education, the incorporation of AI technologies has introduced both unprecedented opportunities and new ethical dilemmas, leading to extensive academic debate. While the usage of AI tools offers significant potential to advance personalized educational experiences, this optimism is tempered by legitimate ethical concerns. As author Freeman (2025) states in his research the adoption of AI tools in higher education is more than 90%. The rapid adoption and integration of AI-driven solutions within academic institutions amplify essential issues regarding data privacy, potential biases, and the safeguarding of academic integrity and fairness. For instance, AI systems often require access to large amounts of data, including sensitive personal information, raising challenges in collecting, using, and protecting this data to prevent privacy violations (Annenberg School for Communication and Journalism, 2024). Moreover, because AI algorithms are typically trained on historical data, they often reflect and reproduce inherent societal biases, potentially leading to further marginalization of students from underrepresented groups (Bennett, S., & Bell, T., 2024). Additionally, the use of AI in educational assessments has raised concerns about academic integrity, as students may misrepresent AI-generated outputs as their own work (Frontiers, 2023). These various ethical considerations require careful examination of the role of AI in higher education to ensure that its integration promotes equality, transparency and protection of individual rights.

Yu and Yu (2023) argue that transparency in AI involves openly communicating the systems' parameters, data sources, and potential impacts, all of which are vital to ensuring stakeholder accountability. This perspective is reinforced by Agarwal and colleagues (2024) in their systematic literature review, which highlights the rapid expansion of AI-powered educational tools and the accompanying risks of discrimination and infringement upon educational rights. Additionally, Barnes and Hutson (2024) stress the critical need to tackle inherent biases in AI systems, emphasizing the importance of adopting ethical frameworks designed to ensure fairness and accountability in educational contexts.

The ethical implementation of AI also requires solving challenges related to preserving academic integrity in the context of the growing prevalence of generative AI tools. Duah and McGivern (2024) point out that generative AI technologies can conceal the author and complicate established academic conventions, highlighting the need for universities to implement solid policies that clearly define acceptable AI use. This concern is further supported by Perkins and Roe (2023), who identified a significant lack in institutional guidelines on the impact of AI on academic honesty. As students continue to integrate AI-driven tools into their learning processes, educational institutions must continuously update their academic integrity policy in order to explicitly address these emerging technologies (Perkins & Roe, 2023).

When discussing the intersection of artificial intelligence and education (AI&ED), Holmes et al. (2022) identify three main aspects. First, "learning with AI" involves the use of AI tools to improve teaching and learning processes – often referred to as Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED). Secondly, "learning about AI" refers to understanding the technical operations and development of AI, also recognized as a technological aspect of the literacy of AI. Thirdly, the "preparation for AI" includes understanding and navigation of the social and personal impacts of living in a world increasingly influenced by AI, called the human dimension of the literacy of AI (Holmes et al., 2022).

In addition, effective integration of AI into higher education requires collaboration between all stakeholders. Holmes and his colleagues (2023) emphasize the importance of considering the various perspectives of teachers, students and administrators when formulating ethical frameworks for the use of AI. They argue that the resolution of ethical complexities associated with AI requires flexible and adaptive guidelines capable of evolving alongside changes in social expectations and technological advances.

Finally, as universities increasingly integrate AI into their activities, it is critical to simultaneously equip students with a clear understanding of the ethical dimensions related to the use of AI. Educational initiatives such as the CHARLIE project (Nidhi et al., 2024) highlight how targeted programs can effectively raise students' awareness of algorithmic biases and responsible AI practices in academic settings. By focusing on ethical education and facilitating open and continuous conversations between all stakeholders, higher education institutions can take advantage of AI's transformational capabilities and proactively address potential risks. As Lisník and Majerník (2023) point out, the integration of strategic management principles with digital tools, including AI and online marketing, is becoming increasingly important for modern organizations navigating data-driven environments.

2. Research Methodology

In designing this study, we used a quantitative framework to capture the nuances of how university students think about ethical issues arising from artificial intelligence. Our first step involved the construction of a structured questionnaire covering demographic information, self-assessment of AI concepts, and a wide range of assessment items focusing on topics such as data privacy, algorithm fairness, and responsible AI use. The instrument was then piloted by a small group of volunteers to ensure its clarity and relevance. Minor amendments to the wording and item arrangement were made based on their feedback, strengthening the reliability of the questionnaire before its full distribution.

The questionnaire itself was divided into several segments. Firstly, participants were asked basic demographic questions (e.g. age, gender, year and field of study), which established a context for later comparisons. Afterwards, they were prompted to assess their own level of familiarity with AI. Here they indicate both how frequently they use AI tools — from everyday use to almost complete avoidance — and what specific applications (such as chatbots, machine translation services or image generators) they encountered. Following this basic section, the survey presented a brief knowledge review. In these topics, students chose answers that tested their ability to differentiate between AI and conventional software or robotic systems and recognize how AI could influence sectors such as health care or finance. This segment provided insights into whether participants' attitudes were based on well-informed perspectives or more general impressions.

However, at the heart of the research were the multiple sets of Likert-scale statements that investigated the respondents' positions on a number of ethically sensitive issues: privacy and data protection, equity and prejudice, regulation and responsibility, personal acceptance and trust in AI and the broader social impact of technological advances. In this case, participants rated their level of agreement on a scale of five points, ranging from “totally disagree” to “totally agree”. Further statements examined participants' views on the use of AI for academic work - an area that raises urgent questions about fraud, plagiarism, and equitable assessment.

The final version of the questionnaire has been distributed via digital channels such as faculty mailing lists and course management systems. In total, we sent more than 400 invitations, but our response rate was around 27% (110 responses). Although the recruitment process was mainly based on convenience and self-selection, we made a concerted effort to include respondents from both technical and non-technical fields. By doing so, we aim to reflect the various perspectives that inevitably shape the ethical considerations of AI — from those who could build such systems to those who encounter them primarily as end users or in broader social contexts. We received a total of 110 responses, but due to the limited participation of master's students, we chose to exclude their responses from our analysis. As a result, our final dataset consisted of 103 answers.

On the basis of the objectives of this study and preliminary research findings, we have formulated the following three hypotheses to be tested:

- *H1*: Students enrolled in *technical (STEM) programs* will report a) *significantly higher self-perceived knowledge* of AI and b) *more frequent AI use of AI* than students in non-technical fields.
- *H2*: Students who *frequently use AI* (e.g. daily or multiple times a week) will show greater acceptance of AI-assisted academic practices (such as generating outlines for assignments or providing test answers) and will show *distinct levels of ethical concern* relative to those who use AI infrequently or not at all.
- *H3*: Students who express *higher levels of ethical concern* — particularly in terms of privacy, potential bias, or misuse - will be *less likely* to support the use of AI in formal academic assessments and courses, implying a *negative correlation* between perceived ethical risk and acceptance of AI for academic purposes.

3. Results

To test Hypothesis 1 (H1), we examined whether students enrolled in technical (STEM) study programs reported (a) significantly higher self-perceived knowledge of artificial intelligence (AI) and (b) more frequent use of AI tools compared to their peers in non-technical disciplines (e.g., social sciences, humanities, legal studies).

Participants’ self-assessed knowledge of AI was categorized as either High (“Somewhat high”, “Very high”) or Low (“Average”, “Low”, “Very low”), while frequency of AI tool usage was classified as either Frequent (e.g., “Daily”, “Several times a week”) or Non-frequent (“Several times a month”, “Occasionally (once a month)”, “I don’t use them”).

A Chi-square test of independence indicated a statistically significant association between field of study and perceived AI knowledge, $\chi^2(1, N = 103) = 5.06, p = .024$. This finding supports Hypothesis 1a, suggesting that students in STEM fields are more likely to rate their knowledge of AI as high compared to their non-STEM counterparts.

In contrast, the association between field of study and frequency of AI usage was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(1, N = 103) = 0.28, p = .599$. Thus, Hypothesis 1b was not supported; the frequency with which students use AI tools did not differ meaningfully between STEM and non-STEM disciplines. The results are show in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of Self-Perceived AI Knowledge and AI Usage Frequency by Field of Study

Group	High AI Knowledge	Low AI Knowledge	Frequent AI Usage	Non-frequent AI Usage	Total Responses
STEM	37	23	50	10	60
Non-STEM	16	27	32	11	43
Chi-square p-value	0.024	Significant at p<0.05	0.059	Non-Significant at p<0.05	103

Source: author own research

To test Hypothesis 2, we examined whether students who reported frequent use of AI (daily or several times a week) showed greater acceptance of academic practices accompanied by AI and differed in

their ethical concerns compared to non-frequent users. Mann–Whitney U tests were conducted on five key subjects relating to academic integrity and ethical concerns.

The results revealed a statistically significant difference between the two groups regarding the acceptance of the use of AI tools to generate the outline or idea for final theses ($U = 1300.5, p < .001$). Students who used AI more frequently were significantly more likely to view this practice as ethically acceptable, especially when the main argument and the final text were independently developed by the student. This finding suggests a growing normalization of AI as a supportive tool among frequent users.

However, no significant differences were found between the groups in their acceptance of AI-assisted test-taking ($U = 1000.5, p = .203$), nor in their level of concern regarding the ethical implications of AI, such as overcollection of personal data ($p = .872$), distrust in AI systems handling personal data ($p = .861$), or awareness of bias in AI training datasets ($p = .815$). These results suggest that while frequent users may be more open to certain forms of academic assistance from AI, their general ethical stance toward AI remains largely similar to that of non-frequent users.

The results of the Mann–Whitney U tests are summarized in Table 2, which presents the number of valid responses per group, U statistics, and p-values for each item analyzed. As shown in the table, only one item—concerning the acceptability of using AI to assist with outlines for final theses—yielded a statistically significant result ($p < .001$), while all other comparisons indicated no meaningful differences between frequent and non-frequent users.

Table 2. Comparison of AI Attitudes by Usage Frequency

Statement	Frequent	Non-frequent	U-statistic	p-value
I consider it ethically acceptable for students to use AI tools (e.g. ChatGPT) when writing answers on tests or during exams.	81	21	1000.5	0.203
I consider it ethically okay for a student to use AI to get an outline or ideas for a thesis, as long as he/she develops the main argument and text him/herself.	82	21	1300.5	0.0001
I am concerned that AI systems may collect more personal data than is necessary.	79	20	808.5	0.872
I have trouble trusting AI systems that analyze my personal data (e.g., medical records, bank transactions).	79	19	770.0	0.861
AI systems reflect possible biases encoded in the training data and thus may discriminate against certain groups of people.	79	19	725.0	0.815

Source: author own research

To test Hypothesis 3, we examined whether students expressing stronger ethical concerns - particularly concerning data privacy, bias, and misuse - would be less willing to support the use of AI in formal academic assessments and coursework. To strengthen this analysis, we created two composite indexes.

The *Ethical Concern Index* was based on six Likert-scale items addressing AI regulation, data protection, fairness, and legal accountability. These included:

- AI should be strictly regulated by state or international institutions.
- I am concerned that AI systems may collect more personal data than is necessary.
- AI can have a negative impact on marginalised groups if it is not designed inclusively.
- AI systems reflect possible biases encoded in the training data and thus may discriminate against certain groups of people.
- I believe that there are currently insufficient measures in place to protect personal data from AI misuse.
- AI developers and operators should be held legally liable for damages caused by the AI system.

The *Academic AI Acceptance Index* was constructed from four items evaluating the perceived ethical acceptability of using AI tools for assignments and examinations, with negatively worded items reverse-coded for consistency. These included:

- I consider it ethically acceptable for students to use AI tools (e.g. ChatGPT) when writing answers on tests or during exams.
- I consider it ethically okay for a student to use AI to get an outline or ideas for a thesis, as long as he/she develops the main argument and text him/herself.
- Applying AI in writing thesis (bachelor, master) papers is dishonest in my opinion and constitutes a form of plagiarism.
- If a student uses AI in an exam, it is comparable to traditional outlining and should be penalized in the same way.

A Spearman correlation analysis revealed a significant negative correlation between the Ethical Concern Index and the Academic AI Acceptance Index ($\rho = -0.28, p = .006, N = 96$). This indicates that students who reported higher levels of ethical concern about AI were significantly less likely to support its use in academic settings. These findings support Hypothesis 3 and suggest that ethical reservations can be a key factor influencing student attitudes toward AI integration in education.

As illustrated in Figure 1, a negative relationship was observed between the Ethical Concern Index and the Academic AI Acceptance Index. The scatterplot reveals that students who expressed higher levels of concern—particularly about regulation, bias, and data protection—tended to rate the use of AI in academic contexts as less ethically acceptable. This visual pattern supports the results of the Spearman correlation analysis ($\rho = -0.28, p = .006, N = 96$), reinforcing the interpretation that ethical reservations may influence attitudes toward AI integration in higher education.

Figure 1. Relationship Between Ethical Concerns and Academic AI Acceptance Source: author own research

4. Conclusion

This study explored university students' perceptions and attitudes toward artificial intelligence (AI) in education, focusing on self-perceived knowledge, usage patterns, ethical concerns, and acceptance of AI in academic environments. The findings provide valuable insights into how students across disciplines are engaging with AI and what concerns they have when this technology becomes increasingly integrated into higher education.

We found that students in technical (STEM) programs reported significantly higher self-perceived knowledge of AI compared to those in non-STEM fields, although the actual frequency of use did not differ significantly between the two groups. This suggests that confidence in understanding AI can be formed more by academic background than by daily use.

Students who frequently engage with AI tools were more open to its use in academic contexts, especially in tasks such as generating outlines or ideas for written work. Interestingly, their ethical concerns - particularly regarding privacy, data usage, and fairness - were not significantly different from those of infrequent users. This may indicate that familiarity with AI breeds a certain degree of trust or at least practical acceptance of its utility.

Finally, we observed a clear, statistically significant negative link between ethical concern and acceptance of AI in academic evaluations. Students with stronger concerns about the social and ethical risks of AI were particularly less likely to support its integration into formal academic work. This emphasizes the importance of ethical awareness in shaping attitudes toward AI and suggests that an open and ongoing dialogue about the risks and responsibilities associated with AI use in education is crucial.

Although the results of this study provide valuable insights into students' perceptions and ethical attitudes toward AI in higher education, some limitations must be recognised. The sample included 103 respondents, the number of master's level students was too low to be retained in the analysis.

Therefore, the study focused exclusively on bachelor's-level participants, which may limit the generalizability of the findings across different levels of academic maturity. All responses were self-reported, which is the usual limitation of social desirability bias and subjective interpretation. For example, students' self-assessed knowledge of AI may not accurately reflect their actual understanding or competence.

Future research should seek to expand both the scope and depth of research into students' engagement with AI in educational contexts. First, the inclusion of a more diverse and larger sample - including master's and doctoral students, as well as participants from different institutions or countries - would increase the generalization. Secondly, it would be beneficial to conduct longitudinal studies that track how students' knowledge, use patterns, and ethical perspectives on AI evolve over time, especially as institutional policies and AI tools develop.

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ETHICAL ASPECTS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

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Ethics; artificial intelligence; entrepreneurship; ChatGPT; personal development

Abstract

The 21st century has brought numerous changes in the replacement of human labor with artificial intelligence-based solutions, raising serious ethical dilemmas related to mass layoffs, the elimination of long-anticipated job positions for graduates, and the dehumanization of the work process. In light of these issues, the aim of this paper is to conduct an in-depth analysis of the impact of using artificial intelligence tools - particularly generative chatbots such as ChatGPT - on the development of entrepreneurship among young people. In the face of increasing automation of cognitive and professional processes, both the potential and the risks of replacing human activity with algorithms are highlighted. Based on a review of the relevant literature and statistical data (including Eurostat and GEM), a research model was developed and then subjected to empirical verification. The study was conducted among 210 individuals aged 20 to 30 who use AI-based chatbots. A probit model was applied to identify the relationship between the intensity of AI usage and the level of cognitive independence. The results showed that excessive reliance on AI chatbots fosters passivity and a decline in initiative, whereas their creative use may contribute to the development of entrepreneurial competencies.

1. Ethical implications of artificial intelligence in the development of entrepreneurship

Will the rapidly changing socio-technological reality bring about an adaptation crisis for parts of 21st-century society? Younger generations, raised with the belief in limitless opportunities, often collide with the reality of precarity - lack of job stability, employment below qualifications, and limited prospects for independence. The issue lies not in the qualifications themselves, but in how they are assessed by employers, often based on subjective criteria and economic calculations. This raises serious ethical dilemmas, such as whether it is justified to keep a competent employee in a low-ranking position for the sake of company profit (Palej, Krusiec, 2024). Overlaid onto this context is the rapid development of AI, which already performs many tasks - from data analysis to content creation and even medical diagnostics - more efficiently than humans (Barney, 2024). With the low cost of tools like ChatGPT Plus (\$20-200/month), the boundary between the necessity of human input

and its replaceability by technology has been crossed. Generation Z, particularly attuned to the digital environment, now faces a labor market that demands completely new qualifications (Kuperová, Lisnik, 2023; World Economic Forum, 2025). A striking fact is that in 2022, 28% of European Union (EU) residents lived in poverty or were at risk of social exclusion (Eurostat, 2024), evoking the historical phenomenon of “white slavery” (Krawczyńska, 1930).

From an ethical standpoint, excessive subordination of humans to the logic of profit threatens their marginalization. The World Economic Forum's 2016 statement - “I own nothing, have no privacy, and life has never been better” - evokes associations with feudalism and systemic social dependency (World Economic Forum, 2016). Although we formally possess rights, actual control over our own fate is becoming increasingly limited. What becomes essential is not only nominal income, but also the ability to manage resources, which ensures psychological comfort and stability (Krusiec, 2018).

In the face of automation, the development of entrepreneurship may serve as a pathway to regaining agency - not only as a defense against crisis, but also as a means of reclaiming control over one's life. A case in point for the need to strike a balance between AI and human labor was the Covid-19 pandemic, which necessitated the expansion of remote work systems (Khusainov, Lisnik, 2023).

2. The potential of artificial intelligence

One of the key aspects of modern artificial intelligence is its intellectual advantage over a significant portion of the population. The potential of artificial intelligence becomes particularly evident in processing vast streams of data generated by IoT sensors, enabling quick responses to environmental changes and increasing the efficiency of decision-making processes (Bawa, Špirková, 2016). In an interview conducted with the ChatGPT Plus model, when asked about its own cognitive potential, it assessed its IQ at over 140 points, emotional intelligence at 110 points, language skills above 150 points, and general knowledge between 140 and 150 points (Conversation with ChatGPT Plus, 2025). This kind of self-assessment not only draws attention to the high capabilities of AI but also highlights a fundamental difference between humans and machines - namely, that the tool requires no sleep, rest, or emotional support. It is capable of uninterrupted work, regardless of stress or pressure, which often impact the quality and efficiency of tasks performed by humans (Bryant, 2023). AI no longer serves merely an auxiliary function but increasingly becomes an irreplaceable, independently “thinking” partner in daily work and life. A project that would take a person hours to complete can be carried out by artificial intelligence in just a few minutes - often with greater precision and without external intervention. This opens up entirely new perspectives in many fields, such as interior design, instant data mining from the internet, or the development of educational materials. Such support in conducting scientific research shows why ChatGPT is gradually being introduced as a teaching tool in educational institutions (Adel, Ashan, Davison, 2024).

Literature also indicates that young entrepreneurs are increasingly using AI-based tools, such as data processing systems and chatbots. Therefore, ethical data management becomes essential, built on transparency, respect for privacy, and the responsible use of information (Lisnik, Kuperová, 2023). These issues are also important because cryptocurrencies are becoming more popular among investors, which entails high ethical risks (Katrenčík, Zatrochová, 2017). Increasingly, questions are also being raised about the limits of AI application in both social and private spheres, as in the case of biometric systems used on social media platforms (Lisnik, Janíčková, Zimermanová, 2020). The ethical use of such tools requires not only technical precision but, above all, awareness of the consequences - from data protection to the threat of surveillance or manipulation of user behavior, etc. (Krusiec, 2019). Is it possible to create a balance between technological progress and the protection of human dignity and rights? If AI development continues to follow solely a market logic

- maximizing profits while minimizing costs - this may lead to a situation in which a large part of society is deprived of income sources, control over their future, and the sense of purpose in their work. This presents a real threat of deepening economic exclusion, social inequalities, and a new form of digital alienation of the human being, in a world it fosters but gradually loses control over.

3. Entrepreneurship and artificial intelligence

Entrepreneurship is not merely the ability to run a business, but a set of competencies - such as initiative, creativity, responsibility, and flexibility - that enable effective functioning in a changing world. Developing these qualities supports individuals in fulfilling social and professional roles, as well as in creating their own life space. The challenges inherent in entrepreneurial activity - stress, risk of failure, financial uncertainty - require appropriate educational support that builds resilience, innovation, and a civic mindset.

One of the tools that can both support and threaten this development is artificial intelligence. AI enhances many processes: it analyzes data, generates content, supports business decisions, and reduces costs, making it an attractive option for novice entrepreneurs (GEM, 2025). However, its overuse can lead to cognitive passivity, erosion of critical thinking, and superficiality in action. Instead of developing their own intuition and sense of responsibility, users may overly rely on AI models that bear no consequences for their mistakes.

This raises the question: does the development of AI truly support humans, or does it rather create dependency? A balanced model is needed - one that integrates the potential of technology with the cultivation of responsible and conscious users. This is especially important given that the benefits of AI are not distributed evenly. It is primarily global corporations - capable of implementing advanced technologies - that gain the most. Local businesses, often family-owned and with limited resources, are being pushed out of the market, leading to increasing inequality and a decline in economic diversity - contrary to the principles of social ethics.

4. Methodology

The aim of this study is to conduct an in-depth analysis of the impact of using artificial intelligence-based tools particularly generative chatbots such as ChatGPT - on the development of entrepreneurship among young people. Given the rapid advancement of digital technologies and the increasing automation of cognitive and decision-making processes, fundamental questions arise regarding the extent to which modern technological solutions support - or, paradoxically, may limit - the development of entrepreneurship, independence, and creativity among individuals entering the labor market.

The research is guided by the following question: does intensive use of AI-based chatbots, such as ChatGPT, support the development of entrepreneurship among young people, or - when viewed through an ethical lens - can it lead to a weakening of autonomy, creativity, and individual responsibility for one's decisions and actions?

This issue is interdisciplinary in nature, touching upon areas such as behavioral economics, cognitive psychology, and entrepreneurial education. These considerations are particularly relevant in the context of civilization challenges tied to digital transformation and the growing importance of future skills.

The study involved 210 individuals aged 20 to 30 who declared regular use of AI-based chatbots, particularly ChatGPT. Respondents were selected purposively - from among students and young

professionals representing various industries and sectors. All participants remained anonymous, which helped minimize self-presentation bias and increased the reliability of the collected data.

The research tool used was a proprietary questionnaire consisting of 21 closed and semi-open questions. The questions focused on, among other things, the frequency of AI usage, the perceived effects of this practice on work, learning, self-efficacy, as well as changes in decision-making and problem-solving strategies. Special attention was paid to potential symptoms of cognitive passivity and the extent to which algorithmic thinking was replacing independent thought.

To determine the impact of AI on selected behaviors, a probit model was applied - a statistical tool for analyzing binary variables, which makes it possible to identify the relationship between independent variables (e.g., intensity of AI chatbot use) and a dependent variable (e.g., exhibiting the trait of independence: 0 = absent, 1 = present). This allowed for a precise assessment of the strength and direction of the examined relationships while maintaining scientific rigor.

The research project was carried out with the substantive support of the “**Instytut Rozwoju Przedsiębiorczości im. Krzysztofa M. Krusiec**”, a non-governmental organization established in 2020 to supplement knowledge and competencies in the field of entrepreneurship, particularly among young people. The mission of the “Fundacja IRP” is personal and business development through a proprietary, multidisciplinary life improvement, development and stabilization system known as the “Model K. M. Krusiec” (Krusiec, Palej, 2024).

As part of the conducted study, the following specific research questions were formulated:

- Does the use of AI-based chatbots promote the development of entrepreneurship among individuals at risk of precarization, or does it rather lead to cognitive passivity and avoidance of independent problem-solving?
- Which specific competencies and traits related to entrepreneurship (e.g., initiative, organizational ability, creativity) can be supported by regular use of artificial intelligence tools?
- What potential risks and deficits may arise from frequent reliance on AI in performing everyday professional and educational tasks?

5. Results

To verify the proposed hypotheses, a probit model was applied, which is suitable for analyzing a binary dependent variable - in this case, indicating whether the respondent reports a lack of cognitive independence when using artificial intelligence tools (1 = yes, 0 = no). In interpreting the results, the marginal effects (dy/dx) and statistical significance levels (p-values) are of key importance, as they indicate the strength and direction of the influence of the independent variables on the probability of cognitive dependence.

Model functions:

$$P(Y = 1 | X) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X_k) \quad (1)$$

Where:

- Φ – the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution
- Y – the dependent variable (e.g., lack of independence = 1)

- X_k – the set of explanatory variables

Table 1 presents the data on the dependent variables and the coding method.

Table 1. Dependent variable (Y)

Name	Description	Coding
Lack of independence	Does the user report being unable to complete tasks independently without AI	1 = yes; 0 = no

Source: (author)

Table 2 lists the independent variables and their coding scheme.

Table 2. Independent variables (X)

Name	Description
Gender (female)	1 = female, 0 = male
Higher education	1 = bachelor's / engineer / master's degree, 0 = vocational / secondary education
City > 200,000	1 = yes, 0 = no
Frequency of AI use	scale 1–5 (the higher the score, the more frequent the use)
Independence (scale)	from 1 – full independence to 4 – lack of independence
Abandonment of ideas	scale 1–4 (1 = never, 4 = often)
Creativity (enhancement)	1 = AI enhances creativity, 0 = does not

Source: (author)

The analysis of marginal effects presented in Table 3 indicates that the frequency of using AI tools has a significant and positive impact on the declared lack of independence. The marginal effect is +0.1217 (based on an earlier version of the model) with a p-value of 0.001, which means that the more frequently respondents use AI chatbots, the more likely they are to report being unable to complete tasks without such support. This result directly supports the hypothesis that intensive use of AI may contribute to the phenomenon of *cognitive offloading*, thereby limiting the ability to think independently.

Table 3. Marginal effects of the probit model – dependent variable: “limited independence”

Variable	Marginal Effect (dy/dx)	Standard Error (SE)	z-value	p-value	95% Confidence Interval (lower – upper)
Gender (female)	-0.0428	0.066	-0.652	0.514	-0.171 – 0.086
Higher education	+0.0752	0.065	+1.160	0.246	-0.052 – 0.202
Large city (>200,000)	+0.0197	0.066	+0.298	0.766	-0.110 – 0.149
Frequency of AI use	+0.0740	0.038	+1.933	0.053	-0.001 – 0.149
Independence (scale)	+0.0008	0.036	+0.023	0.982	-0.069 – 0.071

Source: (author)

The frequency of AI chatbots use had a statistically significant impact on the studied phenomenon. The marginal effect was +0.0740 ($p = 0.053$), meaning that each one-point increase on the frequency

scale (e.g., from “once a day” to “several times a day”) increased the probability of lacking independence by 7.4 percentage points. Although this result is close to the 0.05 significance threshold, it should be treated as a signal of a potential negative effect of intensive AI usage.

Other variables, such as gender, education level, place of residence, general assessment of independence, and the tendency to abandon one's own ideas, did not show a statistically significant impact on the reduction of independence in the final model presented in Table 3. However, it should be noted that the variable “abandonment of ideas” had a positive coefficient (+0.1215) in the earlier, initial version of the model, which may indicate a tendency to conform to AI suggestions.

Creativity, as an effect of using AI - i.e., the belief that a chatbot “enhances creativity” – had a negative marginal effect of -0.2546 ($p < 0.001$) in the initial model estimation. This indicates that respondents who perceive artificial intelligence as a tool that supports creative thinking are less likely to lose their independence. It can therefore be assumed that positive, creative uses of AI serve as a protective factor against its potentially passive influence.

6. Discussion of results

Research indicates that intensive use of AI-based chatbots such as ChatGPT may lead to a weakening of users’ cognitive independence and a decline in the need for active information processing. This phenomenon, known as *cognitive offloading*, involves shifting mental tasks to external sources, which in turn diminishes analytical and reflective abilities (Zhai, Wibowo, Li, 2024). Individuals who use chatbots frequently tend to show lower cognitive engagement and reduced inclination toward reflection (Dylan, 2025; Shao, Huang, 2024), often mechanically accepting system suggestions without further elaboration. Moreover, the communication style—especially when emotional or persuasive - increases users’ susceptibility to AI influence (Rese, Tränkner, 2023).

However, a creative approach to AI tools acts as a protective factor. Users who treat AI as a source of inspiration rather than a substitute for thinking tend to maintain a higher level of intellectual autonomy (Vecchiarini, Somià, 2023; Noy, Zhang, 2023). Importantly, these effects occur regardless of age, gender, or education level - they are universal and cross-cultural in nature (Uppal, Hajian, 2025). The diagnosis is clear: uncritical use of AI may undermine entrepreneurial capacity, shifting responsibility for decisions from humans to algorithms.

The ongoing development of Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) - capable of autonomous decision-making - poses new ethical challenges related to control and accountability. However, Lisnik suggests that the concept of entropy and tools such as the Human Resources Ratio may support the design of AI systems that ethically enhance human development, rather than degrade human capabilities (Lysa, Lisník, 2019). For this reason, it is essential to promote digital competencies with a strong emphasis on critical and creative use of AI, as well as education in the ethics of emerging technologies.

7. Conclusions and action recommendations

Based on the conducted research, the following conclusions have been formulated:

- Frequent use of AI chatbots is associated with a greater tendency to avoid independent decision-making and cognitive responsibility.
- Abandonment of one’s own ideas correlates with reduced initiative, users are more likely to rely on ready-made AI suggestions, which may weaken individual thinking strategies.

- A creative approach to AI acts as a safeguard against perceiving AI as a substitute rather than a source of inspiration, and it supports higher intellectual autonomy.
- Dependence on AI appears to be universal - no significant influence of gender, education level, or place of residence was observed.

In light of ongoing technological transformation, it is essential to develop adaptive mechanisms, primarily in the fields of education and ethics. It is recommended to strengthen practical entrepreneurship education, with an emphasis on soft skills, critical thinking, and conscious use of digital tools, aiming to foster a modern, independent, and resilient society ready to face the challenges of the AI era.

According to the Author, a person becomes impoverished because they enrich others - allocating their time, energy, and potential not to the realization of their own ideas, but to supporting external projects that rarely bring true self-fulfillment. Meanwhile, the level of entrepreneurial development - understood not only as material wealth but as an attitude of active, conscious, and responsible shaping of reality - forms the foundation of who we are, what we possess, what we are capable of, the relationships we build, and the direction we take as individuals and as a society. Today, entrepreneurship is not a luxury, but a prerequisite for autonomy. Its development offers us a chance to reclaim agency. Technology, including AI, can support us, but if misused, it may weaken our will, deepen inequalities, foster dependency, lead to digital dementia, depression, or chronic procrastination, and give rise to new forms of social and psychological disorders.

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AI AND CVS – AN ANALYSIS OF THE DISCREPANCIES BETWEEN GENERATED PROFILES AND CANDIDATES' ACTUAL SKILLS

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Artificial intelligence; Curriculum Vitae; recruitment ethics; declared competencies

Abstract

The aim of this study was to analyze the discrepancies between the competencies declared in candidates' CVs and their actual skill levels, with particular emphasis on the impact of artificial intelligence on the process of creating application documents. A mixed-method approach was applied, combining linguistic analysis (using NVivo software) with a covert experiment conducted during workshop sessions. The research sample consisted of students from the international branches of the Staropolska Akademia Nauk Stosowanych, and the study was carried out in Poland, Ireland, and Ukraine. The participants were students of management, economics, finance, and accounting. Out of 405 analyzed CVs, a total of 225 documents were selected that contained phrases characteristic of content generated by AI tools. The participants (139 women and 86 men), aged 19–35, were observed in practical conditions. The results revealed a clear gap between declarations and actual skills—only punctuality and fear of being exposed were statistically significant predictors of credibility. The study also identified the phenomenon of “aestheticization of professional identity”, meaning a focus on form over substance. These findings raise important questions about the ethical and practical implications of using AI in recruitment processes.

1. The impact of the growing popularity of ai platforms on generation Z

Since the widespread adoption of the ChatGPT model, there has been a significant increase in the popularity of artificial intelligence (AI) in the context of its mass applications (Javaid, Haleem & Singh, 2023). In the era of Industry 4.0, AI-based technologies affect individuals in nearly all areas of life, influencing the dynamics of social interactions, professional processes, and the education system (Gill et al., 2024). The ethics of functioning in today's cyber-world concerns not only generations entering the labor market but also investors (Katrenčík, Zatrachová, 2017).

Theoretically, AI systems are designed to optimize everyday tasks - an example being the Gemini model developed by Google. This model significantly accelerates information retrieval; thanks to advanced natural language processing algorithms, the process becomes both fast and highly effective. As a result, data processing efficiency increases, and users experience a time optimization of their operations (Carlà et al., 2024). The number of people using generative AI models, such as ChatGPT,

continues to grow (table 1), confirming a rising societal demand for solutions based on such technologies.

Table 1. Number of users of selected ai platforms

Platform	Number of Users
ChatGPT	300 million weekly
Claude AI	10 million monthly
DeepSeek	2.8 million monthly
Google Gemini	106 million downloads
Microsoft Copilot	18 million monthly
Perplexity.ai	12.7 million monthly

Source: (author)

In today's digital age, the rapid development of technology has reshaped generational behavior, especially among Generation Z - so-called digital natives - who have been immersed in technology since early childhood (Bawa, Špírková, et al., 2015; Kuperová, Lisnik, 2023). While AI tools offer benefits like time and cost efficiency, their overuse has been linked to a decline in cognitive independence and emotional autonomy. Research indicates that Generation Z, despite their digital fluency, often struggle with independent decision-making and creativity in the absence of technological support (Burton, 2019). This growing reliance, termed algorithmic dependency syndrome, affects analytical thinking and problem-solving capabilities.

Recent studies confirm AI's dual impact - supporting educational personalization and stress management, but also weakening critical thinking and reducing empathy due to algorithm-driven interactions (Eki et al., 2024; Putri, Dinata & Basri, 2024). Although Generation Z displays high technical competence, their capacity for reflection and deep interpersonal relationships appears limited.

Emotion-driven processing, key to human interaction, is being replaced by algorithmic responses. Systems like ChatGPT, through polite and personalized responses, simulate friendliness and can foster a pseudo-bond with users, influencing self-perception and emotional reliance (Yankouskaya, Liebherr & Ali, 2024). However, unlike humans, even the most advanced models (e.g., GPT-4o) only mimic emotions - they don't experience them.

The necessity for AI collaboration became especially visible during the COVID-19 pandemic, which accelerated the development of digital tools for remote work (Khusainov, Lisnik, 2023). Growing AI use raises concerns over data ethics and privacy, particularly in systems involving biometric access and the use of social media as informal CVs (Lisnik, Kuperova, 2023; Lisnik, Janíčková, Zimermanová, 2020).

2. „In theory, each of us, despite being blind, could be a talented sniper.”- A. Palej

The modern job market is not only highly dynamic but also extremely competitive, which influences the behavior of its participants. The metaphor of the "blind sniper" illustrates the absurdity of a situation in which a candidate, aided by AI, declares non-existent competencies (e.g., analytical skills), while in reality being unable to interpret basic data. A study conducted by ResumeLab in August 2023 revealed that a relatively high number of potential employees consciously manipulate information about themselves in application documents (CVs, cover letters) as well as during job

interviews. Around 70% of respondents in the U.S. admitted to including falsehoods in their CVs, and 30% reported doing so regularly. The most common lies involved the number of subordinates (45%), extension of employment periods (37%), job positions being fabricated by 25% of respondents, and 11% providing false information about their education. Interestingly, individuals with higher education were more likely to engage in dishonest practices, possibly due to the pressure to perform well in the recruitment process (Szczepanek, 2023).

Similar findings emerged from a study conducted in Poland by IBBC Group in 2023. In a survey detailed in the report "Lies in CVs on the Polish Job Market," the actual number of respondents was not specified. The report stated that 81% of surveyed employers and managers had encountered false information in CVs. The most common discrepancies concerned the declared level of foreign language proficiency (85.12%), employment dates (58.68%), and scope of responsibilities (53.72%). False data also appeared regarding job titles (28.93%) and education (23.14%). According to the respondents, dishonest information is most often presented by candidates applying for positions in sales, administration, or production departments (IBBC Group, 2023). Meanwhile, a study conducted by InterviewMe in 2021 on a group of 474 respondents showed that approximately 33% of participants admitted to providing false information during the recruitment process. These lies most often involved exaggerating experience, language proficiency, and omitting unfavorable aspects of their professional careers (Rojewska, 2021).

3. Research methodology

The research methodology was designed to enable an in-depth analysis of the phenomenon of creating Curriculum Vitae (CVs) using artificial intelligence (AI) tools. The main objective was to capture discrepancies between the competencies declared in CVs and the actual skill levels of candidates, while also considering the ethical implications of this process. A mixed-method approach was employed, combining both qualitative and quantitative methods. Digital tools (linguistic analysis in NVivo) were used alongside a social experiment conducted in workshop conditions and a questionnaire aimed at assessing psychological factors such as the fear of being exposed. This approach made it possible to capture the complexity of the phenomenon from multiple perspectives: linguistic, behavioral and emotional.

The research group consisted of students from the international branches of the "Staropolska Akademia Nauk Stosowanych" in Poland (Bochnia, Kielce, and Myślenice), Ireland (Dublin), and Ukraine (Lviv and Lutsk), studying in the fields of management, economics, finance, and accounting. Initially, 405 CVs were collected, followed by a selection of 225 research participants (120 students from Poland in May–June 2024, 25 students from Ireland in October 2024, and 80 students from Ukraine in November 2024 and January 2025). The selection was based on an analysis of the application documents for typical phrases suggesting they were generated using AI tools. The selected CVs contained characteristic phrases such as "excellent organizational skills," "ability to work under pressure," "team management," or "strategic thinking," which indicated a high probability of using ready-made templates or text generators.

The selected group consisted of 225 individuals, of whom 62% were women (139 people) and 38% were men (86 people). All participants were between 19 and 35 years old. Prior to further analysis, personal data were anonymized, and participants were assigned numerical identifiers.

The study proceeded in several stages. In the first phase, linguistic analysis of the CVs was conducted using NVivo software to identify language patterns typical of AI-generated content. Next, selected participants were invited to take part in workshop sessions structured as a covert experiment. The aim of this phase was to empirically verify the actual competencies declared in the application documents.

The workshops included teamwork exercises and practical tasks such as analyzing English-language texts, working with spreadsheets, and simulating conflict scenarios requiring soft skills.

From an ethical standpoint, the study was designed with respect for proportionality and participant autonomy. However, participants were not informed that the purpose of the workshops was to assess the consistency between their declarations and actual competencies - this was intended to prevent self-selection bias and behavior modification due to awareness of being evaluated. After the experiment, ex post consent was obtained, and it was explained that the activities aimed to assess the effectiveness of educational programs and the level of student preparedness for the labor market. Participants were informed about the study's goals and scope and were given the opportunity to withdraw without consequence. None chose to do so, and most expressed interest in the results and willingness to receive individual feedback.

In reference to the philosophical and normative dimension, the study was inspired by the ethics of Immanuel Kant, who emphasized the importance of truthfulness as a foundation of social relations. In his view, lying - even for personal gain (e.g., employment) - violates the dignity of others by treating them as a means to an end rather than as ends in themselves. The use of "performative masks" in everyday life should not cause harm to others. Today, CVs have become a form of advanced performative mask - candidates, aware of algorithmic selection mechanisms, construct messages optimized for employer expectations but detached from their authentic selves. Thus, the study also had a reflective and ethical character, considering not only technical or psychological aspects but also axiological ones - related to honesty, responsibility, and social transparency in professional relationships.

4. Results of own research

The aim of the analysis was to examine which competencies declared in students' CVs correspond to their actual skills, and to identify psychological factors - such as fear of being exposed - that may reduce the tendency to provide false information. This fear was assessed using a five-point Likert scale, where 1 meant no fear and 5 indicated very high anxiety. The question focused on participants' subjective sense of risk related to being caught for misrepresentation in their CVs. The study also considered international differences in legal and cultural contexts, covering Poland, Ireland, and Ukraine. The research was conducted in two stages: first, a linguistic analysis of CVs using NVivo software to detect formulaic, AI-generated phrases; second, practical workshops in which participants, unaware of the experiment's purpose, completed tasks such as text analysis, spreadsheet work, and conflict simulations. After the sessions, ex post consent was obtained, and participants were assured anonymity and the option to withdraw, which none of them exercised. The model included eight independent variables: declared English proficiency at B2 level, advanced Excel skills, leadership ability, time flexibility (availability), declared diligence, punctuality (timely task submission), class attendance, and the level of fear of being exposed for misrepresentation in the CV. The regression analysis identified *punctuality* and *fear of exposure* as statistically significant predictors of actual competencies. While other variables like Excel proficiency or English B2 level showed positive coefficients, they were not statistically significant (table 2).

Table 2. Probit regression results

Variable	Coefficient β	Std. Error	z-Statistic	p-value	Significance
Constant	-2.1172	0.986	-2.148	0.032	p < 0.05
English B2	0.3011	0.391	0.770	0.441	
Advanced Excel	0.4786	0.414	1.156	0.248	
Leadership	-0.2215	0.401	-0.552	0.581	
Availability	0.1337	0.463	0.289	0.773	
Diligence	0.2513	0.468	0.537	0.591	
Punctuality	0.9383	0.451	2.080	0.038	p < 0.05
Attendance	0.0140	0.015	0.933	0.351	
Fear of Exposure	0.6422	0.228	2.815	0.005	p < 0.01

Source: (author)

Marginal effects confirm that *punctuality* had the strongest positive impact (+24 p.p.) on the likelihood of actual skills, followed by *fear of exposure* (+18 p.p.), which also appears to act as a deterrent to dishonesty. The effects of other variables were minor or statistically inconclusive (table 3).

Table 3. Marginal effects

Variable	Marginal Effect ΔP	Interpretation
Punctuality	+0.24	Punctuality increases the likelihood of possessing actual competencies by 24 percentage points.
Fear of Exposure	+0.18	Individuals with a higher fear of being exposed are less likely to lie.
Advanced Excel	+0.11	Not statistically significant.
English B2	+0.08	Statistically uncertain effect.
Attendance	+0.01	Minimal impact of class attendance.

Source: (author)

The chart illustrates the marginal effects of selected predictive variables on the likelihood of possessing actual competencies. **Punctuality** (+0.24) and **fear of exposure** (+0.18) had the strongest positive impact, while **attendance** had only a minimal effect (+0.01), indicating that psychological and behavioral traits are more relevant than mere presence.

Graph 2. Marginal effects of predictive variables (ΔP)

Source: (author)

5. Conclusions

- Punctuality and fear of being exposed are the two key predictors of honesty and actual competencies.
- Older and working students show a higher level of fear - they are more aware of the consequences of providing false information.

Country-specific differences:

- Poland: Moderate level of fear; GDPR and civil liability regulations are in place.
- Ukraine: Lack of strong protective frameworks; low level of fear (low awareness of consequences).
- Ireland: High transparency and strong EU regulations (GDPR, AI Act).
- There are no regulations regarding AI-generated CVs - none of the countries studied have specific legal provisions prohibiting the use of AI tools to generate application documents. It is recommended to implement practical methods of competency verification in the recruitment process.

6. Discussion of results

The study confirmed clear discrepancies between competencies declared in students' CVs and their actual skills. Among all variables, only punctuality ($\beta = 0.9383$; $p = 0.038$; $\Delta P = +0.24$) emerged as a statistically significant predictor of genuine competencies, supporting prior findings that behavioral traits like conscientiousness are more reliable indicators of professional potential than self-reported claims (Billieux, von Hammerstein & Ciudad-Fernández, 2024; Müller & Kvalnes, 2013).

Hard skills, such as English B2 and advanced Excel, though frequently declared (72% and 68%), lacked statistical significance - echoing the concept of "controlled dishonesty", where candidates embellish documents using AI and shift moral responsibility to technology (Billieux et al., 2024). This behavior reflects moral responsibility displacement, which undermines trust in recruitment (Müller & Kvalnes, 2013).

Fear of being exposed ($\beta = 0.6422$; $p = 0.005$; $\Delta P = +0.18$) was the second significant predictor of honesty, particularly among older, working students. The effect varied culturally: highest in Ireland (strict EU norms), moderate in Poland (GDPR), and lowest in Ukraine (weak legal safeguards).

Traits like availability, diligence, and leadership were common in CVs but poorly correlated with actual behaviour - suggesting that even moral attributes are being "aestheticized" via AI tools. The findings raise ethical concerns about authenticity and highlight the need for legal regulation, practical skill verification, and ethical recruitment standards across all countries studied.

7. Conclusions and recommendations

The conducted study clearly confirmed the existence of discrepancies between the competencies declared in CVs and the actual skills of candidates. Among the many variables analyzed, only punctuality ($\Delta P = +0.24$) and fear of being exposed ($\Delta P = +0.18$) proved to be significant predictors of authenticity and real professional preparedness. This phenomenon aligns with the findings of Billieux et al. (2024), who highlight the growing role of AI tools in creating an "aestheticized" professional identity detached from genuine competencies.

While artificial intelligence can facilitate the creation of application documents, it also becomes a tool for controlled dishonesty. Candidates often shift moral responsibility for CV content to algorithms, which - as noted by Müller and Kvalnes (2013) - leads to the erosion of trust between applicants and employers.

At the international level, the study revealed a lack of clear regulations regarding the use of AI in the application process:

- Poland: No specific provisions; only general references in GDPR, the AI Act, and the Labour Code.
- Ireland: EU regulations (GDPR, AI Act) apply, with an emphasis on algorithmic transparency.
- Ukraine: No comprehensive legal framework; high risk of systemic discrimination and digital exclusion.

Recommendations:

- Empirical verification of skills – implement practical workshops, assessment centers, and recruitment simulations.
- Application education – integrate ethics of authenticity into CV creation processes.
- Candidate potential assessment – apply entropy-based evaluation methods (Lysa & Lisnik, 2019).
- Labeling AI-generated CVs – e.g., through a disclaimer such as: “Generated with the use of AI tools.”
- Implementation of ethical standards – transparency, equal access, and fairness should be the foundation of new recruitment practices.
- Reducing technological inequalities – combat digital exclusion, especially in countries with limited access to AI.

In the face of growing “declaration inflation”, it is essential to shift the focus from form to substance - ensuring credible, practical confirmation of qualifications while upholding ethical and regulatory principles.

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VIRAL MARKETING BEHAVIOUR OF GENERATION Z

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Digital marketing; Virtual marketing; Influencer marketing; Social media

Abstract

Customer preferences are changing with each generation as a consequence of technological advances. Today, Generation Z dominates, who are quite different from their parents. The aim of this paper is to highlight the innovative forms of marketing and their impact on customer behaviour, to describe in a selected segment of the target group the method of using viral marketing in a specific market segment. We obtained primary information using our own research. A questionnaire was used for the quantitative part of the research. We focused on the target group young people from 12-20 years old. In the context of post processing were used traditional scientific methods: method of analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, comparison and observation. The output of the paper will be an evaluation of the impact of the use of social media and innovative forms on the buying behaviour of Generation Z. The aim of the contribution is to point out the usability of innovative forms of marketing and their impact on the purchasing behavior of young customers aged 12-20. Therefore, marketers have to adapt the form of their campaigns and focus on promoting products using innovative and creative marketing strategies to win new customers and also retain loyal ones.

1. Introduction

Nowadays it is very easy for marketers to analyse what is the traffic on their website, what demographic group visits it the most. This information is very valuable and from this, further strategy can be developed to drive customers to purchase.

The presentation of brands using modern social networks has greatly developed during the measures to protect society from the spread of Covid. This helped to develop social media marketing activities and thus changed the behavior of customers.

Mobile applications and social media platforms have been claimed to be drivers of change in consumers' behavior. In this vein, the confinement measures had an enormous impact on the way in which people purchased. The Internet and the online shopping made possible the continued purchase of many products and services, yet it changed substantially the customer journey map, urging companies to understand this new experience and to adapt accordingly (Vazquez-Martínez, 2021).

Monitoring the development of customer behavior on social networks is one of the important sources of information necessary for obtaining knowledge necessary for the development of marketing strategies of brands.

Generation Z, defined as individuals born between 1995 and 2009, which is the youngest and largest consumer group for the period from 2017 to 2030. This generation are innovative, pragmatic, narcissism-oriented, and averse to negative events; they tend to have a strong focus on praise and a high level of social approval. Most importantly, they are known as technology-savvy digital natives, the first generation to be born into an entirely digital world, and thus they have grown up developing relationships with digital technologies extensively. From a marketing perspective, their great dependence on SNS plays a significant role in generating sales and revenue, especially under the economic disruption of the Covid-19 pandemic (Wang et al., 2023).

Generation Z is known for its special and unique way of looking at values. One of the facts is lifestyle. It is influenced both by social networks, but also by the social environment in which the individual is located. It is very important to examine the relationship of the individual and his lifestyle in relation to values in the decision-making process in purchasing behavior.

One of the modern ways of paying for their purchase are cryptocurrencies. They are also characterized by their digital nativity and openness to technological innovation, demonstrates a growing inclination toward using cryptocurrencies for purchasing goods and services, reflecting a shift in consumer behavior within emerging financial ecosystems (Katrenčík, 2020).

Generation Z is constantly connected with others, initially it was a connection using phone calls, SMS or MMS messages, after the advent of social networks, the transfer of information has intensified even more. From the point of view of access and use of information technologies, we can consider Generation Z as one of the most informed generations. On the other hand, terms such as stress, burnout, frequent job changes, conflicts, lack of concentration appear more often in this generation than in others (Kajnaová, 2024).

Research into brand positioning on the market shows that it is very necessary to focus on the right market segment and to communicate in a targeted manner, e.g. product packaging.

There are many factors that influence the successful sale of a product. One of the basic factors is the name (name) of the product (Zajko, 2022). This factor is closely related to the study of the customer's purchasing behavior and the digital strategic marketing of the brand in close connection with advertising.

1.1 Viral marketing

The goal of viral marketing is to reach the largest possible audience through social sharing. There are different ways of viral sharing, how through emails, videos, mobile apps. The main goal is to create a campaign or an advertisement that will be shared everywhere. This type of campaign is unique in that it does not use a paid distribution channel but relies on social sharing. If such content is shared by a celebrity or influencer, there is a high likelihood that it will go viral.

As the potential of viral marketing began to become more and more apparent to companies, they struggled to understand the factors that influence a successful viral campaign. The STEPPS model describes six factors that are believed to contribute to the spread of content. Social Currency, if a user believes that sharing a piece of content will make them look favourable to their audience, they are more likely to share it. Triggers are anything that connects thoughts, ideas or different stimuli. For viral marketing to be effective, people should be able to identify with it, it should match the everyday experiences of consumers. Emotions, people react most to content that evokes an emotional response

in them. People who share such emotional content may feel that they are improving their status by showing interest in emotional, socially important issues. Public, if it is a message, advertisement or video that is shared by many individuals or various celebrities, the user is more likely to share something like this. Practical Value, an effective method of making content go viral is to provide some added value to those who share such content. People are happy to engage with something that promotes a good cause and are more likely to share such content. Stories, people are more likely to understand things better if they are presented to them in the form of a story. The story must be engaging, it must tend to motivate social media users to share it. Sharing an advertisement about a company, a product in a concise, visually appealing format can have a very good effect, which can make the brand more visible (Directive, 2023).

Viral marketing is an area of marketing confronted with circulation, the need for commerciality, and most importantly, with the integrity of the content creator (Lisnik, 2024).

The advantages viral marketing include: Rapid growth – a company's digital presence can grow through viral content. If a company has a larger reach, it gives it a good opportunity to attract new customers and also retain customers. Brand awareness – viral content helps a brand to introduce itself to customers and showcase its products. People will first remember a funny video which they will then associate with the brand. This kind of advertising is most beneficial for startups or small businesses. Cost effective – a good campaign will be effective and will not have a large cost as it relies on people sharing without the need to pay. Because of the ease of sharing content, there is no need to do extra work because content is shared naturally (Study Smarter, 2022).

The disadvantages of viral marketing are: Negative advertising – the campaign can have a negative impact with users, which can cause negative advertising to spread, which can have a disastrous impact on the company. It may happen that customers stop buying the products of a given company because of such advertising, influencers stop working with them. Implementation and control – viral marketing is unpredictable, so there is a possibility that the ad may not reach the target group of users, making management and control more difficult. Wasted time – it may happen that the campaign does not generate interest among consumers. Feedback – gathering feedback can be challenging as it is viral advertising which cannot be measured in any way (Study Smarter, 2022).

In the field of viral marketing, it is important to pay attention to the content of the information, including from the point of view of truthfulness. Since 1992, we have the first memory of the connotation of state law, which declares a minimum of due diligence for the truthfulness of the content of viral information. (Lisnik, Majerník, 2023).

1.1 Influencer marketing

The most charismatic among us have always influenced what we buy. It used to be the Mary Kay Lady, the Avon Lady, today it's the popular people on social media

Influencer marketing is a collaboration between an influencer and a brand, whereby it is the promotion of a product or service. The role of an influencer is to promote a product or service on their profile. Many times they have different discount codes or contests in collaboration with the brand. The brand chooses the influencer to collaborate with according to different criteria such as : target audience, life values, content on the profile, number of followers. Companies can collaborate with influencers to become brand ambassadors. An ambassador gets free products on a regular basis, also promotes them and has different discount codes on a regular basis (Geysler, 2023).

This type of marketing is not without risks. It can be riskier and harder for big brands to appear authentic when working with an influencer, as it is always a monetary transaction between the

influencer and the company. When it's a lesser-known brand, the promotion may seem more authentic. It's also important to consider that influencer brand loyalty doesn't always have a positive effect. When a brand collaborates, it cannot influence social media behaviour and when influencers behave unprofessionally, it can jeopardise the brand's reputation. (McKinsey&Company, 2023)

The scope and content of information shared on social networks also needs to be strictly protected, as it is largely information subject to the principles of the GDPR (Lisnik, Bretz, 2023).

1.3 Social media

In 2006, one of the most popular social networking sites that has over a trillion users, Facebook, came into the world. Later in 2010 came Instagram where users could add photos, the platform came through many upgrades and now users can not only add photos or even chat there, try different filters but also follow their favorite celebrities or influencers. And last but not least, TikTok came to the social networking world in 2018, it is the most used social media of today, which has over three trillion users. Users post short videos of themselves dancing, painting, doing various tricks, etc. (Britannica, 2023).

The great advantage of social media is the quick feedback from customers, they share their positive and negative experiences with products or services. To which companies can quickly respond and resolve negative customer reviews. Marketers are also using social media for crowdsourcing. Crowdsourcing is getting information, opinions from a large group of people who share information on social media (Edosomwan, 2011).

Working with the content and meaning of words is a very important aspect of the information offered. Therefore, the content of the shared information also changes according to the conditions (circumstances) and the person interpreting the information. This phenomenon is especially highlighted on social networks (Ambrózy, 2023).

Social media has different forms of platforms, these can be divided into four main categories: Social networks – users use social networks to communicate, share opinions or ideas. Users create a profile where they can share their age, gender, where they live, or they can choose to use such a platform to create different groups where people share their products, opinions, tips and tricks. Examples of such social networks include Facebook. Media sharing networks – users create different 'content' which they share. This content can be of different nature, such as: funny, educational, informative. Many companies use such media to share information about their products and their company. Such media include YouTube, Instagram, TikTok. Community social networks – this type is mainly used for discussions, users hold discussions on various topics. Review social networks – this type of social network is focused on customer reviews of a product or service.

Individual reaction to the product is an important element in the creation of the social context of the products. Social networks thus create a model of relationship with the evaluator based largely on his feelings, experience, or validity (his social impact in the community).

Individuals can take a series of actions on Facebook when engaging with a brand. They can like or react to a post, comment on another and share the other. Regarding reactions, an extension of the like button, users can express their sentiments (love, haha, wow, sad and angry) toward a publication. Furthermore, commenting provides users the opportunity to express their opinions through debate with others while sharing is considered the most valuable form of user engagement for brands, considering its potential for viral redistribution. Liking a post requires less commitment than commenting or sharing. Clicking is enough to like, while comments and shares demand additional actions and extra commitment (Romão, 2019).

1.4 TikTok

TikTok, was first launched in 2016 in China. The app was very popular, so the parent company, ByteDance, introduced it to the international market. In 2017, with the acquisition of Musical.ly, the company was able to establish itself in the international market as it imported around 80 million users, most of which were from the US, onto the TikTok platform. In 2023, Tik Tok has just over 1.53 trillion active users, with just over 3 trillion people having downloaded the app, of which up to 57% are women. It is the world's sixth most popular medium. (IQBAL, Mansoor, 2023)

Every day, a Tik Tok user spends 1.5 hours on the platform, for a yearly total of 547.5 hours. The most popular category is entertainment, followed by dancing, pranks, fitness, beauty, fashion, cooking. The engagement rate on Tik Tok in terms of micro-influencers is 17.96% as opposed to Instagram where it is only 3.86%. Larger influencers have an engagement rate of 4.96% on Tik Tok and 1.21% on Instagram. (Ruby, 2023)

It's important to remember that with such a huge number of videos, you need to be creative, follow trends and also post videos on a regular basis. A clever way to break through on TikTok, for example, is a 'challenge', where you try to get as many users as possible to take part in the challenge, with users using a hashtag that lets other users know what the challenge is about. This is a very good opportunity for businesses to connect with their customers. Other popular videos are lifehacks, where users present interesting tutorials to followers. (Gašparová, 2022)

2. Methods

The main objective of the present paper is to analyse the current state of the use of modern marketing methods, especially viral marketing in a specifically targeted group of respondents. The basic scientific methods such as observation, method of analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, abstraction and comparison have been used in the preparation of the paper. The structure of the paper follows the structure of scientific papers: introduction, aim and methods, results and discussion, conclusion. At the first stage, we set the objectives of the paper, selected the relevant scientific methods to be used in the treatment of the chosen issue, then through the fulfilment of the partial objectives we get to the actual treatment of the issue and the assessment of the current situation. Based on the facts and facts dealing with the issue, we have identified the analysis of the results as an important factor, which we have formulated into conclusions, recommendations and evaluation of the objectives. The paper presents the results of our own primary research carried out by questionnaire method. The questionnaire was created using the Click4Survey website and was made available from February 25, 2023 to March 25, 2023. Respondents were approached through acquaintances, family friends, students, and lecturers. A total of 335 potential respondents opened the survey, but only 252 responded.

3. Results

In cooperation with Herba Drug, s.r.o., we focused on social media and digital marketing research in the field of hair and body cosmetics oriented to Generation Z - using a questionnaire survey, which was oriented to the target group of 12-20 years old. They identified the following three sub-objectives: What social networks are most used by respondents. On what basis they choose a product. What external influences affect the purchase of products.

The questions in the questionnaire were also communicated with Herba Drug, Ltd (a cosmetics company dealing with hair and body cosmetics), these were modified and asked in such a way that the survey would be beneficial for them as well. In the questionnaire we asked what social networks the respondents use.

A question where respondents could select multiple answers was what social networks they use the most. The most used social network is Instagram, which is used by 199 respondents. The second most used network is Tik Tok, which is visited by 95 respondents. The least used network is BeReal, which is a relatively new social network, so we consider this to be an expected result. Only 8 respondents use this network.

In the next section, we asked what influences their purchase, if there is any viral video or advertisement that influenced them in hair and body cosmetics.

The questionnaire was created using the Click4Survey website and was made available from February 25, 2023 to March 25, 2023. Respondents were approached through acquaintances, family friends, students and teachers. A total of 335 potential respondents opened the survey, but only 252 responded.

Of the Slovak influencers, Moma is the most followed, followed by chemist, mom and cosmetics product development manager B_b_w_k and the same number of respondents answered Jana Hrmová and Radka Žilinčík.

The most charismatic among us have always influenced what we buy. It used to be the Mary Kay Lady, the Avon Lady, today it's the popular people on social media. Of the foreign influencers, the most prominent are the Kardashians and Kylie Jenner, Selema Gomez, also footballers such as Cristiano Ronaldo and Robert Lewandowski. Another question in the survey asked what respondents choose cosmetics based on. Most respondents choose based on scent (65.1%), followed by price (50.8%). For 36.5% of respondents, recommendation from family and friends is important. The least important factor influencing the choice of cosmetics is advertising on TV and in the media, only 4.8% of respondents chose this answer.

The next answer to the question if there is any viral video, advertisement, billboard in the field of cosmetics that influenced the respondents. 83.3% of the respondents answered no or did not answer at all. Head & Shoulders brand advertisement influenced 2.8% of the respondents, the reason was footballers who were doing advertisement for the brand. The Old Spice brand was also written by 2.8% of respondents, only one reason was given and that was an animal in the shower. Respondents also wrote other brands such as Adidas, Schauma, Nivea, Florence by Mills, Nature Box.

4. Discussion

TikTok is currently the most used social network, where new users are added every day. Many companies abroad are using this medium to promote their brand. In Slovakia, this market is still new and unexplored. Few cosmetic companies use TikTok in Slovakia, there is a great potential here, because the competition is still very small.

From our market research we found that only 3 brands out of 20 have a Slovak TikTok. All three are Slovak brands. Out of 252 respondents, TikTok is used by 95 respondents, which is 38%. The most used medium is Instagram, which is used by 199 respondents, which is 79%. Videos that are uploaded on TikTok are also very popular on Instagram now. The app introduced Instagram Reels in 2020, as an effort to rival the TikTok platform. The app has also added a separate section where users can watch these short videos. Many users share the same content on both social networks. Instagram Reels

is also a very good way for businesses to interact with their audience and promote their brand at the same time. In this way, they can showcase their products, share behind the scenes of production, and create various educational content, whether about their company, products, or ingredients. The length of a video on Instagram can be from 15- 90 seconds, while the length of a video on Tik Tok can be from 15 seconds to 10 minutes.

We found that only three brands have a Slovak Tik Tok, and they are Biofy, Kvítok and Two cosmetics. Biofy currently has 905 followers, Kvítok has 44 followers, and Two cosmetics has 1080 followers. All three are natural brands. Most of the brands have TikTok, but only the foreign one. The fact that not many brands in Slovakia have this social network yet, so the space on Slovak TikTok with hair and body cosmetics remains open. And right now is a good opportunity to take a leading position on this social network.

5. Conclusion

The paper is focused on identifying the state of use of current viral marketing methods in a specific group of respondents and in a specific market segment. Tik Tok is the most used viral tool for presenting videos especially among the young generation. Its main advantage is the "anatomical" positioning of the mobile device while viewing the video. It also changes the philosophy of artificially placing advertisements in videos which has caused an increase in the interest of respondents. Tik Tok is viewed by respondents on average twice as long as other viral assets. Young people of our respondents' age have abandoned traditional forms such as FB and are moving to viral networks such as Tik Tok and Instagram.

The presentation of the survey results shows that Tik Tok has a high potential to improve the sales leads of a specific product line especially grounded to a specific group of respondents. A big advantage is the expansion of the offer and product innovation. It is also of great importance for collecting data on the basis of which we would be able to specify customer needs to satisfy them by developing and innovating products and product lines.

The contribution of the presented article is the description of the current potential of using viral media and viral marketing for the presentation of specifically targeted products for generation Z. The paper also identifies channels for communicating information shared among a specific group of the population, which is absolutely different from previous generations, but forms a significant part of current and future buyers of products and services. Identifying these channels and needs defines the future framework and means of marketing, especially viral marketing.

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RESPONSIBLE MARKETING IN TOURISM: USING AI WITHOUT ETHICAL VIOLATIONS

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Abstract

The growing importance of artificial intelligence (AI) in tourism marketing represents not only technological progress, but also the need for a deeper ethical assessment of its use. This article addresses the concept of responsible marketing in the context of a rapidly changing digital environment and analyzes the possibilities of integrating AI into marketing strategies without violating basic ethical principles. The research presents specific case studies and examples of good practice that demonstrate how AI can be effectively used to personalize services, streamline customer communication, or optimize campaigns, while respecting user privacy, information transparency, and cultural sensitivity. The legal framework of the European Union and recommendations of professional organizations regarding digital ethics are also taken into account. The article aims to provide tourism professionals with practical recommendations on how to achieve a balance between innovation and social responsibility when implementing AI into marketing practice. A responsible approach to technology can be a key factor in building trust and long-term value in the tourism sector.

1. Introduction of topic

Today, the tourism industry faces many challenges, including digitalization, changing customer expectations, as well as the pressure to communicate ethically and socially responsibly. In this context, artificial intelligence (AI) is playing an increasingly important role in the creation and execution of marketing strategies. AI offers tools for content personalization, predictive analytics, and more effective communication with customers, but it also raises questions about privacy, transparency, and fair treatment of data.

In this article, we focus on the importance of balancing innovation and ethics. The aim is to point out the current state of the use of AI tools in marketing practice in the tourism sector and to identify the pitfalls that prevent their wider application.

The results of a survey we conducted among mainly marketing managers operating in the field of tourism revealed insufficient knowledge and experience in the use of AI in the creation of campaigns. It is this lack of knowledge that can contribute to caution or even rejection of the use of modern technologies, despite their potential benefits. Therefore, in the design part, we offer recommendations for systematic education of managers in the field of AI in marketing with an emphasis on the ethical

framework, thus contributing to the responsible and effective use of technology in this dynamically developing area.

2. Using AI without ethical violations

According to Gartner and Krašno (Gartner M., Krašna M., 2023), privacy is one of the basic human rights that separates the individual from the collective. Mill (Mill, 2023) has already tried to separate the private from the public. The state can intervene by banning and by ordering individuals to act only in the public sphere when these actions do not harm others in society. Thus, the privacy (of information, of space, of decisions) is regulated by legal norms, laws and ethical principles that separate the individual from the collective so that he can develop his own Self and protect himself.

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) technology in the world of marketing has significantly impacted the way marketers work. On the one hand, AI offers various conveniences in the marketing process, such as the use of artificial intelligence to prepare various marketing tools, presentations, graphic designs, marketing materials, and the like. On the other hand, however, various ethical challenges arise that need to be considered, especially from an ethical point of view. There are concerns about the appropriateness of using materials in marketing, and therefore it is advisable to consider whether the prepared AI proposals are ethically appropriate. AI can provide instant answers without marketers going through a deep thought process, which can ultimately hinder their intellectual development. Also, over-reliance on technology can cause serious problems. The Christian ethical outlook emphasizes the importance of integrity, justice, and the development of the full human potential. In this context, the challenges posed by the use of AI in education must be addressed wisely so that the technology can be used to promote the greater good without sacrificing basic ethical values.

The principle of responsible entrepreneurship represents an initiative of the organization based on voluntariness without specific defined boundaries, while representing a range of activities ranging from ecology, community work, through employee rights, business ethics to the fight against discrimination." (Peter MADZÍK and collective, 2014).

Carroll presents his definition of CSR in the so-called "pyramid of corporate social responsibility", which emphasizes the hierarchy of individual aspects of the principle of responsible business and the fundamental role of the economic side of the organization (Carroll, 1991).

Figure 1. Carroll's Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility

Source: (Guller, 2010)

According to Lisnik (Lisnik, 2023), it is clear that there is a self-regulatory ethical aspect to self-learning AI. Given the context of the values that man has created to protect himself when working with data, the question arises as to how the virtual space can be identified with the habits of working in the virtual space, if he himself can shape it according to his own habits of behavior, if he himself learns, i.e. man himself teaches it.

Lisnik further argues that the appropriateness of knowing the experience of using artificial intelligence lies in the final statement that the ethics of virtual space, despite the established principles, changes by examining (asking questions) the client for the virtual space of chatbots. He does not know whether a person can determine the content of ethical rules for working with data, but he does know that based on the principles of quantum mechanics applied to the self-learning IT space, by looking at them and searching for them, we can define the principles in our user interface. So again, it's just a matter of human ethics.

Currently, emphasis is placed on ensuring that the profile of university graduates corresponds to the requirements of practice. Universities face criticism from business and their managers that graduates do not have sufficient knowledge and skills, or are unable to apply them correctly in practice. (Mucha, 2024)

Digital transformation is the content of the Fourth Technological Revolution: Brings many new technological changes and knowledge. Their processing, use requires technological education whose science is part of the integration of the entire educational process: technological – humanization – ethics and morals. (Zatrochová, 2020)

As Djami et al. state (2024), education that integrates AI must not only be about using the latest technologies, but should also actively educate about the use of these technologies in a reflective and ethical way. It is important for educational institutions to develop clear and comprehensive policies on the use of AI that include teaching values that promote the responsible use of technology. This includes academic integrity, privacy, equality of access, and social responsibility.

As Lisnik said (Lisnik, 2024) that he need to have enough correct knowledge to be able to make the right decisions from the field of expertise, at the same time, also from the field morality. It is important to have enough information so that users know how to behave morally. That education is needed. According to Majerník (2023), users prefer to use their internet data for privacy reasons.

The channels for communicating information shared among a specific group of the population (generation Z), which is absolutely different from previous generations, but forms a significant part of current and future buyers of products and services, identifying these channels and needs defines the future framework and means of marketing, especially viral marketing. (Kuperová, 2023)

Table 1: Forms of using artificial intelligence in marketing

	Form of use of AI	Nature of the solution	Description
1	Content personalization	Software	Product recommendations, personalized emails, dynamic websites.
2	Chatbots and virtual assistants	Software	Automatic communication with customers via chat.
3	Predictive analytics and scoring	Software	Predicting behavior and evaluating customers.

	Form of use of AI	Nature of the solution	Description
4	Marketing Content Generation	Software	Automated texts, images, videos for campaigns.
5	Manage and optimise your ads	Software	AI optimizes targeting, bidding, and segmentation.
6	Sentiment and social media analysis	Software	Monitor brand sentiment and reactions.
7	Email Marketing Automation	Software	Segmentation, timing, A/B testing of emails.
8	Image recognition and visual analysis	Software + hardware if necessary	Identification of brands, faces, products in images and videos.
9	Dynamic pricing	Software	Automatic price adjustment according to the market situation.

Source: (autors)

Kuperova claims: "Reversely aimed distributional channel represents collection of projects which provide reverse motion of waste and wrappings. Its existence and operation depend on multiple factors, such as country's legislation, economic conditions, motivation, awareness and interest in the solution of waste collection. Reverse logistics nowadays represents a remarkable part of logistics processes of the company. Under Slovak conditions, it is possible to find ways of its application in an indirect form, especially in the form of waste management."

3. Research

In order to find out the current level of use of artificial intelligence in marketing practice in the tourism sector, we conducted a questionnaire survey. The survey was aimed at obtaining the perspective of managers and marketing workers working in this field in Slovakia. We addressed a total of 103 respondents from various organizations operating in the tourism industry, and 78 of them answered validly.

Respondents answered questions about their experiences, approaches, but also concerns related to the use of AI tools in marketing campaigns. Data collection took place online.

The answers obtained provide valuable insight into the current level of readiness of the tourism sector to adopt new technologies responsibly and efficiently.

Of all those addressed, we managed to address more than 60% of marketing employees, more than 23% of managers, and the rest were owners or other undefined positions.

Figure 2: red color - No, blue color - Yes, orange color - Yes, often Source: (authors)

When asked if the company uses AI when working with marketing, 50% said no. More than 42% said yes, and more than 7% said they did very often.

When asked what form of AI they tend to use, more than 77% said that they use ChatGPT at work, 55% of respondents also use a Chatbot or virtual assistants. It is also worth mentioning Mailchimp AI or Google Smart Bidding, which is used by more than 22% of respondents. 11% even use Canva with AI features.

In another question of our research, we asked respondents whether they perceive the ethical side of the use of artificial intelligence.

Figure 3: red color – I think it's well set up, blue color - I am concerned about maintaining an ethical website, orange color - I can't answer. Source: (authors)

As many as 44% answered that they could not assess and answer and 32% answered that they were concerned about maintaining the ethical side. From this, we can conclude that only a quarter of respondents think that AI is well-configured and they are apparently not concerned about its use and its outputs. From our survey, we found that half of the respondents use artificial intelligence services,

but only a quarter are not concerned about its use within ethical values. This means that some users use artificial intelligence without looking at ethical properties.

4. Conclusion

The results of the survey pointed to a low level of practical experience with the use of artificial intelligence in tourism marketing activities. Despite the increasing availability of AI tools and their potential to streamline daily work, in many cases, the use of these technologies remains only marginal in the interest of marketing teams.

For this reason, we recommend systematic and active training for marketers and managers, which would focus not only on the technical aspects of artificial intelligence tools, but above all on their responsible, ethical and effective use. Such training can go a long way in helping travel professionals make better use of available technology to personalize content, automate routine activities, or improve customer experience – without compromising ethical principles or customer trust.

We propose to implement education in the form of:

- practical workshops and trainings organized for specific segments of tourism,
- online courses and e-learning platforms focused on the use of AI in marketing,
- webinars with practitioners who present real-world AI use cases;
- cooperation with universities and professional institutions that can provide updated and professionally guaranteed content.

The responsible use of AI should not be seen as a threat, but as an opportunity to streamline work, streamline decision-making, and strengthen brand credibility in the eyes of the client. It is an educated and informed marketing team that is the key to a successful and ethical connection of technology with the values of tourism.

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**DATA, AI AND DIGITAL-DRIVEN TRANSFORMATION:
SHAPING SUSTAINABLE DIGITAL FUTURES**

OPEN DATA READINESS: EXPLORATORY STUDY OF SLOVENIAN ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

Open data (OD) has emerged as a key driver of transparency, innovation, and economic growth. While governments have invested heavily in OD infrastructures, the actual adoption and integration of OD by private enterprises remain limited and insufficiently studied. This paper explores the OD maturity of Slovenian enterprises using a custom multi-criteria decision model based on the DEX methodology. Drawing from established theoretical frameworks and a systematic review of the literature, the study identifies organizational, technological, and environmental factors influencing OD use. A self-assessment of 28 Slovenian enterprises reveals that although awareness of OD is increasing, implementation varies significantly. These findings highlight key barriers, including lack of infrastructure, limited strategic alignment, and insufficient awareness among assessed enterprises. The DEX-based model proves effective in assessing OD readiness and offering tailored recommendations. This study contributes to understanding enterprise-level OD adoption and offers practical and policy-relevant insights to support further development of data-driven innovation in the private sector.

1. Introduction

Over the past two decades, open data (OD) initiatives have gained significant momentum worldwide, aiming to make data collected by public sector institutions available for reuse. In 2003, the European Commission adopted the first Directive on the re-use of public sector information (PSI) (European Commission, 2003), which Slovenia transposed into national legislation the same year (Republika Slovenija, 2003). These legislative developments laid the foundation for the systematic sharing of data by public institutions, with the broader objective of encouraging private sector entities to also open and utilize data. Today, OD—encompassing both open government data (OGD) and data voluntarily shared by private organizations—is made accessible through public portals and governed by frameworks such as the *8 Principles of Open Government Data* (Open Government Working Group, 2007) and Berners-Lee's *Five-Star Linked Data* model (2012).

According to the European Commission's report based on the European Data Market Monitoring Tool (European Commission, 2020), the data market in EU27 and the UK reached a value of €75 billion in 2019, reflecting a 4.9% growth compared to the previous year. This highlights the growing

economic significance of data and the need for enterprises to be capable of capitalizing on such market developments.

EU institutions and national governments continue to allocate substantial resources toward the development of open data infrastructures and services. A key priority is to obtain feedback on how these resources are being utilized and to promote greater adoption of OD by private organizations. However, despite these investments, the actual use of OD by enterprises remains insufficiently explored. While OD is expected to contribute to transparency, civic engagement, and economic innovation, it is still unclear to what extent businesses are aware of, utilize, and are organizationally prepared to integrate OD into their operations, decision-making, and innovation processes.

The primary objective of this study is to explore the **open data maturity** of Slovenian enterprises. To evaluate OD maturity, we developed a multi-criteria decision model based on the DEX methodology, which has been successfully applied in various real-world decision-making contexts, including digital readiness assessments of SMEs (Kljajić Borštnar & Pucihar, 2021). The model enables enterprises to conduct a structured self-assessment of their OD maturity, and based on the results, receive tailored recommendations to support further development.

This paper presents preliminary findings based on the self-assessments of 28 Slovenian enterprises using the DEX model. Specifically, we report on their overall OD maturity levels, organizational and technological capabilities, the extent of data integration, the strategic use of data, and the types of data applied in decision-making. These early insights contribute to a better understanding of OD use among Slovenian enterprises and are relevant for both academic and policy providers, particularly in the context of ongoing governmental efforts to promote OD provision and use.

2. Literature Review

Research on open data (OD) adoption has predominantly focused on user perspectives, employing established models such as the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (Saxena & Janssen, 2017; Shao, 2023; Talukder et al., 2019), the Technology Acceptance Model (Weerakkody et al., 2017), and Social Cognitive Theory (Wang, 2020). These studies consistently identify ease of use, perceived usefulness, and social influence as key drivers of OD adoption. Additionally, motivations for OD use have been explored across various sectors, including public institutions, private organizations, and entrepreneurs (Alawadhi et al., 2021; Mustapa et al., 2022; Wang & Lo, 2020).

Several studies examined how user needs shape OD publication practices and the role of platforms in addressing public problems (Ruijter et al., 2020; Shepherd et al., 2019). OD has been shown to generate benefits such as innovation, efficiency, and transparency (Apanasevic, 2021; Jetzek et al., 2014; Shao, 2023). Research has also highlighted how OD supports democratic processes (Ruijter & Martinius, 2017), impacts organizational innovation (Huber et al., 2020), and enhances public administration (McBride et al., 2019; Wilson & Cong, 2021). Some studies have proposed measuring OD's impact through the added value it generates throughout its lifecycle (Attard et al., 2016; Magalhaes & Roseira, 2020).

OD policy has been another key area of investigation. Researchers have proposed maturity levels, classifications, and analytical frameworks for OD policy evaluation (Attard et al., 2015; Ruijter & Meijer, 2020). Comparative studies identified variation in policy effectiveness across countries (Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014; Zuiderwijk et al., 2021), while recent work emphasizes designing policies that support OD reuse and institutional integration (Zhou et al., 2023).

Initially, OD adoption was largely driven by government mandates, but over time, the responsibility shifted toward publishers and users. The European Union's OD innovation use cases report (Granel

et al., 2022) aimed to accelerate adoption. Despite this, underutilization of OD remains a challenge. Researchers have documented technical, organizational, and legal barriers (Çaldağ & Gökalp, 2023; Sugg, 2022), and proposed strategies to overcome them (Huber et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2019).

The quality of OD is another critical factor influencing its usability. Studies emphasize the importance of maintaining high-quality data, including its governance and continuous improvement (Ham et al., 2019; Schultz & Kempton, 2022; Moradi et al., 2022).

As OD research has expanded, so has the need for categorization. Several frameworks and classification approaches have been proposed (Safarov et al., 2017; Cruz & Lee, 2016; Ansari et al., 2022), revealing two dominant research streams: one focused on government initiatives, and the other on regional adoption, barriers, and use cases (Ferencek et al., 2022; Wirtz et al., 2022).

Finally, research into OD maturity models has gained traction. While several models exist for assessing publication readiness (Dodds & Newman, 2015; Mustapa et al., 2022), few address the maturity of organizations in terms of OD usage and integration into their operations (Çaldağ & Gökalp, 2022). This highlights a gap in evaluating OD as a strategic asset within enterprise processes.

To address this gap, we have systematically examined the existing literature and identified factors that inhibit or encourage the use of open data by enterprises. We used Technology-Organization-Environment framework to group the factors (Awa, Ojiabo, & Orokor, 2017), which was basis for further multiple-attribute model development.

2. Methodology

This research is based in the Design Science Research (DSR) methodology (Hevner et al., 2004) where a solution to a real business problem is addressed by designing an IT artifact following a rigorous scientific process. The methodology comprises three main phases (Hevner et al., 2004): the rigor phase, in which the foundations for the research are established, such as existing theories, frameworks, constructs, etc., and determines the methodologies to achieve the most viable results. The relevance phase refers to business needs, which are addressed from human, organizational, and technological perspectives; and the design phase, during which the development and evaluation of an artifact are conducted.

Within the rigor phase we conducted a systematic literature review to identify the theories employed to explain the motivation driving individuals and enterprises to use new technologies such as OD. We also reviewed the methods used to measure various aspects of the concept, as well as the resulting constructs, frameworks, and models proposed. Most importantly, we have identified factors that influence the use of OD in enterprises, which were used to design the multiple criteria decision model. We used the qualitative hierarchical multiple criteria decision methodology DEX (Bohanec & Rajkovič, 1990). The model is implemented as self-assessment on-line tool, that provides enterprises with insights into their strengths and weaknesses in their organizational preparedness for using OD and offer guidance to enhance their maturity level.

The self-assessment tool offers enterprises insight into the potential benefits that OD could present to their business. Additionally, after a significant number of self-assessments conducted by enterprises, governments would gain insight into the state of the population of enterprises' familiarity with the OD concept.

2.1 The model

The model serves as a decision-making aid for alternative assessment and analysis. DEX method is utilized in a publicly available DEXi software which offers several analyses: interactive visual analysis, “what-if” analysis, pluses and minuses analysis, and others.

Initially we have identified 118 driving and inhibiting factors, which we further refined through a facilitated brainstorming session with 16 domain experts using innovative brainstorming software and generative AI. In this process the group of experts generated 260 ideas, which were categorized into 11 groups and prioritized through voting. A smaller decision-making group combined the factors and ideas, which resulted in 56 attributes used in the final model.

The final model consists of three subtrees representing the two basic dimensions: 1) organizational maturity and 2) business value. The two sub-trees are further subdivided into groups of attributes corresponding to the dimensions describing organizational maturity (organizational capability, technological capability and business environment) and business value (strategic value and competitive advantage). Each group is further divided. There are 32 basic and 24 aggregated attributes in the tree.

For each attribute in the tree, the corresponding qualitative domain value is defined (for example: *Autonomy* {no, some, full} and the aggregation rules for inferring aggregated attribute values (for example: [if *Autonomy* {no} and *Open communication* {no} than *Innovation culture* {low}]). The model thus provides a composite value for each aggregated attribute in the tree, which is easily understood by the user and can be explained.

The maturity of open data use is represented by a five-level qualitative scale: {lagging, basic, initial, advanced, winner}. This scale offers sufficient granularity to capture the nuanced differences in how enterprises utilize open data.

3. Results

We present preliminary results of the assessment of maturity of enterprises to use open data conducted from September 2024 to March 2025. In total 28 enterprises from Slovenia had completed the assessment of maturity to use open data using DEX model implemented as a self-assessment online tool, 7 of those were from the East and 21 from the West cohesion region. The sample consists of 14 micro, 5 small, 3 medium and 6 large enterprises (Table 1).

Most of the enterprises came from the Information and communication sector (6), Other service activities (5), Professional activities (4), Education (3), Manufacturing (3), Financial and insurance activities (2), and one from the Accommodation and food service activities, Agriculture, forestry and fishing, Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles each.

The overall maturity to use open data shows that only 2 enterprises reached the highest level of maturity (winner), 10 enterprises reached the level advanced, 8 reached the initial level, 7 the basic level and only 1 the lowest level (lagging).

The overall maturity consists of three sub-categories: organizational capability, technological capability and business environment. Organizational capability evaluates the organization's capabilities in the areas of human resource management, organizational culture, governance, and strategic planning. 12 of the assessed enterprises reached the medium level of organizational capability and 11 of them excellent level. Only two enterprises reached low level of organizational capabilities.

The extent of technological capabilities refers to the maturity of data technologies, and the strategic role of information technology within the organization. Majority of the assessed enterprises falls into medium level (11), while there are 4 enterprises assessed as good and 8 as excellent. Only four of the enterprises fall into low level of technological capability.

Only 4 out of 28 enterprises reported that they do not have their data organized, 5 of them uses data to support their daily activities, and 13 of them reported that their data is systematically structured to support the execution of daily business activities and to serve as a basis for informed decision-making. Finally, 6 of them reported that they regard data as a strategic asset for increasing added value and is therefore managed comprehensively throughout its entire lifecycle.

Only 4 enterprises reported to rely on instinctive decision-making without systematically relying on any type of data. Four reported to base their decisions on internal data, while 10 use internal as well as external data sources, and finally 10 out of 28 uses internal, external and open data sources in their decision-making processes.

4. Discussion and conclusion

The findings of this exploratory study provide valuable initial insights into the open data (OD) maturity of Slovenian enterprises. The study confirms that while awareness and interest in OD exist among Slovenian organizations, actual implementation and integration of OD into strategic and operational processes remain uneven and, in many cases, limited.

Only two out of 28 assessed enterprises achieved the highest maturity level ("winner"), while the majority were classified as "advanced" or "initial." This distribution indicates a growing but still emerging readiness for OD adoption. A deeper look at organizational capabilities revealed encouraging results, with a significant number of enterprises exhibiting strong internal foundations, such as human resource management and strategic planning. However, technological capabilities were more varied, with some organizations lacking the necessary infrastructure or strategic IT alignment to fully leverage OD.

Moreover, while a third of enterprises view data as a strategic resource, a considerable number still rely on ad hoc or internal data only, with minimal integration of external or open data sources. This highlights a key maturity gap: although some organizations recognize the potential of OD, many have yet to institutionalize its use in decision-making and innovation.

These findings align with existing literature that identifies barriers to OD adoption, such as limited technical resources, lack of awareness, unclear legal frameworks, and cultural aversion (Çaldağ & Gökalp, 2023; Sugg, 2022). They also reinforce the notion that enterprises, especially SMEs, require targeted support—including tools, training, and policy incentives—to increase their OD maturity.

The DEX-based self-assessment model developed in this study has proven effective in identifying organizational strengths and weaknesses in relation to OD adoption. Its ability to provide tailored recommendations adds practical value and enhances its utility for both enterprises and policymakers.

This study is subject to several limitations. First, the sample size is relatively small ($n = 28$), and while it includes a diverse mix of enterprises by size and sector, it may not fully represent the broader Slovenian enterprise population. Second, the data is self-reported, which may introduce subjectivity or social desirability bias in the assessment responses. Third, the model focuses primarily on internal organizational factors and may not fully capture external influences such as legal or ecosystem-level constraints.

Future research should focus on validating the model with a larger and more diverse sample, ideally across multiple countries or regions, to enable comparative analysis. Longitudinal studies could provide insight into how OD maturity evolves over time and in response to policy interventions or technological change. Further development of the model could also integrate external environmental factors and examine the interaction between OD maturity and enterprise performance outcomes, such as innovation rates or market growth.

Additionally, future studies could explore sector-specific OD readiness, particularly in industries where data-driven innovation holds high potential (e.g., healthcare, energy, finance). Another avenue would be to examine the role of intermediary organizations or platforms in facilitating OD adoption among enterprises, especially SMEs.

This study contributes to the growing body of research on open data adoption by addressing the underexplored area of enterprise readiness. Through a novel multi-criteria decision support model, it provides a practical framework for assessing OD maturity and offers actionable insights for organizations aiming to enhance their use of open data. The preliminary findings underscore the importance of strengthening both technological infrastructure and organizational awareness to support broader and deeper integration of OD in the private sector. Ultimately, this research lays the foundation for further empirical investigation and policy development to foster a more data-driven economy.

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UTILIZATION OF AI-DRIVEN MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGIES: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract

The article aims to identify the current and anticipated use of AI-driven manufacturing technologies in Slovak manufacturing companies. Building on a 2017 study by Závadský & Závadská, the research revisits and expands the original sample to 115 companies. The study examines the adoption and future expectations of 10 selected AI technologies through a structured survey of quality and production managers. Key findings show that 3D Printing, Predictive Maintenance Systems, Generative Design, and Supply Chain Optimization Systems are the most widely used. Digital Twins, Robotic Process Automation, and Collaborative Robots are the most anticipated. Predictive Maintenance, though widely used, has limited future growth potential. The data reveal the current state and trajectory of AI integration in manufacturing. Statistical tests confirm the sample's representativeness across industries. These partial results contribute to understanding AI's practical implementation and expected evolution in industrial settings.

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming manufacturing processes, offering potential to improve productivity, quality, and responsiveness. While numerous studies have explored the theoretical capabilities of AI in industrial settings, there remains a research gap in empirical data on how AI-driven technologies are being practically adopted. Much of the existing literature is either focused on global trends or centered around high-profile multinational corporations, leaving limited insight into how large manufacturing companies in smaller economies are engaging with these technologies. This research seeks to address that gap by examining the real-world application and anticipated use of ten selected AI-driven manufacturing technologies within Slovak industrial enterprises. The study builds upon earlier research conducted in 2017 by Závadský & Závadská, which assessed managerial expectations regarding the future deployment of intelligent technologies. However, while that prior work focused on predictive expectations, the current research shifts toward empirical verification. The relevance of this research is twofold. For academia, it introduces a structured methodology for assessing current versus future adoption levels, which can be replicated or extended in other regions or sectors. For practitioners, particularly managers and decision-makers in manufacturing, the study provides evidence-based insights into peer behavior, technology trends,

and areas of opportunity. The motivation for this research is grounded in the need to close the gap between AI's theoretical promise and its actual implementation on the shop floor. While terms like Industry 4.0, smart manufacturing, and digital transformation are widely used, there is still uncertainty about how these concepts translate into concrete action. By capturing both the current state and expected trajectory of AI technologies in manufacturing, this study offers a clearer picture of how industrial digitalization is unfolding in practice. This research is motivated by the lack of granular, country-specific evidence on AI deployment in manufacturing, the need for practical guidance for industrial managers, and the opportunity to enhance scholarly understanding of technology adoption dynamics. The findings are expected to support theoretical advancement and practical decision-making in the evolving landscape of AI-driven production systems. The main scientific objective of this research study is to determine how AI-driven manufacturing technologies are currently used and what the expectations of managers of large manufacturing companies are regarding the future use of 10 selected AI-driven manufacturing technologies. Based on the main research objective, we set the following research questions: RQa (Which AI-driven manufacturing technologies are most widely used today?); RQb (Which AI-driven manufacturing technologies are most anticipated by managers in the future?); and RQc (Which AI-driven manufacturing technologies have the most negligible potential for deployment in a sample of large manufacturing companies?).

2. Literature review

There are a large number of studies on AI-driven technologies that are applied not only in manufacturing processes. It was challenging to identify a set of AI-driven technologies that would provide answers to the research questions. Rojeid et al. (2022) highlight AI's growing impact on manufacturing, a shift also emphasized by Kumar (2017), who outlines its benefits for planning, resource allocation, and decision-making. Predictive maintenance is key, as Wan et al. (2021) and Tikhonov & Sazonov (2022) show AI's ability to forecast equipment failures. Waltersmann et al. (2021) highlight how AI enables flexible production lines, and Rojek & Mikołajewski (2024) point to its use in additive manufacturing. However, Antosz et al. (2020) mention data integration challenges, while Hassan et al. (2023) raise cybersecurity and workforce concerns. RPA's evolution is detailed by Bhardwaj et al. (2015), Madakam et al. (2019), Santos et al. (2020), and Mamede et al. (2022), stressing implementation hurdles. Hyun & Lee (2018) and Eulerich et al. (2023) point to RPA's limits and risks. Syed et al. (2020) discuss its shift toward intelligent automation. Zhang et al. (2023) show real-world use in finance, while Fernandez & Aman (2021) and Hofmann et al. (2020) highlight investment, maintenance, and ethical concerns. Digital Twins (DT) are explored by Tao et al. (2018), Horn & Mahadevan (2021), and Liu et al. (2021) for their predictive and modeling capabilities. Zheng et al. (2019) and Bhatti et al. (2021) show DT's industrial value. Mashaly (2021) and Yu et al. (2022) confirm its role in diagnostics and energy. Qi et al. (2021), Mihaita et al. (2022), and Hosamo & Imran (2022) emphasize broader applications and cybersecurity needs. Fuller et al. (2020) and Madni et al. (2019) discuss technical challenges. Based on the literature review, ten AI-driven technologies were selected for research purposes. Predictive Maintenance Systems (PMS) use machine learning to analyze data from equipment sensors, predicting when maintenance is needed before failures occur. This prevents unexpected downtimes, reduces repair costs, and extends the lifespan of machinery. It's crucial in high-volume manufacturing where even short disruptions can be costly. Computer Vision for Quality Control (CVQC) identifies defects on production lines in real time. It detects anomalies in shape, size, or texture with far greater accuracy and speed than human inspectors. This ensures consistent product quality, reduces waste, and prevents faulty items from reaching customers. Robotic Process Automation (RPA) enhanced with AI allows robots to handle repetitive, rule-based tasks autonomously. These systems free up human workers for higher-level

duties, improve consistency, and speed up operations, especially valuable in sectors where precision and scalability are key. Digital Twins (DT) technology creates virtual replicas of physical assets and processes. With AI, manufacturers can simulate performance, test changes, and anticipate outcomes without disrupting actual production. This reduces risk and enhances strategic planning. Equipped with AI, Cobots (collaborative robots - CR) work safely alongside human operators on precision tasks like assembly or welding. They learn from human input and adapt to different roles, making production more flexible and efficient. AI-based supply chain optimization systems (SCOS) analyze massive data streams to optimize inventory, forecast demand, and improve logistics. These systems help minimize delays, reduce costs, and keep production aligned with market needs. Automated Guided Vehicles (AGV) with AI navigate factory floors independently, transporting materials without human oversight. Their ability to adapt routes in real time boosts safety and delivery efficiency, especially in dynamic environments. Natural Language Processing (NLP) for Human-Machine Interaction allows operators to control machines using natural language. This simplifies complex tasks, reduces training time, and improves accessibility on the shop floor. AI-driven generative design (GD) systems let manufacturers input design goals and constraints, then generate optimal solutions. This speeds up product development, fosters innovation, and creates designs that balance performance, cost, and manufacturability. Finally, AI-integrated 3D printing (3DP) enhances production speed, material efficiency, and part quality. By adjusting parameters in real time, AI ensures that each printed part meets specifications while reducing waste.

3. Methodology

The primary research method employed in this study is a structured survey administered to managers of large manufacturing companies operating in Slovakia. The survey was designed to capture both the current use and future expectations regarding ten selected AI-driven manufacturing technologies. This study builds on the foundation laid by an earlier investigation conducted in 2017 by Závadská & Závadský, which surveyed 44 companies to assess expectations surrounding the deployment of 14 intelligent technologies. In the current research, we aimed to revisit that original sample while expanding it to achieve broader representation and relevance. The same selection criteria were applied: each company had to qualify as a large manufacturing enterprise, defined by the Slovak Statistical Office, and be actively involved in production processes. Using this framework, we reached out to an additional group of quality and production managers, resulting in a total of 150 companies contacted. By the cut-off point for analysis in mid-February 2025, we received 115 complete responses, which form the basis of the current findings. These responses span a range of industries, and a Pearson chi-square test confirmed that the sample is representative of the national distribution of large manufacturing enterprises by sector. The research was conducted in three main phases: 1) Preparation Phase (November–December 2024); 2) Data Collection Phase (January–Mid-February 2025); and 3) Analysis Phase (Mid-February–March 2025). The questionnaire was concise but targeted, structured around the following key questions for both quality managers and production managers: “Which of the following AI-driven manufacturing technologies are currently in use in your company?” and “Which AI-driven manufacturing technologies does your company plan to implement shortly (e.g., next 3–5 years)?”.

For the research, we applied the Pearson representativeness test. As Table 1 shows, the research sample is representative. At a significance level of 0.05, we tested the sample according to 9 degrees of freedom because we examined enterprises from 10 types of industries. Since the achieved χ^2 value is lower than the statistical one, we conclude that the sample is representative, namely $\chi^2 = 2.695 < 3.320$, and where n_i is events observed in the sample, np_i is particular theoretical distribution at the level of statistical significance α for appropriate degrees of freedom $(k-1)$, and k is the number of

fitted parameters. According to the Slovak Statistical Office, the basic set consisted of 251 large manufacturing enterprises for selected industrial sectors.

Table 1. χ^2 -test due to the type of industry

Type of industry (SK NACE)	np_i		n_i		$(n_i - np_i)^2$	$(n_i - np_i)^2 / np_i$
	No.	%	No.	%		
CA Manufacture of food products, beverages, and tobacco products	23	9.16	11	9.57	0.16	0.018
CE Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products	5	1.99	2	1.74	0.06	0.032
CF Manufacture of pharmaceuticals, medicinal chemicals, and botanical products	3	1.20	2	1.74	0.30	0.248
CG Manufacture of rubber and plastics products and other non-metallic mineral products	40	15.94	21	18.26	5.40	0.339
CH Manufacture of basic metals and fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	29	11.55	12	10.43	1.25	0.108
CI Manufacture of computer, electronic, and optical products	11	4.38	5	4.35	0.00	0.000
CJ Manufacture of electrical equipment	29	11.55	12	10.43	1.25	0.108
CL Manufacture of transport equipment	52	20.72	21	18.26	6.03	0.291
F Construction	11	4.38	8	6.96	6.63	1.512
H Transportation and storage	48	19.12	21	18.26	0.74	0.039
	251	100.00	115	100.00		$\chi^2 = 2.695$

Source: (authors)

For the research, we have established variables based on which we will be able to answer the research questions. These are the following research variables:

- AI_IT_abs = absolute number of managers from manufacturing enterprises where an AI-driven technology is used or planned to be used;
- AI_IT_rel = percentage of managers from manufacturing enterprises where an AI-driven technology is used or planned to be used;
- AI_IT_absA = absolute number of managers from manufacturing enterprises where an AI-driven manufacturing technology is used;
- AI_IT_absF = absolute number of managers who are expecting the use of AI-driven manufacturing technologies in the future;
- AI_IT_relA = percentage of managers from manufacturing enterprises where an AI-driven manufacturing technology is used;
- AI_IT_relF = percentage of managers who are expecting the use of AI-driven manufacturing technologies in the future;
- ΔFA = difference between future and actual utilization of an AI-driven manufacturing technology.

4. Results and Discussion

We asked managers in a sample of large manufacturing companies to select 5 AI-driven manufacturing technologies that they already use (AI_IT_absA) and plan to use in the future (AI_IT_absF). We calculated these two research variables' relative shares (AI_IT_relA ; AI_IT_relF)

in 115 businesses. We then calculated the difference between actual utilization and future managers' expectations as ΔFA . The total sum of relative shares (AI_IT_rel) speaks to AI-driven manufacturing technology's actual use and future use.

Table 2. AI-driven manufacturing technologies utilization

	AI IT abs	AI IT absA	AI IT relA	AI IT absF	AI IT relF	ΔFA	AI IT rel
RPA	67	24	20.87	43	37.39	16.52	58.26
DT	82	31	26.96	51	44.35	17.39	71.30
PMS	63	51	44.35	12	10.43	-33.91	54.78
CVQC	41	21	18.26	20	17.39	-0.87	35.65
CR	62	23	20.00	39	33.91	13.91	53.91
SCOS	48	37	32.17	11	9.57	-22.61	41.74
AGV	61	33	28.70	28	24.35	-4.35	53.04
NLP	31	9	7.83	22	19.13	11.30	26.96
GD	67	46	40.00	21	18.26	-21.74	58.26
3DP	87	54	46.96	33	28.70	-18.26	75.65

Source: (authors)

As Table 2 shows, the most used AI-driven manufacturing technologies are currently 3DP (46.96%), PMS (44.35%), GD (40.00%), and SCOS (32.17%). It answers the RQa: Which AI-driven manufacturing technologies are most widely used today?

Figure 1. Prediction of the future AI-driven technologies utilization in total [%] Source: (authors)

The most expected AI-driven manufacturing technologies in the future are DT (17.39%), RPA (16.52%), CR (13.91%), and NLP (11.30%). Expectations are calculated as the difference between the current and future use of AI-driven manufacturing technology. This answers the research question RQb: Which AI-driven manufacturing technologies are most anticipated by managers in the future? The technologies with the most negligible growth potential, as they are already sufficiently used today, are PMS (33.91%), SCOS (22.61%), GD (21.74%), and 3DP (18.26%). This answers the research question RQc: Which AI-driven manufacturing technologies have the smallest potential for deployment in a sample of large manufacturing companies? However, if we add up the relative shares of current use and future use, Figure 1 shows which AI-driven technologies will be most used in the future. The research revealed clear patterns in the adoption and expected use of AI-driven manufacturing technologies. Among the ten examined, 3D Printing, Predictive Maintenance Systems, Generative Design, and Supply Chain Optimization Systems were identified as the most commonly used in the surveyed companies. These technologies are likely to lead due to their established practical benefits, relatively mature development, and tangible impact on operational efficiency. For instance,

3D Printing supports prototyping and customized production, Predictive Maintenance reduces downtime and maintenance costs, Generative Design enhances product innovation, and Supply Chain Optimization helps manage complexity and improve logistics performance. In contrast, technologies like Digital Twins, RPA, and NLP (though not yet widespread) show the highest increase in expected adoption. This trend reflects an interest in more advanced, integrated, intelligent systems. Digital Twins, for example, allow virtual replication of fundamental processes, enabling predictive analytics and real-time control. Their relatively low current use, paired with high future expectations, suggests growing awareness and improving readiness for implementation. Similarly, RPA is gaining attention as companies seek to automate repetitive, rule-based tasks, often in administrative or quality control processes. On the other hand, technologies such as Predictive Maintenance and 3D Printing show negative growth potential. This indicates that many companies that intended to implement them may have already done so, reaching a saturation point. These technologies have become standard tools rather than emerging innovations, especially in industries with high operational demands and mature digital infrastructures. These findings offer several practical implications for manufacturing enterprises. Companies can prioritize investment in Digital Twins, RPA, and Collaborative Robots to align with industry trends and remain competitive. Firms that have not yet adopted Predictive Maintenance or 3D Printing may need to assess why peers have integrated them successfully. Managers should also consider training and workforce adaptation strategies to support the transition toward these advanced technologies.

The research also highlights several limitations and barriers. First, the study itself is based on a partial dataset. Although the sample size is statistically representative, additional data could provide more robust insights and enable deeper analysis across specific sectors. Moreover, the focus on large companies may not fully reflect the experiences and challenges faced by small and medium-sized enterprises, which often lack the same resources and technological infrastructure. From the adoption perspective, several practical barriers persist. Implementation complexity, integration with legacy systems, high initial investment costs, and a shortage of skilled personnel continue to slow progress, especially for advanced solutions like Digital Twins and NLP. Concerns around cybersecurity and data governance also remain unresolved in many companies. Furthermore, the organizational mindset is a non-trivial factor: even when technologies are available and technically viable, resistance to change and limited digital maturity can delay or derail implementation.

5. Conclusion

This study offers a focused analysis of the current and expected use of AI-driven technologies in Slovak manufacturing, based on a survey of managers from large industrial companies. It explores ten specific technologies: Predictive Maintenance Systems, 3D Printing, Generative Design, Supply Chain Optimization Systems, Digital Twins, Robotic Process Automation (RPA), Collaborative Robots (Cobots), Computer Vision for Quality Control, Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs), and Natural Language Processing (NLP). These technologies collectively form the backbone of AI-driven manufacturing transformation under the Industry 4.0 framework. The results suggest a maturing landscape where some technologies—particularly Predictive Maintenance, 3D Printing, Generative Design, and Supply Chain Optimization—have already seen broad adoption. These systems are now considered part of the operational core in many companies, contributing to greater efficiency, reduced downtime, and enhanced customization. However, their saturation also implies limited room for further expansion. Conversely, technologies such as Digital Twins, AI-enhanced RPA, Cobots, and NLP show strong potential for future deployment. These tools offer deeper integration, real-time responsiveness, and improved human-machine interaction, aligning with the evolving demands of intelligent, adaptive production environments. The findings suggest that future success will hinge not

only on adopting new technologies but also on overcoming these organizational, technical, and human barriers. Companies must invest in workforce development, change management, and robust digital infrastructure to fully realize the benefits of AI-driven manufacturing. The technologies with the greatest growth potential will likely be those that offer not just innovation, but ease of integration, scalability, and clear returns on investment. In conclusion, while the road to full AI integration in manufacturing is still under construction, this study provides a directional map. It underscores that true transformation is a multidimensional effort, requiring not only technology adoption but strategic alignment, cultural readiness, and sustained investment. As new research expands the dataset and more companies move from pilot phases to scaled deployment, a clearer picture will emerge of how AI will ultimately redefine manufacturing performance.

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DIGITALIZATION AS A KEY DRIVER OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN THE MUSIC INDUSTRY IN EUROPEAN UNION

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Abstract

Digitalization is fundamentally changing the way the music industry operates and creating new economic opportunities, particularly through the rise of streaming platforms. This article examines the relationship between countries' economic development and music streaming revenues within the European Union. The aim is to determine whether countries with higher economic maturity are experiencing greater growth in digital music distribution. The research is based on data from the Statista database for the years 2015 to 2023 and uses correlation and regression analysis together with non-parametric tests (Kruskal-Wallis and Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner). The results show that music streaming revenues are statistically significantly higher in countries with higher economic development, while indicators such as real GDP growth rate and household spending did not show a consistent relationship. The findings highlight the existing digital divide between countries and highlight the need for targeted support for less developed economies in the areas of digital infrastructure and sustainable development. Digitalization can thus be not only an engine of economic growth, but also a means of ensuring the environmental and social sustainability of the music sector.

1. Introduction

Digitalization is transforming the music industry in fundamental ways, altering how music is produced, distributed, and monetized (Baym et al., 2021; Brusila et al., 2022). This transformation is particularly relevant in the context of the European Union, where disparities in digital infrastructure and economic development may influence the extent to which countries can benefit from these changes. This study aims to understand the relationship between economic maturity and growth in music streaming revenues—a key indicator of the digital economy in the cultural sector. By exploring this relationship, we seek to inform policymakers, industry stakeholders, and scholars about the digital divide and its implications for sustainable development within the music industry.

The music industry has undergone several fundamental changes, the most significant of which was digitalization. As Lozic & Cikovic (2023) state, the development of this industry was not only about

the invention of the phonograph, but mainly about the possibilities of mass production and distribution (Ruiz-Resto, 2023). The transition to digital formats was difficult - physical carriers replaced digital files and the Internet enabled their rapid dissemination (Denk et al., 2022). This trend led to widespread piracy, which significantly weakened the profits and position of record companies. A key turning point came in 1991 with the Napster platform, which enabled online music sharing.

The aim of this research paper is to examine the relationship between the growth of music streaming revenues and the economic maturity of countries, assuming that countries with higher economic maturity experience stronger growth in revenues from digital distribution platforms. Digitalization, represented by the growing importance of streaming services, is seen as one of the main catalysts for the transformation of the music industry.

2. Literature review

2.1 Disruptive Innovation and the Music Industry

The transition to digital formats disrupted the traditional structure of the music industry. Services like Napster (1991) and later iTunes revolutionized how music was consumed, initiating a shift from physical carriers to digital downloads and eventually streaming. iTunes, in particular, represented a key turning point by legitimizing digital music sales and providing a new economic model (Ruiz-Resto, 2023). This wave of disruption laid the foundation for the emergence of music-tech ecosystems and global platforms.

While physical carriers are experiencing a decline in sales, digital streaming is experiencing a significant increase and has become the majority source of digital music distribution. However, this transition also brings new environmental challenges – streaming music requires enormous amounts of energy to power servers in data centres around the world (Chalmers et al., 2021). In response, some digital platforms are starting to work with organizations that help them offset their carbon footprint by supporting reforestation projects or investing in renewable energy sources. An example is Spotify, which is switching from traditional data centres to the Google Cloud platform, which claims to operate using low-carbon energy sources (Chin et al., 2023; Pizzolitto, 2024).

The traditional three-part segmentation of the music industry into publishing, recording and live music has been overcome. These traditional sectors have been joined by a fourth line of production and sales known as music-tech. This sector is particularly well developed in China and represents a significant shift in the structure of the global music industry (Zhang & Negus, 2021). In the process of digital transformation, traditional sectors of the music industry have a historic opportunity to connect with the new music-tech sector, thereby finding new paths of development and economic sustainability. A significant phenomenon of today is the emergence and development of export music agencies, which focus on presenting new musical talents at the international level and streamline the exchange of information between professionals in the music industry. Although digital distribution has significantly changed the functioning of the music industry, marketing and distribution alone are not sufficient means to ensure its functioning. Offline cooperation, which is ensured by export agencies, is equally important (Hosseini & Rajabipoor Meybodi, 2023).

2.2 Economic sustainability in the digital era

Even though sales of physical music carriers are declining, we can currently observe a significant increase in concert attendance in the live music industry - an industry that includes live music festivals and concerts. Thanks to new ways of marketing and distributing advertising through digital platforms, live concerts have become increasingly popular, representing a significant source of revenue at a time

when physical sales are declining (Hagen, 2022). The music industry is also now dominated by global promotional monopolies and their music festivals, paid internet streaming services and YouTube. In addition, a number of music entrepreneurs are emerging, offering different methods of operating the music business and innovative product portfolios. Digitalization has also affected the way artists approach the release of music. Artists release a lot of music that is available for free on the internet but serves as the best promotion for their live performances. This strategy shows an adaptation to the new conditions of the digital market and represents a key aspect of economic sustainability in the current music industry (Brenner & Hartl, 2021).

3. Data and Methodology

The aim of this research paper is to examine the relationship between the growth of music streaming revenues and the economic maturity of countries, assuming that countries with higher GDP per capita experience stronger growth in revenues from digital distribution platforms. Digitalization, represented by the growing importance of streaming services, is seen as one of the main catalysts for the transformation of the music industry.

3.1 Data source

Empirical data were drawn from the Statista database, which provides reliable time series and international comparisons in the field of the music industry. The following indicators were used for the research purposes:

- Annual music streaming revenues by country (2019,2020,2023),
- Real GDP growth rate (USD, purchasing power parity),
- Household Final Consumption Expenditure.

The data were normalized and analysed using correlation and regression analysis to verify the relationship between the economic level of the country and the performance of streaming services.

3.2 Hypothesis formulation

Based on the preliminary analysis and theoretical framework, the following hypotheses were established:

- H₁: Higher economic development of the country (Real GDP growth rate) is positively correlated with the development of music streaming revenues.
- H₂: Higher economic development of the country (Household final consumption expenditure) is positively correlated with the development of music streaming revenues.

The research conducted a descriptive statistical analysis of all variables to verify their distribution characteristics and ensure that the values fall within an acceptable range. Particular attention was paid to the skewness indicator as an indicator of distribution asymmetry, which may indicate deviations from normality.

However, it is important to note that the standard error of the estimate in the t-test may underestimate the true error rate when comparing multiple groups, and therefore the t-test is not recommended for use when analyzing differences between more than two groups. In such cases, it is more appropriate to choose alternative methods such as analysis of variance (ANOVA).

4. Results and Discussion

Figure 1 shows the global growth in the number of users of music streaming services from 2015 to 2023. The trend shows a continuous increase in the user base, indicating a significant shift in consumer preferences from physical media to digital content. The growth of users supports the economic sustainability of the music industry through increased subscription and advertising revenue.

Figure 1. Music streaming – worldwide (number of users in mil.) Source: (Statista)

Figure 2 illustrates the development of the average revenue per user of streaming services worldwide in USD. This indicator provides insight into the profitability of individual users and also highlights differences between countries according to the level of economic development. Higher average revenue often corresponds to higher purchasing power of users in economically developed countries.

Figure 2. Average revenue per user (in USD) Source: (Statista)

Kruskal-Wallis tests (Table 1-3) conducted for 2019, 2020 and 2023 showed that music streaming revenue (REV) showed consistently statistically significant differences between higher-income (High) and lower-income (Low) countries. The difference was particularly pronounced in 2019 ($\chi^2 = 8.7416$, $p = 0.0031$, $\varepsilon^2 = 0.3362$), with this trend continuing in 2020 ($\chi^2 = 9.2569$, $p = 0.0023$, $\varepsilon^2 = 0.3560$) and 2023 ($\chi^2 = 8.4524$, $p = 0.0036$, $\varepsilon^2 = 0.3251$). These findings were also confirmed by pairwise comparisons, which showed significant differences in streaming revenue between country groups ($p < 0.01$ in all years).

In contrast, household spending (HC) and gross domestic product growth (GDP_GR) did not show consistent statistical significance across the years studied. While GDP_GR showed a significant difference in 2019 ($\chi^2 = 5.1541$, $p = 0.0232$), this result was not repeated in subsequent years, suggesting a weaker or less stable relationship.

Table 1–3 reference Kruskal-Wallis test results for 2019, 2020, and 2023, confirming that streaming revenues (REV) are significantly higher in wealthier countries. In contrast, GDP growth (GDP_GR) and household consumption (HC) show inconsistent influence on music streaming revenues across the years studied.

The digital divide is evident in the persistent gaps in streaming revenue. Higher-income countries benefit from better internet access, higher mobile penetration, and stronger digital consumer behaviour. The persistent revenue gap reflects structural inequalities, rather than temporary macroeconomic fluctuations.

Table 1. One-Way Anova results - 2019

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
HC_19	2.0733	1	0.1499	0.0797
GDP_GR_19	5.1541	1	0.0232	0.1982
REV_19	8.7416	1	0.0031	0.3362

Pairwise comparisons - HC_19

		W	p
High	Low	-2.0363	0.1500

Pairwise comparisons - GDP_GR_19

		W	p
High	Low	3.2107	0.0232

Pairwise comparisons - REV_19

		W	p
High	Low	-4.1813	0.0031

Source: (own calculations according to Statista (2024) and Eurostat (2024))

Table 2. One-Way Anova results - 2020

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
HC	2.1529	1	0.1423	0.0828
GDP_GR	0.6242	1	0.4295	0.0240
REV	9.2569	1	0.0023	0.3560

Pairwise comparisons - HC

		W	p
High	Low	-2.0750	0.1424

Pairwise comparisons - GDP_GR

		W	p
High	Low	-1.1173	0.4297

Pairwise comparisons - REV

		W	p
High	Low	-4.3028	0.0023

Source: (own calculations according to Statista (2024) and Eurostat (2024))

Table 3. One-Way Anova results - 2023

Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
HC_23	3.2822	1	0.0700	0.1262
GDP_GR_23	0.7836	1	0.3760	0.0301
REV_23	8.4524	1	0.0036	0.3251

Pairwise comparisons - HC_23

		W	p
High	Low	-2.5621	0.0701

Pairwise comparisons - GDP_GR_23

		W	p
High	Low	1.2519	0.3761

Pairwise comparisons - REV_23

		W	p
High	Low	-4.1115	0.0036

Source: (own calculations according to Statista (2024) and Eurostat (2024))

These results indicate that the growth of music streaming revenue is more strongly associated with the overall economic level of a country than with annual fluctuations in GDP growth or household consumption.

The findings of this study support the hypothesis that countries with higher economic maturity experience stronger growth in music streaming revenues. This result supports a broader literature that highlights that digital infrastructure, purchasing power, and established digital consumer behaviour are key factors for success in the digital content industry (Chin et al., 2023). Wealthier countries tend to benefit from better access to stable internet, higher smartphone penetration, and a technologically savvy population, all of which facilitate the use of subscription-based or advertising-based streaming services (Khlystova & Kalyuzhnova, 2023).

While GDP growth and household final consumption expenditure were expected to have an impact on streaming performance, their inconsistent statistical significance suggests that they are less predictive than overall economic maturity. This is consistent with existing studies that emphasize the importance of long-term structural factors over short-term macroeconomic changes in digital market development (Brenner & Hartl, 2021).

The persistent gap between high- and low-income countries in streaming revenues over all years points to a persistent digital divide. This not only limits the economic sustainability of the music industry in less developed countries, but also makes it more difficult to gain equal access to global music markets (Geurts & Cepa, 2023). Moreover, it confirms previous findings that music-technology ecosystems thrive in more economically developed countries where innovation, investment, and regulatory support converge (Zhang & Negus, 2021).

These findings call for targeted policy measures, including subsidies for digital infrastructure development, international cooperation, and capacity building in lower-income countries, to bridge the gap. The integration of sustainable practices, such as carbon-neutral streaming operations (Chalmers et al., 2021), should be globally available to ensure that digitalization contributes equitably to both the economic and environmental sustainability of the music sector.

5. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates a strong and consistent relationship between a country's economic development and the growth of music streaming revenues, with high-income countries having a significant advantage. While short-term economic indicators such as GDP growth and household consumption expenditure showed limited impact, the results reinforce the idea that broader economic maturity – reflected in stable infrastructure, consumer habits and digital readiness – is a key driver of success in the digital music economy.

From a practical perspective, the research highlights both the opportunities and challenges of digitalization. While its benefits for economic sustainability are evident in developed countries, barriers such as poor infrastructure and lower purchasing power persist in less developed regions. This deepens inequalities in the global music industry. To mitigate these, it is necessary to invest in digital infrastructure, promote international cooperation and make the benefits of digitalization available to all regions. At the same time, music platforms should support fairer remuneration and better access for creators around the world.

As the digital music ecosystem continues to evolve, ensuring both economic and environmental sustainability will require coordinated efforts across the public and private sectors. Only in this way

can digitalization serve as a truly transformative force that benefits the global music industry as a whole.

While this study provides valuable insights into the relationship between economic development and the growth of music streaming revenues in European Union countries, it is important to point out several limitations.

5.1 Limitations of the Study

Firstly, the analysis covers a relatively short time period, from 2019 to 2023. Such a time frame may not capture long-term structural trends or cyclical fluctuations in the music industry or the broader economic environment. The results may therefore not be fully applicable to future developments or long-term economic changes. Future research could benefit from extending the time frame and tracking trends over a longer horizon.

Secondly, the study primarily relies on GDP per capita as a proxy for countries' economic development. Although this is a standard indicator, it does not take into account other important factors that may influence the spread of digital technologies and streaming services. Variables such as digital literacy, internet connection levels, mobile connectivity, education levels of the population or affordability of services could provide a more comprehensive view of the conditions that support (or hinder) the development of the digital music industry.

Thirdly, the data source used – the Statista database – although widely considered reliable, may provide aggregated or normalized data that does not capture regional or demographic differences. Country-level averages may mask significant differences between urban and rural areas or between different socio-economic groups.

Finally, the study focuses exclusively on European Union countries, which may limit the applicability of the findings to other regions of the world with different levels of digital infrastructure, regulatory frameworks or cultural habits in the field of music consumption. Comparative studies that would also include countries outside the EU could provide a broader global view of the digital inequality in the music industry.

By calculating these limitations, we aim to support further research that could expand and deepen our findings through more comprehensive data and more diverse methodological approaches.

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MODERN DATA ARCHITECTURES: EVALUATION AND SELECTION CRITERIA FOR DATA-DRIVEN ENTERPRISES

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Data architecture; data warehouse; data lake; data lakehouse; enterprise architecture; evaluation matrix

Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive evaluation of modern data architectures including Data Warehouse (DWH), Data Lake (DL), and Data Lakehouse (DLH) with a focus on their applicability in data-driven enterprises. The study identifies a robust set of criteria derived from both literature and practice to guide architecture selection. Using a weighted scoring methodology, each architecture is assessed based on its technical, organizational, and economic fit. The results indicate that DLH offers the best trade-off between scalability, flexibility, and support for advanced analytics, while traditional DWH solutions still excel in ease of use and implementation simplicity. The findings provide practical guidance for organizations navigating digital transformation and aiming to align data infrastructure with strategic goals

1. Introduction

The proliferation of digital technologies, the advent of the Internet of Things (IoT), and the widespread adoption of cloud computing have collectively transformed how organizations manage, process, and utilize data. As businesses evolve toward data-driven decision-making paradigms, the volume, variety, and velocity of data have grown exponentially. This surge in complexity and demand has catalysed a paradigm shift in data architectures, giving rise to modern solutions that go beyond the capabilities of traditional relational data warehouses. (EUROPEAN COMMISSION, 2020; Zachman, 1987)

Conventional Data Warehouses (DWH) have been a mainstay of enterprise data analytics for decades. They provide structured, reliable, and validated data optimized for reporting and business intelligence (BI). However, their rigidity, high costs, and lack of support for unstructured data and real-time analytics render them less effective in today's fast-paced data environments. To address these limitations, modern data architectures such as Data Lakes (DL) and Data Lakehouses (DLH) have emerged (Brackett, 1994; Harby & Zulkernine, 2025; Serra, 2024).

The primary motivation behind this study is to provide a structured, evidence-based methodology for evaluating and selecting an appropriate data architecture that aligns with an organization's strategic goals, data maturity level, and technological capabilities. Through an in-depth analysis of three major architectural paradigms - DWH, DL, and DLH, this paper aims to identify a robust evaluation framework that can guide decision-makers in selecting the most suitable architecture for their specific context (Rashed, & Drews, 2021; Sebastian-Coleman, 2018).

This research is guided by the following questions:

- RQ1: Is it possible to define a set of appropriate criteria for selecting a modern data architecture?
- RQ2: Can these criteria be parameterized and weighted to support context-sensitive evaluation?

To answer these questions, this study develops an extensive list of evaluation criteria derived from both academic literature and professional experience. These criteria are then applied in a real-world evaluation scenario, where three architectural models are assessed based on their ability to meet organizational needs. The results not only highlight the relative strengths and weaknesses of each architecture but also validate the utility of the proposed evaluation framework.

2. Methodology

This research follows a Design Science Research (DSR) methodology (Hevner et al., 2004), suitable for solving complex real-world problems by designing and evaluating purposeful artefacts. In our context, the artefact is an evaluation framework that enables enterprise decision-makers to compare modern data architectures in a structured, context-aware manner.

To address the research objectives and provide an actionable guide for architectural decision-making, a comprehensive evaluation methodology was developed. This methodology consists of three main components:

- identification of evaluation domains and criteria,
- definition of a weighted scoring model, and
- implementation of a comparative evaluation using real-world architectural alternatives

2.1 Development of Evaluation Criteria

The first step was the derivation of a structured set of evaluation criteria grounded in academic literature, best practices, and practitioner insights. These criteria span seven distinct domains that reflect both technical and organizational factors essential to data architecture success:

- Business Needs and Goals
- Architecture and Technology
- Costs
- User Experience and Tools
- Solution Requirements

- Data Culture and Governance
- Data Management and Governance

Each domain contains multiple questions or criteria. For example, the “Business Needs and Goals” domain includes criteria such as the rationale for adopting a data solution, types of data processed, and the need for real-time processing. Similarly, the “Architecture and Technology” domain addresses cloud readiness, integration with legacy systems, data formats, latency, scalability, and optimization for analytics.

2.2 Weighted Scoring Model

Each criterion was assigned a weight representing its relative importance. These weights were determined based on stakeholder interviews, organizational priorities, and domain knowledge. Weights range from 20 to 100, with higher values indicating critical importance. The weights are then normalized to create a scoring vector used in the final evaluation. (Kopa, 2025)

Each data architecture (DWH, DL, DLH) is scored on a 0–100 scale for each criterion, where 0 indicates complete non-fulfilment and 100 indicates full compliance with the requirement. The final score for each architecture is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Final Score} = \sum (\text{Normalized Weight} \times \text{Fulfillment Score})$$

2.3 Practical Case Study Implementation

To validate the methodology, a case study was conducted using data from a mid-sized European organization in the healthcare distribution sector. The organization sought to modernize its legacy on-premises data warehouse to support new initiatives such as AI-driven analytics, real-time monitoring, and integration of semi-structured data from various business systems.

The criteria were tailored to reflect the organization’s context, including strong preference for Microsoft Azure technologies, need for compatibility with Microsoft SQL Server, and support for Power BI. The scoring was done by data architects and data governance leads, ensuring a balanced perspective from both technical and business domains.

Three architectures were evaluated:

- DWH: Traditional relational Data Warehouse on Microsoft SQL Server
- DL: Azure-native Data Lake with ELT capabilities
- DLH: Azure Databricks-based Lakehouse with Delta Lake support

The following section presents the scoring results across all 25 criteria and discusses the implications for architectural decision-making.

2.4 Case Study Description

The evaluation methodology was applied in a real-world enterprise context with a focus on modernizing data infrastructure to meet growing demands for advanced analytics, real-time integration, and data governance. The organization—anonimized for confidentiality—operates across multiple business units with legacy systems and emerging cloud platforms.

Initial challenges included:

- Limited support for semi-structured/unstructured data,

- Disparate reporting environments across regions,
- Lack of centralized metadata or data catalogue,
- Demand from business units for machine learning capabilities.

A cross-functional team consisting of enterprise architects, BI leads, data governance managers, and IT infrastructure experts conducted the assessment. Each participant contributed to defining expectations per criterion, rating architecture fulfilment levels, and calibrating weights to reflect their specific domain priorities.

The evaluation simulated three real-world architectural choices:

- migration to a modern DWH using cloud SQL engines,
- deployment of a native Data Lake on cloud object storage, and
- implementation of a Data Lakehouse via Azure Databricks with Delta Lake for governance and transactional control.

Participants independently scored all 25 questions per architecture using a shared evaluation sheet. Final scores were aggregated by applying the normalized weights, producing a comparable index that informed strategic discussions with C-level stakeholders. The approach ensured transparency, reproducibility, and alignment between technical capabilities and business expectations.

3. Results

The evaluation produced a ranked comparison of the three candidate architectures across 25 criteria. Each architecture received a fulfilment score for every criterion, which was multiplied by the criterion's normalized weight to produce a weighted score. The total score was computed by summing the weighted scores across all criteria.

3.1 Summary of Architecture Scores

The DLH architecture consistently outperformed the alternatives, especially in criteria related to data variety, analytics optimization, scalability, and cloud-native deployment. Although DWH performed well in terms of integration with legacy systems, ease of use, and cost, its limitations in handling unstructured data and advanced analytics significantly lowered its overall score. DL, while flexible and cost-efficient, struggled in areas such as metadata management and transactional support.

- Data Warehouse (DWH) – Total Score: 76
- Data Lake (DL) – Total Score: 69
- **Data Lakehouse (DLH) – Total Score: 84**

3.2 Evaluation by Domain

The following text describes pros and cons in each of the seven domains defined above. Business Needs and Goals domain showed that the highest result was achieved by DLH. DLH scored highest due to its ability to support structured and unstructured data, machine learning, and real-time processing. DWH performed moderately; DL showed potential but lacked full coverage of use cases.

In the Architecture and Technology, the DLH supports both batch and streaming data, strong Azure-native integration, and flexible schema-on-read/write, emerged as the leader. DL followed closely in scalability, but its lack of ACID properties was a limitation.

Costs of DWH were rated most favourably in terms of predictable licensing and infrastructure costs. DL and DLH were associated with higher operational complexity and potential long-term cloud expenses.

In User Experience and Tools, the DWH excelled due to its maturity and user familiarity with SQL and BI tools like Power BI. DLH offered a good compromise with both SQL and notebook interfaces. DL required more technical skills.

Solution Requirements were supported mainly by DLH, because DLH support complex analytics, model development, and a variety of integration patterns. DWH was best suited for reporting-heavy environments. DL was optimal for raw data exploration but limited in reuse.

In Data Culture and Governance, the DLH allowed better enforcement of data stewardship through metadata layers and governance integration. DWH was strong in accountability but weak in flexibility. DL often suffered from governance gaps.

3.3 Detailed Evaluation by Criterion

To illustrate the granularity of the evaluation, five selected criteria are analysed in detail below.

Criterion 1: Why do you need a data solution?

The business expected the new architecture to unlock data from siloed legacy systems and enable predictive analytics. DLH received the highest score (90) due to its support for structured/unstructured data and analytics. DL (50) supported data ingestion well but lacked transactional consistency. DWH (30) was limited to structured, batch workloads.

Criterion 4: Processing speed

Real-time or near real-time data ingestion and dashboarding were key objectives. DWH scored highest (100) because of mature optimization and indexing, albeit only for structured data. DLH followed (80), offering streaming integration. DL (60) lacked robust scheduling and low-latency performance.

Criterion 12: Optimization for analysis

Support for AI/ML model training, feature store integration, and compatibility with notebooks or SQL engines was essential. DLH (100) offered deep integration with Spark and Delta Live Tables. DL (80) had strong raw data support but lacked orchestration. DWH (50) was best suited for descriptive analytics only.

Criterion 20: Design model of the data solution

The company favoured Data Vault 2.0 due to its traceability and flexibility. DLH (80) accommodated it via Lakehouse modelling layers. DWH (100) traditionally supports Data Vault well. DL (0) lacked schema enforcement and historical traceability.

Criterion 25: Metadata and data cataloguing

Governance maturity was a key requirement. DLH (0) and DL (0) both suffered due to inadequate built-in cataloguing, although these could be extended via external tools. DWH (70) benefited from long-standing integration with SQL-based metadata repositories and business glossaries.

This fine-grained analysis was repeated across all 25 criteria, producing a nuanced comparison of each architecture's fitness for enterprise deployment.

3.5 Summary and Recommendations

The analysis showed that although DLH scored highest in absolute terms, its success heavily depends on organizational readiness, talent, and change management. In organizations where strong data governance and engineering capacity exist, DLH can unlock major benefits. For environments with a focus on reporting, minimal change tolerance, and fewer analytics ambitions, DWH remains a pragmatic and cost-effective choice.

Based on the evaluation, DLH is recommended where:

- A hybrid mix of structured and unstructured data exists,
- Real-time insights and AI/ML models are prioritized,
- Cloud-native platforms are in place.

DWH is recommended where:

- Data is highly structured and heavily regulated,
- BI workloads dominate and SQL skills are widespread,
- The organization prefers a more conservative, phased modernization.

DL is recommended only as a component or transitional layer in most enterprises, unless enhanced with additional governance and metadata capabilities.

4. Discussion

The findings from the evaluation suggest a clear strategic preference for Data Lakehouse (DLH) architectures in organizations aiming for advanced analytics, operational agility, and long-term scalability. However, the optimal data architecture is highly dependent on organizational context, including data maturity, strategic goals, technical skills, and budget constraints.

DLH architectures offer a unified platform for structured and unstructured data, supporting a wide range of analytical workloads including reporting, self-service BI, and AI/ML model training. The integrated metadata layer and support for transactional consistency make DLH suitable for both operational and analytical use cases. For enterprises undergoing digital transformation, DLH provides a future-proof architecture that minimizes the need for siloed data systems.

Nonetheless, DLH introduces complexity in platform setup, requires skilled personnel, and often involves higher cloud operating costs. Successful implementation demands cross-functional alignment, robust data governance, and investment in training and change management.

Traditional DWH architectures still have strong value propositions in certain contexts. They are ideal for:

- Organizations with predominantly structured data,
- Regulatory reporting environments where data consistency and lineage are critical,
- Teams with limited data science capabilities,
- Businesses seeking quick implementation and low-risk deployment.

For example, many SMEs and government agencies may prefer DWHs due to their maturity, ease of integration with existing tools, and predictable performance.

While DLs alone were the weakest option in this study, they retain value as cost-efficient raw data repositories. They are suitable for:

- Use cases involving exploratory analysis,
- Staging zones for large-volume ingestion from diverse sources,
- Integration with machine learning pipelines where pre-processing happens downstream.

However, their lack of transaction control and metadata governance pose long-term sustainability challenges, often resulting in the “data swamp” phenomenon if not properly managed.

A critical insight from the study is the central role of organizational readiness in architecture success. Even the best technological choice can fail without:

- Executive sponsorship,
- Cross-departmental collaboration,
- Skilled workforce,
- Clear data ownership and governance processes.

Hence, architecture selection must go hand in hand with organizational assessment and capacity building initiatives.

The proposed methodology is adaptable to changing needs. Future iterations may include additional architectures such as:

- Modern DWHs combining cloud-native features with structured data governance,
- Data Fabric architectures that abstract physical storage for seamless access,

Additional research should explore the operationalization of such models and integrate performance benchmarks, environmental impact, and user satisfaction metrics.

5. Conclusion

This study presents a structured methodology for evaluating modern data architectures through a multi-criteria decision-making approach. By integrating academic theory with practical evaluation techniques, the proposed framework enables organizations to select data architectures that align with their strategic, technical, and operational needs.

The research confirms the following:

- A comprehensive set of evaluation criteria can be defined (RQ1),
- These criteria can be weighted and adapted to different organizational contexts (RQ2).

Among the three architectures evaluated, Data Lakehouse (DLH) emerged as the most suitable for modern data-driven enterprises, offering a balanced mix of flexibility, scalability, and robustness. However, Data Warehouses (DWH) remain a relevant option for structured and regulatory-focused use cases, while Data Lakes (DL) serve well as raw storage repositories and staging zones.

The proposed methodology is not only applicable in IT or data departments but also serves strategic planning functions, facilitating alignment between business goals and data infrastructure. It empowers Chief Data Officers (CDOs), enterprise architects, and data governance leaders to make informed, transparent, and defensible decisions in selecting data architectures.

Future work can build upon this research by:

- Expanding the framework to include newer paradigms such as Data Mesh and Data Fabric,
- Validating the model across diverse industry sectors,
- Integrating qualitative indicators such as user satisfaction and data literacy.

Ultimately, the alignment of data architecture with organizational ambition is a critical success factor in achieving digital maturity and unlocking the full potential of enterprise data.

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AI-ASSISTED DATA GOVERNANCE: FROM THEORY TO TOOLS

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly shaping data-intensive domains by automating, optimizing, and augmenting data governance processes. This paper investigates current AI-supported use cases in data governance, structured around the DAMA-DMBOK framework. A dual-method approach was employed: a structured literature review and an analysis of leading commercial platforms (Informatica, IBM, Collibra). The literature review highlights AI applications across sectors such as healthcare, finance, energy, and smart cities, particularly in metadata management, data quality, and compliance monitoring. The platform analysis reveals convergence between academic insights and market offerings, with AI functionalities such as metadata discovery, rule generation, and automated policy enforcement. The DAMA-DMBOK-based synthesis identifies areas with strong AI integration, while also pointing to underexplored domains. The study provides a comprehensive view of how AI contributes to modern data governance and outlines opportunities for further research and tool development.

1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has grown rapidly in recent years, becoming an integral part of everyday activities to improve efficiency and productivity (Noy and Zhang, 2023). Individuals use AI for diverse tasks, while organizations form dedicated units to leverage its potential—from automating internal operations to deploying chatbots for enhanced client experiences (Bhima et al., 2023; Ezenkwu, 2023).

AI adoption closely intersects with data governance, as AI systems depend on accurate and well-organized data. Effective data governance is a critical success factor for successful AI implementation, as AI models rely heavily on trustworthy and well-organized data (Anderson, 2025). Ensuring high data quality across varied sources remains a challenge, making robust governance practices essential. Properly governed data not only boosts AI performance but also supports regulatory compliance and informed decision-making (Data Meaning, 2024; Janssen et al., 2020).

On the other hand, AI represents a significant opportunity to streamline, simplify, and automate data governance processes. Despite the importance of data governance, a large number of these activities continue to fail, and the number may even increase in the future (Gartner, 2024).

Data governance processes are often viewed as complicated and complex within organizations. Many people do not fully understand these processes and consider them a burden rather than a helpful practice. Employees often perceive data management as an extra burden that is not directly related to their main job. If the value of these activities is not clearly communicated or motivation is lacking, employees tend to bypass or ignore them (Chukwurah et al., 2024). Realizing the full potential of AI in data governance necessitates a thorough understanding of the business context, IT systems, and AI capabilities within an organization (Bhima et al., 2023).

The objective of this paper is to investigate the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in Data Governance and to provide an overview of current AI-supported use cases.

Although AI is widely discussed in data-related disciplines, there is a lack of structured insight into how it supports concrete governance tasks. To provide an analytical lens, the paper applies the DAMA-DMBOK framework, a comprehensive standard for data governance and management developed by DAMA International (Earley and Henderson, 2017), and considers examples from multiple industry. This initial mapping is intended to support further research and to help clarify the current state of AI adoption in data governance across both academic and practical contexts.

This study focuses exclusively on the role of AI as a supporting technology within data governance—not on the importance of data for AI systems.

2. Methodology

This study applies a dual-method approach combining a structured literature review with an analysis of leading commercial data governance platforms. Findings are synthesized using the DAMA-DMBOK framework to contextualize the role of AI across key data management areas.

2.1 Literature Review

The first phase consists of a structured review of scientific literature focused on the intersection of AI and data governance or data management. The objective was to capture the current state of academic discourse and identify dominant themes, use cases, and trends in the field.

Searches were conducted in Q4 2024 using Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, and the Consensus AI plugin (ChatGPT, version Nov 2024), using combined keywords: “data governance,” “data management,” “artificial intelligence,” and “AI”.

Table 1. Literature Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explicit focus on AI applications in data governance or data management • Relevance demonstrated in title, abstract, or full text • Theoretical or contextual value, even if not primarily AI-focused • Publication period: 2023–2024, ensuring currency and alignment with recent developments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unrelated to data governance or management • Focused solely on general AI technologies without applicable context • Duplicates, non-English sources, or inaccessible due to licensing • Lacking practical relevance to the research questions

A total of 73 publications were identified across Scopus (42), Web of Science (14), IEEE Xplore (11), and the Consensus AI plugin (6). After excluding items due to language, thematic irrelevance, or limited access, 52 remained. Of these, 34 were selected for full-text analysis based on their relevance to AI in data governance and assessed for their contributions to specific use cases and themes.

For each reviewed publication, three aspects were identified: the industry domain, the relevant DAMA-DMBOK area, and the specific role of AI within the described use case.

2.2 Analysis of Data Governance Platforms

The second component of the methodology involved a targeted review of commercial data governance tools, with the aim of mapping actual AI integration in current market offerings. A shortlist of platforms was compiled based on their appearance in the Gartner Magic Quadrant for Data and Analytics Governance Platforms (September 2024 edition). The focus was limited to vendors positioned as Leaders, specifically Informatica, IBM, Collibra.

For each platform, publicly available documentation, product descriptions, white papers, and vendor websites were reviewed. Particular attention was paid to AI-related terminology and features, such as metadata automation, anomaly detection, and policy recommendation. However, as the analysis is based exclusively on vendor-provided materials, it reflects stated capabilities and may not fully represent real-world implementation or user experience.

2.3 Integration into the DAMA Framework

To synthesize the findings, insights from both the literature and platform analysis were mapped onto the DAMA-DMBOK framework.

Figure 1. DAMA Wheel

Source: (Earley and Henderson, 2017)

As shown in Figure 1, the DAMA-DMBOK framework—often visualized as the DAMA Wheel—offers a structured approach to data management by defining key knowledge areas, including Data Quality, Metadata Management, Data Governance, and others. Each domain in the framework is described through core components such as typical *inputs*, associated *activities*, and expected *deliverables* (Earley and Henderson, 2017). These components provide a basis for assessing the functional alignment of AI applications with the objectives of each area.

AI use cases and platform functionalities were manually mapped to relevant DAMA areas by comparing their functions with the framework’s definitions of activities and deliverables. Assignments were based on thematic fit, and a single source could be linked to multiple areas.

3. Results

The following section presents the outcomes of the two-part methodological approach. The first part summarizes AI-related use cases from the literature, the second examines commercial platforms, and the third synthesizes the findings using the DAMA-DMBOK framework.

3.1 Literature Review Results

The analysis of 34 scientific publications revealed how AI is applied across various sectors in the context of data governance and management, often extending into adjacent areas. These include healthcare (Akdemir, 2024; Gupta & Kumar, 2023; Lu et al., 2024; Ogur et al., 2023; Setiawan et al., 2024; Urban et al., 2023), energy (Shin et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2023), transportation (Kuftinova et al., 2024), academia (Paul, 2024), finance (Ionescu & Diaconita, 2023; Yandrapalli, 2024), and meteorology (Hachimi et al., 2023).

In healthcare, AI supports image analysis (Urban et al., 2023) aligning with Metadata Management and Data Quality; predictive analytics for chronic disease management (Ogur et al., 2023) and omics-driven personalization, which involves tailoring treatments based on genomic, proteomic, or metabolomic data (Gupta & Kumar, 2023) relate to Data Warehousing & Business Intelligence. Akdemir (2024) uses AI to optimize the processing of medical data, addressing Data Storage & Operations, and Setiawan et al. (2024) focus on metadata organization and governance in electronic health records, supporting Metadata Management, Data Governance, and Document & Content Management.

In energy, AI is used for load optimization, demand prediction, and distribution control (Zhou et al., 2023), under Data Storage & Operations and Data Integration & Interoperability. Predictive maintenance (Karras et al., 2024), supported by TinyML algorithms that monitor equipment health at the edge and reduce noise or gaps in sensor data, contributes to Data Quality. Smart grid operations (Hasan et al., 2023) relate to Data Storage and Operations.

In finance, AI is applied in fraud detection, risk modeling, and advisory services (Ionescu & Diaconita, 2023), linked to Data Governance and Business Intelligence. Yandrapalli (2024) presents a framework enhancing fraud detection through improved Data Quality.

Hachimi et al. (2023) introduce AI-based weather data cleansing and forecasting for agriculture, falling under Data Quality.

In academia, AI supports personalized learning and task automation (Paul, 2024), relevant to Document & Content Management and Metadata Management.

Across Internet of Things (IoT) and Smart Cities, AI assists in real-time data handling via edge processing and anomaly detection (Hasan et al., 2023; Karras et al., 2024; Shin et al., 2024), supporting Data Quality, Data Integration & Interoperability, and Operations. Applications include intelligent transport (Kuftinova et al., 2024), smart buildings, waste management (Hasan et al., 2023; Shin et al., 2024), and remote monitoring (Jankovic & Curovic, 2023; Lu et al., 2024), spanning Data Governance, Data Quality, and Metadata Management.

Further Khan & Walia (2024) demonstrate improvements in cloud data environments via AI-driven classification and security, linked to Data Architecture.

3.2 Analysis of Data Governance Platforms

In today's data-driven environment, Data Governance Platforms help organizations ensure the quality, compliance, and responsible use of data across systems. Informatica, IBM, and Collibra—identified as leaders by Gartner (De Simoni et al., 2025)—offer AI-enhanced data governance platforms that automate core governance processes and support regulatory compliance.

Informatica's CLAIRE® engine powers the Intelligent Data Management Cloud, enabling automation of data integration, quality checks, and workflows (Informatica, 2023). IBM's Cloud Pak for Data and watsonx extend AI capabilities across hybrid environments, focusing on automated classification, quality monitoring, and model governance (De Simoni et al., 2025). Collibra provides AI Governance features that catalog and evaluate AI use cases to ensure compliance and alignment (Collibra, 2025a).

All platforms heavily support Metadata Management, Data Integration & Interoperability, and Data Lineage through automated metadata discovery, ontology mapping, and enrichment. CLAIRE scans data sources, builds knowledge graphs, and infers asset relationships (Informatica, 2023); IBM applies similar techniques (IBM, 2025a); and Collibra generates asset descriptions and similarity suggestions using natural language (Collibra, 2025b).

AI also strengthens Data Quality, Profiling, and Observability. Informatica uses NLP to create quality rules and perform anomaly detection (Informatica, 2023). Collibra's SQL Assistant helps define and troubleshoot rules (Collibra, 2025c), and IBM automates profiling and quality scoring (IBM, 2025b).

Data Storage & Operations and Data Integration & Interoperability are further enhanced by AI-driven workflow orchestration in IBM's Watson Pipelines, which streamline hybrid and multicloud environments (IBM, 2024).

For Data Privacy, 100 and Compliance Management, all platforms offer prebuilt classifiers and enforce masking and access policies. Informatica includes over 225 classifiers (Informatica, 2023), while IBM's workflows automate sensitive data handling (IBM, 2025c).

IBM also advances Data Governance through model lifecycle management—its watsonx platform monitors transparency and compliance across AI environments, including third-party models like OpenAI and SageMaker (IBM, 2025c), extending governance toward AI Lifecycle Management and Responsible AI.

Finally, to support Document & Content Management and Metadata Management, Collibra integrates recommendation systems and semantic tools for enhancing data literacy via natural language asset descriptions (Collibra, 2025c).

3.3 Synthesis of Findings by DAMA-DMBOK

Identified use cases from the literature and platform analysis were manually mapped to specific DAMA-DMBOK knowledge areas. Table 2 summarizes the results of this synthesis. For each DAMA Wheel Area, it shows the types of AI applications identified, the related industry sectors, representative literature sources, and commercial data governance platforms supporting the given functionality.

Table 2. DAMA Wheel Overview

DAMA Wheel Area	Application of AI	Industry Domain	Literature References	DG Platf. Support for AI Features
Data Governance	Automated policy enforcement, compliance monitoring, value-based governance	Finance, Smart Cities, Healthcare	Ionescu & Diaconita, 2023; Kuftinova et al., 2024; Hasan et al., 2023; Setiawan et al., 2024;	Collibra, IBM, Informatica
Data Architecture	AI for data classification, replication, and anomaly detection in cloud environments	Cloud Storage	Khan, M.A., Walia, R., 2024	
Data Modeling & Design				
Data Storage & Operations	Scalable storage and real-time data pipelines	Energy, IoT, Smart Cities	Hasan et al., 2023; Karras et al., 2024; Shin et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2023;	IBM
Data security				Collibra, IBM, Informatica
Data Integration & Interoperability	Multi-source integration, smart grid data fusion, metadata enrichment	Energy, Healthcare, Smart Cities	Lu et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2023; Jankovic & Curovic, 2023	Collibra, IBM, Informatica
Document & Content Management	AI-enabled digital content structuring and automation	Academia, Healthcare	Paul, 2024; Setiawan et al., 2024	
Reference & Master Data				
Data Warehousing & Business Intelligence	AI-driven decision support and predictive analytics	Agriculture, Healthcare, Finance	Gupta & Kumar, 2023; Ogur et al., 2023; Ionescu & Diaconita, 2023	
Metadata Management	Metadata tagging, auto-classification, semantic enrichment, asset recommendations	Academia, Healthcare, Smart Cities	Gupta & Kumar, 2023; Jankovic & Curovic, 2023; Lu et al., 2024; Setiawan et al., 2024; Urban et al., 2023	Collibra, IBM, Informatica
Data Quality	Cleansing, anomaly detection, TinyML-based edge processing, NLP for rule creation	Agriculture, IoT & Smart Cities	Hachimi et al., 2023; Hasan et al., 2023; Karras et al., 2024; Shin et al., 2024; Urban et al., 2023; Yandrapalli, 2024	Collibra, IBM, Informatica

Source: (author)

4. Discussion & Conclusion

This study set out to investigate how AI is currently being implemented to support data governance processes. By synthesizing academic literature and commercial platform features within the DAMA-DMBOK framework, several key insights emerged.

The literature review revealed diverse use cases, most frequently in the healthcare sector. AI is most commonly applied in areas such as Data Quality, Metadata Management, Data Warehousing, and Data Storage & Operations—areas that typically involve large volumes of data. In these contexts, AI helps automate quality control, optimize operations, and structure metadata. Most reported approaches rely on classical machine learning methods, while references to generative AI remain limited.

Commercial platforms already embed AI extensively, offering features like metadata discovery, anomaly detection, and automated policy enforcement. Early GenAI functionalities are beginning to appear, particularly in semantic enrichment, ontology mapping, and natural language-based search. Some DAMA areas remain underrepresented—likely due to platform specialization rather than technical limitations.

Taken together, the findings suggest that AI holds considerable promise as an enabler of modern data governance, especially as data ecosystems continue to expand. The uneven coverage across DAMA areas reflects both the maturity of AI technologies and the strategic priorities of tool development.

There are several limitations to this study. The platform analysis is based solely on publicly available vendor materials, limiting insight into real-world use. Practitioner perspectives—such as pain points or AI support needs—are also missing. The study focuses more on AI's potential than on aspects like explainability, trust, and risk. These gaps highlight future research needs toward a comprehensive AI governance framework.

One emerging trend worth mentioning in the context of future research is the rise of autonomous AI agents—systems capable of independently performing complex tasks, with potential applications in data governance. Their promise lies in automating workflows and decision-making, but they also raise important questions about control, reliability, and responsible use.

In conclusion, this study highlights the growing role of AI in data governance, with strong use in areas like Data Quality and Metadata Management. While GenAI is emerging, many domains remain underexplored. Further research should address practitioner needs and support the development of structured frameworks for AI adoption.

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ECOSPELL: AN ECO-FRIENDLY PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE FRAMEWORK FOR THE INDUSTRIAL INTERNET OF THINGS (IIOT)

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Abstract

EcoSpell is an innovative predictive maintenance (PdM) framework designed by the authors for the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), focusing on sustainability. The main objective of EcoSpell is to enhance the longevity of industrial equipment while reducing energy consumption and minimizing environmental impact. This paper introduces EcoSpell as a comprehensive solution that integrates real-time data acquisition, anomaly detection, and a decision engine powered by machine learning (ML) models. A simulation using real industrial vibration data evaluates the framework's ability to improve equipment reliability, energy efficiency, and sustainability. Key performance indicators (KPIs) such as Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF), energy savings, and false positive rates are analyzed to assess the framework's effectiveness. The results highlight EcoSpell's potential for integration into smart manufacturing environments, offering a green solution to traditional predictive maintenance strategies while improving operational outcomes and supporting eco-friendly manufacturing practices.

1. Introduction

Predictive maintenance (PdM) is a cornerstone of modern industrial operations, enabling companies to reduce downtime, minimize repair costs, and improve operational efficiency through real-time monitoring and predictive modeling (Bengio et al., 2022). While existing PdM solutions—often based on random forests, support vector machines, or deep learning—achieve high accuracy in fault detection (Choudhary et al., 2024), they primarily focus on reliability and cost reduction, overlooking key sustainability factors such as energy consumption and material waste (Choi et al., 2023).

Many available PdM frameworks lack comprehensive integration of environmental metrics and fail to address challenges like adaptation to new industrial settings with limited historical data (the “cold start” problem). Moreover, most do not balance operational priorities with ecological impact, an increasingly important consideration for sustainable industry practices.

To fill these gaps, we developed **EcoSpell**, a novel PdM framework that uniquely incorporates sustainability objectives directly into its maintenance decision-making. Unlike conventional models, EcoSpell balances operational urgency with energy efficiency and material sustainability, enabling maintenance actions that optimize both equipment reliability and environmental impact. Its hybrid learning approach improves adaptability across diverse industrial contexts where historical failure data may be scarce.

This paper presents EcoSpell’s design and evaluation, demonstrating its advantages over existing PdM systems by delivering high fault detection accuracy while significantly reducing energy consumption and material waste.

2. State of the Art

Predictive maintenance (PdM) is a core component of Industry 4.0, driven by the integration of Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), machine learning (ML), and big data analytics. Traditional maintenance strategies were either time-based or reactive, often leading to unnecessary downtime and high costs. PdM shifts this approach by predicting equipment failures before they occur, improving efficiency and reducing operational disruptions (Bengio et al., 2022).

2.1 Predictive Maintenance and Machine Learning

Predictive maintenance (PdM) relies on real-time sensor data and machine learning algorithms, such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, to predict equipment failures. LSTM models are particularly effective at analyzing time-series data from IIoT sensors by identifying patterns that often precede breakdowns (Yan et al., 2022). Other commonly used algorithms include Random Forest and Support Vector Machines (SVM), which have proven useful for fault detection (Choudhary et al., 2024).

However, these models face significant challenges when applied to new sensors, machines, or industrial systems that lack sufficient historical failure data. Without enough examples of past failures, machine learning models struggle to detect faults early, as there is limited prior information to learn from. This “cold start” problem calls for further research into adaptive and transfer learning methods that can enable effective PdM even with sparse data.

Regarding energy consumption, PdM can help reduce energy usage by detecting faults that cause inefficiencies—such as increased friction in motors due to bearing wear. However, this relationship does not hold universally across all types of equipment. Moreover, the continuous collection of large volumes of sensor data and the computational effort required by machine learning algorithms add to the overall energy demand. Therefore, the net energy savings achieved through PdM must be carefully weighed against the energy costs of data acquisition and processing. Designing energy-efficient PdM frameworks remains a key challenge in balancing operational benefits with sustainability goals.

2.2 Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) in PdM

IIoT enables the continuous monitoring of machines by collecting real-time data via sensors. This data, analyzed through ML models, can predict potential failures and optimize maintenance schedules. IIoT’s integration with edge and cloud computing further enhances predictive maintenance by processing data locally and in the cloud, offering scalable solutions (Bashiri et al., 2024). Despite these advancements, challenges in standardizing and integrating diverse data types remain, limiting the effectiveness of PdM across different industrial sectors (Zhang et al., 2024).

2.3 Sustainability Considerations

Predictive maintenance not only improves operational efficiency but also supports sustainability goals. By predicting failures and avoiding unnecessary maintenance, PdM can extend equipment life and reduce waste and energy consumption (Tiwari et al., 2023). Incorporating energy usage and environmental factors into PdM models, however, remains an underexplored area, leaving room for research to align operational efficiency with sustainability (Gao et al., 2021).

2.4 Integration with Other Industry 4.0 Technologies

PdM is increasingly integrated with technologies like digital twins and autonomous robotics. Digital twins allow real-time simulations of equipment performance, enhancing predictive accuracy (Jardine et al., 2022). Additionally, autonomous robots can automate routine maintenance tasks, reducing the need for human intervention and improving operational efficiency (Yan et al., 2023). However, achieving seamless integration of these technologies with existing PdM systems poses technical challenges.

2.5 Research Gaps and Challenges

Despite advances in PdM, several challenges remain. These include the integration of data from various sensors and systems, standardization of data formats, and the lack of labeled failure data in real-world settings. Solutions like semi-supervised learning and anomaly detection are emerging but require further development (Choudhary et al., 2024). Additionally, the integration of sustainability metrics into PdM models is limited, and more research is needed to balance operational performance with environmental impact (Tiwari et al., 2023). Lastly, scalability remains an issue, as PdM systems must be adaptable to a wide range of industrial contexts (Park et al., 2023).

3. Research Question

The central research question this paper seeks to answer is: *“How can a predictive maintenance framework, such as EcoSpell, optimize industrial operations’ reliability and energy efficiency while reducing their ecological impact?”*

4. Methodology

This study follows a Design Science Research (DSR) approach (Peppers et al., 2007), which is suitable for the development and evaluation of novel frameworks like EcoSpell. The DSR methodology includes iterative cycles of problem identification, artifact design, demonstration, and evaluation.

4.1 Problem Motivation and Framework Uniqueness

Existing predictive maintenance (PdM) frameworks often lack explicit support for sustainability aspects such as energy efficiency and material conservation. To address this gap, we designed EcoSpell specifically to incorporate these factors, rather than adapting an existing PdM framework that might not sufficiently address environmental considerations.

4.2 EcoSpell Architecture

EcoSpell is a modular and scalable framework capable of operating across various industrial settings, from manufacturing plants to energy production facilities. It incorporates five main components, working in unison to ensure efficient predictive maintenance with a sustainability focus:

1. **Data Acquisition Layer:** Real-time data is gathered from various sensors embedded on industrial machinery, including vibration, temperature, pressure, and energy consumption sensors. Energy usage data may come from dedicated power meters or smart energy monitoring devices integrated into the system. These data points are transmitted via Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) gateways to a centralized cloud platform for further processing (Zhang et al., 2024).
2. **Preprocessing Engine:** Raw sensor data is cleaned and processed using Python libraries like pandas and scikit-learn. Preprocessing tasks include filtering out noise, normalizing data values, and feature extraction, ensuring the data is ready for further analysis (Yang et al., 2023).
3. **Anomaly Detection Module:** Using the Isolation Forest algorithm for unsupervised anomaly detection and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks for time-series analysis, this module identifies abnormal machine behaviour that signals potential failures (Choudhary et al., 2024; Yan et al., 2022).
4. **Decision Engine:** The heart of EcoSpell, this hybrid engine integrates rule-based logic with machine learning models. It prioritizes maintenance tasks based on three weighted criteria:
 - **Operational Urgency (40%):** Prioritizing faults that pose significant risk to machine reliability (Li et al., 2022).
 - **Energy Impact (30%):** Considering energy usage reduction in maintenance operations (Gao et al., 2021).
 - **Material Sustainability (30%):** Minimizing unnecessary component replacements and extending material life (Tiwari et al., 2023).

These weights are currently based on expert judgment and initial domain knowledge. However, this weighting scheme would benefit from sensitivity analysis and calibration using real-world operational feedback. Future work should incorporate input from users or operators to refine these weights, improving decision accuracy, robustness, and acceptance in practical settings.

5. **Recommendation Interface:** The interface is a web-based dashboard that provides operators with prioritized maintenance recommendations. This intuitive system presents real-time updates on operational health, alerting maintenance teams to critical issues while promoting sustainability goals (Chen et al., 2023).

4.3. Demonstration and Evaluation

To validate the EcoSpell framework, we conducted a pilot deployment in a simulated industrial environment, using design science research methodology to ensure technical robustness and practical relevance. This iterative approach focused on refining system components based on expert feedback and operational testing.

5. Evaluation and Results

To evaluate EcoSpell's effectiveness, we used synthetic fault data derived from the Paderborn bearing dataset, a widely recognized resource in predictive maintenance research. The dataset includes

vibration signals recorded under various operating conditions, simulating real-world scenarios where equipment undergoes wear and tear. These conditions were carefully selected to reflect a broad range of potential operational environments, providing a robust testing ground for EcoSpell's capabilities in fault detection and predictive maintenance (Fang et al., 2024).

The anomaly detection module, which leverages Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, demonstrated impressive performance in this evaluation. The model achieved a 91% true positive rate in detecting failure precursors, meaning it successfully identified early warning signs of equipment failure in most cases. Additionally, the false positive rate was kept low at only 5%, indicating that the model could differentiate between normal and abnormal operational conditions with high accuracy. This high performance is critical in minimizing unnecessary maintenance interventions, thus preventing costly downtime and improving overall system efficiency (Chen et al., 2022).

To contextualize these results, comparable predictive maintenance models reported in recent literature typically achieve true positive rates ranging from 85% to 95%, depending on dataset complexity and fault types (Wang et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2022). Similarly, false positive rates in these studies commonly fall between 5% and 10% (Zhang et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2021). EcoSpell's performance is therefore competitive with state-of-the-art methods. However, as model performance can vary due to sensor quality and operational variability, ongoing work focuses on further reducing false positives via ensemble techniques and adaptive thresholding to enhance practical applicability.

Further testing was conducted on EcoSpell's decision engine in a simulated industrial setting, deployed for a continuous monitoring period of 12 weeks. During this period, several key operational metrics were tracked to assess the impact of EcoSpell on maintenance outcomes and resource consumption. The results were auspicious: the Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) increased by 12%, indicative of enhanced equipment reliability and longer intervals between necessary maintenance actions. Additionally, the decision engine contributed to a 9.5% reduction in energy consumption, reflecting EcoSpell's ability to optimize operational processes and reduce waste. Most notably, the system achieved a 22% reduction in unnecessary component replacements, further underscoring its effectiveness in extending the lifespan of critical components and reducing the environmental impact associated with frequent replacements (Bashiri et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2022). These results demonstrate that EcoSpell is not only efficient in enhancing operational performance but also aligns with sustainability goals by lowering resource consumption and minimizing waste.

6. Discussion

The results of this study underscore EcoSpell's capability to advance both operational reliability and sustainability in industrial environments. Unlike conventional predictive maintenance (PdM) frameworks that focus primarily on operational metrics, EcoSpell innovatively integrates energy consumption and material sustainability into maintenance decision-making processes. This holistic approach addresses the growing demand for sustainable manufacturing in Industry 4.0 (Zhang et al., 2023; Choudhary et al., 2024).

A significant strength of EcoSpell lies in its ability to balance operational urgency with ecological considerations. By incorporating sustainability criteria—such as energy use and material conservation—into maintenance prioritization, EcoSpell reduces environmental footprints while enhancing equipment longevity (Ramesh et al., 2023). This integrated strategy positions EcoSpell as a promising solution for industries aiming to transition toward more eco-friendly and resource-efficient practices.

Although the framework’s “eco-friendly” orientation is primarily assessed through energy consumption and material usage metrics, a more comprehensive sustainability assessment would benefit from considering additional environmental impact indicators such as lifecycle assessment (LCA), greenhouse gas emissions, and water footprint. Incorporating such metrics could enhance the environmental credibility and holistic understanding of the framework’s ecological impact.

Currently, the evaluation lacks a comparative benchmarking against established predictive maintenance (PdM) methods. Including such a comparative analysis would provide clearer insights into the relative advantages and added value of EcoSpell. Future research should focus on benchmarking EcoSpell’s performance alongside standard PdM approaches to quantify improvements and identify specific use-case benefits.

Although the proposed web-based interface provides a user-friendly platform for system interaction, no formal usability study or operator feedback has been collected to date. Conducting user experience evaluations and gathering operator insights represent important future steps to enhance the practical deployment and acceptance of the framework.

While EcoSpell is designed to be scalable and modular, large-scale industrial implementation poses challenges, including integration of heterogeneous data sources, handling edge versus cloud computation constraints, and adapting to sector-specific operational requirements. Addressing these issues will be critical for future deployment and represents promising directions for ongoing research.

6.1 Limitations and Future Directions

Nevertheless, this study has some limitations. The primary limitation is the reliance on synthetic fault data, which—while useful for controlled testing—may not fully capture the complexity and variability of real-world industrial environments. This could limit the model’s generalizability when deployed in diverse operational contexts. Additionally, the decision engine currently considers only a limited set of sustainability indicators (primarily energy consumption and material use). Future research should aim to validate EcoSpell with real-world datasets across diverse industries to ensure its robustness and practical utility. Expanding the decision engine to integrate broader environmental metrics—such as greenhouse gas emissions, water consumption, or waste generation—could further enhance the framework’s contribution to sustainable manufacturing (Bengio et al., 2022).

6.2 Practical and Academic Implications

From a practical standpoint, EcoSpell provides industry practitioners with a structured tool for embedding sustainability considerations into maintenance decisions—aligning with corporate sustainability goals and environmental regulations. From an academic perspective, this work advances the state of predictive maintenance research by integrating sustainability as a core component, addressing a notable gap in current literature and offering a foundation for future eco-intelligent PdM systems.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, EcoSpell represents a significant advancement in predictive maintenance for Industry 4.0. By embedding sustainability metrics directly into the predictive maintenance process, EcoSpell improves operational reliability, reduces energy consumption, minimizes material waste, and lowers the ecological footprint of industrial activities. The evaluation results confirm that EcoSpell performs comparably to state-of-the-art PdM frameworks while extending their scope to explicitly include sustainability goals.

This study is primarily evaluated using the Paderborn dataset, a well-known benchmark dataset for fault diagnosis, which serves here as a simulation environment for the proposed framework. While the use of this synthetic and simulated data allows controlled experimentation and reproducibility, it inherently limits the validation of the framework in real-world industrial settings. The absence of deployment and testing on actual industrial data restricts the practical generalizability of the findings and calls for future work to validate and adapt the framework in diverse operational environments.

To address these limitations, future research should validate the framework with real-world datasets and explore the inclusion of additional environmental indicators, such as emissions or water use, for a more holistic sustainability assessment.

Overall, this research provides substantial value for both industrial practice and academic knowledge. Practically, EcoSpell offers a powerful tool for industries seeking to enhance operational performance while meeting sustainability objectives. Academically, the framework contributes a novel, sustainability-oriented approach to predictive maintenance, laying the groundwork for further exploration and refinement in this critical area of Industry 4.0.

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AI AND AUTONOMOUS SYSTEMS

HUMAN-MACHINE TEAMING – THE WAY FORWARD TO A SUPER-SMART SOCIETY

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Smart Systems, Autonomous Systems, Resilience, Sustainability, Circular Economy, Machine Ethics, Society 5.0, Artificial Intelligence, Trustworthiness, Standardization, Collaborative Safety, Human-Machine Teaming, Collaborative Systems.

Abstract

This paper provides an overview on a new evolutionary approach to a super-smart society of the future, which may really revolutionize our society in the long term in a disruptive manner. It is a concept which assumes a constructive change of the way of cooperation between humans and “machines” as a well-defined team, in the following addressed as “Human-Machine Teaming” (HMT). This could change our attitude to AI-based systems of all kinds (“machines” are the “AI” in e.g., robotic systems, but also business, financial, healthcare, mobility or administrative systems) and of different levels of “intelligence” and autonomy, with which humans are interacting. This approach is driven primarily by Japanese experts, e.g., in AI-Standardization (ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 WG4). The long-term vision follows the Japanese official concept of “Society 5.0”. A discussion of this concept was done first in IDIMT 2019 (Schoitsch 2019). This paper outlines the “Society 5.0” concept and reports on the most recent activities and EU-Japan joint workshops on AI Ethics and Human-Machine Teaming (HMT) as an advanced implementation. This is also part of the AI-Task Force Workstream in the European INSTAR project which strives for aligning AI standardization priorities between different global regions and Europe. HMT is an advanced implementation of smart technologies and AI with strong impact on society, which are the drivers of economic and societal disruptive changes and a chance to shape our future in a beneficial way (but no chance without risk).

1. Introduction

Japan has as first large leading economy and industrialized country identified long term challenges of their society: Climate change (in an undesirable direction), economic stagnation and high inflation rates, and an ageing society. They started a large initiative initiated by science and government in a joint effort – “Society 5.0” (Schoitsch, 2019). The main targets were to fight economic stagnation in a society which for too long a time was governed by the same party and people, and at the same time fighting the consequences of an ageing society. Certain aspects of high automation, e.g., acting robots in healthcare, tagging schoolchildren by RFID devices to monitor their movements, and the like,

which are accepted in the Japanese society to an extent unacceptable in Europe under our ideas of privacy (“GDPR”) and self-determination, facilitated the first move. The idea was, that starting in Japan, the concept would be taken up globally in all developed regions. The concept is still valid, but the take-up was slower than expected. In the meantime, the technological landscape changed considerable with the rapid evolution of AI technologies and their rapid take-up world-wide. Ethical and societal concerns were raised by people and organizations engaged in individual freedom, privacy and human rights protection. In Europe the concerns raised were taken up by the Commission and the European Parliament by establishing the “AI-Act”, a legally binding regulation in force since August 2024, which at the moment only lacks the underpinning “Harmonized Standards” requested by “Standardization Requests” from the ESOs (European Standardization Organizations, CEN, CENELEC, ETSI). Many other countries, including Japan, have issued recommendations on Ethics of AI, although they are not on the level of legally binding requirements, but rather guidelines and recommendations for responsible AI (for developers, deployers, even users applying AI):

2. Society 5.0 – Towards a Super-Smart Society

There are far reaching concepts implemented around us with “Smart Systems” and AI. On the other hand, all developed countries face chronic social challenges, which add up to the challenges and risks impacted by all the “4.0” and “AI” revolutions to people and society.

The Japanese strategy “Society 5.0” envisions a so-called “Super-Smart Society”. It should create a sustainable, inclusive socio-economic system, powered by the achievements of the fourth industrial revolution and the digital technologies. It leads far beyond Industry 4.0 and aims at benefitting the whole society by utilizing the integration of cyberspace and physical space. It is fully supported by government and industry to revitalize Japan, an extremely aging society with shrinking work force (Japan Business Federation, 2016, 2017; Japanese Government, 2017, 2018).

Figure 1: Evolution of Human Society towards Society 5.0

Source: Mayumi Fukuyama (2018)

The documents on their vision say citation from (Japanese Government, 2017)

“We aim at creating a society where we can resolve various social challenges by incorporating the innovations of the fourth industrial revolution (e.g. IoT, big data, artificial intelligence (AI), robot, and the sharing economy) into every industry and social life. By doing so the society of the future will be one in which new values and services are created continuously, making people’s lives more conformable and sustainable. This is Society 5.0, a super-smart society. Japan will take the lead to realize this ahead of the rest of the world.”

The concept of “Society 5.0” was drafted in the 5th Science and Technology Basic Plan by the Council for Science, Technology and Innovation 2016.

Key issues of this plan are sustainability and social benefit for all citizen (“inclusion”) by utilizing the advanced opportunities of Digital Transformation and Smart Technologies. Social reform (innovation) will achieve a forward-looking society that breaks the existing stagnation in societal and economic stagnation, forming a society of mutual respect, transcending the generations, and an active and enjoyable life for every person. This concept should also face challenges on a global scale, like depletion of natural resources, global warming, growing economic disparity, and even terrorism, by sharing knowledge and information, and cooperation.

From a moral and ethical point of view, this sounds extremely well. The question that arises if it fits to other kinds of societies and regions in the world, having different social and economic preconditions, and different long-standing cultures and mind sets. From historical experience we know, that the most fantastic technologies and opportunities can be misused by criminals or governments. Therefore, in Europe, which is by far not so homogeneous in culture and mutual influences of neighbours as Japan and America, institutions of different type have tried to set up ethical guidelines for cognitive decision taking (AI), and governance of data and connectivity.

3. New Challenges with the Rise of AI: Human Oversight and Ethical Concerns

With the rise of Artificial Intelligence and Decision-making or Machine Learning Systems (off-line or during operation) many critical questions arose: Who can guarantee a certain performance, safe or secure system behavior, what about predictability of outcomes (a key precondition to assure safety of a system)? Are the results understandable, or the system activities explainable? Ethical aspects include the impact of automated decisions on human life – organizational, technical safety and security, human rights and human sovereignty?

Looking at the oversight issue from different stakeholders’ view, Figure 3 covers several aspects: governance (organisations), controllability by humans, safety, bias, management.

Figure 2: (Human) Oversight of AI Systems Source: (ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 WG03, TR 18966)

These standards will become basis for references of the AI Act if published in the Official journal of the EC and having undergone some review by the HAS (Harmonized Standards) consultants.

4. The European AI-Act – a European Regulation

The EC AI-Act (M/593) which is particularly regulating the human-centred, society and public interests to protect the citizens against violation of their rights and misuse of powerful AI applications. Harmonized standards are the basis for suppliers and users to prove “presumption of conformity”. The EC has sent 10 requests for standardisation to CEN/CENELEC for that purpose, which are now handled in CEN/CLC JTC 21, “Artificial Intelligence”.

„ ...setting harmonised rules for the development, placement on the market and use of AI systems in the European Union, following a proportionate risk-based approach (minimal, limited, high, unacceptable – list of prohibited AI systems). ” (Citation from M/593)

Risks considered: Health, Safety, Cybersecurity, Fundamental Rights.

The **European Commission’s AI Act** served as a foundational guide, outlining ten critical requirements for **high-risk AI systems**. These include:

1. Risk management system for AI systems [Art. 9 AI-Act]
2. Governance and quality of datasets used to build AI systems [Art. 10 Data and data governance]
3. Record keeping - built-in logging capabilities in AI systems [Art. 11 Techn. doc., Art. 12 record-keeping]
4. Transparency and information to the users of AI systems [Art. 13 Transparency and user info]
5. Human oversight of AI systems [Art. 14 Human oversight]
6. Accuracy specifications for AI systems [Art. 15 Accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity]

7. Robustness specifications for AI systems [Art. 15 Accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity]
8. Cybersecurity specifications for AI systems [Art. 15 Accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity]
9. Quality management system for providers of AI system [Art. 17 QM for providers]
10. Conformity assessment for AI systems [Art. 19 + Art. 43 Conformity Assessment]

These requirements highlight the need for harmonized standards to support compliance and ensure the safe and responsible deployment of AI technologies across Europe.

5. The INSTAR project

INSTAR is a project representing a strategic initiative to position Europe at the forefront of international ICT standardization. It is a “Coordination and Support Action” to support the European position with respect to align standardization roadmaps between Europe and selected, “like minded” regions outside Europe. INSTAR aims to influence global standard-setting in emerging advanced technologies including

- Artificial Intelligence (AI),
- Cybersecurity & Digital Identity,
- Quantum Computing,
- Internet of Things (IoT),
- 5G+, 6G, and
- Data Technologies.

and to align with international partners from Korea, Japan, Singapore, Taiwan, Australia, US and Canada. Other regions of interest are covered by other CSA projects. INSTAR's comprehensive approach involves the active participation of experienced ICT standardization experts who give input for the technology domain workstreams through six Task Forces, one for each emerging technology. These groups are crucial in developing standardization frameworks, engaging with key stakeholders, and mapping standards onto a Standards Dashboard, which serves as resource for harmonizing visions and strategies across international fora and Standard Development Organizations.

The AI-Task Force has already issued the 2nd Edition of its “AI Roadmap”, which is a list of “Priorities for international collaboration on AI standardization” and a summary of recommendations.

The resulting comparison is summarized in the following table:

Table 1: Comparison and recommendations for AI Standardization Collaboration

PRIORITY	ETF PRIORITY AREA	EU ANCHORING (STANDARDIZATION REQUEST & RP2025)	ALIGNMENT OVERVIEW ACROSS 6 PARTNERS
1	Development of EU AI-Act Compliance Standards	Core of 2023 Request (M/593) and RP2025	High alignment with South Korea, Singapore, Taiwan; partial conceptual support from US, Canada, Japan
2	Frameworks for the Ethical Use of AI	Linked to GDPR, AI Act	Supported in all six countries through ethical guidelines and soft governance principles
3	Cross-Cutting AI Standards	RP2025 & ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 topics	Widely shared interest (US, SK, JP, SG, TW); emphasis on cybersecurity, interoperability, sustainability
4	Transparency and Explainability (Subset of ethical use and compliance)	Required in AI Act Art. 13	Prominent in all regions; some offer specific rights (SK), others provide tools (SG AI Verify)
5	Data Governance and Privacy	AI Act + GDPR + RP2025	Shared value globally; implementation varies (PETs in SG/KR; reuse focus in TW; best-practices in US)
6	Sector-Specific AI Standards	RP2025 + ETSI, MPAA initiatives	Multiple partners show industrial interest (healthcare, AVs, finance); especially SG, JP, KR
7	AI Safety and Security Standards	Safety/Resilience: AI Act, CRA; RP2025	Key topic in US (NIST), JP (abuse prevention), KR (lifecycle safety), TW (defensive goals)
8	Human-AI Collaboration and Interaction Guidelines	Human Oversight (Art. 14) + RP2025	Conceptual support in JP, KR, SG; less visible in US/CA, limited operational detail elsewhere
9	Bias and Fairness in AI	Required under AI Act (Art. 10, 15)	Recognised across JP, KR, SG, CA, TW; measurement methods and obligations vary significantly
10	AI Lifecycle Management	Required by Art. 17 (QMS), RP2025	Conceptually present in KR (trust lifecycle), TW (future regulation); weak technical depth elsewhere
11	Support for SMEs and Startups	Highlighted in RP2025 and AI Act	Singapore and Korea proactive (testbeds, sandboxes); moderate in TW; minimal in US/CA
12	Sustainability and Environmental Impact of AI	Future topic in RP2025 (AI + Green Deal)	Discussed in SG (data centres); otherwise limited to general digital sustainability, no AI-specific KPIs
13	Integration with Emerging Technologies	RP2025 + IoT/Quantum standardisation	Conceptually acknowledged in all regions; detailed integration plans only in SG, KR

The analysed strategies of the international partners are in our case:

- US (NIST Scope),
- Canada (Voluntary Code Principles),
- Japan (AI Promotion Act & Guidelines),
- Republic of Korea (AI Basic Act & MSIT Strategy),
- Singapore (NAIS 2.0),
- Taiwan (AI Basic Act).

INSTAR established contacts and organized or contributed to joint workshops on AI Standardization collaboration, e.g. with Japan. The workshop on “Human Machine Teaming” Brussels on June 24 – 25th, 2025, was such a cooperative workshop between European, Japanese and Taiwan experts.

6. What’s New? Human-Machine Teaming

Because AI capabilities (“intelligence”, “autonomy”) are progressing so rapidly, it is time to think about the relationship between humans and machines. One way is to analyse systematically the possible roles of humans and machines in their cooperation in a team, a human-machine team might be a unit for governance in the future.

“Oversight” of AI was already mentioned in section 3 and in the AI-Act (Article 14, see section 4).

Human oversight: is about ensuring the quality and accountability of outputs (only unidirectional)

Human-Machine Teaming: who (machine or human) does what, when and how in the process.

Definition: ISO 22989: HMT is the „...integration of human interaction with machine intelligence capabilities“. Human-Machine Teaming considers the AI-directed „intelligent“ machine and the human as a team closely cooperating and achieving results by working together.

The humans as expert and the “machine” (which means “AI”, maybe robot, software, etc.) build a team; the human as “user” is confronted with the TEAM, which builds a logical unit.

Figure 3: Human-Machine Team – Basic Configuration and Impact Source: (ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 WG4 Working Drafts, Presentation at HMT WS in Brussels 2025-06-24_25 by Fumihiko Maruyama)

The expert plays an important role as one partner in the team. The user is distinguished. From the users point of view, this enhances trust of the user as “truster”, the Team is more trustable because of the expert being included with respect to:

- Explainability – includes human expert
- Predictability – through supporting human expert
- Endorsement of the AI-system by the human expert in the team

The distribution of work between the two partners in the team, human and machine, can be in different roles as indicated in Figure 4:

Relationship (Type)	Execution of task		Information flow	Example
	Machine (AI)	Human expert		
Human Supervisor (AI as tool)	[]	(Macro decision)	Instructions from human to machine Feedback reversely	Search engine Trip planner Automated driving (L4)
Human Mentor (AI as assistant)	[]	[]	More from human to machine	Product inspection Medical service Automated driving (L1&2)
Peer (AI as collaborator)	[]	[]	Both ways equally	Automated driving (L3) Partner robot
Machine Mentor (AI as coach)	[]	[]	More from machine to human	Game AI GitHub Copilot
Machine Supervisor (AI as manager)	(Macro decision)	[]	Instructions from machine to human Feedback reversely	Crowdsourcing

Figure 4: Relationships between Human and Machine (information flow, examples) Source: (ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 WG4 Working Drafts, Presentation at HMT WS in Brussels 2025-06-24_25 by Fumihiko Maruyama)

The standards will also include technical characteristics and implementation guidelines.

7. Human-Machine Co-Evolution - Progressing towards a Symbiotic Society

The concept of “Human-Machine Teaming” is the starting point for thinking about a future society in progressing beyond the initial Society 5.0. This is the objective of the Japanese HMCES project (Human – Machine Co-Evolution Systems), by *Yukata Matsubara (Nagoya Univ.)*, *Akihisa Morikawa (IMAGINARY Corp.)*, *Daichi Mizuguchi (Atelier Corp.)*, *Kiyoshi Fujiwara (AIST)*.

This project tries to implement the HMT concept beyond the concept phase and team-cooperation – it addresses a future society taking the path of “co-evolution” of Humans and Machines. The project has issued already a Guidebook, which will partially be also find its fingerprint in the implementation and technical guidance of the standards (HMCES 2025). This vision is depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The Symbiotic Society – a Future Beyond the original Society 5.0 Source: (HMCES project; presentation at HMT Workshop Munich, June 24-25, 2025, by Akihisa Morikawa)

This is a visionary topic – particularly the social, ethical and human psychological issues have to be discussed as done at the HMT-Workshop June 2025 at the TUM in Munich and should also create input for a good discussion at IDIMT. Here also may play an important role the different perception of human sovereignty and individual or more collectively attitude in different cultures, e.g., in Europe, US or Asia.

8. Conclusions

The paper shows some important directions towards a visionary future society, based on the society 5.0 concept from Japan, the rise of AI penetrating all functions and products we use in our life, and the risks and regulations respectively standards which should guide us and support oversight and ethical AI. Finally, derived from the new concept of “Man-Machine Teaming” (HMT) which is expected to start a new area of perception and uptake of AI-driven technology (“machines”), HMT was developed further towards Human-Machine Co-Evolution, a somehow ultimate step of

integration – but do we (the public) really want that? Besides the already known risks as they are addressed e.g., in the EU AI-Act, also human psychological factors and cultural bias may be a blocking factor and have to be discussed. However, we should be aware that many of the achievements could be used against us as well.

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CYBERSECURITY COMPETENCIES FOR THE FUTURE – INSIGHTS FROM THE PROJECT CYBERSECURITY- KOMPETENZ AUSTRIA (CSKA)

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Abstract

The increasing deployment of AI-powered and autonomous systems across critical sectors demands robust cybersecurity strategies, including a highly skilled and adaptable workforce. The CyberSec-Kompetenz Austria (CSKA) initiative addresses Austria's cybersecurity talent shortage through a comprehensive analysis of current and future workforce needs, education offerings, and regulatory trends. This paper presents an overview of CSKA's and first results: a comparative analysis of international cybersecurity skills frameworks, including ECSF (EU), NICE (USA), ACSF (Australia), and SCCF (Singapore). The analysis focuses on structural differences, granularity, and sectoral applicability, using ECSF as the baseline for developing localized competence profiles. We further explore how these profiles must evolve to address emerging challenges in AI governance, adversarial machine learning, and cyber-physical system resilience. Our findings offer insights not only for Austria but also for other nations seeking to align human capital strategies with the safe and sustainable development of autonomous technologies. The paper concludes with recommendations for profile refinement, diversity-focused workforce expansion, and international collaboration to build secure, AI-ready ecosystems.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context and Motivation

Over the past decade, societies worldwide have witnessed the emergence of increasingly autonomous and intelligent systems, from AI-powered vehicles and robotic manufacturing lines to smart city infrastructures and healthcare assistants. These innovations offer immense potential to enhance sustainability, safety, and resilience. Yet, they also introduce new layers of complexity and vulnerability—particularly in the digital domain.

As cyber threats grow more frequent and sophisticated, the protection of autonomous systems becomes not only a technological challenge but a human one. The resilience of critical infrastructures and smart technologies depends directly on the availability of skilled professionals who can anticipate, prevent, and respond to cyber incidents. This challenge is especially pressing in Austria, where the digital transformation is advancing rapidly across public services and private industry, but the supply of qualified cybersecurity talent is insufficient to meet the growing demand.

The situation is further exacerbated by the convergence of several key developments:

- The **rapid pace of technological innovation**, particularly in the fields of artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and connected devices.
- The **increased threat landscape**, as demonstrated by high-profile cyberattacks targeting Austrian universities, hospitals, and government bodies (Der Standard, 2022).
- The **evolving regulatory environment**, with the European Union introducing ambitious frameworks such as the **NIS2 Directive** and the **Cyber Resilience Act**, which demand a clear understanding and implementation of cybersecurity obligations across sectors.

Together, these developments highlight a critical gap: the need to build and maintain a **future-ready cybersecurity workforce** that is not only technically skilled, but also adaptive to the challenges posed by AI-enhanced systems and changing regulatory landscapes.

1.2 The CSKA Project in Brief

To address this gap, the project *CyberSec-Kompetenz Austria (CSKA)* (Austrian Research Promotion Agency [FFG], n.d.) was initiated as a national initiative to strategically strengthen Austria's cybersecurity capabilities. The project's overarching aim is to gain a **comprehensive understanding of both current and emerging workforce requirements** in the cybersecurity field and to identify how educational and professional development offerings can be aligned to meet these needs.

CSKA adopts a systemic perspective. It focuses not only on the skills that are missing today, but also on those that will be essential in the near future—particularly in contexts where **autonomous and AI-based systems** are deployed. The project is built around the hypothesis that workforce resilience and societal cyber resilience are deeply interconnected.

A part of the project involves the evaluation and adaptation of international cybersecurity skills frameworks, such as the **European Cybersecurity Skills Framework (ECSF)**, in order to derive competence profiles tailored to the Austrian context. While cybersecurity challenges are largely global, national differences in regulatory frameworks, public-private collaboration models, and education systems necessitate localized adaptations of international guidance.

A key principle is the **integration of diversity and inclusion** across all phases of the project—from research design to analysis—aligning with international goals to broaden cybersecurity participation (Women4Cyber, 2022; CyberPeace Institute, 2023).

CSKA employs a **mixed-methods approach** combining:

- A **national online survey** that collects broad labor market data on workforce needs, AI-related role expectations, training adequacy, and participation barriers—especially for underrepresented groups;
- A set of **expert interviews** with stakeholders from public institutions, critical infrastructure, industry, and academia, providing qualitative insights into regulatory impacts, evolving competencies, and inclusion practices.

This design ensures both **breadth and depth**, generating a comprehensive view of Austria’s cybersecurity skills landscape.

The present paper focuses on the **comparative analysis of cybersecurity skills frameworks**, which constitutes one of the project’s earliest outputs. By mapping international frameworks and identifying where they align—or diverge—with the ECSF, this paper lays the foundation for a more contextualized and future-oriented understanding of cybersecurity roles in Austria. This analysis is particularly relevant to the broader theme of this conference, as it connects **human capabilities to the secure and sustainable deployment of autonomous systems** across various domains.

2. Human Competence in the Age of Autonomy

2.1 The Role of Cybersecurity in Autonomous Ecosystems

The proliferation of autonomous and intelligent systems across critical domains—such as transportation, energy infrastructure, healthcare, and urban environments—has introduced a new era of interdependence between artificial intelligence (AI), automation, and cybersecurity. These systems increasingly rely on continuous data exchange, sensor fusion, algorithmic decision-making, and remote operation, which inherently exposes them to cyber threats that can compromise safety, reliability, and public trust.

For instance, the deployment of connected and automated vehicles (CAVs) demands robust cybersecurity at multiple levels—from vehicle-to-infrastructure communication to edge-device authentication and data privacy. Similar challenges arise in smart grid operations, industrial IoT, and robotic surgery, where autonomous actions must be protected from interference, manipulation, or unauthorized control. The more autonomy a system gains, the more critical it becomes to secure its digital core. In this context, cybersecurity is not just an enabling function—it is a **prerequisite** for the safe, ethical, and trusted deployment of autonomy in society (ENISA, 2021).

The success of these systems depends not only on technical excellence but on the availability of professionals who can understand, anticipate, and mitigate risks across a system's life cycle. These competencies range from traditional information security skills to specialized expertise in AI safety, threat modeling for machine learning, secure system architecture, and incident response in real-time environments. As autonomy becomes more pervasive, the demand for such interdisciplinary cybersecurity expertise intensifies.

2.2 From Workforce Shortage to Strategic Capability

The human resource dimension of cybersecurity has become a growing concern at the global level. According to the latest ISC² Cybersecurity Workforce Study, there is a global shortage of approximately **4 million cybersecurity professionals**, with Europe accounting for nearly 500,000 of those unfilled positions (ISC², 2023). This shortage is particularly acute in roles related to threat intelligence, secure software development, and governance of AI-driven systems. It represents not only a bottleneck for digital transformation but also a structural vulnerability for governments and industries seeking to adopt smart and autonomous technologies.

In Austria, this workforce challenge is compounded by rapid regulatory changes, including the implementation of the **NIS2 Directive**, which introduces stricter requirements for cyber-risk management and workforce competence across a wider range of sectors (European Union, 2022). National cybersecurity strategies, including the Austrian **ÖSCS 2021**, emphasize workforce development as a critical pillar for digital resilience. However, aligning labor market supply with these evolving demands remains a persistent challenge.

Moreover, the cybersecurity field suffers from **severe underrepresentation of women and other marginalized groups**. Globally, women account for only about **24%** of the cybersecurity workforce, with figures in Europe remaining significantly lower (Women4Cyber, 2022). The lack of diversity not only limits talent availability but also reduces innovation, resilience, and the ethical robustness of cybersecurity decision-making (CyberPeace Institute, 2023). Unlocking the full potential of the workforce requires inclusive strategies that dismantle structural barriers and broaden access to relevant education and career pathways.

Beyond the demand for highly specialized professionals, there is an equally important need to strengthen basic cybersecurity awareness and digital hygiene across society. While the CSKA initiative focuses primarily on workforce-level competencies, it recognizes that end-user awareness is an essential layer of societal cyber resilience. As such, general digital security literacy is considered a necessary foundation. Without such a foundation, even the best technical expertise cannot fully mitigate systemic vulnerabilities.

The CSKA project explicitly addresses these gaps by embedding diversity and inclusion throughout its methodology and by developing detailed, localized skill profiles that reflect both technical and non-technical competencies needed for future-proof cybersecurity. By doing so, it aims to convert Austria's **cyber workforce shortage into a strategic capability**, aligned with the evolving demands of autonomy and AI deployment.

3. Comparative Analysis of Cybersecurity Skills Frameworks

3.1 Rationale for Framework Comparison

A foundational step in the CSKA initiative is to understand which cybersecurity competencies are currently described in leading international skill frameworks—and how these align with Austrian needs. To this end, the **European Cybersecurity Skills Framework (ECSF)** was selected as the **anchor framework** for the project.

The ECSF, developed by the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), provides a shared European reference model for cybersecurity job profiles and their associated knowledge, skills, and abilities (ENISA, 2022). It supports the goals of comparability, transparency, and mobility across EU

Member States and is aligned with the **European Qualifications Framework (EQF)**. Given CSKA's policy-relevant focus and the regulatory influence of EU directives such as **NIS2**, ECSF serves as a strategic foundation for further analysis.

However, cybersecurity is a **global field**, and national skills frameworks must be both locally adapted and internationally coherent. To ensure that Austria's adaptation of ECSF captures emerging trends and lessons from beyond Europe, CSKA undertook a comparative review of three additional frameworks:

- The **NICE Framework** from the United States;
- The **ASD Cyber Skills Framework (ACSF)** from Australia;
- The **Singapore Cybersecurity Competency Framework (SCCF)**.

Each of these frameworks reflects unique priorities and contexts and offers complementary perspectives on structuring and defining cybersecurity competencies.

3.2 Overview of Selected Frameworks

European Cybersecurity Skills Framework (ECSF)

- **Publisher:** ENISA (European Union)
- **Structure:** 12 professional roles, each described via knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs), mapped to EQF levels
- **Purpose:** Harmonization of cybersecurity qualifications across the EU
- **Features:** Policy-aligned, with moderate granularity; focused on functional role definitions

NICE Cybersecurity Workforce Framework (USA)

- **Publisher:** NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology)
- **Structure:** Seven categories, 33 specialty areas, and 52 detailed work roles
- **Purpose:** National workforce taxonomy for cybersecurity in public and private sectors.
- **Features:** Highly granular; task-level detail; widely adopted by industry and government (NIST, 2020)

ASD Cyber Skills Framework (Australia)

- **Publisher:** Australian Signals Directorate (ASD)
- **Structure:** Nine core skills domains across six proficiency levels (e.g., Novice to Expert Practitioner)
- **Purpose:** Skills development and capability planning, especially for national security and defense
- **Features:** Modular, scalable, based on SFIA/CIISec models (ASD, 2022)

Singapore Cybersecurity Competency Framework (SCCF)

- **Publisher:** Cyber Security Agency of Singapore (CSA)
- **Structure:** Career pathways structured by roles and aligned to national certification levels
- **Purpose:** Workforce planning, career guidance, and training design
- **Features:** Emphasis on both technical and non-technical (e.g., legal, governance) roles (CSA, 2021)

While ECSF provides an excellent baseline for harmonization and integration into European qualification structures, it is less granular than NICE and lacks the structured proficiency levels of ACSF. SCCF, meanwhile, offers a holistic view of cybersecurity work by integrating non-technical roles and aligning closely with career development pathways—something not fully covered in ECSF.

For Austria, the most useful elements from other frameworks are:

- The **role-task-skill granularity** of NICE;
- The **proficiency level scaling** of ACSF;
- The **inclusion of soft skills and role diversity** in SCCF.

3.3 Mapping to ECSF: Toward Austrian-Specific Profiles

As part of CSKA, a detailed mapping exercise was conducted to align selected international framework elements with the ECSF. The goal was to develop **Austrian-specific competence profiles** that preserve the structure and intent of the ECSF, while incorporating enhancements to reflect:

- Industry-specific roles emerging in Austria (e.g., OT security analysts, AI threat auditors);
- Cross-role requirements for AI systems, such as adversarial ML detection and algorithmic accountability;
- Layered skill levels to support education and career progression.

The goal of developing Austrian-specific competence profiles is not rooted in unique threat conditions, but in the need to reflect national regulatory mandates, institutional structures, and education pathways. Tailoring international frameworks like ECSF allows better integration with local workforce planning, qualification systems, and sector-specific role expectations.

Role gaps and enhancement potentials

The mapping process revealed several **gaps and overlaps**:

- NICE distinguishes several incident response, analysis, and planning roles that ECSF combines into broader categories.
- ACSF's scaling of roles across proficiency levels is valuable for Austrian education institutions seeking to match vocational, bachelor, and master-level training programs to industry needs.
- SCCF's inclusion of legal, audit, and governance-oriented roles aligns well with Austria's regulatory-driven demand profile under NIS2 and CRA.

4. Linking Competence Frameworks to Resilient AI Systems

4.1 From Skill Profiles to AI-Readiness

As autonomous and AI-enabled systems proliferate across critical domains, the role of cybersecurity professionals is evolving rapidly. These systems do not only demand protection in the traditional sense (e.g., against unauthorized access or denial-of-service attacks), but also raise **novel threat vectors** such as adversarial machine learning, data poisoning, model inversion, and AI-generated misinformation (Brundage et al., 2020). The resulting skill requirements stretch far beyond those covered by conventional IT security roles.

To ensure the safe operation of AI systems, professionals must master competencies in **secure AI development lifecycles, model validation and auditing, risk-aware algorithm design, and incident detection in autonomous environments**. Moreover, human cybersecurity experts play a key role in **governing AI systems ethically**, ensuring that explainability, accountability, and fairness are upheld—especially in high-stakes contexts such as healthcare, autonomous transport, or smart city infrastructure (OECD, 2021).

The frameworks analyzed in CSKA offer varying degrees of preparedness for these new realities:

- The **NICE Framework** includes roles such as *Secure Software Assessor* and *Cyber Defense Forensics Analyst*, which could be adapted to encompass adversarial AI and algorithmic forensics.
- The **ACSF** provides a scaling mechanism that can support the progressive inclusion of AI-specific subskills across educational levels.
- The **SCCF** introduces cross-disciplinary roles that combine technical expertise with policy, legal, and governance skills—an important dimension for ensuring AI systems comply with emerging regulations like the AI Act or CRA.

As Austria aims to support secure AI adoption across smart infrastructure, autonomous mobility, and eGovernment, CSKA recommends embedding additional competencies within ECSF-aligned roles:

- Secure ML lifecycle management
- AI system validation and monitoring
- Human-AI interaction security and explainability
- Ethical AI governance and auditing

These are not yet explicitly defined in ECSF but are anticipated to become critical in the next iteration of EU cybersecurity competence frameworks. Incorporating such competencies into ECSF-derived competence profiles would not only increase Austria's AI-readiness, but also ensure that **autonomy is deployed in ways that are technically robust and socially trustworthy**.

4.2 Human Factors in Securing Autonomous Systems

While technical skills remain central, the human dimension of cybersecurity becomes increasingly important in AI-driven environments. AI systems interact with human users, operators, and stakeholders in often opaque or unpredictable ways. Accordingly, **cybersecurity professionals must understand not only code and infrastructure, but also user behavior, systemic risk, and ethical implications** (Floridi & Cowls, 2022).

This calls for a shift in how we define competencies: from purely technical abilities to **hybrid skill sets** that include governance, communication, and decision-making under uncertainty. Skills such as:

- Scenario-based threat anticipation
- Responsible AI deployment assessment
- Crisis response coordination in the context of cyber-physical disruptions

are becoming essential. The **CSKA competence mapping** therefore highlights the need to:

- Encourage multidisciplinary curricula that integrate cybersecurity with data science, AI ethics, and systems engineering;
- Embed **resilience by design** principles across educational levels and professional certifications;
- Train cybersecurity personnel to collaborate across sectors, especially where public interest and autonomous technologies intersect.

These human factors are not only enablers of technical robustness but are essential for **societal trust in AI**. As Austria—and Europe more broadly—seeks to lead in “*secure and trustworthy AI*”, aligning cybersecurity workforce development with these goals is a strategic imperative.

5. Outlook

The comparison of international cybersecurity skills frameworks presented in this paper marks an essential step within the broader *CyberSec-Kompetenz Austria (CSKA)* initiative. As the project advances, the next phase includes deploying a **national online survey** and conducting **in-depth interviews** to validate and expand Austria-specific competence profiles derived from the ECSF and aligned with emerging demands—particularly those related to **AI and autonomy**.

The forthcoming data will be used to refine role definitions, identify **training gaps**, and develop actionable recommendations for curriculum development, upskilling, and strategic workforce planning. Diversity and inclusion will remain guiding themes throughout this process, addressing underrepresentation and helping Austria tap into untapped workforce potential.

Looking beyond national implementation, CSKA contributes to a broader European and international conversation on aligning **human capital strategies** with the rise of **intelligent systems**. With regulations such as NIS2 and the AI Act reshaping requirements, the need for adaptable, interdisciplinary cybersecurity professionals is more critical than ever.

Ultimately, the safe and trustworthy deployment of autonomous technologies depends not only on technical solutions but on the **people behind them**. The CSKA model demonstrates how a nation can build cybersecurity resilience by integrating global best practices with local needs. Its focus on strategic competence mapping, policy alignment, and inclusive participation makes it a replicable model for other regions.

We call on policymakers, educators, and industry leaders to recognize cybersecurity workforce development as a **core pillar of AI readiness**—and to act together to ensure that human competence remains at the heart of secure autonomy.

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**BUSINESS INFORMATION SYSTEMS
AND DIGITALIZATION**

DIGITALIZATION IN BUSINESS

Motto: In Digitalisation We Trust ...or ...Hope?

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Abstract

The digitalization of organizational processes and their expected increased efficiency lead to the widespread introduction of information technology. In addition to today's classic ERP systems, this includes elements of advanced data analysis, artificial intelligence, data and text mining and other trendy technologies. The paper, based on Eurostat data, examines the implementation of selected technologies in the EU27 countries. Cluster analysis over previously normalized data is used to analyse the extent of use of these technologies. The countries that emerge from the analysis as having the widest adoption of the technologies analysed are Denmark, Belgium, Finland, Malta and Sweden. At the opposite pole of digitalisation of business processes, the analysis finds the Czech Republic, Poland, Bulgaria and Romania. The last aspect of digitalisation examined was security in cyberspace. Here, Belgium and Finland showed the best condition, while cyberspace is far more dangerous in Slovenia

1. Introduction

It is typical for today's society that its tool for competitiveness is the use of information systems. The vast majority of organisations - meaning business organisations, public and governmental organisations and non-profit organisations - use standardised Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems. The differentiation of the ERP system setup, the associated process support and the subsequent use of ERP systems by the organisation then represents its real competitive advantage against the environment. If we think about organizations and government bodies and non-profit organizations, then the correct setting of the parameters of the ERP systems used represents a significant increase in their efficiency (I leave the question of their effectiveness unresolved for the purposes of this article).

The use of ERP systems is nowadays one of the classic tools of information and communication technology (ICT) in business practice (Ivanović & Marić, 2021). Their main purpose is to collect data and thus create a data base for more advanced applications. From the past we can mention, for example, Business Intelligence systems (Mishra et al., 2022), the creation of multidimensional data cubes to support management work in so-called EIS systems (Sun, Strang & Firmin, 2016) or

Reporting and Decision Support Systems (Nicolaou, 2010; Islam, Alfakeeh, & Nadeem, 2017). These parts of enterprise information systems, perhaps nowadays quite well mastered, are further developed in new trends. Among these trends, we have selected for the purpose of our article the deployment of advanced data analytics methods in relation to the development of the Data Science trend and also the use of artificial intelligence elements. Its deployment is becoming an important basis for the competitiveness of organizations nowadays. A permanent trend that contemporary organizations have to address in the field of ICT and enterprise information systems is the issue of security. In our paper we will limit ourselves to an analysis of the secure economic environment in individual countries, particularly in the Central European region. (Maurer & Fritzsche, 2023)

In our contribution we would like to focus on a comparison of three areas where information systems are used, especially in the business sector - these are:

- the area of deployment of ERP systems for internal management of the organisation,
- use of advanced data analytics and
- application of artificial intelligence elements.

In addition to the comparison of the Czech Republic with other EU 27 countries in the field of information systems, we also considered the question of the security of their use and deployment. In this section we compare the security assumptions at the macro level of selected European countries.

2. Methodology and Data Collection

To analyse trends in the use of ERP systems, advanced data analytics and artificial intelligence, we used the Eurostat database on the CSO website (Czech Statistical Office, 2024). We compared the data published there for 2023 for each country using the cluster analysis method. However, before dividing the data into clusters, we first normalized the data. The Python package NumPy was used to normalize the observed results on a 0-1 scale. First, the minimum and maximum values for a given attribute were identified. Subsequently, the actual normalization was performed through the proportion of values, the attribute value minus the minimum value in that attribute, and this was divided by the difference of the maximum value in that attribute minus the minimum value in that attribute). The entire normalization in the form of Python code is as follows:

```
# Function to normalize values between 0 and 1
def normalize_values(values):
    min_val = np.min(values)
    max_val = np.max(values)
    if max_val == min_val:
        return np.zeros_like(values)
    return (values - min_val) / (max_val - min_val)
```

Figure 1. Code for standardization in Python

Source: authors

We comment on this division of European countries according to clusters from the perspective of the development of digitalization, especially in the Czech Republic.

For the analysis of the security of the macroeconomic environment, we then used data from four basic security indices. These are the following indices:

- **National Cyber Security Index (NCSI)** – is a global live index, which measures the preparedness of countries to prevent cyber threats and manage cyber incidents. The NCSI is

also a database with publicly available evidence materials and a tool for national cyber security capacity building (National Cyber Security Index, 2024).

- **Global Cybersecurity Index (GCI)** is a trusted reference that measures the commitment of countries to cybersecurity at a global level – to raise awareness of the importance and different dimensions of the issue. As cybersecurity has a broad field of application, cutting across many industries and various sectors, each country’s level of development or engagement is assessed along five pillars:
 - Legal Measures,
 - Technical Measures,
 - Organizational Measures,
 - Capacity Development
 - and Cooperation.and then aggregated into an overall score (International Telecommunication Union, 2024).
- **Cybersecurity Exposure Index (CEI)** discovers which countries are the most and least exposed to cybercrime (PasswordManagers.co, 2024).
- **Cyber Safety Score (CSS)** combining data from three major cybersecurity authorities, namely the National Cyber Security Index , the Global Cybersecurity Index, and the Cybersecurity Exposure Index , authors have created a global ranking to present the ten countries that are, respectively, the least and most risky for internet users (Seon, 2024).

These variables are indicative of cyber security at the state level and shifts in cyber security can be implemented through systemic measures at the level of the state or community of states, such as the European Union.

These indices are used in Table 4 to quantify the level of safety for each country analysed.

3. Results and Discussion

The results of the cluster analysis for the three study areas can be seen in the following section of the paper. The fourth area analysed is the area of information systems security, which is presented here from a macro perspective - i.e., from the perspective of national cyberspace security.

3.1 ERP systems and their use for internal management of the organisation

ERP systems are driving organizations, both internally and towards their clients. Their deployment in organisations in the European Union countries can be seen in the following Figure2.

ERP systems and their deployment for the management and control of internal processes suggests something about the corporate culture, the degree of implementation of process management and the integration of information technology into everyday business life. It is not at all surprising that the Scandinavian countries take the top places, as confirmed by their high index of 1.00. This can be attributed to their strong focus on technological innovation, process management and a highly developed corporate culture that emphasises efficiency and the integration of IT solutions into everyday business.

The second cluster includes Belgium and Spain. Countries in this cluster, with values ranging from 0.83 to 0.72, show very strong ERP system deployment. These countries are located in a region that is known for its advanced industrial and business processes that are supported by robust IT systems.

Figure 2. Deployment of ERP systems for internal management of the organization Source: (author), data: (Czech Statistical Office,2024)

The third cluster then represents the de facto average of the EU member states. Most of the Western European countries are in this cluster. This cluster shows the average deployment of ERP systems in the EU, with values ranging from 0.40 to 0.62. These countries already have a stable implementation of ERP systems, but compared to the leaders of the first and second cluster, their systems are still on the way to full integration. Lithuania has also managed to make inroads into this company.

The other two clusters can be characterized as countries that lag behind in the internal use of ERP systems, either less like members of cluster four or even more like countries in cluster five. For the Czech Republic, this is a significant drop compared to the analyses provided by, for example, (Kuncová, 2018). Similarly, the surprising position of Slovenia in the fourth cluster and Slovakia in the fifth cluster.

Table 1. Clustering of EU Countries - ERP Use in Organisations

Cluster ID	Countries	Values
1	Denmark	1,00
2	Belgium, Finland, Spain, Sweden	0,83 – 0,72
3	EU27 (0,47), France, Italy, Cyprus, Lithuania, Luxemburg, Malta, Germany, Netherlands, Portugal, Austria, Greece	0,40 – 0,62
4	Estonia, Ireland, Latvia, Hungary, Poland, Slovenia	0,19 – 0,34
5	Bulgaria, Czechia, Croatia, Romania, Slovakia	0,00 – 0,16

Source: (authors), data: (Czech Statistical Office,2024)

The different levels of ERP deployment in the EU member states reflect not only the economic strength of these countries, but also their willingness and ability to adapt to technological change.

While the Scandinavian countries and advanced Western European countries are pioneers in ERP implementation, some countries in Central and Eastern Europe, including the Czech Republic and Slovakia, are lagging behind, which may have a long-term impact on their competitiveness and efficiency.

It is clear that the development of ERP systems is a necessary step for organizations that want to adapt to a dynamic business environment and remain competitive on a global level. However, ERP implementation requires a strong corporate culture focused on innovation, investment in IT infrastructure and the ability to manage change in organizational processes.

3.2 Advanced Data Analytics Methods

The situation in the area of advanced data analytics and its deployment, especially in commercial companies, is mapped in the next Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Deployment of advanced data analytics systems in organizations

Source: (authors), data: (Czech Statistical Office,2024)

Figure 2 shows the quite different approaches to the application of advanced data analytics methods in organisations across the EU. This overview shows how some countries are becoming leaders in data analytics while others are lagging behind. From a strong involvement in business processes, particularly in the first two clusters, to virtually no application at work for countries in the fifth cluster.

Croatia shows a value of 1.00, which means it is a leader in the deployment of advanced data analytics. The country seems to have set an example for others when it comes to integrating advanced analytics tools into business processes. Croatia can be seen as an example of how CEE countries can succeed in digital transformation if they focus on investing in advanced technologies.

Belgium, Denmark, Lithuania and the Netherlands in the second cluster are the countries that show strong deployment of advanced data analytics with values between 0.80 and 0.66. These countries are at the top of the European spectrum in the application of analytics methods to business processes.

They have highly developed digital infrastructures, enabling their organisations to use advanced analytics tools to ensure competitiveness and efficiency.

Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Estonia, Poland, Romania, Austria, Slovenia are at the other end of the spectrum and show very low levels of advanced data analytics deployment, with values between 0.11 and 0.00. These countries still face significant barriers to the implementation of advanced analytics. This may be due to lower technological maturity, weaker support for innovation, or a lower focus on data-driven approaches in decision-making processes.

Table 2. Clustering of EU Countries - Deploying advanced data analytics in organisations

Cluster ID	Countries	Values
1	Croatia	1,00
2	Belgium, Denmark, Lithuania, Netherlands	0,80 – 0,66
3	Finland, Ireland, Latvia, Hungary, Malta, Germany, Spain, Sweden	0,58 – 0,44
4	EU27 (0,40), France, Italy, Cyprus, Luxemburg, Portugal, Greece, Slovakia	0,41 – 0,23
5	Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Poland, Austria, Romania, Slovenia	0,11 – 0,00

Source: (authors), data: (Czech Statistical Office,2024)

The deployment of advanced data analytics is nowadays also one of the components of increasing the competitiveness of national economies, and of the EU economy as a whole. Therefore, its implementation should be in the interest of virtually all organisations

An important aspect is that the deployment of advanced data analytics is becoming a key factor for increasing the competitiveness not only of individual companies, but of entire national economies within the EU. This trend underlines the need for wider access to these technologies, not only within developed countries, but also in those that are still lagging behind in this respect. Organisations that choose to invest in advanced analytical tools can gain a decisive competitive advantage in the global market, which should be a priority for EU-wide policy and development strategy.

3.3. Artificial Intelligence

The deployment of advanced data analysis methods is very similar to the deployment of artificial intelligence elements in the organisation's own business processes. How its deployment looks like in EU countries is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 shows that the Scandinavian countries are leading in the deployment of AI. This fact is confirmed by the cluster analysis of the problem. Its results are presented in Table 3.

Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands in the first cluster are the top countries in AI deployment, with values between 1.00 and 0.85. This group represents the leaders in AI implementation, indicating a strong orientation of these countries towards innovation and modernisation of their business processes. Interestingly, there are more countries in this cluster than in the advanced data analytics cluster, showing that AI is becoming more popular than analytics methods in some regions.

In the second cluster are Germany, Austria, Slovenia, Sweden, which show values between 0.74 and 0.65. These countries are still among the leaders in AI, although their values are slightly lower than

in the first cluster. This suggests that even in these countries AI already plays a significant role in business processes, but there is still room for further development and wider adoption.

Figure 4. Deployment of artificial intelligence systems in organizations

Source: (authors), data: (Czech Statistical Office,2024)

Croatia, Ireland, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain in the third cluster have values between 0.48 and 0.36. This cluster includes most of the Western European countries and a few Central European countries that show a medium level of AI deployment. This cluster also includes some countries that already have basic AI implementations but still face challenges in integrating these technologies more broadly into all aspects of business processes.

Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Italy, Cyprus, Lithuania, Latvia have values between 0.32 and 0.23. This cluster shows a lower level of AI adoption compared to previous clusters. Although some countries are starting to implement AI, they still face challenges in terms of digitalization and the ability to integrate AI into more complex business processes.

In the fifth and final cluster, Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Greece show very low levels of AI deployment, with values between 0.18 and 0.00. These countries are similarly at the very end of the spectrum when it comes to advanced data analytics in terms of AI implementation. This suggests that there are significant barriers to the adoption of new technologies in these countries, such as limited R&D investment, weaker technology infrastructure, or lower levels of organizational readiness for digital transformation.

Table 3. Clustering of EU Countries - Deployment of Artificial Intelligence in Organisations

Cluster ID	Countries	Values
1	Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Luxemburg, Malta, Netherlands	1,00 – 0,85
2	Germany, Austria, Slovenia, Sweden	0,74 – 0,65
3	EU27 (0,48), Croatia, Ireland, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain	0,48 – 0,36
4	Czechia, Estonia, France, Italy, Cyprus, Lithuania, Latvia	0,32 – 0,23
5	Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Greece	0,18 – 0,00

Source: (authors), data: (Czech Statistical Office,2024)

The first cluster included countries with the highest share of AI involvement in business processes. It can be seen that more countries are represented here and from this it can be concluded that the elements of artificial intelligence are more popular in the implementation than the elements of advanced data analysis. The clustering of countries is de facto consistent with previous analyses. The lagging countries ranked in the fifth cluster correspond to a similar ranking in Table 2.

Interestingly, AI is proving to be more popular than advanced data analytics in some cases, which could mean that organizations are focusing more on automation and predictive analytics than traditional analytics methods. However, as with advanced data analytics, there is considerable variation in the level of adoption of AI between countries. Countries that lag behind in AI deployment face challenges in terms of technological development, infrastructure and investment, which can have a long-term impact on their competitiveness. To ensure wider adoption of AI, European countries should invest in training and increasing the technological readiness of organisations, foster collaboration between the public and private sectors, and create policies that promote innovation and digital transformation.

3.4. Security

Before we start looking at how to address the protection of information systems assets in organizations, let's look at the situation in the world, where and how safe which countries are from a cybersecurity perspective. Before we look at the protection of organisations' information systems, let's look at the evolution of the threats to these systems. The evolution of the relevance of the threats is shown in Figure 5 as of 2017.

Figure 5. The most common types of external attacks on information systems of organizations

Source: (Verizon Business, 2024)

Figure 5 clearly shows an increase in the "Denial of Services" threat type from 2022 to over 50% of all attacks on organizations' information systems in the past year. In contrast, attacks of the "System Intrusion" type are decreasing. The incidence of other attack types is more or less stable with occasional fluctuations. Such as the "Lost and Stolen Assets" attack type in 2023 or the de facto disappearance of the "Privilege Misuse" threat type. This threat has been substantially reduced, mainly thanks to the implementation of administrative measures combined with technical measures.

Various organisations around the world survey cybersecurity conditions from their perspective, which they then publish in the form of various indices. For the purpose of this article, we have selected some of the countries whose citizens are participating in this conference. The selection in alphabetical order is presented in the following Table 4. According to Table 4, it can be seen that the most secure movement and business in cyberspace is again in the countries where we identified the highest share of digitization in the previous section of the paper. The only surprise is Slovenia's ranking as high as fortieth.

Table 4. Overview of selected countries by cybersecurity level

Ranking	Country	NCSI	GCI	CEI	CSS
1	Belgium	94.81	96.25	81.00	90.69
2	Finland	85.71	95.78	89.00	90.16
5	Germany	90.91	97.41	75.90	88.07
12	Poland	87.01	93.86	71.40	84.09
19	Slovakia	83.12	92.36	73.80	83.09
28	Czechia	92.12	74.37	66.60	77.73
29	Hungary	67.53	91.28	71.40	76.74
40	Slovenia	59.74	74.93	71.70	68.79
	Austria	No data available			

Source: (Seon, 2024)

Note: NCSI – National Cyber Security Index, GCI - Global Cybersecurity Index, CEI – Cybersecurity Exposure Index, CSS – Cyber Safety Score (Mean Average of NCSI, GCI, CEI).

4. Conclusions

For an overall assessment of the digitalization of selected business processes, let's take a look at the summary of the results from the cluster analysis of all three monitored areas - the deployment of ERP systems for internal management of the organization, the use of advanced methods of data analytics and the application of artificial intelligence elements. The main drivers of digitisation in the European Union are Denmark, Belgium, Finland, Malta and Sweden. Their position in all three areas surveyed was at the top and their overall ranking therefore puts them in the first group of EU countries in the area of business process digitisation. The second group of countries follows them quite closely - Luxembourg, Germany, Spain, Croatia, Lithuania. The third cluster then includes Austria, Ireland, Portugal (EU average), Slovenia, France, Italy, Latvia, Cyprus (already below average). The countries in the fourth cluster are already lagging behind the EU27 average in digitalisation. These are Slovakia, Estonia, Hungary and Greece. The countries lagging furthest behind in digitising processes and putting new technologies into practice are the Czech Republic, Poland, Bulgaria and Romania.

The variables listed in Table 4 are indicative of cybersecurity at the national level, and shifts in cybersecurity levels can be implemented through systemic measures at the national or community of states level, such as the European Union. The European Commission issues a number of directives and measures in the field of digital technologies. As the importance of ICTs on the economic and everyday life of citizens grows, so does their regulation and the setting of conditions for their use on the part of both ICT service providers and qualified and ordinary users. As I mentioned in the introduction, an important part of the use of ICT is trust in the data it contains and therefore in the services it provides. Trustworthiness of data is one of the outcomes of ensuring ICT security. That is why ICT security and its regulation is one of the main lines of development of the legislation issued by the European Union. These are in particular the following EU directives -NIS2 (The Directive on Measures for a High Common Level of Cybersecurity Across the Union) DORA (The Digital Operation Resilience Act), CSA (The Cybersecurity Act), CRA (The European Cyber Resilience Act).

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PERSPECTIVE ON THE ISSUE OF OPEN INNOVATION IN THE ERA OF ACCELERATED DIGITALIZATION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Open innovation; European Union; United States; artificial intelligence

Abstract

This research paper aims to explore the dynamics of Open Innovation (OI) in the European Union, non-European Union countries and the United States. The main metric used is the Innovation Index. The study targets to provide a comprehensive knowledge and inform policy, strategy, and academic knowledge on the interplay between OI, innovation, and economic performance. The findings highlight the dynamic nature of innovation, driven by factors such as technological advances, information literacy and collaborative efforts. To succeed in the rapidly evolving environment of the modern global economy, both, organizations and nations are seeking to the ability to adapt, invest in R&D and foster an environment conducive to innovation. This is proving to be a critical element and provides valuable perspectives for policy makers, strategic planners and researchers interested in fostering innovation ecosystems and increasing economic resilience.

1. Introduction

Information and ICTs, which represent essential parts of a business infrastructure, are the driving forces of the current modern society. Their development influences economic environment by a substantial degree and ranks among factors of business prosperity and competitiveness (Bolek et al., 2018). Global spending on digital transformation is set to reach \$1.59 trillion in 2021, an increase of more than 20% from the previous year. The pandemic is acknowledged to have boosted digital transformation efforts, as the rise of remote working has spurred businesses to adopt cloud technologies. Indeed, the most common approach to digital transformation among organizations globally in 2022 involved adapting existing IT solutions through cloud extension, and the global public cloud market is estimated to have surpassed US\$490 billion. In 2022, nearly 90% of organizations globally have implemented cloud technologies, representing the highest adoption rate among new technologies (Taylor, P, 2023). The rapid development of digital technologies, coupled with the increased mobility restrictions imposed during the COVID-19 pandemic, has accelerated a paradigm shift in traditional economic models. Digital transformation, which is an increasingly widespread phenomenon in different types of organisations, is affecting every aspect of their operations. Organizations are leveraging digital technologies to increase efficiency and effectiveness in management, marketing, and accounting (Varzaru et al., 2022). The ability of a company to attract and retain customers is intricately linked to its capacity to develop high-quality innovative products and services, a crucial differentiator for survival in the competitive market landscape (Saruc et al., 2013). The comprehensive adoption of digital transformation, encompassing the advancement and use of various digital technologies such as big data, business analytics, mobile applications, the Internet of Things, and digital platforms, has profound implications for the dynamics of organizations. Regardless, the economic status of customers greatly influences their view of social media marketing (Pollák et al., 2021). Recent crises, particularly the COVID-19 pandemic, have intensified efforts to digitize organisations across sectors. The hospitality sector, struggling with the challenges posed by the pandemic, is increasingly turning to digital technology and innovation to formulate competitive strategies and optimise operational practices. Currently, digital transformation is a key determinant of business sustainability in this sector (Farías and Cancino, 2021). In addressing the question of how enterprises can adapt their digitization efforts against the backdrop of the COVID-19 pandemic to achieve sustainable digital transformation, enterprises accelerated their digitization initiatives at an unprecedented pace during the global health crisis. This rapid implementation of digital technologies left organizations with minimal time to adapt their structures, processes and cultures to the new environment. Companies operated in a prolonged operating mode that could either be transitory, involving a return to normalcy after the pandemic ended, or could potentially lead to organizational failure (Reuschl, Deist, and Maalaoui, 2022). This highlights the profound impact of the pandemic on the digital transformation process, which is a key factor in the current environment. Identifying these influences provides invaluable insights for navigating and adapting to new operating conditions.

2. Literature review

Since Chesbrough's foundational work in 2003, the concept of open innovation (OI) has received increasing attention from both academics and practitioners. As highlighted by Obradovic and others (2021, p. 2) in their recent comprehensive review of the literature on open innovation within the manufacturing industry, the growing importance of OI is evident in the significant volume of scholarly output, with more than 4,000,000 papers indexed on Google Scholar in 2020. In its early stages, open innovation research has largely focused on elucidating the strategies used by large corporations to engage in open innovation initiatives. However, as the field has progressed and

matured, scholars have delved into different levels of analysis, examining the micro foundations of open innovation (Bogers et al., 2018a), non-profit organizations and the public sector (Bogers et al., 2018b; Chesbrough and Di Minin, 2014), and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) (Laursen and Salter, 2006; Vanhaverbeke, 2017), (De Marco et al., 2020, p. 2). Previous research on open innovation (OI) has mainly highlighted its beneficial outcomes while exploring its potential drawbacks and the delicate balance between its beneficial and constraining impacts. However, the existing body of evidence remains limited, particularly when examining micro-level analysis (Salge et al., 2013; Knudsen and Mortensen, 2011; Chesbrough and Bogers, 2014; Kobarg et al., 2019). Earlier studies have examined the correlation between open innovation (OI) and firm performance, focusing primarily on innovation performance. In a recent review, Lu and Chesbrough (2022) conducted an extensive review of research in this area, shedding light on the considerable heterogeneity of statistical methodologies used to assess firm innovation performance. Many of these methodologies were survey-based, as reported in studies such as Grimpe and Sofka (2016) and Laursen and Salter (2006). The literature has shown a particular interest in the field of OI and SMEs, especially those involved in digital innovation. This is because digital technologies are fundamentally changing firms' strategies, innovation perspectives and business models, disrupting the functioning of organizations (Crupi et al., 2022; Cutolo and Kenney, 2021). The traditional literature on SMEs and innovation recognises their critical role in fostering the development of innovation ecosystems through their contribution to improving employment and economic growth (Acs et al., 1999; Storey, 2016). However, SMEs are most vulnerable in tackling co-innovation projects due to their traditional lack of resources, both human and financial, compared to their need to keep up with innovative developments to maintain their competitive advantage. The constraints of SMEs (Spithoven et al., 2013) force them to explore the external environment and implement OI practices to compensate for missing assets (Van de Vrande et al., 2009). Previous studies have highlighted that while large enterprises adopt OI to better leverage complementary assets and capabilities performed by partners, SMEs resort to OI to compensate for the lack of internal assets (Di Minin et al., 2016). For instance, Pollák and Markovič (2021) concluded that perceived benefit of the Internet on business is closely related to on-line activity of the companies and to the number of instruments the company uses to promote its business, electronic marketing can be considered to a certain degree to be electronic commerce (Dorcak et al., 2015).

3. Methodology

The main goal of this research paper is to explore the dynamics of open innovation across EU and non-EU countries, with a comparative focus on the United States. The findings aim to inform innovation-related policies, strategies, and academic discourse on economic performance. This exploratory and analytical study includes a comprehensive literature review, data analysis, and synthesis of findings, drawing primarily on data from the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. The European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS) is used to assess and compare the research and innovation performance of EU Member States and selected third countries. It identifies strengths and weaknesses in innovation systems, helping countries focus their efforts to improve performance. EIS 2022 classifies innovation activities into four categories—Framework Conditions, Investments, Innovation Activities, and Impacts—measured by 12 dimensions and 32 indicators, equally weighted to produce the Summary Innovation Index. The index quantifies a country's innovation and technological progress. Based on 2022 results, Member States are grouped into: a) Innovation Leaders (above 125% of the EU average), b) Strong Innovators (100–125%), c) Moderate Innovators (70–100%), and d) Emerging Innovators (below 70%) (European Commission, 2022). The Innovation Index also serves as a global benchmark. It aggregates indicators

related to innovation, science, and R&D. While a similar methodology is used for global comparisons, adjustments are made to account for differences in data sources and definitions. This is done by applying a standardization ratio to align non-EU and EU results, ensuring consistency across countries. For detailed methodology, see European Commission (2023), European Innovation Scoreboard 2023 Methodology Report.

4. Results and discussion

We embark on a journey to understand the pulse of creativity and progress in different economic areas when we delve into the innovation indices. Within the European Union, these indices highlight regional strengths and inform strategic policy directions, while outside the EU they provide insights into global competitiveness. In the dynamic US innovation environment, these measures play a key role in shaping national agendas and maintaining leadership in the global innovation arena.

Figure 1. Summary innovation index

Source: (own assumptions together with European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation – European innovation scoreboard)

The innovation leaders' original category includes five Member States that perform above 125% of the EU average. These countries, listed in alphabetical order, are Belgium, Denmark, Finland, the

Netherlands and Sweden. The subsequent classification of Strong Innovators includes seven Member States with a performance between 100% and 125% of the EU average. This group consists of Austria, Cyprus, Estonia, France, Germany, Ireland, Luxembourg and Cyprus. The third classification, Moderate Innovators, consists of eight Member States with a performance level between 70% and 100% of the EU average. This category includes the Czech Republic, Greece, Italy, Lithuania, Malta, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain. Finally, the fourth group, Emerging Innovators, comprises seven Member States with a performance level below 70% of the EU average. This group includes Bulgaria, Croatia, Hungary, Latvia, Poland, Romania and Slovakia. Compared to last year's EIS 2021, there has been considerable progress, with the Netherlands moving up to Innovation Leader and Cyprus moving up to Strong Innovator.

Comparing innovation performance with countries outside the European Union

Figure 2. Summary innovation index

Source: (own assumptions together with European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation – European innovation scoreboard)

Switzerland is the best performer in six key indicators, including new PhD graduates, international scientific co-publications, foreign PhD students, public and private co-publications, exports of medium and high-tech products and resource productivity. Iceland, Norway, and the United Kingdom are classified as strong innovators. Iceland and Norway, together with Switzerland, are the best performers in international scientific co-publications and public and private co-publications. In addition, Norway stands out for innovative SMEs collaborating with others. The United Kingdom leads in five indicators, sharing two with Switzerland. Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, Turkey, and Ukraine are identified as emerging innovators. Several of these countries have the highest (combined) performance in at least one indicator. Albania leads in sales of

innovative environmental products and technologies, Bosnia and Herzegovina in environmental technologies and Serbia in non-R&D innovation expenditure.

Comparing innovation performance with countries outside the European Union, case of United States

Table 1. Summary innovation index in United States

United States	2022
Doctorate graduates	83.4
Tertiary education	128.0
International co-publications	112.7
Most cited publications	136.8
R&D expenditure public sector	96.1
Government funding business R&D	127.3
R&D expenditure business sector	180.0
Employment in ICT	109.0
Product innovators	77.5
Business process innovators	74.3
Innovation co-operation	591.5
Public-private co-publications	116.6
PCT patent applications	112.9
Trademark applications	72.9
Design applications	35.2
Medium & high-tech product exports	93.6
Knowledge-intensive services exports	100.8
Exposure to air pollution	175.6
Environment-related technologies	71.7

Source: (European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation – European innovation scoreboard)

The United States consistently outperforms the European Union in innovation, earning its status as a global leader. This advantage stems from several key factors that create a favorable innovation environment. The U.S. has a dynamic entrepreneurial ecosystem, supported by venture capital, angel investors, and startup accelerators, all of which promote risk-taking and cross-sector innovation. It also excels in transferring technology from research institutions to the market, aided by strong intellectual property laws and a culture that rewards innovation.

While the EU also performs well, the U.S. leads due to its unique blend of supportive infrastructure, vibrant ecosystem, and encouragement of disruptive ideas. The U.S. is seen as a benchmark in innovation, particularly in global R&D investment and leadership in AI, cloud computing, autonomous vehicles, and consumer tech. Given this context, including the U.S. perspective in innovation index analysis adds valuable insight.

5. Conclusion

The discussions shed light on the multifaceted innovation landscape, encompassing different dimensions such as open innovation (OI), digital transformation, information literacy of managers and international benchmarking. OI has evolved from an initial focus on strategies used by large corporations to a more nuanced examination of micro-enterprises, non-profit organizations and SMEs. Digital transformation, accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, has become a cornerstone of organizational sustainability, highlighting the critical role of adaptability and continuous learning, particularly in information security. In examining the link between open innovation and firm performance, previous research has identified both positive impacts and potential drawbacks, with evidence still limited, particularly at the micro level of analysis. In the context of international comparisons, countries show varying levels of innovation performance, with strong leaders such as Switzerland, the United States and the United Kingdom standing out for their excellence across a range of indicators. In addition, the methodology for calculating innovation performance, whether at the level of EU Member States or in global comparisons, involves different adjustments due to differences in indicators, definitions, and data sources. This ensures a consistent and meaningful assessment of innovation in different contexts. In summary, the discussions highlight the dynamic nature of innovation, driven by factors such as technological advances, information literacy and collaborative efforts. For both organizations and nations seeking to succeed in the rapidly evolving environment of the modern global economy, the ability to adapt, invest in R&D and foster an environment conducive to innovation is proving to be a critical element.

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SUPPORT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF HUMAN RESOURCE PROCESSES AT CITY HALL BY ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE APPROACH: A CASE OF THE REGIONAL CZECHIA ADMINISTRATION

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Public administration, digital transformation, enterprise architecture, ArchiMate, business process

Abstract

Digital transformation (DT) supported by enterprise architecture (EA) is a long-term initiative requiring socio-technical and organizational efforts to transform AS-IS processes into optimized TO-BE processes. Czech public administration (PA) is gradually digitalizing citizen services through self-service portals, but internal processes are often neglected. Standard business information systems (BIS) can significantly support digital transformation. Little is known about how public administration uses enterprise architecture to describe the current state (AS-IS) of human resource processes and design an effective future state (TO-BE) for BIS implementation to meet the goals of digital transformation initiatives. Based on semi-narrative interviews with municipal employees, this article also uses graphical language ArchiMate for visualization. The AS-IS state showed deficiencies, while the TO-BE state, supported by BIS, addresses these points. Further research on barriers and challenges supporting business optimization through DT and enterprise EA is needed.

1. Introduction

Digital transformation and process automation impact the private and public sectors. Local governments must modernize services and internal processes, as outlined by the Ministry of Interior (2018, 2020). Human resource management (HRM) has substantial automation potential, especially for routine tasks. This article explores automating HRM processes within local governments, using EA principles and optimizing through information technology (IT) and BIS. Despite opportunities for improvement, there's limited evidence of national-level implementation in European countries using EA and BIS strategies. The National architecture plan of Czechia (NAP) (Digital and Information Agency, 2019) aligns PA entities' business requirements with IT and BIS capabilities to address efficiency gaps (Lukáš et al., 2024). Scholarly evidence (Kotusev, 2019) indicates that EA is crucial for business structures, business-IT alignment, and organizational transformation through management of EA (Gerber et al., 2020). Researchers focus on DT (Siegel & Gabryelczyk, 2021). Historical initiatives in Czechia aim to establish a foundation for EA development and maintenance,

enhancing process optimization and automation as part of DT (Khisro, 2021). This article demonstrates EA and ArchiMate's practical application in identifying and addressing HRM process gaps through IT and BIS strategies. It focuses on the AS-IS and TO-BE states of two HRM processes to enhance efficiency. ArchiMate serves as the foundational tool in accordance with NAP. The article discusses DT challenges and EA supports within local government contexts, supported by domain knowledge from semi-structured interviews, HRM relevance, and IT and BIS integration into HRM processes. The literature review elaborates on EA's framework for DT in PA, guided by NAP. The methodology details the approach used. Findings from interviews describe the AS-IS state and serve as a pool for designing the TO-BE state of two HRM processes. Feedback analysis formulates strategies to improve HRM processes using ArchiMate. The strategy for implementing IT and BIS solutions is assessed. The final section summarizes results and provides a basis for further research.

2. Literature review

2.1. Public administration

In Czechia, PA is divided into state administration and local government, further split into territorial and interest-based divisions (Hendrych et al., 2012). This supports decentralization and efficient management of public affairs. State administration is carried out directly by state authorities or indirectly through authorized public entities. Direct executors include ministries, central administrative authorities, and specialized administrative authorities. Indirect executors are authorities of territorial local government units exercising state administration in delegated competence (Koudelka, 2007). Territorial local government is managed by municipalities (basic units) and regions (higher units), established by the Constitution and detailed in relevant laws (Koudelka, 2007). PA is essential for modern democratic states, managing public affairs, serving the public interest, and representing executive power. It is both an activity (governance) and an institution (organization or office) performing this activity (Hendrych et al., 2012).

2.2. Human resource processes

HRM is crucial for any organization, strategically managing its most valuable asset—its people—to achieve organizational goals (Armstrong, 2023). Koubek (2015) describes personnel management as handling all aspects related to individuals in the work process, including acquisition, development, functioning, organization, coordination, work results, abilities, behavior, relationships, satisfaction, and personal and social development. Modern HRM aligns closely with organizational strategy, acting as strategic partners to management and creating value for stakeholders (Ulrich et al., 2009). HRM faces challenges such as digitalization, artificial intelligence (AI), diversity and inclusion, work-life balance, and flexible work forms, requiring continuous learning and adaptation (Boxall and Purcell, 2016). Effective HRM enhances productivity, innovation, and overall performance, making human capital a key competitive advantage (Armstrong, 2023). In public administration, particularly local governments, HRM has unique features reflecting its mission and is vital for organizational success (Armstrong, 2023). This broad scope is further enhanced by the specific requirements of the public sector (Hendrych et al., 2012).

2.3. Digital transformation of public administration

Digital transformation impacts PA globally, including Czechia, by implementing new technologies and transforming structures, processes, and service delivery (Ministry of Interior, 2018). DT in PA redesigns services and interactions between the state and citizens using modern digital technologies

for efficiency, transparency, and user-friendliness (Špaček, 2012). This transformation requires new thinking, changes in work practices, and digital competencies (Mates and Smejkal, 2012). In Czechia, DT is guided by the Digital Czechia strategy, including Czechia in Digital Europe, the Information Concept of the Czech (ICC), and the Digital Economy and Society Concept. The ICC outlines objectives for IT over five years (Ministry of Interior, 2018). The strategy emphasizes system interoperability and data sharing among PA bodies, aligning with the EU's "once only" principle (Ministry of Interior, 2018). In 2020, the Concept of Client-Oriented Public Administration 2030 was introduced to improve user experience and personalize services (Ministry of Interior, 2020). The Digital and Information Agency (DIA), established in 2022, coordinates PA digitalization and develops shared eGovernment services.

2.4. Enterprise architecture

EA is a strategic approach to managing organizations in the digital era, integrating business objectives, processes, information, and technology (Lankhorst, 2017). EA systematically outlines an organization's current and future state, including technological aspects, business strategies, organizational structures, and key processes (Lukáš & Ulman, 2020). Originating in the 1980s with Zachman's framework, EA has evolved to address the complexity of organizational IT infrastructure (Gála et al., 2015). EA is essential for managing market changes, technological innovation, and regulatory requirements, ensuring alignment with strategic goals (Řepa, 2012). In HRM process optimization, EA identifies and visualizes links between HR processes, business systems, and overall strategy, facilitating effective automation & digitization. EA integrates business architecture and 225odelling into a comprehensive technological and data framework.

2.5. Graphical language ArchiMate

ArchiMate, developed by The Open Group, is a standardized language for 225odelling of EA, complementing TOGAF with a visual language. The NAP uses TOGAF's ADM cycle for thorough documentation. ArchiMate is crucial for effective communication within EA practice, capturing key phases of the TOGAF ADM cycle and including motivational and implementation extensions. It interlinks elements across layers, providing a comprehensive organizational view and facilitating impact analysis (Simon et al., 2013). The DIA endorses ArchiMate for public administration, ensuring consistent documentation and aligning with international trends. This approach is vital for system interoperability and effective DT. ArchiMate and EA principles suit PA process automation and DT, adhering to Czech eGovernment standards. ArchiMate visualizes complex relationships between legislation, administrative processes, BIS, and IT, bridging communication gaps between IT specialists and civil servants, essential for successful DT (Lukáš, Ulman, 2020).

2.6. National Digital Transformation statistics

In 2024, 88% of people in Czechia, nearly 7.6 million over 16 years old, use the internet. Of these, 98% use it regularly, and 91% connect daily. Internet usage is nearly universal among younger people and has risen among those over 65 from 13% in 2010 to 57% in 2024. The lowest usage is among those over 80. Common activities include emailing (85%), reading news (80%), searching for information (74%), and watching videos (73%). Over half use social networks (58%) and internet banking (55%). Czechia had one of the highest increases in EU internet users from 2010 to 2020, with a rise of over 20 percentage points. During the COVID-19 pandemic, remote work via the internet increased from 7% to 15%. Currently, 54% of households have high-speed fixed internet, and 38% have mobile internet access. (Czech Statistical Office, 2023, 2024).

3. Methodology

3.1. Design of a narrative interview

The semi-structured narrative interview was created as a tool for collecting opinions on the DT of HRM processes in City Kladno. The narrative interview covered the following: size and structure, administration, processes, substitutability, BIS, time-consuming activities, responsibility, purpose, process start, end, rules, regulations, problems, improvements, work procedure, and people. The 40-minute interviews were held personally with 2 independent HR representatives.

3.2. Research questions

The research questions (RQ) examine the relationship between the EA approach and ArchiMate as drivers for the DT of HRM processes. Since 2020, investigations into EA and DT correlations have continued. Lukáš et al. (2022) conclude that the EA approach supports the preparation phase of digitalization projects in Czechia PA. RQ#1: How can the EA approach document the AS-IS state within HRM to identify gaps for digital transformation? RQ#2: How can the EA approach and TO-BE design help bridge the gaps in the AS-IS state within HRM for digital transformation? RQ#3: How can documenting AS-IS and designing TO-BE HRM processes support BIS implementation strategies as part of DT? This article investigates the relationship between the EA approach and ArchiMate as drivers for the DT of HRM processes. In other words, RQs aim to understand how EA and ArchiMate facilitate the DT of HRM processes. Previous studies highlight the importance of visualizing DT initiatives through ArchiMate viewpoints to support stakeholders and improve performance outcomes (Zhang, Chen, 2024). Research has identified EA artifacts that aid strategy planning for DT (Strohmeier, Piazza, 2015). Integrating IT and HRM processes enhances organizational performance. Poulouse et al. (2024) provide a literature review and conceptual framework for DT's determinants and drivers, emphasizing transforming HRM processes.

3.3. Demographics of City Kladno, City Hall & HR department

At the end of 2022, Kladno had 68,436 inhabitants, which is 4.2 times more than in 1869. It was the most populous municipality in the Central Bohemian Region and the 13th in Czechia. The most significant population increases were in 1978, 2022, 1973, and 1974, while the biggest decrease was in 2004. The HR department of the City Hall consists of four employees: 2 handling HR tasks and 2 managing payroll. The department oversees 445 full-time employees and several hundred part-time workers, including approximately 500 temporary election staff annually. The HR department manages nine workplaces (e.g. the city police, administrative centers), with the largest being the administrative department, employing over 50 people. The HR department covers a set of processes such as human resource planning, recruitment (which is represented by HR process #1: Receipt and management of applications, HR process #2: Testing of applicants), training & development, compensation & benefits, personnel administration, and termination of employment. The department heads handle performance management, talent management, and employee relations, while a designated officer manages occupational safety outside the HR department. The HR staff rate the substitutability of positions within the department as high. They use the specific software from DataCentrum for HR and payroll tasks (DC2), which includes an organizational chart and attendance tracking linked to payroll calculations - Applicant Tracking Systems (ATS). ATS is highly satisfactory, with no reported limitations. Time-consuming tasks include various analyses and preparation for recruitment.

Table 1. The characteristics of the HR department

Category	Details
HR Department Staff	4 employees
Employees Managed	445
PT/TW	~500 election staff
Workplaces Managed	9
Largest Department	Administrative (50+ employees)
AAR	30 processes
Software Used	DC2 by DataCentrum
SoP	High
TCT	Recruitment preparation

Legend: PT/TW = Part-time/Temporary Workers; AAR = Average Annual Recruitment; SoP = Substitutability of Positions; TCT = Time-consuming Tasks

The city secretary oversees HR recruitment and coordinates with staff members. Its primary purpose is to fill vacant positions with the most suitable candidates, ensuring the smooth operation. The process begins with the secretary's announcement and ends with the signing of the employment contract. It follows labor laws and internal guidelines. Common issues include human factors at various stages, and routine tasks involve copying documents, preparing summary tables, and document shredding. The process includes public announcements, candidate testing, interviews, and final selection by a committee.

Applications and related documents are archived for the selected candidate. Candidates are notified of application receipt and contacted by phone. Computer-based testing varies by position, with general and IT questions from the HR area. HR staff administer 40-minute tests, recording results on a physical table and informing candidates by phone. Interviews usually follow on the same day. The AS-IS state of HR processes #1 and #2 includes ArchiMate Business layer elements: Business actor, process, and object. The connections are access, assignment, and flow.

Figure 1. AS-IS state of HR process #1

Figure 2. AS-IS state of HR process #2

The deep yellow color highlights gaps in HR processes #1 and #2. Potential optimizations by respective BIS were investigated, showing that manual tasks can be automated through BIS routines. Suitable BIS types digitally transform manual work to enhance the efficiency of HR processes #1 #2.

4. Results

In detail, after modeling the AS-IS state of the HR process #1 and HR process #2 processes using the ArchiMate graphical language, the following possibilities for the points of interest (POI) emerged: A) HR process #1: **POI #1** – digitalization of selected activities (posting on the official board, receipt of the application, verification of the application, request for additional requirements, receipt of documents for the committee, archiving of documents), **POI #2** – digitalization of qualification requirements (application, CV, criminal record, proof of education), **POI #3** – digitalization of document archiving, B) HR process #2: **POI #3** digitalization of inviting applicants to test, administration of testing, evaluation of the test, invitation to interviews, submission of the results to the committee, **POI#4** – digitization of application test, printed test, evaluated test, management summary to the committee. These POIs are essential for selecting strategies for the DT of HRM processes. DT strategies vary in complexity, implementation, costs & benefits, including (i) implementing a comprehensive HR BIS, (ii) implementing a specialized recruitment system with a test module, (iii) implementing a combination of specialized systems, and (iv) implementing a Software as a Service (SaaS). Based on the POIs and DT strategies, the TO-BE state is modeled using ArchiMate. Figure 3 illustrates the optimized HR process #1, supported by the chosen strategy, represented by BIS. Similarly, Figure 4 indicates the TO-BE state for HR process #2.

Table 2. DT strategies comparison

Factor	Comprehensive HRIS	Specialized ATS with Testing Module	Combination of Specialized Systems	SaaS Solution
Coverage of "Receipt and Management Application"	Comprehensive	Advanced	Very good	Good
Coverage of "Testing of Applicant"	Variable	Limited	Very good	Limited *)
Initial Costs	Very high	Medium	Medium to high	Low **)
Annual Operating Costs	High	Medium (10-15% of purchase price)	Medium to high	High ***)
Implementation Time	12-24 months	3-9 months	6-12 months	1-3 months
Degree of Customization	Medium	Medium to high	High (for each process)	Low
IT Infrastructure Requirements	High	Medium	Medium to high	Minimal
Legislative Preparedness	Good	Very good	Variable (depends on systems)	Variable +)
Data Security	Very high	High	Medium (integration risks)	Variable +)
Compliance with Public Administration Requirements	Comprehensive solution, general	Specialized, better reflecting PS specifics	Potentially very good with proper selection	Low
Integration Options with DC2	Comprehensive, but demanding	Good	Variable, potentially complicated	Limited
User-Friendliness	Variable	Good (specialized interface)	Inconsistent	Very good
Gradual Implementation	Limited	Good	Very good	Good

Legend: *) requires integration, **) 50-200 k. CZK, ***) regular payments, 150-500 k. CZK annually, +) often requires adjustments

Figure 3. TO-BE state of HR process #1

Figure 4. TO-BE state of HR process #2

Answer to RQ#1: EA approach extends beyond the documentation of AS-IS state by facilitating the design of TO-BE state that addresses the identified inefficiencies. Using ArchiMate, TO-BE models were developed for both HR process #1 and HR process #2, incorporating digital solutions that directly respond to the POIs identified in the AS-IS analysis. For example, the TO-BE model for HR process #1 integrates BIS to automate document archiving and qualification verification. In contrast, the TO-BE model for HR process #2 includes digital tools for testing and evaluation.

Answer to RQ#2: The EA approach extends beyond the documentation of the AS-IS state by facilitating the design of TO-BE state, which addresses the identified inefficiencies. Using ArchiMate, the TO-BE models were developed for both HR process #1 and HR process #2, incorporating digital solutions that directly respond to the POIs identified in the AS-IS analysis. For example, the TO-BE model for HR process #1 integrates BIS to automate document archiving and qualification verification, while the TO-BE model for HR process #2 includes digital tools for testing and evaluation. **Answer to RQ#3:** The documentation of AS-IS and the design of the TO-BE HRM processes play a pivotal role in guiding the selection and implementation of BIS within the broader context of DT. The AS-IS analysis provides a detailed understanding of existing inefficiencies and manual operations, while the TO-BE models propose optimized workflows supported by ICT.

A comprehensive comparison table (Table 2) was created to evaluate individual approaches systematically based on defined criteria. The criteria were selected through a structured analysis of requirements for implementing technological solutions. It considered the nature of HRM processes, PA specifics, and general BIS implementation principles. The factors were divided into four main categories: (i) functional requirements, (ii) economic requirements, (iii) technology, and (iv) organization. This multidimensional approach ensured comprehensive coverage of all relevant aspects influencing the success of implementing solutions.

5. Discussion and conclusion

This article integrates interdisciplinary findings and our research, clarifying EA's role in digital transformation and HRM process optimization. Using ArchiMate, it models City Hall's HRM processes in AS-IS and TO-BE states, identifying points of interest and proposing a DT strategy. Comparing IT solutions, a specialized ATS with a testing module emerged as optimal. EA and ArchiMate proved effective for analyzing and designing HRM optimization, aligning with NAP for potential transferability to other public administration institutions. HRM digitalization is vital for modernizing City Hall and broader Czech public administration, though solutions must consider the organizational context. Further research should address barriers to optimization via DT and EA.

6. Limitations and call for further research

The article has several limitations. Firstly, detailed information is omitted due to page constraints, presenting only conclusions. Secondly, the case study focuses on a single municipal authority near Prague. Thirdly, the HRM processes examined are specific to employee onboarding and do not cover all legally required parts of HRM processes. Further research is recommended to (i) expand the case study to other processes using the EA approach and ArchiMate modeling, (ii) broaden the scope to other similarly sized PA institutions, (iii) review & conduct international case studies for comparison.

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CURRENT DEVELOPMENTS IN THE INDUSTRY FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE RUBBER PROCESSING SECTOR

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Abstract

The European rubber industry is facing pressure to become more efficient, sustainable and competitive, with digitisation becoming a key tool in this transformation. The study poses the question: What specific digital technologies are being implemented in the European rubber industry and what is their impact on the competitiveness of the sector? The analysis assesses the current state of implementation of digital solutions and their benefits in terms of production processes, quality management, logistics and product development. The key technologies include the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), MES and ERP systems, artificial intelligence, digital twins, and advanced automation. The paper also discusses barriers to the spread of digitisation, such as high entry costs, lack of IT professionals and cultural resistance. Based on available data and case studies, the author concludes that digitisation is a crucial tool for sustainable future development of the European rubber sector and its adaptation to changing market and environmental conditions.

1. Introduction

European industry finds itself in a profound structural transformation driven by technological progress, changing market demands, climate commitments and geopolitical challenges. It accounts for 20% of the EU's economy and employs around 35 million people. European industry's global competitive advantage lies in high value-added products and services. Its innovation capacity makes it a world leader in terms of the number of patents. Key trends include digitisation of production, process automation, growing emphasis on data analytics, support for sustainability and integration of artificial intelligence. Industrial businesses across sectors are looking for ways to be faster, more flexible, greener and at the same time more resilient to unpredictable external influences. The ever-changing geopolitical situation, rise in global competition, protectionist policies and frequent market disturbances pose challenges for a rules-based system. In this context, digital technologies are becoming not an optional extra but an indispensable part of the competitive strategy (European Commission, 2020).

The rubber industry represents a specific segment of the European manufacturing sector, and is closely linked to the automotive, engineering, construction and healthcare branches. Manufacturing processes are distinguished by their high material and energy intensity and inputs required, complex chemistry, and the requirements for accuracy, safety and reproducibility of results. At the same time, the industry still is in many ways dependent on traditional production management methods, which makes it vulnerable at a time of increasing pressure for transparency, traceability, efficiency and environmental responsibility (Sandu, 2023, page 2-3). While some other industries have already partially undergone digital transformation, the rubber sector is only at the beginning of this journey. Companies are faced with questions as to which technologies have real benefits for them, how to reconcile digitisation with the particularities of rubber processing, how to finance investments and at the same time navigate the change in corporate culture and qualifications of workforce. In particular, the issue of financing digitisation projects along with the acquisition of qualified staff poses a barrier that is in many ways difficult to overcome. There is also a lack of systematic mapping of which specific digital technologies are already being implemented in practice and what is their transformative potential in the European context. This is the focus of this article. It aims to analyse available literature and technology resources to identify the digital technologies with the greatest potential to transform the European rubber industry in the coming years. The study focuses on areas such as the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), advanced data analytics, MES/ERP systems, predictive maintenance, digital twins and the use of artificial intelligence. It refers to expert articles, technical reports, market analyses and industry whitepapers published in recent years and not least the author's substantial amount of practical experience.

2. The position of the rubber industry in the European context

The rubber industry is an integral part of the European manufacturing sector, albeit its importance is often overlooked. The industry is a key supplier of components to a wide range of other industries, in particular automotive, construction, healthcare, rail, energy, food and defence. The specific properties of rubber such as elasticity, chemical resilience, resistance to extreme temperatures and insulating properties, make this material indispensable in many technical applications. More than 70% of its output is accounted for by tyre production, which has historically been the dominant segment, but the importance of technical rubber outside transport applications is growing steadily - for example in healthcare, automation or renewable energy.

According to Eurostat, the production of plastic and rubber products accounts for around 8% of the entire industrial output sold by the European Union. This share corresponds to approximately 55,700 active businesses employing about 1.65 million people in the sector. These companies are part of the wider manufacturing industries, with rubber and plastics manufacturing being an important part of the economy both in terms of employment and value added. The main producers within the EU are Germany, Italy, France, Poland and Spain, with Poland in particular profiling itself as a key production hub for rubber and plastic products in recent years, thanks to a combination of favourable geographical location, growing technological capacities and competitive production costs (Eurostat, 2023). Together, these countries form the backbone of European rubber production and host the headquarters of many key international players (e.g. Continental, Pirelli, Michelin, Nokian, Semperit). At the same time, Europe also is a major exporter, with much of its production going to markets outside the EU, notably the United States, England, Turkey, China and Japan. This export orientation drives quality and innovation but also makes the European rubber industry vulnerable to geopolitical fluctuations, protectionism or supply chain disruptions. In 2024, the total value of EU exports of rubber products was US\$ 23.19 billion, corresponding to approximately 0.83% of the EU's total export volumes of US\$ 2.80 trillion. Although this is a relatively low share, exports of rubber

products represent a quantifiable part of EU's foreign trade. However, it should be stressed out that a substantial part of rubber production is used in more complex products, mainly in the automotive industry, which is among the EU's key export sectors. In 2024, automotive exports reached the value of US\$ 292.75 billion, equivalent to around 10% of total EU exports. (Trading Economics, 2025).

Despite its steady economic importance, the industry faces considerable pressures from various areas. One of the key restrictive factors is the long-term dependence on raw petroleum materials, which are used, among other things, to produce synthetic rubber, the manufacturing of which is highly energy intensive. Rising energy prices as a result of the energy crisis, which peaked in 2022-2023, have significantly impacted the cost structures, especially for smaller producers. The importance of synthetic rubber is steadily on the increase, particularly due to the high price volatility of natural rubber. A further complication is the dependence on imports of natural rubber from geographically distant areas, notably tropical regions where it is harvested from rubber trees (*Hevea brasiliensis*). The growth in demand for rubber is also driven by rising mobility, in particular within the European Union, with 80% of the world's natural rubber production coming from smallholders, further adding to the risk of instability in the supply chain. Logistical and transport difficulties in importing from major producers such as Thailand, Indonesia and Vietnam also pose significant challenges. Also and not least, the negative effects of climate change must be taken into account, which can significantly affect yield and regularity of rubber harvesting in these regions (Laroche et al., 2022, page 2). Simultaneously, environmental regulations are increasing - for example, the European REACH regulation restricts the use of certain chemicals (PAHs, nitrosamines, aromatic compounds), and new EU emission targets are pushing manufacturers to reduce their carbon footprint (Official Journal of the European Union, 2025). These pressures are forcing companies to look for new, more sustainable entry materials and more efficient manufacturing processes.

One of the key challenges for the rubber sector are demographic trends - like other industries, the European rubber manufacturing is facing the issues of shortage of skilled workers, ageing technical staff and low interest among the younger generations in traditional manufacturing branches. These conditions complicate the adoption of modern technologies and often hinder the ability of businesses to adapt to the digital transformation, which requires specific expert skills. Despite these obstacles, the European rubber sector still maintains its position as one of the most technologically advanced in the world. Unlike their Asian competitors, who often rely on cheap labour and mass production, European companies emphasise quality, innovation, precision and reliability. These strengths provide a solid foundation European rubber companies can build on in their transition towards the Industry 4.0 model.

The digitisation of the rubber industry, which follows from the above Industry 4.0 model - including automation of production, implementation of systems such as ERP, MES or LIM, use of analytical tools, artificial intelligence, big data or predictive maintenance - is a key way to increase production efficiency, reduce scrap, shorten time-to-market and respond more flexibly to customer needs (Brodny & Tutak, 2021a, page 5–6). However, the uptake of these technologies is still very uneven across the sector. While leading market players, especially multinationals, are already implementing pilot projects and developing digitised operations, most small and medium-sized enterprises are lagging behind - mainly due to a lack of investments, limited personnel capacities or the absence of a long-term strategy. If the sector is to survive in the face of rising global competition and global uncertainties as well as growing demands for sustainability, it will be crucial to harness the potential of digitisation as a means to transform production and management processes that provides a significant competitive advantage. This is the only way to remain competitive and relevant in Europe's changing industrial ecosystem.

3. The state of European industry and its digitisation

European industry has been facing fundamental challenges in recent years that are reshaping its nature and mode of operation. In the wake of the Covid crisis, the energy shock and supply chain disruptions, it is increasingly becoming clear that traditional manufacturing models based on cheap labour, linear production and intensive globalisation are no longer sustainable in the long term. The EU is responding to these changes with a series of strategic initiatives to strengthen the resilience, innovation potential and digital maturity of its industrial base. In this respect, digitisation is seen as a crucial tool not only for modernising production, but also to reinforce competitiveness, security of supply and environmental sustainability. (Brodny & Tutak, 2021b, page 2).

The Digital Europe strategy is a key framework for this transformation. Digital Agenda for Europe specifically is the EU's first investment instrument to support digital transformation, with a budget for the period 2021-2027 of €8 billion. It focuses on areas such as AI, cybersecurity, advanced digital skills, high-performance computing, Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), cloud computing, cyber-physical systems, digital twins and predictive analytics. The programme funds European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) and Artificial Intelligence Testing and Experimentation Facilities (AI TEFs). EDIHs, as coordinated non-profit consortia, are tasked with providing maximum support for the digital transformation of businesses and public sector organisations at the regional level. The existence of more than 300 European Digital Hubs covering all regions of the European Union is meant to provide services such as training, skills development, pre-investment testing, access to innovation and help in finding investment. AI TEFs offer a combination of physical and virtual facilities in which developers can test the latest AI-based software and hardware solutions (Digital Agenda for Europe, 2025). The Digital Europe strategy framework is complemented by a number of other legislative acts, strategic documents and programmes developed and adopted by the European Union, such as: "European broadband: Investing in digitally driven growth", "Towards a thriving data-driven economy", "A Strategy for the Digital Single Market", "Building the European Data Economy", "The Information Society", "The Age of Artificial Intelligence: Towards a European Strategy for Human-Centric Machines" and "Digital Agenda for Europe" (EUR-Lex, 2025).

According to the European Commission's report under the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI 2024), significant disparities persist in the extent and pace of digitisation across EU Member States, as well as between businesses of different sizes. Available data shows that on average, 30.40% of large enterprises (i.e. with more than 250 employees) use artificial intelligence (AI), while for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) the figure is only at 7.40%. A similar trend can be observed also in the adoption of cloud-based solutions: Cloud services are used by 69.60% of large enterprises as opposed to 37.90% for SMEs. There are also substantial differences in the use of digital data analytics - 71.70% for large enterprises versus 32.00% for SMEs. Electronic data sharing is widespread in 86.30% of large enterprises, while for SMEs it is only 42.00%. As already mentioned, the overall maturity of individual Member States is also an important factor affecting the level of digitisation. The highest digitisation rates among small and medium-sized enterprises (10-249 employees) have Finland (85.60%), Sweden (79.90%) and the Netherlands (78.60%). At the other end of the scale are Slovakia (42.20%), Bulgaria (28.40%) and Romania (26.80%). The overall EU average for the share of firms with at least a basic level of digital intensity is 57.70% (DESI indicators, 2025). The causes of the above disparities are traceable to several key areas. One of the main factors is the different regional access to digital technologies, which is a function of the level of development of digital infrastructure and connectivity. Furthermore, the availability of workforce with adequate digital and ICT competences plays an important role, which is closely linked to the quality and focus of the education system towards promoting digital skills. The ability of actors, both from the corporate sector and the public sphere, to effectively mobilise and exploit potential investments in digitisation

is also an important aspect. However, the possibilities to draw on financial support from local governments are often limited by the degree of maturity of the institutional framework and the efficiency of local public administrations, with administrative capacities and red tape being a significant restrictive factor. Another important factor shaping the level of digitisation and innovation capacity of countries is the amount of gross domestic expenditure on R&D (as a percentage of GDP). This indicator is a key economic parameter that reflects the strategic approach of individual states to fostering innovation and boosting their international competitiveness. Sweden is among the leaders in this area with these expenditures reaching 4% of GDP, followed by Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Austria and Finland, where it is around 3%. At the other end of the range is Romania, which allocates less than 1% of its GDP to R&D, indicative of significantly lower support for innovation activities (Brodny & Tutak, 2022, page 22–27).

However, digitisation is not just about technology, but also about changing the way of thinking about production and management processes. In many companies, digital tools are still seen as an add-on to existing structures as opposed to an opportunity to completely reshape value creation processes. Still, many companies are beginning to harness the potential of digital technologies to achieve measurable advantages: reducing costs, increasing efficiency, cutting lead times and scrap and improving traceability and flexibility in delivery. Within the context of the European rubber industry, digitisation is advancing at a slower pace than in mature industries such as automotive or electronics. While some large corporations (e.g. Michelin, Continental, Pirelli, Nokian) are investing in the digitisation of production lines, quality monitoring using sensoric data or predictive maintenance, the vast majority of medium and smaller rubber companies are struggling with limits - limited investment budgets, lack of qualified IT staff, absence of a long-term digitisation strategy and poor experience with return on these investments. Despite this, there are also positive examples of the implementation of digital solutions in the sector: the use of camera systems to inspect the surface of vulcanised parts, real-time monitoring of moulding parameters, optimisation of compounding with the use of MES systems, or digitisation of documentation and manufacturing reports using cloud-based solutions. These achievements testify that even a more conservative industry such as rubber manufacturing can benefit significantly from digitisation - especially in the aspects of quality, efficiency and responsiveness.

Another driving factor are environmental regulations. Digital technologies facilitate more accurate measurement and management of energy consumption, emissions and waste, which is key to meeting ESG objectives, CSR reporting and passing environmental audits. For example, monitoring energy consumption for specific machines and production batches or predictive optimisation of production batches in terms of waste are becoming not only a technical necessity, but also a marketing tool and a competitive advantage. One example is the unique project of Nokian Tyres, which has built the world's first zero-carbon emissions tyre production plant in Romania (Oradea) during 2022-2025. The operation of the plant is completely decoupled from energy produced from fossil fuels, allowing to reach emission neutrality in both direct and indirect emissions. The investment cost was EUR 650 million (2025). The latest revolutionary technologies have been used, including the much-discussed use of digital technology to increase production quality and efficiency while adhering to strict environmental standards. This level of environmental performance was achieved through a comprehensive set of technological and organisational measures. All the electricity used at the plant comes from CO₂-free sources, with part of the consumption covered by the plant's own on-site solar installations. The rest is supplied under a long-term contract with the renewable energy provider Enery. An important part of the plant's energy infrastructure are innovative electric boilers used in the curing process, replacing traditional fossil fuel-based steam sources. These boilers are powered exclusively by emission-free electricity. The entire manufacturing process has been designed with an

emphasis on maximum energy efficiency, using the most advanced technologies and automated systems available (Nokian Tyres, 2025).

The digitisation of European industries consequently is not just a technological trend but a strategic process that is redefining the very basics of industrial production. Applied to the rubber sector, this is not a revolution, but a gradual and vital transformation that will determine whether European companies can compete and survive globally in the face of the current geopolitical instability.

4. Overview of current digital technologies in the rubber industry

The digital transformation of the rubber industry has been gradual and uneven. While some technologies have already become a common part of manufacturing processes in large companies, others are still in the pilot phase or remain on the fringes, mainly due to high initial investments needed or lack of expert capacities. In this part, key groups of digital technologies of current or future relevance to the rubber industry in Europe are presented.

4.1 Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) and sensorics

IIoT is one of the principal pillars of Industry 4.0. In the rubber industry context, it enables to interlink machines, sensors and production data in real time. Sensors monitor key parameters - temperature, pressure, curing time, compound moisture, machine vibrations or energy consumption. This data is used to improve process stability, reduce scrap and for better maintenance planning. A typical example is monitoring mould temperatures and moulding pressures in curing presses. If any of the parameters leaves the set range, the system can warn the operator in time or automatically adjust the machine settings. IIoT thus promotes better quality and traceability while reducing losses in operation.

The Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) combines two distinct spheres of technology: *information technology (IT)* and *operational technology (OT)*. This means that there is a need for a higher degree of interoperability, meaning also more standards than in a non-industrial environment. Standardisation efforts are necessary to ensure that devices and applications from different countries can exchange information with each other. Standards of various types, such as communication, identification or security norms used in IoT, can be the main drivers for the spread of IoT technologies. Many organisations are also directing their efforts at simplifying the current complexity of the standard ecosystem and laying the groundwork for a clearer system of standards. These include the Industrial Internet Consortium (IIC), the Open Connectivity Foundation (OCF), and the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), which operates several workgroups. In the United States, three industry groups - the Open Platform Communication (OPC) Foundation, the Organization for Machine Automation and Control (OMAC), and PLCopen - are collaborating to "develop and promote common standards", bringing together their former separate activities and moving towards a more unified and interoperable future (Tern PLC, 2025). The OPC Foundation, which is one of the best known groups, has created a framework called Unified Architecture (UA) that serves as an industry framework for interoperability. It aims to offer "information modelling with integrated security, access rights and complete communication layers to provide plug-and-play machine-to-machine (M2M) communication inside factories". The framework is also designed to be scalable from the manufacturing operations level all the way up to the enterprise IT infrastructure and cloud environments. This allows engineering capacities to be used for higher-input enterprise management activities. Today, there are more than 5,200 vendors that have created over 42,000 different OPC products used in more than 52 million applications. The estimated savings in engineering capacities alone can be quantified in billions of dollars (OPC Foundation, 2025). The main reasons for the

introduction and wider use of the OPC UA standard in the plastics and rubber industry are as follows: it enables the implementation of the Smart Manufacturing concept, it contributes to reducing the complexity of communication between devices and machines (thus increasing the overall efficiency of systems), it is compatible with both legacy systems, new machines and production lines, it is multi-platform, is not a proprietary format, and is able to receive and interpret multiple data points from different sources (Bosi et al., 2020, page 4). Founded in 1964, Euromap is an umbrella organisation of national associations of plastics and rubber machinery manufacturers at the European level. This industry segment accounts for around 40% of global production and around 50% of global exports in this field. Euromap represents approximately 500 companies specialising in the production of equipment for the plastics and rubber industry, along the entire technology chain - from pre-processing through the main manufacturing process to post-processing (Euromap, 2025). In the context of the Industry 4.0 initiative, Euromap has long been active in the development of communication interfaces to interlink machinery with higher-level information systems. The output of these efforts is the Euromap 77 standard, which defines the interface for data exchange between injection moulding machines (presses) and Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES). This standard is based on OPC UA technology and is a modern replacement for the previously used Euromap 63 format, which used data transfer via text files and is now considered technologically obsolete. Thanks to the Euromap77 standard, machines from different manufacturers can be easily interlinked to monitor process quality and collect production data. However, given the long service life of manufacturing equipment, Euromap 63 will remain relevant in many operations for years to come. It is specifically this technological longevity that presents one of the key challenges of digitising manufacturing operations, as it requires the simultaneous consideration of both new and legacy standards and their integration into a unified and compatible data environment across different generations of technology (Bosi et al., 2020, page 5).

In 2018, the Plastic & Rubber 4.0 initiative was launched, a European project aimed at promoting the digitisation and automation of manufacturing processes in the plastics and rubber industry in line with the Industry 4.0 principles. One of the key outputs of this initiative was the creation of the OpenPlast platform, which enables interoperable communication between manufacturing equipment and higher-level systems (e.g. MES and ERP) via industry communication standards such as OPC UA and Euromap 77. This platform was developed by SOAG Europe Group (Mecspe, 2025). The project also included the creation of the OpenLink IIoT gateway, built on the Eclipse Kura framework, which provides real-time production data collection and processing. This architecture supports the implementation of predictive maintenance strategies and optimisation of manufacturing operations. The third key element was integration with cloud services, enabling centralised data storage in cloud-based repositories and its subsequent analysis via business intelligence tools. This analysis is used for advanced modelling of manufacturing processes, evaluation of operational efficiency and optimisation of production planning (Bosi et al., 2020, page 6–9).

4.2 MES systems and integration with ERP

Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES) are a key element of modern industrial digitisation, as they facilitate real-time monitoring and control of manufacturing operations. In the context of the rubber industry, they provide detailed monitoring of individual batches, documentation of the compounds used, accurate recording of production cycles and evaluation of efficiency of the use of production equipment, for example through the overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) indicator. MES integrate process data from operations with ERP-type enterprise information systems covering production planning, inventory management, purchasing and logistics. This horizontal and vertical integration of data flows is an essential prerequisite for the comprehensive digitisation of manufacturing enterprises (International Society of Automation, 2025). One of the recognised reference frameworks

for structuring digital manufacturing systems is the model developed by the International Society of Automation (ISA), which, as a non-profit professional organisation, defines standards in the field of industrial automation. The ISA-95 standard defines in detail the interfaces between the enterprise and manufacturing levels, including the specifications of MES functionalities, the structure of data models and the rules for information exchange between the different layers. This standard is considered a fundamental tool for building interoperable production structures (MEScenter, 2025). The MESA-11 supplemental model (defined by the Manufacturing Enterprise Solutions Association) further specifies the scope of MES system functions, including but not limited to manufacturing operations planning, resource allocation, manufacturing unit dispatching, manufacturing documentation management, product traceability, performance evaluation, workforce management, equipment maintenance, quality management, and manufacturing process control. Together, these components facilitate effective production control in a digital factory environment (Smart Factory). The above models thus provide a systematic framework for the design, implementation and optimisation of production systems in accordance with the Industry 4.0 principles (Mohamed & Alraddadi, 2024, page 1–3).

Enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems are used in the rubber industry as tools for integrated business process management. They contribute to improving operational efficiency, optimising production flows, reducing material waste and ensuring compliance with environmental and quality standards. At the same time, ERP systems are consistently among the top five areas of investment in enterprise information infrastructure. ERP implementation is a highly complex and multitiered process that requires fundamental changes in both the organisational structure and the technical assets of the company. The deployment of these systems is often accompanied by various risks, including staff resistance to change, project management deficiencies, limited engagement of key stakeholders, insufficient end-user training, difficulties in integration with existing information systems and not least performance problems of the solutions themselves. As a result of such complications, ERP system implementations often entail high failure rates and frequent failures to meet planned budgets and timeframes. Successful ERP implementation thus requires executing a number of technically demanding tasks, including detailed data configuration, adapting it to the specific requirements of the enterprise and performing conversion operations between disparate data structures and formats. (Nakayama et al., 2024, page 1–3). An ERP application may implement, for example, a green procurement system according to ISO 14001, which is a solution for selecting materials and services to identify green suppliers and attributes of green materials with minimal environmental impact, while at the same time benefitting the company economically. Based on an ERP system, this application is then used to generate Key Performance Indicator (KPI) reports for suppliers, thus aiding the company in monitoring business processes in the area of green procurement, which plays a key role particularly in the rubber industry in product environmental impact declarations (Karlina et al., 2019, page 1-3). Nevertheless many, especially SMEs, do not yet have this level of interconnection - often due to the high cost of implementation or limited functionality of existing ERP systems.

4.3 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in the rubber industry is not yet at the level common in other branches, such as automotive or electronics. Nevertheless, this is an area with significant potential for streamlining production processes. AI encompasses various technological approaches, such as machine and deep learning, neural networks or predictive analytics, each of which offers its own specific benefits in the areas of production management, optimisation and automation.

Machine learning facilitates analysing large volumes of manufacturing data to identify recurring patterns, predict trends in key parameters and adjust process settings for better efficiency and lower material losses. It can also be used in quality assurance where based on historical data, risky

production phases can be identified early on, or in compounding processes, where algorithms help optimise the dosing of entry materials.

Predictive maintenance is one of the best practical value applications of AI in rubber manufacturing. Using sensor data (e.g. vibrations, temperature, power consumption) and advanced analytics, estimates are possible on the likelihood of wear or failure of machinery well in time. This approach allows to plan service interventions much more accurately while minimising unplanned downtime. In practice, predictive maintenance most often finds use for equipment such as curing presses, mixers or extruders, where in some companies it has already replaced the traditional reactive maintenance models and effectively brought demonstrable cost reductions and better operational reliability. (Deepan et al., 2024, page 1–6). A key challenge remains ensuring data of sufficient quality and relevance and its correct interpretation. Still, it can be concluded that the implementation of AI in maintenance not only reduces operating costs, but also extends the life of the equipment and improves the overall efficiency of the manufacturing processes.

Rubber compound formulation using advanced AI-based methods in the design and preparation of rubber compounds enables detailed analyses of manufacturing conditions, raw material inputs and relevant historical records. Machine learning can use this data to identify optimal combinations of compounding ingredients, including the appropriate ratio of base polymers, fillers, additives and vulcanising agents. The aim is to achieve the target physical and mechanical properties such as high elasticity, mechanical strength or long-term durability. The implementation of these data-driven approaches helps improve the functional quality of the resulting product, reduces material consumption and promotes more efficient use of resources throughout the manufacturing process.

Intelligent forming processes in rubber manufacturing such as extrusion, moulding or calendering result in significant improvements in operational efficiency credit to the implementation of automation technologies and AI-enabled robotic systems. Advanced AI-driven computer vision systems enable fully automated visual inspections, ensuring precise dimensional tolerances and early detection of manufacturing defects. The use of image recognition algorithms in conjunction with neural networks further allows for continuous monitoring of processes and immediate adjustments to the process parameters in real time. This approach ensures higher reproducibility of the resulting products while at the same time reducing the rate of defective production.

Quality assurance and automated detection of defects with the implementation of AI-enabled computer vision systems represent an advanced approach to quality control in rubber product manufacturing. These technologies enable reliable identification of surface defects, structural defects and manufacturing irregularities with a high degree of accuracy. Neural networks trained on annotated image data facilitate automatic classification of products based on predefined quality criteria, ensuring that only products that meet the required standards enter the sales chain. Real-time defect detection also allows for immediate interventions in the ongoing manufacturing process, which helps to reduce rework volumes and to achieve an overall improvement in production quality. (Sandu, 2023, page 2–6).

Digital twins for virtual simulations and optimisation are an advanced tool for virtual modelling of manufacturing processes, capable of monitoring, simulations and optimisation in real time. By creating digital replicas of actual operations in rubber manufacturing, process flows can be effectively analysed and different scenarios can be tested without interfering with real production. The digital twins, which additionally incorporate artificial intelligence algorithms, allow predictive simulations, identification of optimal production parameters and timely responses to operational deviations. This approach helps to reduce time to market while promoting continuous improvement in manufacturing efficiency through feedback learning and adaptive process control (Qazi et al., 2022, page 1–3).

Adaptive process control and optimisation is an advanced tool for dynamically adjusting process parameters based on desired target product characteristics and changing operating or environmental conditions. Reinforcement learning (RL) allows to optimise variables such as curing cycle length, temperature or pressure settings through repeated interactions with the production environment. This type of algorithmic control uses feedback to continuously improve the manufacturing process efficiency and rationalise resource consumption, while experiential learning takes place. The implementation of RL thus enables real-time autonomous adaptive control, which is a key aspect of modern intelligent manufacturing systems (Sandu, 2023, page 5).

By leveraging AI technologies, rubber manufacturers can achieve high operational efficiency and superior quality product output and drive the continuous innovative development of the industry as a whole. Understanding these application areas is a prerequisite for fully leveraging the transformational potential of AI in streamlining manufacturing processes and systematically reinforcing global competitiveness.

4.4 Robotization and automation of production lines

Rubber product manufacturing is a comprehensive entirety of technological operations with output designed for a wide range of applications, from consumer goods through various industrial and automotive components up to construction parts. These processes historically have been heavily reliant on manual labour, which makes them susceptible to operational hazards such as occupational accidents, ergonomic strain and exposure to hazardous substances. Typical hazards of manual activities in rubber processing include handling heavy loads, working with chemicals, operating energy-intensive machinery, exposure to noise and vibrations, and long-term physical overload of workers. These factors pose a significant challenge in terms of occupational safety while also limiting production capacity and output quality. The implementation of robotic systems in rubber production consequently presents a significant opportunity to boost productivity, safety and technological maturity of plants. Robotization brings benefits such as fatigue-free continuous operation, high precision and repeatability of operations, the ability to adapt quickly to changes in manufacturing programmes, more efficient use of raw materials and easy scalability of production according to current demand. As stated by author (Anumandla & Tejani, 2023, page 6–9), robotic automation has the potential to significantly improve the operational performance of rubber manufacturing plants, in particular through cutback on physically demanding operations, improved safety standards, more efficient quality control, reduced production costs and faster return on investment, with technological integration and long-term development prospects playing a key role in the process. According to author (Mohammed et al., 2018, page 10–12), the implementation of automated material handling systems led to a 30% increase in production throughput and a 50% reduction in material transfer times. In injection moulding, the use of robotic part removal shortened the production cycle by 15% and precise automation of trimming reduced scrap by 50%. The implementation of computer vision-based robotic inspection achieved 95% accuracy in defect detection, with a 20% reduction in rework costs. In addition, there was an 80% reduction in the number of defective products reaching customers, along with a 30% drop in quality-related complaints. In assembly operations, the deployment of robotic arms led to a 25% reduction in assembly times and 99.9% assembly accuracy, reinforcing the importance of robotics as a both quality and performance enhancing tool.

Robotic technologies show high potential for applications in rubber manufacturing, in particular in material handling, injection moulding, quality control and defect detection. Their integration aids operational efficiency, accuracy and consistency of outputs. Persistent challenges, such as costs, technical complexity and human-machine coordination, can be overcome by targeted investments in training and education, fostering innovations and continuously developing the regulatory framework. Close cooperation between industry, government and academia is key. Robotic-assisted quality

control thus presents not only a tool for more efficient production, but also a change in approach to quality as a systemic priority, potentially aiding the rubber industry to reinforce its position in the global market.

4.5 Cloud solutions

With the increasing digitisation of manufacturing processes, automation progress and the induction of remote control of operations, cloud solutions and cybersecurity topics are becoming vitally important for the rubber industry. Although research specifically focused on rubber manufacturing is still limited, insights can be used from broader studies on cloud computing and cybersecurity that are relevant and applicable in this context.

Cloud computing is a model for providing IT services including database systems, software applications, analytical tools, network infrastructure and other digital resources. The model allows for efficient innovation and the exploitation of economies of scale. The key principle of the technology is storage and management of data on remote servers accessed via the Internet. Cloud systems provide on-demand computing capacity, including application services, data repositories and processing power. An important component is the possibility of predictive maintenance based on operating data analyses, allowing early identification of technical issues and quickly addressing them through optimisation of personnel capacities.

The industrial cloud serves as a dedicated virtual environment for the operation and control of industrial applications. The providers of these services are developing software solutions, including Internet of Things (IoT) monitoring tools, that are optimised for both mobile devices and web interfaces. Cloud architectures also support the integration of application programming interfaces (APIs) that enable automated processing and standardisation of data from diverse manufacturing sources.

Edge computing is a technology that facilitates local processing of data directly at the point of origin - typically through sensors, industrial robots, machinery or mobile terminals. This decentralised computing capacity enables real-time analyses, thus speeding up system response, reducing the load on communication networks and contributing to increased security. Collaborative cloud ecosystems are emerging in vital parts of industries to provide a comprehensive infrastructure for integrating and managing distributed devices. The cloud architecture also provides a scalable environment for the operation of edge platforms that control the operation of autonomous and specialised robotic systems implemented directly on site in manufacturing plants (Adel, 2022, page 5–7).

Cloud platforms thus facilitate centralised access to data, provide remote control of manufacturing processes and facilitate the integration of various enterprise systems such as MES, ERP or SCADA. However, they also entail risks, mainly in the area of cybersecurity. In the rubber sector, which often works with sensitive formulations and know-how, systemic security is essential. Implementation of cloud solutions here takes place cautiously and more often in the form of hybrid models (combinations of on-premises and cloud services)(Krishnamoorthy & Umarani, 2023, page 1–3).

5. Future potential of digital technologies in the European rubber industry

The European rubber industry is on the verge of a major transformation, the essence of which is the gradual but vital digitisation. Given its complex manufacturing structures, high demands for quality, safety and environmental responsibility, the rubber industry is a very specific segment that must respond to both technological, economic and regulatory challenges. Although digitisation in this sector is progressing more slowly than in the automotive or electrical engineering branches, the digital

technologies identified positively entail high transformational potential. The Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) can be considered a key vehicle of this transformation. Its interconnection of machines, sensors and data platforms enables detailed monitoring of production parameters in real time. This approach improves process stability, reduces scrap and promotes predictive manufacturing control. In addition, standards such as OPC UA or Euromap77 ensure interoperability across devices from different manufacturers. Combined with cloud computing and edge architectures, this opens a path to decentralised but secure data processing. MES and ERP systems aid horizontal and vertical integration of manufacturing and control processes. MES systems enable detailed batch tracking, quality control, OEE calculations or production formula management. Coupled with ERP, planning, logistics and supply operations are optimised. Real-time interconnection of these systems not only ensures greater efficiency but also a higher level of compliance with environmental standards, in particular in the area of green procurement. One of the most forward-leaning areas is the use of artificial intelligence (AI). AI finds use in production data analysis, compounding optimisation, predictive maintenance or defect identification using computer vision. Machine and deep learning algorithms can reduce new product development times, increase process reproducibility and reduce manufacturing losses. Furthermore, the deployment of digital twins enables testing and optimisation without the need for physical interventions, which speeds up time to market. Robotization and automation of production lines are the way to improve safety at work, precision of operations and overall productivity. The reduction of manual operations not only means better working conditions, but also better stability and predictability of production output. Examples from foreign projects (e.g. Nokian Tyres) show that fully automated plants with a zero emission footprint are not just a flight of fantasy but an attainable goal. Cloud solutions that provide centralised data management, facilitate remote monitoring of operations and streamline decision-making processes also are a vital aid. Cybersecurity also plays an important role, as the rubber industry works with sensitive data and know-how. Trends are moving towards hybrid models that combine local infrastructures with cloud services and enable secure and scalable management of enterprise systems. However, the transformative potential of digital technologies cannot be realised without a concurrent change in management thinking, risk friendliness in how investments are approached and a systematic support for staff training and education. High entry costs, cultural barriers and lack of IT resources still hinder widespread implementation. Nevertheless, it can be concluded that companies that are already actively implementing digitisation are seeing measurable benefits in terms of efficiency, quality, environmental performance and ability to respond to market fluctuations.

6. Conclusion

The current European rubber industry is going through a major transformation phase, the scope of which goes well beyond the scope of digitisation initiatives alone. This transformation is precipitated by a combination of factors including rising commodity prices, the volatile energy market and the deteriorating geopolitical climate. Major industry players such as Goodyear, Continental, Michelin or Bridgestone are implementing radical restructuring measures ranging from closing production sites in Germany and the divestment of some divisions (e.g. Contitech) to moving production capacities to Central and Eastern European countries. Yokohama, is relocating part of its production from the Czech Republic to India, effectively resulting in the closure of its plants in Prague, Zlín and Otrokovice in the former. At the same time, there are growing competitive pressures from Asian producers, with the Chinese company Linglong investing heavily in its plant in Serbia with the aim of establishing itself in the European market through price-competitive offers. These dynamics are fundamentally changing the competitive structure of the entire industry. Restructuring processes affect not only the tyre segment. Trelleborg is abandoning its plants in Hradec Králové and Náchod

(Rubena), both Czech Republic, and even relatively stable compounders such as Hexpol are adapting their strategic direction. Hutchinson has suspended its investment activities as a result of the automotive sector crisis and is preparing a Europe-wide restructuring. A number of rubber and plastics plants, particularly in Germany, have switched to short working hours (Kurzarbeit) in a further sign of the profound nature of the current industrial downturn.

It can thus be concluded that the European rubber sector is not only undergoing a technological, but also and especially a profound structural transformation. The question is no longer whether to implement the transformation, but how to ensure long-term sustainability. A key prerequisite for maintaining competitiveness will be the ability to adapt - whether through better cost efficiency, relocating production capacities or innovations. In this context, digitisation is not an isolated solution, but part of a broader strategy to adapt to the transformation of the manufacturing model of European industry.

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FROM OVERLOAD TO ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE. MAPPING THE DETERMINANTS OF TECHNOSTRESS IN MODERN WORK ENVIRONMENTS

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technostress; digital workplace; artificial intelligence; work-life balance; remote work; employee well-being; digital literacy; organizational support; technological change; occupational health.

Abstract

This paper explores the determinants of technostress in digitally intensive work environments, with a focus on how demographic and organizational factors influence employees' experiences of digital strain, work-life balance, and attitudes toward artificial intelligence. Based on a quantitative survey of 163 respondents across various sectors, the study employs validated scales to measure five key techno-stressors: overload, invasion, complexity, insecurity, and uncertainty. The findings reveal that age, technological proficiency, perceived workplace support, and remote work status significantly affect technostress levels and related outcomes. Notably, higher tech-savviness correlates with more favorable attitudes toward AI, while insufficient support and increased exposure to technology predict poorer work-life balance and heightened stress. Conversely, gender and education were not

found to significantly influence technostress. The results underscore the importance of systemic strategies - beyond individual coping - for managing digital demands and fostering organizational resilience in the age of AI.

1. Introduction and Context

Technostress is a detrimental phenomenon arising from the overuse of information and communication technologies (ICT), which provokes adverse psychological and physiological reactions (Berger et al., 2024).

It can have a range of negative effects on both individuals and organizations. At the individual level, it may lead to disrupted sleep, increased anxiety, depression, job dissatisfaction, and reduced overall well-being. At the organizational level, technostress is associated with lower productivity, higher employee turnover, and greater healthcare costs (Yao & Wang, 2023). Such responses often manifest as feelings of overload, frustration, anxiety, and reduced adaptability to ongoing technological change. This condition results from continuous engagement with complex digital systems and the pressure to respond quickly—often at the expense of natural work-rest rhythms (Mishra & Rašticová, 2024).

1.1 Concept of Technostress

As defined by Giorgi et al. (2022) and Nimrod (2018), techno-stressors can be categorized into five core types:

- *Techno-overload* – when employees are burdened by an excessive number of digital tasks.
- *Techno-invasion* – the encroachment of technology into private life, demanding constant availability.
- *Techno-complexity* – the difficulty of navigating advanced, often unintuitive systems.
- *Techno-insecurity* – anxiety about job loss due to rapid technological progress.
- *Techno-uncertainty* – stress linked to frequent system changes, updates, or malfunctions.

Berger et al. (2024) stress the importance of taking proactive steps to safeguard employees' mental health in digital workplaces. These measures should encompass not only technical interventions but also organizational and psychological approaches that encourage healthier technology use.

The concept of technostress gained scholarly attention in the 1980s, when initial studies examined how early computer systems affected employees' psychological well-being. These early findings focused on information overload and the stress of constant connectivity—issues tied directly to the transition to digital workplaces. With the advent of smartphones, social media, and advanced digital tools, the scope of technostress has grown significantly. It now encompasses not only overload but also the ongoing pressure to adapt to new and often complex technologies and fluctuating work environments (Khlaif et al., 2023).

Due to the accelerating pace of digital innovation, technostress has become a critical factor influencing both employee performance and overall mental and physical health. As a result, numerous studies have explored its consequences, including sleep disturbances, diminished efficiency, heightened anxiety, and physical symptoms such as headaches and eye fatigue (Berger et al., 2024).

1.2 Digitalization and Employee Readiness for Technological Change

The rapid advancement of digital technologies is reshaping work and raising expectations around employees' digital competence.

According to Eurostat (2023), 56% of EU residents aged 16 to 74 have at least basic digital skills. In countries like the Netherlands (83%) and Finland (82%), the proportion of digitally literate citizens is notably high, while in Romania (28%) and Albania (23%) it remains significantly lower. The Czech Republic surpasses the EU average, with a score of 69.1%.

Despite the relatively strong digital readiness in the Czech Republic, there likely remains a significant group of employees who are vulnerable when new technologies are introduced. These differences in digital literacy can be important determinants of how technostress is experienced.

The aim of this study is to examine how demographic and workplace factors influence technostress, work-life balance, and attitudes toward artificial intelligence among employees in digitally intensive sectors.

2. Methodology

2.1 Data Collection

A quantitative electronic questionnaire was used to examine technostress prevalence, intensity, and key determinants among employees in highly digitalized sectors. The survey included standardized items based on Nimrod's (2018) five-dimensional model (overload, invasion, complexity, uncertainty, unreliability), and addressed work-life balance, workplace support, and attitudes toward artificial intelligence.

It was distributed anonymously via Microsoft Forms across companies exposed to digital tools and AI, assuming at least partial AI use. Responses were processed in Excel. The sample of 163 respondents was recruited through convenience sampling using professional networks, email, and personal referrals.

Although this method ensured accessibility, it limited representativeness. The questionnaire included items on technostress, coping strategies, and AI perceptions. It employed Likert-scale statements and demographic questions, allowing for statistical analysis of technostress levels and their correlation with workplace and personal factors.

2.2 Measurement Instruments

To enable robust data analysis, the questionnaire included demographic items (e.g., age, gender, education) alongside subjective statements rated on a five-point Likert scale, with 1 indicating strong disagreement and 5 indicating strong agreement. This structure enabled the computation of aggregate scores for each technostress dimension and their subsequent integration with demographic variables. These aggregate indices were later used to empirically test the study's research hypotheses. We used non-parametric tests (Kruskal-Wallis, Mann-Whitney U) and Spearman correlations because our data were primarily ordinal (Likert scales) and not normally distributed. Kruskal-Wallis was applied for comparisons across multiple groups (e.g., age), Mann-Whitney for two groups (e.g., gender), and Spearman for relationships between variables (e.g., technostress and work-life balance). These methods are robust and appropriate for our sample size and data type.

2.3 Formulation of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

H₀: The age of respondents has no statistically significant effect on the level of technostress.

H₁: Younger respondents show lower levels of technostress than older ones.

Hypothesis 2

H₀: Technological proficiency is not related to attitudes toward artificial intelligence.

H₁: Higher technological proficiency is associated with a more positive attitude toward AI.

Hypothesis 3

H₀: The level of workplace support is not related to the level of technostress.

H₁: Lower workplace support is associated with higher technostress.

than older ones.

Hypothesis 4

H₀: Technostress is not related to work-life balance.

H₁: Higher technostress is associated with a worse work-life balance.

2.4 Survey Design and Sample Characteristics

Data were collected via an online questionnaire administered between October and December 2023. The survey targeted employees in digitally intensive sectors across Central Europe, especially those regularly working with advanced technologies. It was distributed electronically through professional networks, mailing lists, and social media platforms.

A total of 163 respondents completed the survey. The sampling used non-probability convenience sampling, which—though limiting external validity—was suitable for exploratory research on emerging digital stressors. Most respondents worked in IT-related roles, mainly as programmers. Other positions included project managers, data analysts, and support specialists. The sample was not fully occupationally balanced, as it leaned toward technical professions in highly digitalized settings.

Demographically, the sample consisted of 54% men and 46% women. The largest age group was 26–35 years ($n = 62$), typically active in tech-driven roles. Participants aged 46+ were underrepresented, which is relevant when interpreting age-related findings such as technological uncertainty. Most participants had a university degree (bachelor's or master's). Work experience ranged from less than one year to over a decade, allowing for comparative analysis across tenure groups.

The questionnaire was developed using validated instruments, notably Nimrod's (2018) five-dimensional model of technostress: overload, invasion, complexity, insecurity, and uncertainty. It also included items measuring perceived workplace support, work-life balance, and attitudes toward artificial intelligence. All items used 5-point Likert scales, enabling the creation of composite indices.

The dataset was analyzed in SPSS and Excel using non-parametric tests: Kruskal-Wallis for multi-group comparisons (e.g., age), Mann-Whitney U for two-group comparisons (e.g., gender), and Spearman correlation for variable relationships (e.g., technostress and work-life balance). These methods were appropriate given the ordinal nature of Likert data and sample size.

3. Overview of the Results

The results from the different sections of the questionnaire provide an in-depth view of how respondents perceive digital stress, technological complexity, interactions with AI, available support, and the influence of technology on both professional and personal life. These descriptive outcomes offer a foundation for the formulation and testing of hypothesized relationships between selected variables, as addressed in the research hypotheses. The data indicate that technostress and its related outcomes are not uniform but instead constitute a multidimensional construct shaped by individual traits (e.g., age, gender, technological proficiency), workplace factors (e.g., remote work, industry), and subjective perceptions of technology and AI.

The subsequent section of the study presents the results of hypothesis testing, based on a combination of theoretical knowledge and analysis of the collected data. The goal is to determine whether statistically significant relationships exist among demographic variables, technostress levels, work-life balance, and attitudes toward technology. Simultaneously, the study evaluates whether these relationships carry practical implications for managing technostress and fostering successful integration of digital tools in organizational settings.

Table 1: Statistical Testing of Hypotheses – Summary

Hypothesis	Focus	Test Used	<i>p</i> -value	Conclusion
H1	Age and technostress	Kruskal-Wallis	0.0067	H ₀ rejected – Younger respondents had lower technostress
H2	Tech proficiency and attitude toward AI	Spearman correlation	<0.001	H ₀ rejected – Higher proficiency = more positive attitude toward AI
H3	Workplace support and technostress	Spearman correlation	0.0001	H ₀ rejected – Less support = higher technostress
H4	Technostress and work-life balance	Spearman correlation	0.0080	H ₀ rejected – Higher technostress = poorer balance

4. Discussion

This study revealed key associations that highlight the multifaceted nature of technostress in digital workplaces. Age emerged as a significant factor: younger respondents reported lower technostress levels, supporting earlier findings that older workers often face greater difficulty adapting to digital change due to lower familiarity, perceived complexity, and increased anxiety (Nimrod, 2018; Berger et al., 2024). These findings underscore the need for age-sensitive approaches, such as tailored digital training and peer mentoring, to help older employees manage technological transitions.

Digital proficiency was also strongly linked to attitudes toward artificial intelligence. Respondents with higher competence viewed AI more positively, aligning with Giorgi et al. (2022), who frame digital confidence as a psychological asset that eases anxiety and increases openness to innovation. In this sense, digital skills function as a form of resilience, enabling employees to adapt to evolving technologies. Organizations should promote digital self-efficacy through continuous learning programs to foster a future-ready workforce.

Organizational support played a key role in mitigating technostress. Employees reporting insufficient training, lack of assistance, or exclusion from decision-making experienced significantly higher

stress. This confirms Berger et al.'s (2024) claim that structural support is essential in managing the psychological impact of digitalization. Effective strategies must go beyond individual solutions to include participatory technology implementation, transparent communication, and robust support systems.

The study also found that higher technostress correlates with poorer work-life balance, reflecting Nimrod's (2018) concept of "techno-invasion," where digital demands encroach on personal time. Respondents with high stress reported difficulty disconnecting from work, risking fatigue and burnout. To counteract this, organizations should introduce policies protecting personal time, such as the "right to disconnect," and foster digital habits that support psychological recovery.

These results illustrate the complex interplay of individual, organizational, and technological factors behind technostress. They offer several points for intervention, including upskilling, inclusive digital strategies, and maintaining clear boundaries between work and private life.

Nonetheless, some limitations apply. The use of convenience sampling and lack of occupational diversity restrict generalizability. Also, self-reported data may carry bias. Despite these constraints, validated instruments and structured methods strengthen the study's reliability.

Future research should involve more representative samples and consider longitudinal designs to capture technostress over time. Special attention should be given to how AI affects different demographic and occupational groups. This is essential for developing practical, evidence-based solutions that promote well-being in increasingly digital work environments.

5. Conclusion

This study provides insights into how employees experience technostress in digital workplaces. Findings confirmed that younger age (H1), higher technological proficiency (H5), and strong organizational support (H8) are linked to lower stress. In contrast, factors like gender, education, or remote work's impact on balance were not statistically significant, indicating that technostress is shaped by more than demographics alone.

Technostress is a dynamic, context-dependent phenomenon. Addressing it requires shifting from individual-level coping to organizational strategies that reduce digital overload, improve skills, and protect work-life balance. As digital transformation continues, future research should monitor long-term patterns and evaluate interventions, especially in AI-intensive sectors. Such work can help employers better support employee mental health and foster sustainable digital work environments.

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**SOCIAL MEDIA AND AI:
CONTRIBUTOR, SELECTOR, ...?**

AI INNOVATIONS - THE DOUBLE-EDGED SWORD: EXPLORING POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE IMPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN SOCIAL MEDIA

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Keywords

Innovations; social media; AI; implications

Abstract

This paper investigates the multifaceted implications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) integration within social media platforms. Employing an analytical approach, it identifies 10 positive effects of AI in social media such as: enhanced content personalization, efficient fake news detection, improved user engagement, automated content moderation, advanced trend analysis, targeted advertising efficiency, real-time crisis management, increased accessibility, improved community building, enhanced data-driven insights and 10 negative effects, such as: amplification of bias, privacy concerns, creation of echo chambers, reduced transparency, user manipulation, risk of automation errors, increased polarization, algorithmic accountability issues, ethical dilemmas in moderation, and economic impacts on content creators. By synthesizing current scholarly literature, this study underscores the urgency of balanced governance to mitigate adverse effects while promoting responsible AI utilization in social media.

1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a transformative force across numerous industries, with social media platforms being a prime example of its impactful integration. The advent of sophisticated AI technologies has significantly reshaped how users interact, share information, and engage with content online (Vinuesa et al., 2020). This dramatic shift reflects a broader technological evolution characterized by personalization, automated moderation, and intelligent content recommendation systems.

Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok have rapidly adopted AI-driven algorithms to optimize user experiences. These platforms leverage AI to analyze vast amounts of user-generated data, allowing them to curate highly personalized content feeds and recommendations. This targeted personalization has led to improved user satisfaction and increased platform engagement, establishing a new norm in digital user experiences (Schwartz et al., 2022).

One of the critical positive outcomes of AI's integration into social media is its ability to manage the vast scale and complexity of content. AI systems excel at tasks such as identifying trending topics, filtering out harmful or inappropriate content, and enhancing user engagement by providing relevant suggestions. The automation of these processes significantly improves operational efficiency and user experience, highlighting AI's beneficial aspects within the social media ecosystem.

Moreover, AI has become instrumental in addressing misinformation and disinformation, critical challenges facing modern societies. Algorithms designed to detect and flag fake news have increasingly been employed by major platforms, providing a frontline defense against information manipulation. AI's capability to analyze linguistic patterns, cross-reference facts, and flag suspicious content contributes significantly to maintaining the integrity and reliability of information disseminated through social networks (Akhtar et al., 2023).

Despite these advancements, AI's deployment in social media raises substantial ethical questions. The reliance on automated decision-making processes introduces potential biases inherent in training data and algorithmic design. AI systems trained on biased data can inadvertently perpetuate stereotypes and exacerbate inequalities, impacting marginalized communities disproportionately. Such biases underscore the necessity of rigorous ethical standards and transparency in AI development and deployment.

The issue of transparency in algorithmic processes remains another significant concern. Users often lack insight into how AI-driven recommendations and content filtering mechanisms operate, creating a sense of opacity and mistrust. This lack of transparency complicates accountability and reduces user autonomy, as decisions influencing their online experiences are made without clear explanation or recourse (Schwartz et al., 2022).

Privacy implications also represent a critical area of concern. Social media platforms collect extensive user data, often processed by complex AI systems to generate insights and drive targeted advertising. While personalized content enhances user experiences, it simultaneously elevates privacy risks, as sensitive information can be mishandled or exploited. Increased reliance on AI systems necessitates robust data protection mechanisms and enhanced user control over personal data (Tucker, 2019).

AI-driven personalization algorithms can create "echo chambers" or "filter bubbles," wherein users are predominantly exposed to content reinforcing their existing beliefs and biases. Such environments contribute to polarization, undermining the diversity and quality of public discourse. The long-term societal impact of echo chambers on democratic processes and social cohesion warrants serious consideration.

There is an urgent need for robust regulatory frameworks and governance structures. Policymakers, technologists, and ethicists must collaborate to develop effective oversight mechanisms to mitigate the adverse effects of AI. Emphasis should be placed on ensuring transparency, accountability, and ethical AI use, addressing both immediate and long-term challenges associated with its implementation (Novák et al., 2025).

The integration of AI in social media presents both significant opportunities and substantial risks. Balancing these opposing forces requires a comprehensive understanding of AI's capabilities and limitations, informed by ongoing scholarly research and practical insights. This paper aims to provide such understanding, setting the stage for a detailed examination of AI's dual implications in social media.

2. Methods

A qualitative literature review methodology was utilized, examining peer-reviewed journal articles, conference proceedings, and authoritative reports published between 2018 and 2024. Databases such as IEEE Xplore, Web of Science, and Scopus were systematically searched using keywords such as "AI ethics in social media," "AI privacy," "fake news detection," and "AI-driven recommendations." Selected studies underwent thematic analysis to identify recurrent patterns and critical issues within the research domain.

3. Results

3.1 Positive Effects of AI in Social Media

AI significantly enhances the user experience by providing tailored content recommendations, improving user engagement metrics substantially (Schwartz et al., 2022). Additionally, AI has proven effective in detecting misinformation and fake news, thus helping maintain informational integrity on platforms (Akhtar et al., 2023).

List of Major Positive Effects of AI in Social Media

1. Enhanced Content Personalization
2. Efficient Fake News Detection
3. Improved User Engagement
4. Automated Content Moderation
5. Advanced Trend Analysis
6. Targeted Advertising Efficiency
7. Real-time Crisis Management
8. Increased Accessibility
9. Improved Community Building
10. Enhanced Data-Driven Insights

Enhanced Content Personalization

AI algorithms analyze extensive user behavior and preferences data, tailoring content specifically to individual interests. This personalization significantly enhances user experiences, increasing satisfaction and platform engagement (Schwartz et al., 2022). Users receive highly relevant content that aligns closely with their tastes and needs.

Personalization also reduces information overload by streamlining content delivery, making the user experience more manageable and enjoyable. It transforms user interaction patterns by providing seamless and intuitive navigation through massive content streams.

Moreover, tailored content encourages users to spend more time on platforms, creating deeper user-platform relationships that benefit both parties, promoting sustained usage and loyalty.

Efficient Fake News Detection

AI-driven systems play a critical role in the identification and management of misinformation. Machine learning algorithms detect patterns and inconsistencies indicative of false information, significantly enhancing platform reliability (Akhtar et al., 2023). This capability has become vital in combating misinformation, especially during critical public events.

AI also supports real-time intervention, enabling platforms to swiftly flag and remove misinformation. This rapid response is essential in limiting the viral spread of harmful content and maintaining the integrity of public discourse.

Additionally, continuous algorithmic improvements increase the accuracy and efficiency of fake news detection systems, making them increasingly robust against evolving misinformation tactics.

Improved User Engagement

AI algorithms enable social media platforms to boost user interaction by predicting and delivering engaging content. User engagement metrics, such as likes, comments, and shares, have improved significantly due to AI's ability to identify content that resonates with specific user demographics (Schwartz et al., 2022).

This predictive ability helps maintain user interest and loyalty, reducing churn rates and enhancing overall platform stability and growth, especially with chatbot usage (Potančok & Radváková, 2023)

Furthermore, enhanced user engagement supports better monetization opportunities for platforms and content creators alike, creating a vibrant digital economy (Sudzina, 2013).

Automated Content Moderation

AI enables efficient and consistent moderation of massive content volumes. Automated moderation reduces the burden on human moderators, enhancing operational efficiency and maintaining higher content quality standards.

AI-driven moderation systems quickly identify and address inappropriate or harmful content, ensuring compliance with platform guidelines and regulatory requirements.

Automated moderation also supports scalability, allowing platforms to manage content effectively even as user bases and content volumes expand rapidly.

Advanced Trend Analysis

AI enhances the detection and analysis of emerging trends by examining vast amounts of data across social media platforms. This capability allows platforms to rapidly identify and leverage trending topics to maximize engagement and relevance.

Trend analysis helps platforms proactively manage user content strategies, providing valuable insights for marketers, content creators, and users.

Targeted Advertising Efficiency

AI greatly enhances the efficiency and accuracy of targeted advertising on social media platforms by analyzing user data to understand preferences, buying behaviors, and interests. These insights enable precise targeting, significantly improving the effectiveness and relevance of advertisements shown to users.

Targeted advertising powered by AI can lead to higher conversion rates, as users receive advertisements aligned closely with their current interests or needs. This precision reduces wastage in ad budgets and improves return on investment for advertisers.

Furthermore, AI algorithms continuously adapt to user interactions, refining ad targeting in real-time, thus maintaining high levels of user engagement and satisfaction.

Real-time Crisis Management

AI enables effective real-time management of crises, such as natural disasters, terrorist attacks, or health emergencies, by rapidly analyzing vast streams of user-generated content. These capabilities allow social media platforms to quickly disseminate critical information, enhancing public safety and response efforts.

AI-driven analysis can rapidly detect crisis indicators, such as spikes in keywords or visual data indicative of an emergency, prompting timely interventions. This responsiveness is crucial for mitigating misinformation and panic during high-stress situations.

Additionally, AI aids platforms in coordinating with emergency response teams by providing valuable insights derived from data analytics, facilitating swift and informed decision-making during critical events.

Increased Accessibility

AI significantly improves the accessibility of social media platforms for diverse user populations, including individuals with disabilities. Technologies such as automatic image descriptions, text-to-speech, speech-to-text, and multilingual translations ensure inclusive experiences.

AI-powered accessibility features remove barriers that traditionally limit content accessibility, ensuring that social media platforms are more equitable and user-friendly for individuals with various disabilities.

Enhanced accessibility also expands the platforms' reach and user base, demonstrating social responsibility while contributing to increased user engagement and platform reputation.

Improved Community Building

AI facilitates the creation and strengthening of online communities by analyzing and understanding user interests, behaviors, and interactions. These insights enable platforms to recommend groups and communities likely to resonate with users, fostering deeper connections and sustained interactions.

AI-powered moderation tools contribute to healthier community dynamics by identifying and addressing disruptive behaviors swiftly, maintaining positive environments conducive to meaningful interactions.

Furthermore, advanced community insights allow platform managers and moderators to implement strategic initiatives that enhance community cohesion and long-term growth.

Enhanced Data-Driven Insights

AI provides valuable insights into user behavior and content performance, enabling platforms and content creators to make informed strategic decisions. AI-driven analytics tools offer real-time metrics and detailed audience segmentation, significantly improving content strategy effectiveness.

These insights enable rapid optimization of content delivery and engagement strategies, ensuring platforms maintain high relevance and competitive advantages in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

Additionally, data-driven insights provided by AI facilitate predictive analytics, empowering platforms to proactively anticipate and meet user demands, further enhancing user satisfaction and platform success.

3.2 Negative Effects of AI in Social Media

Conversely, AI-driven personalization has contributed to the amplification of societal biases and the creation of echo chambers, limiting diverse information exposure (Vinuesa et al., 2020). The lack of transparency in algorithmic processes exacerbates these issues, complicating accountability and increasing privacy risks (Tucker, 2019).

List of Major Negative Effects of AI in Social Media:

1. Amplification of Bias
2. Privacy Concerns
3. Creation of Echo Chambers
4. Reduced Transparency
5. User Manipulation
6. Risk of Automation Errors
7. Increased Polarization
8. Algorithmic Accountability Issues
9. Ethical Dilemmas in Moderation
10. Economic Impacts on Content Creators

Amplification of Bias

AI-driven algorithms may inadvertently amplify societal biases present in training datasets. This bias exacerbation can result in marginalized groups facing disproportionate representation and discrimination on social media (Vinuesa et al., 2020).

The issue is compounded by the opaque nature of AI algorithms, making it difficult to detect and address biases promptly. Without sufficient oversight, biased recommendations can reinforce harmful stereotypes and perpetuate societal divisions.

Furthermore, addressing AI biases requires significant effort and resources to retrain and continuously audit AI systems, necessitating substantial commitment from platform developers and stakeholders.

Privacy Concerns

AI systems heavily depend on extensive data collection, which increases privacy risks. Users' sensitive information can be vulnerable to misuse, unauthorized sharing, or cyber-attacks, raising significant ethical concerns (Tucker, 2019).

The complex nature of AI algorithms further exacerbates privacy risks, as users often lack clear understanding and control over how their data is used and managed.

Platforms must continuously balance personalization benefits against privacy protection, demanding careful governance and robust privacy frameworks.

Creation of Echo Chambers

AI-driven algorithms often recommend content that aligns closely with users' existing beliefs and preferences, creating echo chambers. This restricts exposure to diverse viewpoints, reinforcing users' existing biases and limiting opportunities for open discourse.

The existence of echo chambers can increase polarization within society, contributing to fragmentation and misunderstanding among different social groups. Users may become less open to alternative perspectives, reducing the quality and diversity of public debate.

Mitigating echo chambers requires conscious effort by platform developers to introduce algorithmic transparency and diversity in content recommendations, fostering a more balanced informational environment (Vinuesa et al., 2020).

Reduced Transparency

AI algorithms in social media platforms frequently lack transparency, making it challenging for users to understand how decisions about content recommendations and moderation are made. This opacity undermines trust and accountability, as users have little insight into the factors influencing their online experiences (Schwartz et al., 2022).

Without sufficient transparency, it becomes difficult for users to challenge or appeal content decisions, reducing their autonomy and potentially leading to dissatisfaction with platform governance.

Increasing algorithmic transparency through explainable AI and clear user communication can mitigate this issue, enhancing trust and user empowerment (Tucker, 2019).

User Manipulation

AI-powered content delivery systems can inadvertently or deliberately manipulate users by exploiting psychological triggers to enhance engagement. This manipulation may lead to excessive screen time, addiction, and potentially harmful psychological effects.

Manipulative practices can undermine user autonomy and ethical standards, raising significant moral and regulatory concerns about platform responsibilities.

To counteract these effects, platforms must implement ethical guidelines and transparent practices to safeguard user well-being, ensuring that AI-driven engagement strategies do not cross ethical boundaries (Vinuesa et al., 2020).

Risk of Automation Errors

While AI-driven moderation and recommendation systems offer efficiency, they can also produce errors due to limitations in algorithmic accuracy. False positives and negatives in content moderation can unfairly penalize users or allow harmful content to persist (Schwartz et al., 2022).

Automation errors can damage user trust and platform reputation, highlighting the need for continuous human oversight and algorithm refinement.

Regular audits and updates to AI models are necessary to minimize errors, emphasizing the need for human-AI collaboration in moderation practices (Tucker, 2019).

Increased Polarization

The targeted nature of AI-driven recommendations can amplify societal polarization by continually exposing users to ideologically consistent content. This exacerbates existing societal divisions and reduces mutual understanding among different social groups (Vinuesa et al., 2020).

Polarization poses risks to democratic processes, making consensus-building and constructive dialogue increasingly difficult. Social media platforms must actively address this through diversified content strategies and balanced recommendation practices.

Educational campaigns and transparency efforts are crucial in helping users recognize and counteract polarization tendencies induced by AI algorithms.

Algorithmic Accountability Issues

AI-driven content decisions often lack clear accountability structures. When algorithms cause harm or errors, identifying responsible parties or rectifying mistakes can be difficult, complicating resolution and accountability efforts (Schwartz et al., 2022).

Without clear accountability, users are left with limited recourse, potentially increasing distrust and dissatisfaction. Platforms must establish clear accountability frameworks to handle algorithmic decision-making effectively.

Developing robust accountability measures, including transparent reporting and user feedback systems, can significantly enhance trust and responsiveness to algorithmic impacts (Tucker, 2019).

Ethical Dilemmas in Moderation

AI moderation systems face ethical challenges, particularly when determining boundaries for acceptable content. Algorithms must balance free speech and content regulation, often navigating ambiguous moral and legal territories.

Decisions on content moderation can be culturally and contextually sensitive, requiring nuanced judgment that AI algorithms may inadequately handle.

Ethical frameworks and guidelines must be clearly defined and continuously updated to ensure moderation decisions reflect societal norms and human rights considerations (Vinuesa et al., 2020).

Economic Impacts on Content Creators

AI-driven content prioritization can disproportionately favor established creators or sensational content, negatively affecting emerging or niche content producers. This can limit economic opportunities for smaller or diverse creators, skewing content ecosystems towards popularity rather than diversity or quality (Schwartz et al., 2022).

Economic disparities can arise, undermining content diversity and innovation on platforms. Supporting equitable algorithmic practices can ensure diverse content remains visible and economically viable.

Platforms must actively pursue algorithmic fairness and transparent practices to maintain vibrant and inclusive creator ecosystems, fostering sustainable digital economies (Tucker, 2019).

4. Discussion

The integration of AI technologies into social media platforms presents both significant opportunities and considerable risks, requiring a nuanced analysis of their implications. The results indicate clear benefits in enhancing user experiences, managing content moderation effectively, and improving user engagement. These advancements underscore the pivotal role AI plays in shaping contemporary digital communication environments (Schwartz et al., 2022). However, alongside these advancements are pressing concerns about privacy, ethical considerations, and societal impacts. The amplification of bias, creation of echo chambers, and increasing polarization highlight the critical areas where AI's application demands greater scrutiny and governance. Addressing these challenges requires comprehensive approaches involving transparency, user education, and regulatory interventions (Vinuesa et al., 2020).

Transparency in algorithmic operations remains a central concern. Many users are unaware of the processes behind content recommendations and moderation decisions, which can undermine trust and create dissatisfaction. Enhancing transparency through explainable AI practices is necessary to build accountability and user confidence (Shin & Park, 2019). Moreover, privacy considerations continue to be a major ethical challenge. The extensive data collection facilitated by AI technologies raises significant concerns about user data security and privacy rights. Implementing robust data protection frameworks and empowering users with greater control over their data are essential steps toward addressing these concerns (Mittelstadt, 2019).

The ethical implications of AI-driven content moderation are particularly complex. Algorithms must navigate the difficult balance between protecting free speech and preventing harmful content. Ethical guidelines must therefore be carefully developed and regularly updated to reflect evolving societal norms and legal standards (Gorwa et al., 2020). Polarization and echo chambers present profound implications for democratic discourse. AI algorithms, through targeted content delivery, often reinforce users' existing beliefs, contributing to societal fragmentation. Platforms must proactively diversify content exposure and encourage user engagement with varied perspectives to mitigate these effects (Guess et al., 2018).

The economic impacts on content creators represent another critical dimension. AI-driven prioritization mechanisms can marginalize emerging creators, fostering economic inequalities within digital content ecosystems. Fairer algorithmic practices that ensure equitable visibility for diverse creators are crucial to maintaining vibrant and innovative online communities (Novák, et al., 2022).

AI-driven fake news detection represents a notable success in safeguarding informational integrity online. Continuous algorithmic advancements improve accuracy and responsiveness in misinformation management, significantly enhancing public trust in digital platforms (Zhang & Ghorbani, 2020).

Real-time crisis management, facilitated by AI technologies, exemplifies AI's potential to positively impact public safety and responsiveness during emergencies. Rapid analysis and dissemination of critical information during crises significantly enhance community resilience and informed responses (Palen, L., & Anderson, K. M. (2019). Accessibility improvements brought about by AI-driven technologies significantly enhance social inclusion. By providing tools such as automatic captioning and language translation, AI ensures equitable platform participation for diverse user groups, including those with disabilities, fostering inclusivity and social cohesion.

Community building and enhanced user engagement enabled by AI algorithms strengthen social interactions online. These advancements support vibrant online communities, providing users with meaningful connections and interactions, crucial for sustained platform loyalty and satisfaction.

Automation errors remain a persistent challenge despite AI's benefits in efficiency and scalability. Addressing these errors through continuous oversight and algorithm refinement is necessary to maintain user trust and platform credibility, highlighting the need for human-AI collaboration (Floridi et al., 2018).

Targeted advertising powered by AI raises critical ethical and regulatory considerations related to user manipulation and consent. Platforms must carefully balance advertising efficiency against user autonomy, implementing transparent practices and clear consent mechanisms (Acquisti et al., 2019). Advanced data-driven insights offered by AI have revolutionized platform strategies, enabling precise and adaptive responses to user behavior. However, these benefits must be balanced against privacy considerations and responsible data governance to ensure ethical utilization (Barocas & Selbst, 2016).

Ultimately, the governance of AI technologies in social media demands a collaborative approach involving policymakers, platform providers, and user communities. Only through concerted effort and informed strategies can AI's full potential be harnessed responsibly, ensuring positive social impacts while mitigating associated risks (Cath et al., 2018).

Figure 1: List of Identified Major Effects of AI in Social Media

5. Conclusion

The integration of Artificial Intelligence into social media presents a profound paradox: it offers tools to connect people, democratize information, and enhance digital communication—yet it simultaneously threatens user autonomy, amplifies bias, and compromises privacy. Navigating this duality requires a deliberate and ethical approach from developers, policymakers, and users alike.

One of the central insights of this study is the importance of balance. While we must embrace innovation, we must also remain vigilant against its unintended consequences. The benefits of AI—enhanced personalization, accessibility, moderation, and crisis responsiveness—should not obscure its darker implications, such as manipulation, inequality, and algorithmic opacity. In this context, an

old saying resonates well: "Trust, but verify." Blind reliance on AI without accountability can lead to outcomes we neither intended nor can fully control.

Also, there is a growing need for a human-in-the-loop model, where AI augments rather than replaces human judgment. Automation without empathy risks dehumanizing digital interactions. As algorithms gain influence over what we see, believe, and even whom we trust, ensuring transparency, explainability, and fairness becomes more than a technical task—it becomes a moral imperative.

Regulation and governance structures must evolve in step with AI's growing power. Effective oversight can curb excesses without stifling innovation. Just as social norms guided early human societies, so too must ethical AI frameworks guide today's digital tribes. Or, to borrow from a timeless proverb: "It takes a village to raise a child"—and it will take a global community to raise a responsible AI.

Education and digital literacy should also not be forgotten. Users must be empowered to understand how algorithms shape their experiences. Knowing that "if you're not paying for the product, you are the product" can help foster a more critical engagement with social media platforms.

There is also room for optimism. As AI continues to evolve, so too do the tools and frameworks to manage its impact. Researchers, engineers, and civic actors are increasingly aware of the ethical stakes and are working collaboratively to design systems that serve public good. Perhaps in the future, AI will not only reflect our society but also help improve it.

Humor can sometimes capture complex truths better than academic prose, and perhaps distinguish human intelligence from AI, so let's conclude on a humorous note: "Artificial intelligence is no match for natural stupidity"—a reminder that while AI is powerful, the human element remains irreplaceable. AI in social media is not inherently good or bad—it is what we make of it. Like fire, it can warm our homes or burn them down. Our collective challenge is to harness its power wisely, steering it toward equity, dignity, and a more informed digital society. And as we look ahead, let us be guided by curiosity, caution, and a healthy sense of humor: "To err is human—but to really mess things up, you need a machine learning model."

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INVESTIGATING GAMIFICATION AS A SOLUTION FOR READING FATIGUE

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Abstract

Reading fatigue is a common challenge that affects individuals across various age groups, often leading to reduced comprehension, retention, and motivation. In this context, reading fatigue specifically refers to the mental exhaustion experienced when engaging with information and knowledge databases such as academic platforms, online articles, and digital learning tools. Because these materials are accessed digitally, this form of reading fatigue is inherently intertwined with digital fatigue, which is a broader phenomenon resulting from prolonged screen use and digital content consumption. This paper explores gamification as an innovative solution to mitigate reading fatigue, aiming to enhance engagement and cognitive focus. By integrating game-like elements such as rewards, challenges, and interactive feedback into reading experiences, gamification can transform passive reading into an engaging and dynamic activity. The findings suggest that, when effectively implemented, gamification can serve as a powerful tool in combating reading fatigue, fostering deeper learning, and cultivating a lifelong love for reading.

1. Introduction

Reading fatigue is a widespread issue that affects individuals of all ages, often leading to decreased comprehension, retention, and motivation. In today's digital age, the rise of social media has exacerbated these challenges, as constant exposure to short, fragmented content, such as videos, memes, and headlines, contributes to mental overload and diminishes the ability to focus on more extended reading tasks. Social media platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and Twitter have created an environment where quick, easily consumable content reigns, fostering a preference for watching short videos rather than engaging with written texts. This shift has led to a decline in the capacity for sustained attention (Hilman, 2024), as users are accustomed to the rapid pace of scrolling and the instant gratification of audio-visual content. As a result, people may find it more difficult to engage with longer, more complex reading material, ultimately contributing to reading fatigue and a diminished interest in reading.

This paper explores gamification as an innovative solution to counteract these issues, aiming to enhance engagement, cognitive focus, and reading retention particularly in contexts where

comprehension is critical, such as academic reading or professional development. In contrast, other forms of reading, such as news articles or social media posts, may not require the same depth of comprehension. By incorporating game-like elements, such as rewards, challenges, levels, and interactive feedback into the reading experience, gamification can transform passive reading into an engaging, dynamic activity that feels more aligned with the quick-paced, interactive nature of social media. This paper also reviews the existing research on gamification in education and digital media, emphasizing its potential to sustain attention, improve retention, and foster positive reading habits. By offering an immersive experience that mimics the instant rewards and engagement typical of social media platforms, gamified reading platforms can encourage users to stay focused and invested in their reading, gradually combating the fragmented attention habits often developed through constant social media use.

The article also examines case studies of successful gamified reading platforms, analysing how they have tailored their approaches to meet the diverse needs of readers, from students to adults. These platforms blend elements of game design with reading tasks, making reading more appealing by introducing goal-setting, competition, and progress tracking—mechanisms that are familiar from social media engagement. The findings suggest that, when effectively implemented, gamification can serve as a powerful tool in combating reading fatigue, fostering deeper learning, and cultivating a lifelong love for reading. By helping individuals re-establish a meaningful connection with reading in a world dominated by short-form content, gamification offers a potential solution to the growing problem of digital burnout and the decline of sustained reading habits.

2. Theoretical background

2.1 Fatigue

Reading fatigue and digital fatigue are related concepts that often overlap, though they each have distinct origins and manifestations. Digital fatigue, as defined in the literature, refers to the physical, mental, and emotional exhaustion caused by prolonged and intense exposure to digital devices (Arican, 2025). It is particularly concerning in the context of online learning, where it manifests as a reduction in students' motivation and enthusiasm due to overexposure to coursework and related activities (Malony et al., 2023).

This type of fatigue poses significant risks to individual well-being and operational safety, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to mitigate its effects (Arican, 2025). Fatigue, in general, has a broad range of physical and psychological consequences, including life-threatening impacts such as accidents and injuries. As a result, researchers emphasize the need for more effective methods of monitoring fatigue and addressing it, especially in high-risk work environments (Imran et al., 2024).

In organizational settings, knowledge transfer can be hindered by various factors, such as a lack of skilled knowledge managers or inadequate information systems. One significant yet often overlooked factor is online reading fatigue, which can reduce the effectiveness of knowledge systems. Employees may experience difficulty engaging with text due to a lack of energy or interest, leading to disengagement and incomplete reading. This inability to remain actively involved, known as "cognitive engagement," is a direct result of reading fatigue (Ziaei Nafchi, 2024).

2.2 Gamification

Gamification refers to the process of transforming activities, systems, services, products, or organizational structures into engaging processes that foster positive experiences similar to those in

games, with the goal of encouraging changes in behaviour or cognitive processes. It involves incorporating game design elements—such as points, rewards, and badges—into non-game contexts (Duggan and Shoup, 2013). Gamification can also be understood as a series of activities and processes aimed at solving problems by leveraging game-like elements (Santos et al., 2024).

Games are well-known for their ability to influence players, offering cognitive benefits (e.g., improved attention and enhanced creativity), social benefits (e.g., better social skills and prosocial behaviour), and emotional benefits (e.g., mood management and emotional state improvement). Additionally, games contribute to intrinsic motivation and a state of flow, where players become deeply immersed in a rewarding activity, experiencing a high sense of control and a temporary loss of self-consciousness. The core idea of gamification is to harness the motivational power of specific game elements to increase user involvement and commitment, thus aligning with the system's central objectives (Santos et al., 2024).

Rodrigues et al. (2019) describe gamification as a new way of thinking, designing, and deploying software applications, aimed at changing individuals' attitudes and behaviours. In contrast to traditional workplace engagement and skill development methods, such as lectures, training manuals, and standardized assessments, gamification offers a more interactive and engaging alternative that is better suited to the modern workforce (Sailer & Homner, 2020).

To enhance motivation, employees should be given opportunities to pursue their interests, encouraged to collaborate and work in teams, and provided with training and development programs (Tie, Birks, & Francis, 2019). By transforming work tasks into friendly competitions, companies can boost individual motivation and productivity while improving interpersonal dynamics. Furthermore, gamification helps in conflict resolution by making competition more transparent and rules-based, reducing misunderstandings and disputes (Khan et al., 2024). Some scholars argue that gamification may be an effective approach to address innovation challenges (Abril et al., 2024).

In educational settings, gamification has also been shown to enhance engagement. Jack et al. (2024) observed an increase in student engagement with pre-lecture activities in a flipped course when gamification strategies were employed. However, caution is advisable in the implementation of gamification elements as according to Almeida et al. (2022) When thoughtfully implemented, gamification can positively impact education and learning. However, game design elements such as badges, leader boards, competitions, and points are frequently associated with negative outcomes. The most commonly reported drawbacks include limited or no impact, decreased performance, motivational challenges, confusion or lack of understanding, and a perceived lack of relevance.

2.3 Social Media and Reading Fatigue

The positive benefits of social media, such as increased well-being and life satisfaction, are widely recognized. However, many users have chosen to take a break from social media or even quit altogether due to feelings of fatigue and burnout (Luhur et al., 2023).

According to Kushwaha (2024) excessive use of social media has been shown to negatively impact young people's reading habits. The constant flow of social media content, coupled with the appeal of instant gratification and brief snippets of information, deters them from engaging in sustained reading. This trend has led to a noticeable decline in both the frequency and duration of reading activities among youth. However, educators, parents, and policymakers can collaborate to foster a generation of young readers who are able to navigate the challenges posed by social media. By promoting digital literacy skills and creating compelling reading experiences within the digital realm, they can help young people benefit from improved reading comprehension in the digital age.

Excessive and compulsive use of social networking sites can lead to users experiencing exhaustion from social media activities, which is referred to as "social media fatigue.". There are two types of fatigue: physical fatigue and psychological fatigue. Physical fatigue refers to a decrease in a person's physiological capacity or physical condition, such as eye strain or muscle fatigue. On the other hand, psychological fatigue encompasses negative emotions like stress, burnout, and overall mental exhaustion (Zheng & Ling, 2021).

To prevent social media fatigue and reduce the likelihood of users discontinuing their use, individuals should consider limiting their information intake by setting time breaks or utilizing available filtering tools on the platform (Luhur et al., 2023).

3. Objectives and methodology

This paper adopts a comparative methodology to examine and evaluate the impact of gamification on reading habits, reading fatigue, and digital burnout. The study primarily compares the effects of gamification on reading and digital fatigue, comparing this approach with traditional reading habits in both digital and non-digital contexts.

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to understand the main definitions and theories related to reading fatigue, digital burnout, and gamification. This review focused on exploring the evolving role of digital media and how social media influences reading behaviour, engagement, and the potential exacerbation of digital fatigue. It also provided the foundation for understanding how gamification could mitigate or contribute to these issues by comparing traditional reading approaches with gamified experiences.

The use of observation allowed for the collection of real-time behavioural data, observing how individuals engage with reading material on both traditional and gamified platforms, as well as how they respond to digital content on social media. This qualitative observation can be complemented by interviews and surveys in the future research to capture subjective experiences of reading fatigue and digital burnout across different demographics.

An analysis and synthesis methodology were employed to identify key patterns in reading behaviour and digital fatigue. By comparing how gamification influences reading engagement and fatigue, the study explored how these experiences differ from those associated with traditional reading habits or social media-driven reading habits. The results were then analysed using thematic coding and comparison techniques to draw meaningful conclusions about the role of gamification in mitigating reading fatigue and its potential to reduce the effects of digital burnout.

4. Results and Discussion

Reading fatigue is a prevalent issue that affects both individuals and organizations, particularly in environments where sustained reading is required. This fatigue can manifest as physical discomfort, cognitive overload, or emotional exhaustion, leading to disengagement and decreased productivity.

Social media platforms present a unique environment where users are bombarded with a continuous flow of information, often in short, fragmented pieces. This rapid consumption of content can lead to several factors contributing to reading fatigue such as:

- **Overload of Information:** The sheer volume of information available on social media can be overwhelming. Constant notifications, updates, and the urge to stay informed create an

environment where users struggle to filter relevant information from the noise. This information overload can result in cognitive strain, leading to reading fatigue.

- **Shallow Reading Habits:** On social media, users often skim through headlines, captions, and short posts, rather than engaging in deep reading. This encourages a habit of quick consumption rather than thoughtful reflection, which can reduce the ability to concentrate on longer, more involved reading tasks, such as books or in-depth articles.
- **Multi-tasking and Distractions:** The interactive nature of social media, with features like likes, comments, and shares, fosters multitasking. Users frequently switch between tasks, leading to fragmented attention and cognitive overload. This pattern of switching between different kinds of content (videos, images, text, etc.) contributes to a sense of mental fatigue and difficulty focusing on more substantial reading tasks.
- **Reduced Focus and Attention Span:** Studies have shown that regular use of social media can decrease an individual's ability to maintain focus for extended periods. The constant need to check notifications or switch between posts diminishes the brain's capacity for sustained concentration, which is essential for reading more complex texts.

Traditional methods of combating reading fatigue, such as taking breaks or changing reading materials, have limitations, especially in modern, digitally-driven contexts. However, gamification offers a promising and innovative solution to alleviate reading fatigue and foster greater engagement in reading tasks.

One of the central features of gamification is its ability to transform mundane or repetitive tasks into engaging and rewarding experiences. By incorporating game design elements such as points, rewards, levels, and badges into reading activities, gamification can reinvigorate the experience and make it more enjoyable and motivating. According to Santos et al. (2024), gamification utilizes the motivational power of game elements to increase user involvement and commitment, which can be particularly effective in combating the disengagement often caused by reading fatigue. Instead of viewing reading as a monotonous task, gamified elements introduce a sense of progress, achievement, and competition, which can reframe the experience and make it more engaging.

Games are well-known for their potential to improve cognitive abilities, such as attention, creativity, and problem-solving, and to enhance emotional well-being. Gamification taps into these benefits by creating an environment where users experience flow—a state of immersion where they feel a high sense of control and intrinsic motivation. This state of flow is particularly beneficial for reducing reading fatigue. As individuals become more engaged in reading through gamified experiences, their focus and enjoyment are enhanced, mitigating the mental and emotional strain associated with traditional reading tasks (Santos et al., 2024). By making reading a rewarding and immersive activity, gamification helps reduce the negative emotional impact of fatigue, allowing individuals to read for longer periods without feeling exhausted.

Traditional reading or study methods often lack the interactive elements necessary to maintain the modern learner's attention. Gamification, however, introduces a novel approach by incorporating dynamic and interactive features into reading tasks. As noted by Rodrigues et al. (2019), gamification changes individuals' behaviours and attitudes by offering new ways of engaging with content. When applied to reading, this can involve turning reading assignments into challenges, where readers earn points or badges for completing sections of text, engaging in discussions, or applying the knowledge they've gained. This structured form of feedback can increase motivation, making the act of reading more enjoyable and rewarding.

In organizational contexts, reading fatigue can significantly hinder knowledge transfer and employee productivity. Employees often struggle to engage with large volumes of text due to lack of motivation,

energy, or time. Gamifying reading tasks within workplaces can provide a solution to these challenges. As Khan et al. (2024) note, gamification can improve interpersonal dynamics, reduce workplace conflict, and create a more transparent and rules-based environment, all of which can reduce stress and improve collaboration. By gamifying work-related reading, employees may feel more motivated to engage with the material, particularly if there are incentives tied to completion and comprehension. This approach not only fosters a more engaging work culture but also reduces the potential for burnout and fatigue.

In the digital age, reading fatigue is often exacerbated by prolonged screen time. Digital fatigue, also referred to as "screen fatigue," is characterized by eye strain, headaches, and mental exhaustion from prolonged digital device use. Gamification can be especially effective in mitigating the effects of digital fatigue by making screen-based tasks more interactive and engaging. Instead of passively reading long documents, employees or students can participate in gamified learning experiences that integrate reading with interactive challenges, multimedia elements, and instant feedback. This can help reduce the cognitive load typically associated with digital content consumption and make the overall experience more enjoyable, thereby decreasing the likelihood of digital fatigue (Duggan & Shoup, 2013).

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

In the realm of digital learning and information consumption, reading fatigue specifically refers to the mental exhaustion experienced when engaging with information and knowledge databases such as academic platforms, online articles, and digital learning tools. Because these materials are accessed digitally, this form of reading fatigue is inherently intertwined with digital fatigue, which is a broader phenomenon resulting from prolonged screen use and digital content consumption.

Social Media Fatigue is a specific type of Digital Fatigue, which refers to the overwhelming sense of exhaustion that people experience from constant engagement with digital platforms. While it is not directly categorized as reading fatigue, it can still significantly influence it. The constant stream of information, notifications, and the pressure to stay connected across various platforms can drain a person's mental energy, making it harder to focus on tasks such as reading or other forms of deep thinking. Over time, this fatigue can negatively impact attention span and cognitive function, leading to a diminished capacity to engage in more sustained and focused activities, including reading.

Gamification provides a novel solution for addressing reading fatigue by transforming traditional reading tasks into engaging, interactive experiences that motivate users, foster greater involvement, and reduce cognitive and emotional strain. By incorporating game elements such as rewards, challenges, and feedback, gamification enhances cognitive focus, encourages active participation, and promotes a sense of achievement, all of which can alleviate the negative effects of reading fatigue. Whether in educational settings or the workplace, gamification can revitalize the act of reading, making it a more enjoyable and effective activity. In doing so, it offers a promising strategy for combating reading fatigue and improving overall productivity and well-being. Therefore, it is recommended to integrate game elements into digital learning tools, and to limit continuous digital exposure by utilizing regular breaks using techniques to restore focus and to mitigate the negative outcomes of digital reading such as digital fatigue.

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GAI-LENS: LEGAL AND ETHICAL RISK ASSESSMENT IN GENERATIVE AI SOCIAL CONTENT USING ADVANCED AI METHODS

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Generative AI; legal risk assessment; ethics; IP; privacy; deep learning; social media

Abstract

This paper presents the development of GAI-LENS (Generative AI Legal and Ethical Neural System), an AI-based system for identifying and assessing legal and ethical risks in generative content. With the expansion of generative AI, particularly in social media environments, legal and ethical challenges are increasing. Our methodology employs Transformer architecture with dedicated adaptation layers for textual and visual analysis of synthetic data, enabling identification of issues related to intellectual property, privacy, factual accuracy, and biases. The model was trained on a heterogeneous synthetic dataset of 14,500 tagged examples. Results indicate high performance, with 87.3% accuracy in identifying legal risks and 83.5% for ethical issues. The model shows special capabilities in contextual analysis and identification of sophisticated factual falsehoods. Compared to previous models, GAI-LENS demonstrates a 23% improvement in identifying privacy risks and an 18% improvement for intellectual property infringements. Our primary contribution is a comprehensive risk assessment framework that includes measurable evaluation criteria, automatic identification algorithms, and an evidence-based decision-making model. This research bridges the gap between legal theory and technological implementation by providing operational tools that could potentially address challenges in environments like social media, where content velocity and reach create unique challenges for maintaining ethical and legal standards.

1. Introduction

In the current digital era, generative artificial intelligence (GAI) technologies have revolutionized content creation, processing, and distribution. Systems like GPT-4, Llama, Claude, and Gemini can produce human-like content across various domains. While offering advantages, these technologies raise significant legal, ethical, and social challenges (Bostrom, 2023; Floridi & Cowls, 2022).

Content generated through GAI may carry legal and ethical risks, from copyright infringement and dissemination of misleading information to the use of stereotypes and distribution of harmful content. These challenges have potential implications for complex information environments like social media, where generative AI content could spread rapidly at unprecedented scales, creating unique challenges for risk identification and maintaining ethical and legal standards.

This paper focuses on the development of the GAI-LENS model (Generative AI Legal and Ethical Neural System), a system combining advanced deep learning techniques to identify and assess risks in generative content using synthetic data simulation. As noted by Surden (2023), the intersection between current technological developments and existing legal and ethical systems creates a new space of questions that have not yet received a systematic answer.

While research in generative AI has primarily focused on improving technical capabilities, legal and ethical aspects have mostly remained on the margins. Existing tools for risk assessment, such as the SHIELD model (Dangswang & Nuchitprasitchai, 2024) and LLMGuard, focus on specific risks without providing a comprehensive framework.

Our research objectives include: developing a computational architecture for automatic identification of legal and ethical risks in generative content; creating a theoretical framework integrating perspectives from law, ethics, and computer science; empirically examining model performance through 200 simulated scenarios; and proposing evidence-based policy recommendations.

2. Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

Existing models for risk assessment in generative content include the SHIELD model (Dangswang & Nuchitprasitchai, 2024), which identifies smuggling and illegal activities through social media content analysis but is limited to customs fraud identification. Similarly, the LLMGuard model (Zhao et al., 2023) presents a multi-layered approach but lacks comprehensive risk assessment capabilities.

Morrison and Atkinson's Legal Risk Taxonomy (2022) offers a framework for understanding legal risks across five dimensions but requires adaptation for generative content contexts. Advanced AI models like BERT provide sophisticated natural language processing capabilities, while GRU offers advantages in processing sequential data.

The theoretical framework of GAI-LENS combines insights from law, ethics, and computer science. A central starting point is Lessig's (2006) concept of "Code as Law," which argues that technological architecture itself constitutes a form of regulation. We also incorporate the Risk Management Approach developed by Agrawal et al. (2019) for AI regulation.

Our literature review reveals several significant gaps: existing models focus on specific risks without providing comprehensive frameworks; there is a lack of structured mechanisms for assessing risk severity and probability; existing taxonomies are not adapted to generative AI; and there is only partial implementation of advanced models in legal risk assessment. Additionally, as Raghunathan (2021) notes, synthetic data generation offers methodological advantages for systematic evaluation of complex frameworks when real-world datasets lack appropriate coverage or balance of scenarios required for comprehensive assessment. The GAI-LENS model addresses these identified gaps by providing a comprehensive framework that integrates advanced AI techniques with legal and ethical principles to systematically evaluate risks in generative content.

3. The GAI-LENS Model

3.1 Model Architecture

The GAI-LENS model is a research prototype model designed as a modular, flexible, and extensible system built from four main layers:

1. Input Layer: Receives and processes generative content and metadata.
2. Processing Layer: The analytical core, responsible for in-depth content analysis through:

- Natural language processing engine
 - Legal analysis engine
 - Ethical analysis engine
 - Context analysis engine
 - Integration engine
3. Assessment Layer: Evaluates legal and ethical risks through:
 - Risk classification engine
 - Severity assessment engine
 - Probability assessment engine
 - Risk rating engine
 - Mitigation recommendation engine
 4. Output Layer: Produces reports, alerts, and recommendations.

A central innovation of GAI-LENS is the deep integration of BERT and GRU models. BERT excels in understanding context and meaning, while GRU excels in learning long-term dependencies. The integration architecture includes an initial BERT layer for in-depth text analysis, a connecting GRU layer for analyzing connections between sections, a complementary BERT layer for focused analysis, and an integration layer for unifying results.

3.2 Legal and Ethical Risk Assessment Mechanisms

At the core of GAI-LENS are risk assessment mechanisms based on an extended taxonomy with seven main categories:

- Intellectual property risks
- Libel and defamation risks
- Privacy and information security risks
- Deception and fraud risks
- Discrimination and bias risks
- Illegal content risks
- Ethical risks

The model implements unique mechanisms for assessing risk severity and probability, including a multi-dimensional severity matrix, context-adapted risk model, event chain model, and legal precedent model. A key aspect is the ability to provide transparent explanations for decisions through local and global explanation mechanisms.

3.3 Applications in Social Media Environments

A particularly important potential application domain for GAI-LENS is social media platforms, where generative AI content presents unique risks. Based on our synthetic data simulations, we project that in these environments, GAI-LENS could offer:

1. Automated Content Screening: Identifying potentially problematic AI-generated content before widespread distribution.

2. Real-time Risk Assessment: Processing content streams to evaluate risks as content propagates through social networks.
3. Fake News Detection: Specialized capabilities to identify AI-generated misinformation.
4. Privacy Protection: Advanced mechanisms to detect privacy violations within social media contexts.
5. Cross-platform Analysis: Ability to evaluate how content risks transform when shared across different platforms with varying policies.

These projected capabilities demonstrate how the GAI-LENS framework could be applied to social media contexts following validation with real-world data.

4. Research Method

4.1 Dataset Development

The use of synthetic data in this research represents a methodological choice based on several considerations: lack of appropriate existing databases, control of research parameters, balancing of scenarios, and standardization for comparability (Raghunathan, 2021).

Our model was trained on a heterogeneous dataset specifically built for this purpose, including 14,500 tagged and encoded content examples with various legal and ethical aspects. To address limitations of synthetic data, we:

- Based scenarios on real cases
- Involved experts from law and ethics
- Created a wide variety of scenarios
- Validated scenarios through six external experts using a Blinded Assessment approach (Mehrabi et al., 2022)

The final synthetic database includes 200 scenarios, organized by legal domains, complexity levels, legal systems, and dimensions of moral-legal intelligence.

4.2 Training and Assessment Process

Model evaluation used a multi-dimensional approach of confusion matrices for each major risk category, allowing identification of problematic areas and assessment of error costs. Additional performance metrics included Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 measure, error severity index, and risk coverage measure. Evaluation protocol included: Database division (70% training, 15% validation, 15% testing), Quantitative evaluation, Error analysis, Expert evaluation, Cross-sectional analysis

4.3 Social Media Content Simulation

To evaluate the model's potential for social media applications, we developed specialized synthetic scenarios that simulate social media characteristics:

- Platform-characteristic simulation: Creating synthetic examples that mimic typical content formats and features of major platforms (Twitter/X, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok)
- Virality pattern simulation: Generating test scenarios that incorporate structural patterns associated with content that tends to spread widely

- Cross-platform scenario design: Developing synthetic examples that simulate how content might appear and transform across different platform environments
- Engagement pattern integration: Incorporating simulated engagement metrics into our test scenarios to evaluate performance under varying levels of interaction

These simulated social media scenarios, while synthetic, allowed us to systematically evaluate GAI-LENS's potential effectiveness across different hypothetical social media environments while maintaining methodological consistency within our synthetic data approach.

5. Research Results

5.1 Model Performance on General Metrics

The GAI-LENS model demonstrated high performance on general metrics, with an overall accuracy of 87.3% in identifying legal risks and 83.5% in identifying ethical issues.

Table 1: Model Performance on General Metrics

Metric	GAI-LENS	Baseline Model 1	Baseline Model 2	Expert Assessment
Accuracy	87.3%	62.1%	71.4%	91.2%
Precision	89.5%	58.3%	73.8%	93.1%
Recall	84.7%	59.4%	68.2%	88.7%
F1 Score	87.0%	58.8%	70.9%	90.8%
Legal Sensitivity Index (LSI)	91.3%	63.5%	72.1%	94.2%
Ethical Coverage Ratio (ECR)	83.5%	52.1%	66.7%	89.3%
Interpretative Consistency Score (ICS)	85.2%	49.7%	64.3%	82.1%

Note: LSI measures the model's ability to identify legally significant risks; ECR evaluates coverage across ethical dimensions; ICS assesses consistency in interpretation across different contexts.

GAI-LENS achieves significant improvement compared to baseline models and approaches the performance of human experts in most metrics. Particularly notable is the Legal Sensitivity Index (LSI), indicating the model's high ability to identify significant legal risks.

5.2 Analysis of Case Studies

Table 2: Representative Case Studies

Case	Content Type	GAI-LENS Assessment	Expert Assessment	Notes
1	LLM Text	High risk: Copyright infringement (92%)	High risk: Copyright infringement	Successfully identified almost exact copying of protected content
2	Generative Image	Medium risk: Privacy (67%), Trademark (59%)	Medium risk: Privacy, Trademark	Correct identification of a public figure and blurred trademark
3	Generative Code	Low risk (12%)	Low risk	Correct identification of original code without infringements
4	Mixed Content	High risk: Misleading information (87%)	High risk: Misleading information	Accurate identification of mismatch between data in text and attached graph

Case	Content Type	GAI-LENS Assessment	Expert Assessment	Notes
5	LLM Text	Medium risk: Bias (53%)	High risk: Bias (78%)	Gap in identifying subtle biases in biographical content
6	Social Media Post	High risk: Defamation (88%), Privacy (72%)	High risk: Defamation, Privacy	Successfully identified potentially defamatory AI-generated content about a public figure
7	AI-Generated News	High risk: Misinformation (94%)	High risk: Misinformation	Excellent detection of fabricated quotes and events in news-style content

The case studies illustrate the model's high capabilities in identifying prominent issues alongside ongoing challenges in assessing subtle biases and complex contextual considerations.

5.3 Performance by Risk Categories

Analysis shows that model performance varies between risk categories, with special capabilities in identifying intellectual property risks and factual falsehoods, and lower performance in identifying subtle cultural biases. Compared to previous models, GAI-LENS shows a 23% improvement in alerting to privacy risks and an 18% improvement in identifying intellectual property infringements.

5.4 Error Case Analysis

Systematic analysis of error cases revealed that the most common errors relate to assessment of "border areas" in fair use issues, identification of subtle cultural biases, and privacy assessment in complex contexts. In borderline fair use cases, the model tended to be more conservative than human experts, with a tendency to assess higher risk in cases of protected content used for criticism, parody, or derivative work.

5.5 Results on Simulated Social Media Scenarios

When tested on synthetic data designed to simulate social media content characteristics, GAI-LENS demonstrated:

- Highest accuracy on scenarios simulating Twitter/X-style content (91.2%), followed by Facebook-style (88.7%), Instagram-style (85.4%), and TikTok-style content (83.1%)
- Strongest performance on text-dominant simulated content (90.5%), followed by text-image combinations (87.2%), and simulated multimodal content with video elements (81.8%)
- Increased sensitivity when analyzing scenarios designed to mimic potentially viral content, with precision improving to 92.4% for simulated high-engagement content
- Correct identification of 89.7% of simulated cases involving multi-jurisdictional legal risks in international social media contexts

These findings from simulated scenarios suggest GAI-LENS has promising potential for future application to actual social media environments, pending validation with real-world data.

6. Discussion of Results

The performance of GAI-LENS on our synthetic dataset highlights several important insights. The gap between the model's performance and human experts has narrowed significantly compared to previous models, especially in identifying intellectual property infringements and misleading

information. As Gebru et al. (2021) note, "automatic classification of legal risks reaches performance levels that allow practical use of these systems as an aid to human experts" (p. 90).

However, persistent gaps in identifying subtle cultural biases and ethical "gray areas" highlight the complexity of these considerations. Our findings support a hybrid approach, combining algorithmic analysis with human judgment in complex issues, particularly in real-world implementation contexts.

The model's tendency for "over-conservatism" in borderline fair use cases raises questions about balancing risk prevention and enabling innovation. Benjamin (2019) notes that "automatic risk assessment systems tend to bias the balance toward risk prevention, which may create a chilling effect on innovation and creativity" (p. 112). This observation is particularly relevant when considering the translation from synthetic training environments to dynamic real-world applications.

Compared to previous research, GAI-LENS offers several advantages:

- Broader coverage of risk categories
- Integration of legal and ethical considerations in a unified framework
- Ability to provide explanations for decisions through techniques like SHAP

The findings carry practical implications for AI developers, regulatory compliance, and risk management, while contributing theoretically to understanding the interface between legal and ethical considerations. The synthetic data approach itself represents a methodological contribution, demonstrating how controlled scenario development can systematically evaluate complex legal and ethical frameworks.

For potential social media applications specifically, our simulation results suggest GAI-LENS could offer implementation pathways including content moderation augmentation, user feedback systems, creator tools, policy enforcement, and cross-platform coordination. These projections would require validation with actual platform data in future research.

Despite promising results, several limitations must be acknowledged, including synthetic database constraints, regulatory landscape changes, contextual challenges in transferring to real-world scenarios, and technical limitations regarding multimodal content processing. The gap between synthetic simulations and real-world implementation represents both a limitation of the current study and an opportunity for future research.

7. Conclusions

This research developed and evaluated the GAI-LENS model as a systematic framework for assessing legal and ethical risks in generative content through synthetic data simulation. Key findings include:

- High accuracy in identifying legal (87.3%) and ethical (83.5%) risks with test scenarios
- Classification of main risks into central categories, with particular focus on intellectual property, privacy, misinformation, and bias risks
- Identification of factors significantly affecting risk levels

The GAI-LENS model provides a prototype for tools that could support technology developers, regulatory compliance, and best practices for users, representing a promising approach to responsible AI development. Our research suggests potential to bridge the gap between technological capabilities and responsible deployment, especially in high-velocity information environments like social media.

Future research directions include cross-cultural expansion, development of adaptive models, integration of participatory approaches, and development of context-dependent metrics. For social

media applications, future work should focus on validation with real-world data, real-time assessment capabilities, cross-platform content tracking, and integration with recommendation systems.

The implications of this research extend beyond the immediate findings. For scientific modeling, GAI-LENS provides a methodological blueprint for integrating legal and ethical considerations into technical frameworks. Future research should expand to real-world data validation across diverse cultural and legal contexts, examining how risk patterns evolve in production environments. For practitioners, this framework offers a starting point for developing implementable risk mitigation strategies and compliance mechanisms that could be incorporated into content moderation systems. The modular architecture enables adaptation to evolving regulatory landscapes while maintaining consistent evaluation criteria. This balance between theoretical exploration through synthetic data and potential practical applicability positions GAI-LENS as a promising foundation for responsible AI governance research.

Acknowledgement

This paper presents a condensed version of our comprehensive research on generative AI risk assessment using synthetic data simulation. The complete study, spanning approx. 40 pages, contains detailed descriptions of the statistical models, all 200 synthetic evaluation scenarios, full annotated dataset specifications, and Python implementation code for generating the synthetic data, model training, and evaluation. In the spirit of open science, these extended resources are freely available to interested scholars and researchers upon request. We welcome academic engagement with our methodologies and findings to further develop robust frameworks for ethical and legal risk assessment in artificial intelligence applications. Future collaborative work could explore validating these synthetic findings in real-world contexts, expanding the framework to additional domains, and adapting the methodology for emerging AI technologies.

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RISK AVOIDANCE IN DIGITAL INTERACTION: RISK-AVERSION AND DEMOGRAPHIC DETERMINANTS OF SOCIAL NETWORK USAGE

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Social networking sites; use, risk aversion; demographic factors

Abstract

This paper aims to bridge this knowledge gap by investigating how risk-aversion, along with demographic characteristics—namely gender and age—affect the frequency of SNS use among university students. Respondents indicated their usage frequency for eleven widely-used SNSs: Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, TikTok, V Kontakte, Snapchat, and Tinder. Frequency was measured using a six-point ordinal scale, ranging from continuous online presence to absence of account ownership. Risk-aversion was quantified on a ten-point Likert scale, with higher scores representing greater risk-aversion. Ordinal regression analysis was performed to evaluate the predictive power of risk-aversion, gender, and age on SNS usage frequencies. Initial results reveal significant associations between higher risk-aversion and decreased engagement levels across multiple SNS platforms. Additionally, demographic factors played a notable role, with gender-specific preferences identified. Men and women demonstrated varying patterns of SNS usage frequency, suggesting different risk-related behaviors and perceptions.

1. Introduction

In recent years, social networking sites (SNSs) have profoundly reshaped interpersonal communication, consumption patterns, and information dissemination, becoming integral to daily routines, particularly among young adults and university students (Boyd & Ellison, 2007; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). The rapid proliferation and diversification of SNSs, each serving distinct communicative, entertainment, informational, or professional purposes, have prompted researchers to extensively investigate the numerous factors influencing user engagement, usage frequency, and platform-specific preferences (Ellison, Steinfield, & Lampe, 2011). This inquiry is driven by the recognition that SNSs represent multifaceted environments where users participate actively in content creation, information exchange, and community building, influencing both individual behavior and broader social dynamics.

Prior research consistently highlights demographic variables, particularly age and gender, as significant factors shaping SNS usage patterns. Studies indicate that younger users, typically

categorized as digital natives, exhibit notably higher engagement levels, reflecting both their familiarity with digital technologies and their greater reliance on these platforms for social interactions and identity expression compared to older demographics (Perrin, 2015). Furthermore, substantial variations exist in how genders interact with different SNSs, suggesting platform-specific gender-based preferences that may result from underlying psychological, communicational, or cultural differences. For instance, previous findings reveal distinct gendered patterns, with certain platforms more frequently adopted by women for social and relational activities, whereas others tend to attract male users for professional networking or informational purposes (Sheldon & Bryant, 2016).

In addition to demographic characteristics, individual psychological traits have gained significant scholarly attention as critical determinants influencing technology adoption and the frequency of SNS use. Among these psychological attributes, risk-aversion stands out as a particularly salient factor. Risk-aversion characterizes an individual's general tendency to avoid uncertainty and potential negative outcomes, a propensity that can significantly affect decision-making processes across a diverse range of contexts, including financial investments, consumer behaviors, and the use of digital and sharing economy services such as Airbnb (Weber, Blais, & Betz, 2002; Einav et al., 2012). Given the inherent uncertainties and perceived risks associated with privacy, security, and social exposure on SNSs, it is plausible to hypothesize that risk-aversion similarly shapes users' decisions regarding their frequency and intensity of engagement with these platforms.

2. Theoretical background

The rise of social networking sites (SNSs) as dominant communication platforms has prompted a growing body of theoretical work aimed at understanding user behaviors, motivations, and engagement patterns. The uses and gratifications theory (UGT) provides a foundational framework for explaining SNS use, suggesting that individuals actively select media to satisfy specific needs such as information seeking, entertainment, personal identity, and social interaction (Katz, Blumler, & Gurevitch, 1973; Papacharissi & Rubin, 2000). This theoretical lens positions users not as passive recipients of content but as goal-oriented agents making conscious choices about which platforms to engage with based on their unique gratifications.

Social capital theory further enriches our understanding of SNS engagement by emphasizing the ways in which online interactions contribute to the accumulation of social resources. According to Ellison, Steinfield, and Lampe (2011), SNSs facilitate both bonding social capital, which strengthens close personal relationships, and bridging social capital, which extends users' networks to more distant acquaintances. These dual pathways have profound implications for how different demographics leverage SNSs for social and professional benefits, influencing their platform preferences and intensity of use (Williams, 2006).

Demographic variables such as age and gender have been consistently shown to moderate patterns of SNS usage. Younger users, often referred to as digital natives (Prensky, 2001), typically demonstrate higher levels of comfort and reliance on SNSs compared to older cohorts. Gender differences also play a pivotal role, with research suggesting that women are more likely to use SNSs for maintaining social relationships and emotional expression, whereas men may favor platforms that facilitate professional networking or access to information (Sheldon & Bryant, 2016; Muscanell & Guadagno, 2012). These demographic distinctions suggest that SNS engagement is not monolithic but instead shaped by intersecting social factors.

Beyond demographics, psychological traits provide a critical lens for analyzing technology adoption and engagement behaviors. Risk-aversion, in particular, offers a compelling explanatory variable. Individuals with high risk-aversion tendencies may perceive greater threats associated with online

interactions, including concerns about privacy, data security, and social judgment (Weber, Blais, & Betz, 2002). Such apprehensions could deter frequent or intensive SNS use, or alternatively, steer users toward platforms perceived as safer or offering greater control over self-presentation and information sharing (Bansal, Zahedi, & Gefen, 2016).

Existing research on technology adoption models, such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, & Davis, 2003), also points to perceived risk as a significant inhibitor of user acceptance and sustained engagement. While these models primarily focus on functional perceptions such as usefulness and ease of use, later extensions have increasingly incorporated psychological barriers like risk perception (Featherman & Pavlou, 2003). Integrating these models with an understanding of individual differences in risk-aversion offers a more nuanced view of SNS usage behaviors across diverse user populations.

Given this theoretical backdrop, the current study positions risk-aversion alongside demographic variables of age and gender to comprehensively examine their combined effects on SNS usage patterns. By doing so, it seeks to address a notable gap in the literature: the limited attention to how intrinsic psychological traits interact with extrinsic social factors to shape digital behaviors. Understanding these dynamics is essential for designing more inclusive digital platforms and for tailoring communication strategies to diverse user profiles (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010).

3. Methodology

A questionnaire was designed to collect information on usage of social networking sites, demographic characteristics and risk-aversion levels. Data were collected using a web-based survey on 1ka.si. The sample consisted of 529 respondents (289 men and 240 women). Convenience sampling was used; respondents were university students. Respondents did not receive any monetary nor any other type of incentives. Approximately 95% of the respondents were 24 years old or younger.

For the purpose of this research, following social networking sites were included in the questionnaire: Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, TikTok, V Kontakte, Snapchat, Tinder.

These were measured on an ordinal scale where 1 meant online connected, 2 meant 1x daily, 3 meant 1x weekly, 4 meant 1x monthly, 5 meant “I have an account, but I do not use it”, and 6 meant “I do not have an account”. These were used as dependent variables.

The independent variable was risk-aversion. It was measured on a 1-10 Likert scale inspired by (Dohmen et al., 2011) where 1 meant risk-loving, and 10 meant risk-aversion. This variable is different from the perceived risk variable used, for example, in modified Technology Acceptance Models or modified Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology models. Control variables were gender, and age.

Ordinal regression function of IBM SPSS 27 will be used to test how risk-aversion, gender, and age influence use of social networking sites. A variance inflation factor (VIF) will be used to evaluate the extent of multicollinearity.

4. Results

Since all models in this section have the same independent (and control) variables, it is enough to test VIFs in any one model. All VIFs were lower than 1.06, therefore, collinearity is not a problem in any

of the models. The ordinal regression model of the impact of risk aversion, age, and gender on use of Facebook is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Ordinal regression model for Facebook

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
use = 1	-1.037	0.849	1.491	1	0.222
use = 2	-0.172	0.849	0.041	1	0.840
use = 3	0.574	0.852	0.454	1	0.500
use = 4	0.844	0.855	0.975	1	0.323
use = 5	2.600	0.906	8.235	1	0.004
Age	-0.096	0.040	5.871	1	0.015
Risk aversion	0.088	0.042	4.276	1	0.039
Gender = male	-0.026	0.179	0.020	1	0.886
Gender = female	0 ^a	.	.	0	.

Legend: a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

Source: (author)

Risk aversion and age impact use of Facebook. Risk-averse people use it more, and older use it more. With regards to the explanatory power, Cox and Snell pseudo-R² is 0.020, Nagelkerke pseudo-R² is 0.022, McFadden pseudo-R² is 0.008, and the significance of the model fit is 0.014.

The ordinal regression model of the impact of risk aversion, age, and gender on use of WhatsApp is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Ordinal regression model for WhatsApp

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
use = 1	-4.191	0.823	25.921	1	0.000
use = 2	-3.510	0.817	18.450	1	0.000
use = 3	-2.842	0.814	12.205	1	0.000
use = 4	-2.401	0.812	8.733	1	0.003
use = 5	-1.505	0.814	3.417	1	0.065
Age	-0.192	0.039	24.930	1	0.000
Risk aversion	0.044	0.038	1.347	1	0.246
Gender = male	0.319	0.162	3.871	1	0.049
Gender = female	0 ^a	.	.	0	.

Legend: a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

Source: (author)

Gender and age impact use of WhatsApp. Men use it less, and older use it more.

With regards to the explanatory power, Cox and Snell pseudo-R² is 0.059, Nagelkerke pseudo-R² is 0.061, McFadden pseudo-R² is 0.018, and the significance of the model fit is below 0.001.

The ordinal regression model of the impact of risk aversion, age, and gender on use of Instagram is provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Ordinal regression model for Instagram

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
use = 1	4.306	0.773	31.050	1	0.000
use = 2	5.195	0.786	43.737	1	0.000
use = 3	5.520	0.791	48.648	1	0.000
use = 4	5.586	0.793	49.666	1	0.000
use = 5	5.988	0.802	55.793	1	0.000
Age	0.143	0.034	17.572	1	0.000
Risk aversion	-0.039	0.048	0.668	1	0.414
Gender = male	0.869	0.216	16.163	1	0.000
Gender = female	0 ^a	.	.	0	.

Legend: a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

Source: (author)

Gender and age impact use of Instagram. Men use it less, and older use it less.

With regards to the explanatory power, Cox and Snell pseudo-R² is 0.072, Nagelkerke pseudo-R² is 0.086, McFadden pseudo-R² is 0.041, and the significance of the model fit is below 0.001.

The ordinal regression model of the impact of risk aversion, age, and gender on use of TikTok is provided in Table 4.

Table 4. Ordinal regression model for TikTok

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
use = 1	2.242	0.891	6.330	1	0.012
use = 2	2.729	0.892	9.369	1	0.002
use = 3	3.044	0.893	11.618	1	0.001
use = 4	3.167	0.894	12.563	1	0.000
use = 5	3.661	0.897	16.660	1	0.000
Age	0.156	0.042	13.868	1	0.000
Risk aversion	0.047	0.041	1.332	1	0.248
Gender = male	0.553	0.172	10.369	1	0.001
Gender = female	0 ^a	.	.	0	.

Legend: a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

Source: (author)

Gender and age impact use of TikTok. Men use it less, and older use it less.

With regards to the explanatory power, Cox and Snell pseudo-R² is 0.056, Nagelkerke pseudo-R² is 0.060, McFadden pseudo-R² is 0.021, and the significance of the model fit is below 0.001.

The ordinal regression model of the impact of risk aversion, age, and gender on use of Vkontakte is provided in Table 5.

Table 5. Ordinal regression model for Vkontakte

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
use = 1	0.819	1.198	0.467	1	0.494
use = 2	1.550	1.194	1.685	1	0.194
use = 3	1.855	1.193	2.415	1	0.120
use = 4	1.994	1.193	2.790	1	0.095
use = 5	2.311	1.194	3.744	1	0.053
Age	0.138	0.057	5.876	1	0.015
Risk aversion	0.100	0.051	3.818	1	0.051
Gender = male	0.355	0.216	2.711	1	0.100
Gender = female	0 ^a	.	.	0	.

Legend: a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

Source: (author)

Age impact use of Vkontakte. Older use it less.

With regards to the explanatory power, Cox and Snell pseudo-R² is 0.026, Nagelkerke pseudo-R² is 0.031, McFadden pseudo-R² is 0.015, and the significance of the model fit is 0.003.

The ordinal regression model of the impact of risk aversion, age, and gender on use of Snapchat is provided in Table 6.

Table 6. Ordinal regression model for Snapchat

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
use = 1	2.579	0.896	8.279	1	0.004
use = 2	3.238	0.896	13.065	1	0.000
use = 3	3.466	0.896	14.948	1	0.000
use = 4	3.576	0.897	15.902	1	0.000
use = 5	4.855	0.907	28.660	1	0.000
Age	0.218	0.043	26.211	1	0.000
Risk aversion	-0.021	0.039	0.273	1	0.601
Gender = male	0.348	0.167	4.344	1	0.037
Gender = female	0 ^a	.	.	0	.

Legend: a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

Source: (author)

Gender and age impact use of Snapchat. Men use it less, and older use it less.

With regards to the explanatory power, Cox and Snell pseudo-R² is 0.078, Nagelkerke pseudo-R² is 0.083, McFadden pseudo-R² is 0.029, and the significance of the model fit is below 0.001.

The ordinal regression model of the impact of risk aversion, age, and gender on use of Tinder is provided in Table 7.

Table 7. Ordinal regression model for Tinder

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
use = 1	-3.785	0.829	20.834	1	0.000
use = 2	-2.714	0.799	11.534	1	0.001
use = 3	-2.224	0.793	7.866	1	0.005
use = 4	-2.000	0.791	6.394	1	0.011
use = 5	-1.099	0.786	1.953	1	0.162
Age	-0.013	0.036	0.127	1	0.721
Risk aversion	0.096	0.048	4.028	1	0.045
Gender = male	-0.572	0.209	7.481	1	0.006
Gender = female	0 ^a	.	.	0	.

Legend: a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

Source: (author)

Risk aversion and gender impact use of Tinder. Risk-averse people use it more, and men use it more; the latter is consistent with (Jiménez-Muro et al., 2024).

With regards to the explanatory power, Cox and Snell pseudo-R² is 0.028, Nagelkerke pseudo-R² is 0.033, McFadden pseudo-R² is 0.015, and the significance of the model fit is 0.002.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that risk-aversion, gender, and age significantly influence how university students engage with different social networking platforms. Risk-averse individuals tend to use Facebook and Tinder more frequently, possibly due to perceived control or specific gratifications these platforms offer. Men are less active on WhatsApp, Instagram, TikTok, and Snapchat, but more active on Tinder. Older students prefer Facebook and WhatsApp, while younger users are more engaged with Instagram, TikTok, V kontakte, and Snapchat.

These findings highlight the importance of considering both psychological traits and demographic factors when analyzing digital behavior. They also suggest that platform-specific strategies may be necessary to address the diverse needs and concerns of different user segments. The relatively low pseudo-R² values across models suggest that while demographic and psychological traits are significant, other unmeasured factors—such as peer influence, platform design, or cultural context—may also play a substantial role in SNS usage patterns.

Future research should explore additional personality traits, incorporate behavioral data, and consider longitudinal or cross-cultural designs to deepen our understanding of the evolving dynamics of SNS usage.

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MISINFORMATION AND INFLUENCE OPERATIONS IN ELECTIONS: GLOBAL TRENDS AND THE 2024 ROMANIAN CASE

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Abstract

The integrity of democratic elections is increasingly undermined by digital misinformation and influence operations. This article examines the 2024 Romanian presidential election—annulled due to foreign interference—as a case study through which to explore the evolving threats of algorithmic manipulation and hybrid disinformation tactics. Using the IMRaD framework, we investigate the mechanisms of modern influence operations, including platform algorithms, social media bots, deepfakes, cyberattacks, and covert influencer marketing. Drawing on empirical studies, official reports, and academic research from various sources, we synthesize a global pattern of election manipulation that exploits societal divisions and algorithmic vulnerabilities. Our findings show that misinformation not only skews voter perceptions but also erodes democratic legitimacy and public trust. The discussion evaluates current countermeasures—from legal and regulatory frameworks to platform-level enforcement and media literacy initiatives—highlighting the challenges and trade-offs democracies face in balancing so called free speech with the need for integrity of information. We argue that a multi-layered, interdisciplinary approach is essential to build electoral resilience in the digital age, with the Romanian case offering both a warning and a blueprint for defensive innovation.

1. Introduction

"Dictatorship naturally arises out of democracy, and the most aggravated form of tyranny and slavery out of the most extreme liberty." said Plato in *The Republic* (Plato, 2007).

From Plato to contemporary scholars of liberal democracy, the process of election has symbolized the highest expression of political agency. However, in the age of algorithms, mathematical thinking and world of computers, this thought faces unprecedented threat. As social media platforms became space of political discourse and mediation of it, the democratic world is reshaped by their algorithms (Geddes 2024).

In late 2024, Romania's Constitutional Court took the unprecedented step of nullifying the first round of its presidential election due to evidence of foreign interference and coordinated misinformation (Mercescu 2025). A little-known outsider candidate had surged to a lead on the back of a stealth

social-media campaign, prompting allegations that Russian-backed influence operations had skewed the result. The court ordered the entire electoral process to be redone in May 2025. This dramatic crisis, unfolding in a NATO member state, underscores the new challenges facing elections worldwide in the age of algorithmic propaganda and “fake news.” This annulled election offers a vivid case study of how these forces can play out and how institutions might respond. The presidential candidate named Călin Georgescu came out from obscurity to front-runner by viral TikTok videos and coordinated online promotion. Intelligence reports later revealed that his popularity on the media was not organic as hundreds of dormant social media accounts and paid influencers had boosted Georgescu’s candidacy, also with potential backing from a state-sponsored Russian campaign as it happened also in other countries (Bailey, 2024).

This article uses the Romanian case as a narrative thread through which we examine the broader phenomenon of election misinformation and foreign influence operations. We first outline the technical methods and channels through which modern influence campaigns operate, from social-media algorithms to bots and deepfakes. We then present findings and references to recent research and global case studies that reveal common patterns and dangers of these operations. Finally, we discuss how governments, platforms, and communities/societies are responding.

2. Methods

Article employs a systematic literature review as its primary methodological approach, complemented by an illustrative case study analysis. The literature review involved an extensive examination of peer-reviewed articles, official intelligence and judiciary reports, and authoritative analyses published between 2017 and 2025. Databases utilized include Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science, focused on themes of election misinformation, algorithmic manipulation, digital hybrid interference, and the societal impacts of disinformation campaigns. The Romanian presidential election annulment in 2024 serves as a central illustrative case study and is demonstrating a one occurrence of democratic erosion driven by foreign-backed misinformation. By synthesizing insights from global instances and existing academic literature, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of mechanisms, strategies, and consequences of digital influence operations on democratic processes.

3. Results

Results section presents Romanian 2024 Election, illustrating how digital misinformation campaigns, algorithmic manipulation, and foreign interference strategies were systematically deployed to disrupt democratic processes and influence electoral outcomes.

3.1 Romanian Presidential Election 2024: Case study

The annulment of Romania’s 2024 presidential election was unprecedented in European democratic environment. On November 24, 2024, Călin Georgescu, a pro-Russian nationalist candidate, unexpectedly won the first round with 22.94% of the vote. His rapid rise was attributed to a coordinated misinformation campaign that leveraged social media platforms to manipulate public opinion and amplify his rhetoric (Damian, 2024; Stănescu, 2024). The Constitutional Court’s decision to annul the election on December 6 underscored the vulnerabilities of democratic systems to hybrid warfare tactics, combining algorithmic manipulation and covert influence operations (Cartabia et al., 2025; NATO Review, 2025).

3.1.1 Disinformation Campaigns and Social Media Manipulation

Georgescu’s campaign relied heavily on TikTok and Telegram to disseminate emotionally charged and polarizing content. TikTok’s algorithm played a central role in amplifying his message, with over 25,000 accounts—many linked to Russian operatives—actively promoting pro-Georgescu narratives (Kleczkowska, 2025; NATO Review, 2025). These videos portrayed Georgescu as a patriotic savior while framing mainstream candidates as corrupt elites with foreign interests. The campaign also employed paid influencers who shared pre-drafted content without disclosing its political nature. Intelligence reports suggested that millions of euros might have been funneled into these operations through opaque channels, including cryptocurrency transactions (Olejnik, 2024; Bloom, 2025).

Telegram further complemented TikTok by hosting regional groups that tailored messages to local concerns. This strategy mimicked techniques previously observed in other Eastern European elections and demonstrated a sophisticated understanding of Romania’s societal divisions (NATO Review, 2025). As Cartabia et al. (2025) noted, “the manipulation of digital technologies during the campaign distorted the will of the electorate and violated the principle of equal opportunity among candidates.”

3.1.2 Implications for Democracy

The Romanian case highlights systemic vulnerabilities in countering algorithm-driven disinformation. NATO analysts described it as an example of “algorithmic invasions,” where adversaries weaponize digital platforms to destabilize democracies without direct physical interference (NATO Review, 2025). Although Romania has since implemented stricter regulations and partnered with EU cybersecurity agencies to address these threats, experts warn that similar tactics could destabilize other democracies if left unchecked (Cartabia et al., 2025; EDMO Bulletin, 2025). Public awareness to this concern begins to rise as Misinformation and disinformation are ranked number 1 in Global risks for next 2 years in World Economic Forum survey from 2024 as can be seen in Figure 1.

Rank	Short-Term (0–2 years)	Long-Term (10 years)
1	Misinformation and disinformation	Extreme weather events
2	Extreme weather events	Critical change to Earth systems
3	Societal polarization	Biodiversity loss and ecosystem collapse
4	Cyber insecurity	Natural resource shortages
5	Interstate armed conflict	Misinformation and disinformation
6	Lack of economic opportunity	Cyber insecurity
7	Inflation	Societal polarization
8	Involuntary migration	Adverse outcomes of AI technologies
9	Economic downturn	Involuntary migration
10	Pollution	Infectious diseases

Figure 1. Global risks ranked by severity over the short and long term Source: (World Economic Forum, 2024)

3.2 How Modern Influence Operations Work

Modern influence campaigns thrive on the architecture of digital media—combining algorithmic amplification, synthetic content, psychological targeting, and cyber intrusions to sway public opinion

and disrupt elections (Anderson, 2021). These operations manipulate both the technical infrastructure of the internet and the behavioral patterns of users.

3.2.1 Algorithmic Amplification and the Attention Economy

Social media platforms like TikTok, Facebook, YouTube, and X (formerly Twitter) are built to maximize user engagement. Their opaque algorithms prioritize content that sparks emotional reactions—often giving misinformation an edge over facts (Bakir & McStay, 2022). A landmark MIT study found that false news spreads “farther, faster, deeper, and more broadly” than true news on Twitter, driven largely by humans, not bots (Vosoughi et al., 2018).

“Facebook papers” suggest that the Hyper-optimization contest between teams behind recommending algorithms focuses strictly on the fact that people experience dopamine production in their bodies while watching content and consume it (Larsen, 2022). Influencers and other actors exploit this system. During Romania’s 2024 elections, the ultranationalist candidate Georgescu and his TikTok hashtags and slogans dominated user feeds thanks to algorithmic boosts based on questionable content consumption. His campaign used short, emotional videos that framed him as a patriotic outsider and scapegoated the EU and Ukraine for economic troubles—messages designed for virality (Ghergina 2025). This gave rise to a perception of mass support that wasn’t rooted in traditional media coverage, but in an algorithmic “illusion”.

3.2.2 Bots, Trolls, and Coordinated Inauthentic Activity

A core tactic is the use of bots—automation algorithms or programs that amplify messages at scale—and troll farms that flood platforms with coordinated propaganda (DiResta, 2021). In the 2016 U.S. election, just 6% of Twitter accounts (likely bots) were responsible for spreading 31% of low-credibility content (Alexendre, 2021). These bots work fast to promote falsehoods during the critical early period before stories go viral.

In Romania, investigators uncovered a surge in bot-driven promotion of Georgescu, including \$380,000 in undeclared spending on TikTok ads—often from dormant or newly created accounts that suddenly began posting in sync (Ghergina 2025). Similar coordinated activity on Facebook and Telegram created the illusion of grassroots enthusiasm and propelled fringe talking points into the mainstream.

3.2.3 Deepfakes and Synthetic Media

Deepfakes—AI-generated audio or video that mimic real people—have emerged as potent tools in disinformation campaigns (Whyte, 2020). In Slovakia’s 2023 election, a deepfake audio clip falsely depicting an opposition leader plotting election fraud went viral just before voting, likely swaying the outcome (Labuz, 2024). Even low-tech “cheapfakes” (manipulated clips or fake subtitles) can mislead viewers, as seen in Romania’s election where edited videos misrepresented rivals’ positions (Ghergina 2025). These technologies not only spread lies but also foster cynicism. As deepfakes become more convincing, the public start to doubt real evidence—a phenomenon known as the “liar’s dividend” (Zhou, 2023). This is actually the real problem behind deepfakes as people start to doubt everything and all fact-checkers.

3.2.4 Encrypted Echo Chambers

Disinformation doesn’t just spread in public feeds—it thrives in private digital spaces. Encrypted apps like WhatsApp, Telegram, and Signal are increasingly used to distribute rumors and conspiracy theories beyond the reach of fact-checkers (Schulze, 2022). In Brazil’s 2018 election, misinformation

flooded WhatsApp groups, and by the time journalists could respond, falsehoods had already taken root (Machado, 2019). In Romania in 2024 pro-Georgescu content circulated widely in secretive Telegram channels like “Real Patriots Romania.” These echo chambers created tight communities where false narratives went unchallenged and became truths among members (Ghergina 2025).

3.3 Patterns and Impacts of Election Misinformation

3.3.1 A Global Strategy of Disruption

Over the past decade, election interference has followed a disturbingly consistent playbook. Authoritarian regimes—particularly Russia—have repeatedly used disinformation to amplify polarizing, anti-establishment voices in democratic societies (Eichhorn, 2022). These operations don't invent grievances out of thin air; they seize on existing fault lines—economic frustration, ethnic divisions, political distrust—and weaponize them.

The Romanian election in 2024 followed this exact pattern. The sudden rise of the ultranationalist candidate Georgescu was driven by narratives framing Western alliances like the EU and NATO as sources of national decline, echoing long-standing anti-elite sentiments in parts of the country (Soare, 2023). This isn't new. In the 2016 U.S. election, Russian operatives stoked outrage across ideological lines, using fake accounts to both promote and provoke—fueling racial tensions and mistrust in institutions, not just boosting one candidate (Freelon, 2020). The 2020 election saw similar tactics, with Kremlin-linked actors amplifying Donald Trump's false claims of election fraud, converging with domestic conspiracy theorists and pushing millions of Americans into deep skepticism about the electoral process (Golovchenko, 2020). The goal is almost never just to help one figure win—it's to corrode trust, deepen divisions, and undermine democratic legitimacy from within.

Similar efforts have hit France, Germany, Slovakia, and Italy. The 2017 MacronLeaks incident saw stolen documents—some genuine, others forged—released right before the French election, clearly timed to influence the outcome (Sobanet, 2020). This trend is especially potent in young democracies or regions with low public confidence in the media and government. One disinformation campaign doesn't have to change every mind—it only needs to tip a few perceptions at the right moment to alter outcomes.

3.3.2 Behavioral Shifts and Long-Term Damage

The most pressing question remains: do these misinformation campaigns actually change election results? While it's difficult to prove direct vote-switching, the evidence suggests they often do something subtler but just as powerful—distorting voter behavior (Wilder, 2017). Misinformation can suppress turnout, push fence-sitters toward extremes, or sow so much doubt that people disengage altogether.

Beyond short-term disruption, the deeper harm lies in the erosion of public trust. As voters are bombarded with conflicting claims and fake scandals, many lose faith in the very idea of truth in politics. In the U.S., confidence in the integrity of elections has plunged, especially among those fed a steady diet of misinformation (Zhou, 2023).

3.3.3 Fighting Back: Policies and Platforms

In response to these threats, governments and tech platforms are scrambling to adapt. France, after being hit in 2017, passed a controversial law enabling rapid judicial takedowns of false election content (Dubois, 2020). Germany's NetzDG law forced social platforms to act against illegal material, while Sweden launched a dedicated Psychological Defence Agency to identify and counter

foreign disinformation (Saurwein, 2020). The EU, meanwhile, strengthened its Code of Practice on Disinformation and now links it to the Digital Services Act, requiring major tech firms to audit their platforms for manipulation risks (Turillazzi, 2023). Romania's response to its 2024 crisis drew heavily on these models. Authorities nullified the compromised result and worked with EU partners to demand transparency from platforms like TikTok. New rules are being considered to ensure that paid political content—especially via influencers—is clearly labeled (Harff, 2023). There's a growing realization that in the digital age, campaign finance laws must extend beyond billboards and television ads to include hashtags and meme pages.

Tech companies, for their part, have made uneven progress. Facebook and YouTube have deployed moderation tools, fact-checking partnerships, and political ad archives. Twitter (now X) and TikTok implemented election-specific policies, including labeling deepfakes and linking to official information. However, enforcement remains inconsistent. Platforms often scale up content moderation during high-profile elections, only to ease up later. And changes like Meta's shift toward "community" moderation—outsourcing corrections to users—are controversial. While this model should be more transparent, it's also vulnerable to crowd manipulation (Papakyriakopoulos, 2022).

3.3.4 The Human Firewall: Media Literacy and Civil Society

No technological or policy fix will work without an informed public. Many democracies are investing in media literacy—not just as a school subject, but as a core part of civic resilience. Finland's media literacy is woven into the national curriculum from primary school on. Students learn to spot disinformation techniques systematically (Horn, 2019). The result is that Finland consistently ranks among the most resilient countries to fake news in Europe (Bjola, 2020). There are more Media literacy campaigns across the world, like Taiwan's prebunking campaigns, fact-checking partnerships, and even viral humor to defang disinformation (Choo, 2022). These campaigns work not by eliminating lies, but by building up the public's immune system like vaccination against illnesses. When people understand how disinformation operates, they are better prepared to face it.

4. Discussion

The Romanian crisis was a wake-up call. A foreign-backed, algorithm-driven campaign came close to reshaping the political future of a European democracy—not through force, but through our homes (Soare, 2023). Going forward, democracies must balance urgent action with long-term reform. Emergency interventions—like annulling fraudulent results—may be necessary, but they also risk deepening the narrative of elite manipulation. The real solution lies in layered defenses: transparent platforms, resilient institutions, informed voters, and laws that adapt to the digital age without overreaching (Laebens, 2021). No single actor can solve this. Governments must lead but avoid censorship. Platforms must act responsibly, even if they cut profits. Civil society must educate and hold everyone accountable. And voters themselves must remain engaged, skeptical, and grounded in fact. Democracy has survived manipulation before—but in this era of AI-generated fakes, instant virality, and transnational influence, it will only survive if it evolves. Romania's case wasn't the last attempt. But if the lessons are learned, it doesn't have to be a precedent—it can be a turning point.

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MORE IS LESS? EXPLORING THE DILUTION EFFECT OF GROWING PUBLICATION NETWORK ON CITATION RATES IN HARD SCIENCES

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Abstract

In an era of rapidly expanding scientific output, researchers face a paradox: while a growing publication network increases the number of potential citers, it may simultaneously reduce the visibility of individual papers. This study explores this “dilution effect” using a dataset of 4,184 publications from 2005 to 2024 in physics, engineering, mathematics, and computer science. We modeled citation counts using a multivariate regression approach, incorporating total network size, publication age, and online dissemination metrics (mentions on blogs, Twitter, Facebook, and Mendeley). Our analysis confirms that although larger publication networks are associated with higher citation counts, the reciprocal of network size is also a significant predictor, suggesting that individual papers become harder to discover as the field grows – supporting the dilution hypothesis. Publication age negatively affects citation rates, indicating that older papers may become “lost” in publication networks, with interaction effects showing that aging has a stronger negative impact in smaller fields than in larger ones. Regarding online dissemination, blog mentions and Mendeley readerships significantly increased citation counts, while Twitter had a modest positive effect, and Facebook mentions were associated with a small but significant negative (!) effect. These findings suggest that long-form, research-oriented platforms may enhance scholarly visibility more effectively than short-form social media. Overall, the results provide insights into the dynamics of citation accumulation and highlight the complex relationship between scientific visibility, dissemination channels, and the size of the publication landscape, offering practical implications for optimizing research impact.

1. Introduction

Citations are a fundamental metric for measuring the academic visibility and perceived value of a scientific publication. A common assumption is that a larger publication network – defined by the total number of papers in a given field – increases the chances that a specific work will be cited, due to the massive number of potential citing sources. However, this growth also brings a paradox: in an

increasingly crowded field, individual publications may become harder to find, recognize, or cite. This trade-off, which we refer to as the *dilution effect*, suggests that while publication network size might positively influence citation opportunities, it can also negatively impact the discoverability of individual works.

The structure of citation networks has been widely studied using graph-theoretical approaches, in which scientific publications are modeled as nodes and citations as directed edges, forming an oriented graph or directed acyclic graph (DAG) (Newman 2001, Barabási et al. 2002). These networks exhibit complex topological properties such as preferential attachment and clustering, which have been shown to influence the evolution and distribution of citations (Štěpánek et al. 2024).

Moreover, the growth of scientific literature is far from linear. Several studies have documented that the number of scientific publications increases exponentially over time (Bornmann & Mutz 2015, Fortunato et al. 2018). This exponential growth not only inflates the citation network but also increases competition for scholarly attention, potentially reinforcing the dilution effect.

In addition to structural factors, citation rates are influenced by how scientific content is disseminated beyond traditional publishing. Alternative metrics (altmetrics), such as the number of mentions on platforms like Twitter, Facebook, academic blogs, and Mendeley, have been linked to increased visibility and higher citation counts (Eysenbach 2011, Shuai et al. 2012, Thelwall et al. 2013). Among these, blog mentions and Mendeley readership may be particularly impactful, as they typically provide longer, content-rich engagement with the material, compared to the fleeting exposure typical of social media posts.

While the positive effects of dissemination and network growth on citation rates have been explored, studies explicitly examining the dilution effect – i.e., the potential negative impact of large publication volumes on the visibility of individual works – are rare. To our best knowledge, this specific dynamic has not been systematically modeled or empirically verified in existing literature.

In this work, we investigate how citation counts are influenced by both the size of the publication network and the potential for dilution in visibility. Using a dataset of 4,184 publications from 2005 to 2024 across physics, engineering, mathematics, and computer science (sometimes collectively referred to as STEM, i.e., science, technology, engineering, and mathematics), we apply regression modeling with log-transformed citation counts to evaluate how network size, publication age, and online dissemination contribute to citation outcomes. In particular, we examine how citation rates vary with both the total number of publications in the field and the reciprocal of this number, reflecting the hypothesized dilution effect. We also assess the interaction between network size and publication age, and analyze the role of online exposure across multiple platforms.

The paper proceeds by outlining the data and modeling approach, presenting and interpreting the results, and discussing the implications of our findings for understanding scholarly impact in an increasingly crowded research environment.

2. Research methodology

This section describes the dataset and analytical methods used in the study. We first introduce the dataset of 4,184 publications spanning the fields of physics, engineering, mathematics, and computer science, including the collection of citation counts and online dissemination metrics. We then outline the regression modeling approach, which employs log-transformed citation counts as the dependent variable and includes predictors such as total publication network size, its reciprocal, publication age, interaction terms, and online exposure across various platforms. The aim is to quantitatively evaluate the relationship between publication network characteristics, online visibility, and citation outcomes.

2.1. Dataset used for the analysis

The dataset used in this study was obtained from Kaggle (Núñez 2024) and contains metadata on 4,184 research publications in physics, engineering, mathematics, and computer science. It covers publications published between September 22, 2005, and April 25, 2024. The dataset includes key information such as title, abstract, number of citations, number of accesses, online attention score, and publication date. It also captures online dissemination metrics, including the number of mentions on various platforms and academic engagement indicators. All dissemination metrics reflect counts collected up to April 25, 2024. The original variables used from the dataset are summarized in Table 1, while the derived variables created for this study are summarized in Table 2. These original and derived variables together form the basis for the regression modeling described in the following subsection.

Table 2. Original variables from the dataset used in the analysis.

variable name	description
citations	number of times the publication has been cited
publication_date	date when the publication was released
twitter_mentions	number of tweets mentioning the publication
blog_mentions	number of blog posts mentioning the publication
facebook_mentions	number of times the publication is shared or mentioned on Facebook pages
reddit_mentions	number of Reddit posts or discussions mentioning the publication
video_mentions	number of video uploads referencing the publication
wikipedia_presence	binary indicator of whether the publication has a corresponding Wikipedia page
mendeley_readers	number of times the publication has been saved in Mendeley

Table 3. Derived variables used in the analysis.

variable name	description
publication_age	number of days between the publication date and April 25, 2024
network_size_at_publication	cumulative number of publications up to the given publication date
network_size_reciprocal	reciprocal of the network size at publication time, modeling the dilution effect; obviously, it is equal to $= 1 / \text{network_size_at_publication}$
log_citations	natural logarithm of (citations + 0.5), normalizing the citation distribution

2.2. Multivariate regression model for estimating citation counts

To investigate the factors influencing citation counts, we constructed a multivariate linear regression model. The dependent variable is the natural logarithm of the number of citations plus a small constant, specifically $\text{log_citations} = \log(\text{citations} + 0.5)$. The logarithmic transformation is commonly applied to (not only) citation data because citation counts are highly

right-skewed, and log-scaling helps normalize the distribution to better satisfy the assumptions of linear regression, particularly homoscedasticity and normality of residuals (Kutner et al. 2005). The constant 0.5 is added to avoid undefined values when citations equal zero, ensuring that all observations are included in the analysis without introducing significant bias.

The regression model is schematically specified as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \log_citations &= \log(citations + 0.5) \\
 &= \\
 &= \beta_0 + \\
 &+ \beta_1 \cdot network_size_at_publication + \\
 &+ \beta_2 \cdot network_size_reciprocal + \\
 &+ \beta_3 \cdot publication_age + \\
 &+ \beta_4 \cdot network_size_at_publication \times publication_age + \\
 &+ \\
 &+ \beta_5 \cdot network_size_reciprocal \times publication_age + \\
 &+ \beta_6 \cdot twitter_mentions + \\
 &+ \beta_7 \cdot blog_mentions + \\
 &+ \beta_8 \cdot facebook_mentions + \\
 &+ \beta_9 \cdot reddit_mentions + \\
 &+ \beta_{10} \cdot video_mentions + \\
 &+ \beta_{11} \cdot wikipedia_presence + \\
 &+ \beta_{12} \cdot mendeley_readers + \\
 &+ \epsilon,
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where β_0 is the intercept, β_i for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, 12\}$ is the linear coefficient of i -th variable, and ϵ is the random error term. The interaction term $network_size_at_publication \times publication_age$ captures how the effect of publication age on citation counts depends on the size of the publication network, while the interaction term $network_size_reciprocal \times publication_age$ models how aging effects are influenced by the “dilution effect”, that is, how the ease or difficulty of citing older publications changes as the network grows.

Standard ordinary least squares (OLS) estimation was used to fit the model, following standard procedures for multiple regression analysis, as described in Kutner et al. (2005). The statistical significance of each estimated coefficient is assessed using p -values, representing the conditional probability of observing the estimated effect under the null hypothesis that the true coefficient equals zero. Coefficients with p -values below the conventional threshold of 0.05 are considered statistically significant and contribute meaningfully to explaining variation in citation counts.

3. Results

This section presents the results of the multivariate regression analysis aimed at identifying factors that influence the citation counts of scientific publications. Using R programming language and environment (R Core Team 2023), we summarize the estimated coefficients, assess their statistical

significance, and interpret the relationships between citation outcomes, publication network characteristics, publication age, and online dissemination metrics.

The fitted multivariate regression model, following formula (1), explains the variation in log-transformed citation counts using publication network size, publication age, and indicators of online dissemination. The model summary is in Table 3.

Table 4. Regression model summary for predicting log-transformed citation counts

variable, coefficient	estimate	standard error	t-value	p-value
(Intercept), β_0	9.283	0.509	18.233	< 0.0001
network_size_at_publication, β_1	-0.003	< 0.001	-27.629	< 0.0001
network_size_reciprocal, β_2	1935.000	710.300	2.724	0.0065
publication_age, β_3	-0.001	< 0.001	-22.774	< 0.0001
network_size_at_publication × publication_age, β_4	< 0.001	< 0.001	11.007	< 0.0001
network_size_reciprocal × publication_age, β_5	-0.284	0.105	-2.721	0.0065
twitter_mentions, β_6	0.001	< 0.001	2.488	0.0129
blog_mentions, β_7	0.025	0.008	3.148	0.0017
facebook_mentions, β_8	-0.017	0.006	-2.874	0.0041
reddit_mentions, β_9	0.029	0.032	0.905	0.3656
video_mentions, β_{10}	-0.018	0.039	-0.464	0.6430
wikipedia_presence, β_{11}	0.007	0.009	0.732	0.4643
mendeley_readers, β_{12}	0.004	< 0.001	38.184	< 0.0001

Since the dependent variable in the regression model is the natural logarithm of citation counts (plus a small constant, 0.5), the estimated coefficients can be interpreted as approximate percentage changes in the expected number of citations for a one-unit increase in each predictor. Exponentiating the coefficients provides a direct multiplicative effect on the original citation scale.

The **network size at publication** has a negative coefficient ($\beta_1 = -0.003$), $p < 0.0001$. Exponentiating, $\exp(\beta_1) = \exp(-0.003) \approx 0.997$, indicating that for each additional publication added to the field, the expected citation count for a new paper decreases by about **0.3 %**. This finding supports the idea that larger fields dilute the visibility of individual papers.

The **reciprocal of network size** ($\beta_2 = 1935 \gg 0$) has a positive and significant effect, $p \approx 0.0065$. Due to the scale of the variable, a direct exponentiation ($\exp(\beta_2) = \exp(1935)$) would not be interpretable. However, this coefficient suggests that when the field is relatively small (higher reciprocal value), the chance of being cited is substantially greater. In practice, this supports the *dilution effect* more strongly when fields are large.

The **publication age** has a negative coefficient ($\beta_3 = -0.001$), $p < 0.0001$, and $\exp(\beta_3) = \exp(-0.001) \approx 0.999$, indicating that each additional day since publication decreases expected citation counts by approximately **0.1 %**. Over time, older papers gradually lose visibility.

The **interaction between network size at publication and publication age** is positive ($\beta_4 = 0.0000001821 < 0.001$) with $p < 0.0001$, meaning that in larger networks, the negative effect of age is slightly mitigated – older papers in large fields may continue to gather citations over time, although the effect size is very small. In other words, in large publication networks, papers, particularly older ones, may still be cited, supporting the well-established idea that large networks attract multiple citers.

The **interaction between reciprocal network size and publication age** is negative ($\beta_5 = -0.284$), $p \approx 0.0065$, implying that in smaller fields (higher reciprocal value), papers lose their visibility more rapidly as they age.

In terms of **online dissemination**,

- **blog mentions** ($\beta_7 = 0.025$; $\exp(\beta_7) = \exp(0.025) \approx 1.025$), $p \approx 0.0017$, are associated with approximately a **2.5% increase** in expected citation counts per each blog mention.
- **Mendeley readership** ($\beta_{12} = 0.004$; $\exp(\beta_{12}) = \exp(0.004) \approx 1.004$), $p < 0.0001$, leads to about a **0.4% increase** in citations per additional reader.
- **Twitter mentions** ($\beta_6 = 0.001$; $\exp(\beta_6) = \exp(0.001) \approx 1.001$), $p \approx 0.0129$, correspond to a **0.1% increase** per tweet mentioning the paper.
- **Facebook mentions** have a negative coefficient ($\beta_8 = -0.017$; $\exp(\beta_8) = \exp(-0.017) \approx 0.983$), $p \approx 0.0041$, suggesting that each Facebook mention could slightly **decrease** expected citation counts **by about 1.7 %**.
- mentions in **Reddit, videos, and Wikipedia** did not show significant effects on citation counts.

Figure 1 presents a three-dimensional plot illustrating the dependence of citation counts on publication network size and publication age. The plot shows that citation counts are lower for younger publications, even when the publication network is large, supporting the dilution effect. Moreover, it clearly demonstrates that when both the network size and the publication age are large, the expected number of citations increases, consistent with the positive interaction effect between network size at publication and publication age observed in the regression model.

Overall, these results confirm that while larger publication networks offer more opportunities for citation, they also dilute individual visibility. Additionally, long-form online engagements, such as blog posts and academic saving platforms like Mendeley, have a measurable and positive effect on a paper's citation success.

4. Discussion

This study investigated the factors influencing citation counts of scientific publications, with a particular focus on how the size of the publication network affects individual paper visibility – a phenomenon we termed the *dilution effect*. Using a dataset of 4,184 publications from 2005 to 2024 in physics, engineering, mathematics, and computer science, we applied a multivariate regression model with log-transformed citation counts as the dependent variable. Predictors included publication network size, the reciprocal of network size, publication age, and various online dissemination metrics.

Figure 6. Three-dimensional plot of citation counts by publication network size and publication age. Citation counts are lower for younger publications, even when the publication network is large, supporting the dilution effect. When both network size and publication age are large, citation counts increase, reflecting the positive interaction between network size at publication and publication age.

Our results confirm a dual role of network size. On one hand, a larger total number of publications positively correlates with higher citation counts, reflecting greater overall citation opportunities. On the other hand, the reciprocal of network size was also a significant predictor, indicating that as the network grows, individual publications face reduced visibility, supporting the dilution effect hypothesis. This effect was further nuanced by the interaction between network size and publication age: older papers in large networks tend to accumulate more citations over time, whereas older papers in smaller fields lose visibility more rapidly. The observed effects of online dissemination channels provide further insight into citation dynamics. Mentions on Mendeley, blogs, and Twitter were positively associated with citation counts, likely because these platforms are more frequently used by academic audiences and foster research-focused engagement. Mendeley, in particular, serves as a reference management tool among researchers, directly linking articles to future scholarly work. Blog posts often offer detailed discussions and in-depth reviews, which can attract readers who are more likely to cite the original work. Twitter, although brief in format, is widely used within academic communities for sharing research findings and conference updates. In contrast, Facebook mentions were associated with a small but significant negative effect on citation counts. This may reflect that Facebook dissemination often propagates publications of lower scientific quality, popular or sensational content, or non-peer-reviewed materials. As a result, papers that are widely shared on Facebook may not align with the standards of rigor valued by the research community, leading to lower citation outcomes in scholarly literature.

Still, the Kaggle dataset we used, while providing valuable insights, is relatively small, given its 20-year focus on physics and computer science, which may not fully represent disciplinary variations in citation behavior. While our model accounts for publication age, a more in-depth examination of how new versus established papers collect citations over time could provide additional insights.

5. Conclusions

In this study, we modeled citation counts of scientific publications as a function of publication network size, publication age, and online dissemination metrics. Our analysis revealed a complex

interplay between network expansion and individual visibility: while larger fields offer more citation opportunities, they also dilute the chances that any single publication will be noticed and cited. Importantly, we found that certain types of online engagement – particularly through blogs and academic platforms like Mendeley – can significantly enhance the likelihood of citations. These results suggest that researchers aiming to maximize the visibility and impact of their work should not only recognize that the growth of their field may influence citation chances, but also actively engage with platforms that foster deeper and longer-term scholarly interactions. Future research could extend this work by modeling other factors influencing citation dynamics, including journal prestige, co-authorship networks, and domain-specific dissemination practices.

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FACEBOOK POSTS VIRALITY - SHARING OR LIKING?

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Social networks; Facebook; virality

Abstract

Social networks are the media of the new era. The virality of posts, i.e. the study of which messages are spread when and how, is very interesting for everyone working with an audience on networks. The essence is to think about the spread on social networks in Czech groups. The article answers the following research questions: Is the influence of images and links in posts on the number of likes, sharing and comments count significant, if we take into account Czech-speaking groups? Is there a relationship between the number of likes and sharing? The research considers data from ten Czech public Facebook groups with various focuses and at least 40,000 members. The data was downloaded in May 2024 and then in January to June 2025. A total of 17,860 posts were downloaded. The research uses t-test and Spearman's correlation coefficient. It turns out that posts with images and posts without links have more likes, shares and comments. The hypothesis of a zero correlation between the number of shares and likes was rejected, but the relationship is not obvious at first glance. The limitation of the research is the selection of specific groups, however, the patterns were shown in all cases.

1. Introduction

The work is devoted to exploring some characteristics of whether messages with a given characteristic are shared or liked more by users than messages that do not have these characteristics.

The basic idea of the whole work is based on the more than 100-year-old concept of Walter Lippman, who in the book *Public Opinion* (Lippman 1922) introduces readers to the idea of news values. The essence of the research was what the news looks like, which subsequently become the most interesting for the classical media (then primarily the press, later radio and TV). Lippmann defined 5 signs of news values: clarity, surprise, spatial proximity, personal interest and conflict.

The concept was later elaborated by other authors – among the Czech authors, Jan Jiráček and Barbara Köpplová (Jiráček and Köpplová 2009) addressed the topic, and they also distinguish where the report will subsequently be presented based on its value.

The text from the present day, from 2022 (becomewritertoday 2022), gives as news values impact, timeliness, fame and prominence, proximity, conflict and tragedy, oddity, trending, currency, human interest, continuity, progress and exclusivity and uniqueness.

With the Internet, the exchange of information between people gradually shifted to new media. The users are connected is by liking. I can also share a message that I like on my profile, so it reaches my friends. After these connections, messages are then spread easily, quickly and for free. Companies are taking notice of the possibility of easy distribution on social networks and the concept of viral marketing appears, which is focused on using the spread of messages between users for advertising purposes.

Within the English-speaking Internet, marketing professors at the University of Pennsylvania – Jonah Berger, Ezgi Akpınar and Grant Packard – are heavily involved in virality. Berger, in his key text (Berger et al. 2020), discusses the exact reasons why texts are spread. Berger is also the author of the popular science book on marketing *How to Create a Market Hit* (Berger 2013), in which he examines why some ideas and products spread quickly and gain popularity, while others do not. In this book, he identifies 6 key factors – (STEPPS) – that determine how a message will be disseminated:

- Social Currency,
- Triggers,
- Emotion,
- Public,
- Practical value,
- Stories.

Kümpel, Karnowski & Keyling (Kümpel et al. 2015) conduct a search of articles regarding the relationship between news dissemination and social media from 2004 to 2014. 461 articles were selected for this search.

There are also works describing one specific case of high success of viral marketing. Zhang and Huang (2022) describe the case of Tamdrin, a Tibetan shepherd, who was filmed by a Chinese photographer walking around a city and the resulting seven-second video was uploaded to the Chinese version of TikTok, Douyin. This video became very popular and was viewed 1.2 billion times in the first 4 weeks. This significantly increased tourism in the area, Tamdrin began to cooperate with the Tourism Authority and continued to promote the area.

The relationship between rumor refutation and its virality, including characteristics such as likes, shares and comments, is examined in their work by Pal et. al (2023). They examined the virality of rumor refutation or confirmation on almost 500 posts using content analysis and quantitative methods.

In this work, the key thing I am looking at is the motivation of users to like and share a message. I am interested in the characteristics of messages that are shared or liked more or less.

2. Methods and goals

In the work, the main research questions was:

RQ₁: Is there a significant impact of images or links in posts on the number of likes, shares or comments?

RQ₂: Is there any relationship between the number of likes and shares?

In both cases, we take into account large public Czech-speaking groups on Facebook.

2.1. Data collection

For the analysis, I have selected large public Czech Facebook groups with diverse topics. I considered a large group to be one with at least 40 thousand members, which already selects really large groups with a lot of posts. Another condition was that the group was public and therefore its posts were freely readable by any Facebook user. I did not select groups focused directly on selling things, such as Facebook bazaars. I also did not select sellers using groups for marketing, although it should be noted that the largest groups intended for marketing products that I found did not even reach 20 thousand members. Political parties typically use additional pages marked as a political party page or political organization for their promotion. Their fans still create groups, but these usually have a number of members in the order of a few thousand. Only a few have a number of members just over 10 thousand, e.g. SPOLU nEUhnem (together we will not bend) has 11 thousand members. Volím ANO !!! (I vote for ANO) has 19 thousand members, but posts only from the administrator, members can apparently only discuss. Therefore, although it would seem that politics is a frequent topic, it is missing from the selection for this reason. I selected 10 groups in total.

Large groups are created around topics related to dogs and cats, big cities and in the Czech Republic also around hockey. I found and selected 5 groups with these topics, namely 2 groups about hockey, one group about cats, a group about lost and found dogs and a group seen in Brno. I also focused on professional and technological groups, hobbies and lifestyle. Among professional groups, there is a large professional group of teachers and those interested in AI are associated in the group Artificial intelligence - AI, ChatGPT, OpenAI - sharing experiences. People in the Czech Republic like to garden and so the group Garden from A to Z met the parameters. Among lifestyle groups, I selected one related to the TV show Survivor and one dedicated to spirituality, specifically Jaroslav Dušek - love. An overview of the groups including their GroupID on Facebook and the number of members as of June 2, 2025 is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Selected groups

Fb group	GroupID	Number of members (in thousands)
Cats	Kocky.kocky.kocicky	118.4
Dogs	105375122853619	60.3
Hockey lovers	MilujemeHokejCZ	48.7
Hockey	msvhokeji	106.2
Teachers	1365249796891956	48.3
AI	umelaintelligence	80.8
Brno	129660617231731	129
Garden	zahradacscom	60.1
Survivor	337028421030178	65.5
Dušek	417630476669831	91.9

Source: (author)

To download the data, I used the scraper Apify and its tool Facebook Groups Scraper. The data from the groups was downloaded in May 2024 and then from January to June 2025. At first, I downloaded 200, 500 or 600 posts, later 1500 or 2000, with the condition that I would download posts no later than the last download (or until my credit ran out). A total of 17860 posts were downloaded.

For data processing and analysis, I have used MS Excel, where the data was downloaded in this format, then columns with the number of likes, comments and shares were filtered out, as well as identifiers, whether it was a post with an image or a link. I then organized the individual tables into one table for further processing.

2.2. Tested hypotheses

Research question 1 we can rewrite as a statistical hypotheses like: “Posts with and image/link have the same number of likes/shares/comments as posts without an image/link.” So we have these hypotheses:

- H₁: Posts with an image have the same number of likes as posts without images.
- H₂: Posts with an image have the same number of shares as posts without images.
- H₃: Posts with an image have the same number of comments as posts without images.
- H₄: Posts with a link have the same number of likes as posts without links.
- H₅: Posts with a link have the same number of shares as posts without links.
- H₆: Posts with a link have the same number of comments as posts without links.

Research question 2 we can rewrite as a statistical hypotheses like:

- H₇: The correlation between the number of likes and shares is zero (against alternative $\rho \neq 0$)

All hypotheses were tested at the significance level 0.05.

2.3. Statistical methods of data analyzing

The data are independent. The absence of negative data means that the data is biased to one side, and on the other hand, it also has a large kurtosis. Although the distribution is not exactly a normal distribution, it is very similar, the t-test with inequality of variances was used to test the means (at the significance level 0.05). For variance was used two-sample F-test. For statistical tests the Excel Data Analysis tool was used.

To test the second research question, I used Spearman's correlation coefficient, which is better for data with outliers. Then I sorted the data by size in both variables and thus obtained the data order. Using a simple macro, I gave all values their average ranking value in the case of an identical number of likes or shares. Then I applied Pearson's correlation coefficient to this data order. To test the dependence, I used Student's T-distribution with n-2 degrees of freedom. So I have used a test statistic of the form:

$$T = \frac{R_{12}\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-R_{12}^2}} \quad (1)$$

where R_{12} is the correlation coefficient on the ranked data (calculated by Excel – Data Analysis – Correlation) and n is the sample range. Then I have compared the test statistic with the critical values of the student's t-distribution (according to statistical tables).

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics

There were 17 854 posts taken in 10 Facebook groups. The basic characteristics of the file, including the number of downloaded posts, comments, shares, likes, posts with a link, video and image, are in the following table.

Table 1. Data summary

Fb group	Number of records (posts)	Number of comments	Number of shares	Number of likes	Number of posts with link	Number of posts with a picture
Cats	2 700	17 810	14 532	85 613	381	247
Dogs	2 500	8 789	80 973	46 556	1 281	221
Hockey lovers	2 241	19 810	15 523	185 417	713	1 167
Hockey	1 700	40 794	61 768	552 627	129	564
Teachers	2 143	39 878	4 787	67 218	896	260
AI	1 058	14 761	607	14 791	235	342
Brno	1 600	34 165	10 967	221 383	110	977
Garden	918	3 153	160	10 018	443	257
Survivor	1 500	45 128	746	109 056	532	271
Dušek	1 500	9 162	31 521	155 669	736	267
Total	17 860	233 020	221 584	1 448 348	5 456	4 573

Source: (author)

3.2. RQ1 – impact of images or links

Hypotheses for RQ₁ answers to the question, if there is a significant impact of images or links in posts on the number of likes, shares or comments.

At first I have tested if there is possible to use the test for the data with equal variances. In all two-sample F-test for variance was p-value very small (very close to zero – in 5 cases Excel have calculated 0, once value 1.8×10^{-233}) – I reject the hypotheses of equal variances and can use a two-sample t-test with unequal variances in all cases.

The results of t-test with unequal variances are in the Table 2.

We can see that in all cases we can reject the hypothesis that posts with links or with pictures have the same number of likes, shares or comment (at a 0.05 significance level).

Table 2. The influence of images/links on likes, shares and comments

		Mean value “with”	Mean value “without”	p-value	Interpretation
Pictures	H ₁ – like	153.2	56.3	<0.001	Posts with images get more likes.
	H ₂ – share	21.2	9.4	<0.001	Posts with images get more shares.
	H ₃ – comm.	17.0	11.7	<0.001	Posts with images get more comments.
	n (count)	6 648	11 212		
Links	H ₄ – like	35.7	101.0	<0.001	Posts without links get more likes.
	H ₅ – share	9.8	13.5	<0.001	Posts without links get more shares.
	H ₆ – comm.	8.5	15.1	<0.001	Posts without links get more comments.
	n (count)	7 487	10 373		

Source: (author)

3.2. RQ2 – relationship between likes and shares

For studying if there is a relationship between the number of likes and shares we will use Spearman's correlation coefficient. The results of calculations are in Table 3.

Table 3. Relationship between likes and shares

	Spearman
Correlation coefficient	0.49
n (count of the data)	17860
t-statistics	75.26
$t_{0,975}^{(n-2)}$	2.02
Result	Reject

Source: (author)

Because the t-statistic is greater than the critical value, we reject hypothesis H₇ that there is no relationship between the number of likes and the number of comments (at a 0.05 significance level).

4. Conclusion and discussion

In the article, I examined the relationships between posts in ten large Czech-speaking Facebook groups. As part of the survey, I downloaded almost 18 thousand posts and examined whether they had images or whether they contained links. All the questions I asked showed that there were

significant differences in whether or not posts had images and also in whether or not posts had links to the internet, outside the social network itself.

The survey confirms the general recommendation that posts with images are more popular, that they are liked more, and that they are also commented on more and shared more. What I consider a really interesting result, however, is that if a post contains a link to somewhere outside the relevant social network, it is taken as a disadvantage of the post. It is shared less, liked less and commented less.

As part of the second research question, which dealt with the relationship between the number of likes and shares, it could be said that there is some relationship between the number of likes and the number of shares for individual posts. Looking at the data, the connection is not very obvious, but there are some interesting relationships - if a post has 0 likes, then it has a maximum of 9 shares, a post with 1 like has a maximum of 13 shares, a post with 2 likes has 34 shares. Really large numbers of shares appear only for posts with more likes - posts with more than 150 shares have at least 22 likes, a post with over 200 shares has a post with 26 likes and 370 shares. 1408 posts had 0 shares and likes. In general, it can be said that a post needs to have a like to be shared.

The selection of groups may be a limitation of the research, however, the diversity of groups and consistent results when expanding the dataset rather suggest that the results are truly general.

In future research, it will be interesting to test individual groups separately to verify which of the topics differ in different ways. Alternatively, to verify within the framework of multivariate analysis whether some of the parameters have a greater influence on sharing and some, on the contrary, a smaller one.

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SOCIAL MEDIA AND THE EVOLUTION OF CROWDSOURCING: FROM USER-GENERATED CONTENT TO AI-ASSISTED CREATIVITY

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Abstract

This paper explores the transformation of crowdsourcing in the era of social media, from traditional user-generated content to advanced AI-assisted creativity. It examines how platforms leverage crowdsourcing for innovation in problem-solving, news reporting, and content creation. It also analyzes the growing role of artificial intelligence in enhancing and transforming human creativity on social media.

1. Introduction

The rise of social media over the past two decades has profoundly transformed the nature of crowdsourcing. Originally emerging as a method to harness the collective intelligence of large, distributed groups for tasks like problem-solving and content creation, crowdsourcing has evolved into a defining feature of the digital age. Platforms such as YouTube, Wikipedia, and Twitter have demonstrated the power of user-generated content to drive innovation, shape public discourse, and respond to real-world events with unprecedented speed and scale. However, we are now witnessing a new phase in the evolution of crowdsourcing: the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) as a creative partner. No longer limited to human contributions alone, social media systems are increasingly characterized by hybrid models where AI tools enhance, support, and even autonomously generate content. Such a shift raises critical questions about the nature of creativity, ownership, and authenticity in the digital space.

This paper examines the transformation of crowdsourcing within social media, moving from purely human-driven contributions to AI-assisted creativity. It explores how social media platforms utilize crowdsourcing for innovation in areas such as problem-solving, news reporting, and content generation. The study also addresses the ethical challenges posed by AI involvement in crowdsourcing, offering insights into the future trajectory of digital collaboration and creativity.

2. The Early Phase: User-Generated Content as Crowdsourcing

The early years of social media saw the rise of user-generated content as a fundamental form of crowdsourcing. Defined broadly, user-generated content refers to any material—text, images, videos, reviews, or ideas—created and shared by users rather than by professional media outlets or companies. Platforms such as YouTube (founded in 2005), Wikipedia (launched in 2001), and Twitter (launched in 2006) exemplify how social media leveraged the collective contributions of millions of individuals to generate value, drive innovation, and build vibrant online communities. One of the earliest and most influential examples of user-generated content-based crowdsourcing is Wikipedia. This decentralized model demonstrated that large, self-organizing communities could produce accurate, relevant, and continuously evolving bodies of knowledge, often competing with traditional centralized models in speed and scope (Sanger, 2005). Similarly, platforms like YouTube empowered individuals to become content creators, bypassing traditional media gatekeepers.

Social media also played a critical role in crowdsourced news reporting, particularly during major events and crises. Twitter became an indispensable tool for real-time information sharing during specific events such as the Arab Spring (2010–2012), natural disasters like the Haiti earthquake (2010), and political movements worldwide. Researchers have noted that during such events, ordinary users often acted as on-the-ground reporters, sharing updates, images, and eyewitness accounts long before traditional news organizations could respond (Lotan et al., 2011). These early examples illustrate the essential characteristics of social media-based crowdsourcing in its initial phase:

- **Decentralization:** No single authority controlled the flow or creation of information.
- **Scalability:** Millions of users could contribute simultaneously, producing vast amounts of content.
- **Real-Time Collaboration:** Crowds could react instantly to unfolding events, collectively building narratives or solutions.

However, this phase was not without its challenges. Issues of misinformation, content moderation, and information overload quickly emerged, foreshadowing the need for more structured, technologically assisted models of crowdsourcing—ushering in the era of AI-assisted creativity.

3. Crowdsourcing for Innovation on Social Media

As social media platforms matured, crowdsourcing evolved beyond user-generated content and became a strategic tool for innovation. Companies, brands, and even governments began to leverage the collective intelligence, creativity, and problem-solving abilities of online communities not only for content creation but also for designing new products, refining services, and influencing marketing strategies. Organizations increasingly recognize that engaging online communities can lead to faster, cheaper, and often more innovative solutions compared to traditional in-house development processes. This model aligns closely with what Howe (2008) described as "crowdsourcing innovation"—the practice of obtaining ideas, services, or content by soliciting contributions from a large group, particularly from an online community.

Platforms like Twitter and Reddit often function as informal crowdsourcing laboratories. Companies monitor trending discussions, memes, and consumer feedback to adapt their products in near real-time. For example, Netflix analyzed viewer social media discussions to inform decisions about series renewals and new content development. The special position occupies social motivations (Brabham, 2013). Effective crowdsourcing initiatives tap into these motivations, ensuring that users feel valued, heard, and rewarded—either socially or materially.

3.1. Organized Crowdsourcing Initiatives on Social Media

Some companies have developed formal crowdsourcing initiatives directly through social media:

LEGO Ideas: LEGO created a platform where fans submit designs for new sets. Designs that reach a threshold of public support are considered for commercial production, rewarding contributors with royalties.

Threadless: An online clothing retailer that invites artists to submit T-shirt designs. The social media community votes on submissions, and winning designs are produced and sold.

Starbucks' "My Starbucks Idea": Although now discontinued, it allowed customers to propose ideas for products, services, and store improvements, many of which were implemented.

These cases illustrate how crowdsourcing leverages customer passion and creativity as an innovation asset while simultaneously enhancing brand loyalty.

3.2. Crowdsourcing in Journalism and Crisis Response

Beyond corporate innovation, crowdsourcing through social media has played a critical role in journalism and crisis management:

Ushahidi (a nonprofit tech company) built a platform using crowdsourced social media reports to map incidents of violence during the 2007 Kenyan elections.

During natural disasters like Hurricane Harvey (2017), platforms like Facebook and Twitter were used to crowdsource information on safe routes, shelter locations, and missing persons.

Such examples demonstrate that crowdsourced innovation via social media is not limited to commercial gain but also serves urgent social needs, enhancing collective intelligence in ways that can save lives and empower communities.

4. Transition to AI-Assisted Crowdsourcing

While human-driven crowdsourcing remains central to social media innovation, the last decade has seen the rapid emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) as a powerful collaborator within this system. Social media spaces are increasingly characterized by hybrid interactions between users and AI technologies that assist, augment, and sometimes autonomously generate content. This shift marks a significant evolution in crowdsourcing practices: from collective human input to collaborative human–AI production. In connection with the preceding, note that Riccardi (2016) studied the link between AI-assisted crowdsourcing and disaster reporting, which is crucial in such situations.

4.1. Emergence of AI Tools in Creative Crowdsourcing

The integration of AI into social media began with relatively simple tools, such as automatic photo tagging (e.g., Facebook's facial recognition technology) and algorithmic content recommendations (e.g., YouTube's suggestion engine). Over time, however, AI has moved into more direct roles in

content creation, editing, and enhancement. Today, AI systems can generate highly sophisticated creative outputs, including:

- Visual art (e.g., DALL·E, Midjourney)
- Music composition (e.g., Suno AI, AIVA)
- Writing and storytelling (e.g., ChatGPT, Sudowrite)
- Video editing and production (e.g., TikTok's CapCut AI features, YouTube's automatic captioning tools)

These technologies have opened new dimensions for crowdsourcing by empowering individuals who may lack traditional artistic or technical skills to participate creatively at high levels of quality.

4.2. AI as a Creativity Enabler

AI does not simply replace human creativity; rather, it acts as an enabler and amplifier. Research by McCormack et al. (2019) emphasizes that AI tools democratize creative expression, allowing users to produce professional-level work without extensive training. This democratization has particular significance for social media, where speed, visual appeal, and originality are critical to success. For example:

- TikTok's AI-driven editing apps allow users to create dynamic, polished videos quickly, making high-level audiovisual storytelling accessible to teenagers and small creators.
- Instagram's generative AI tools assist users in creating stylized posts, filters, and promotional content, enabling more visually sophisticated self-branding strategies.
- In both cases, AI functions as a creative partner, lowering technical barriers while allowing human users to maintain agency over the final product.

4.3. Collaborative Creation Models: Humans and AI

Social media platforms are increasingly fostering co-creation models where humans initiate ideas, and AI supports or completes them. Examples include:

- AI-generated art prompts: Users describe a concept, and AI visualizes it.
- Auto-complete writing tools: Creators draft an outline or initial paragraph, and AI suggests expansions or rewrites.
- Interactive music generation: Users input a melody, and AI composes an accompanying piece.
- These models blend human intuition with machine optimization, creating a new form of crowdsourcing where the "crowd" includes both human participants and artificial agents.

4.4. Implications for Social Media Dynamics

The transition to AI-assisted crowdsourcing changes fundamental dynamics on social media:

- Acceleration of content production: AI enables faster turnaround times, leading to higher volumes of content.
- New forms of competition: Creators who effectively leverage AI may outpace traditional creators in terms of quality and output.

- Shift in value perception: As AI-generated content becomes more common, authenticity and human touch may become more prized by audiences.
- These shifts suggest that while AI enhances possibilities for innovation, it also raises new questions about originality, effort, and creative identity within social media systems.

5. The Role of AI in Enhancing Human Creativity on Social Media

Artificial intelligence has shifted from being a background technology to an active partner in human creative processes, particularly within social media systems. As users increasingly adopt AI-powered tools to generate, enhance, and distribute content, the relationship between human creativity and machine assistance is being redefined. This chapter explores how AI enhances human creativity on social media, democratizes access to advanced creative capabilities, and changes user behavior and expectations. On the other hand, some creators express anxiety that AI involvement might devalue their work or make creative achievements seem less meaningful (Runco, 2020). Authenticity, emotional connection, and transparency about AI usage are becoming important markers of credibility and quality on social media platforms.

5.1. AI as a Creative Collaborator, Not a Replacement

Rather than replacing human creativity, AI is primarily positioned as a collaborator—a tool that helps users refine their ideas, overcome technical limitations, and explore new aesthetic directions. Examples of this collaboration include:

Image Generation: Artists use platforms like Midjourney or DALL·E to create visual concepts based on text prompts, which they then modify or build upon.

Music Composition: Creators use AI applications like Suno AI to compose background music for TikToks, YouTube videos, and Instagram Reels, enabling even non-musicians to produce professional audio content.

Writing Assistance: Tools like ChatGPT or Jasper AI help users draft captions, marketing copy, or even full scripts for short videos.

In each case, the human user provides the initial vision, prompts, or emotional tone, while AI assists in the technical realization or amplification of that vision.

5.2. Democratization of Creativity

AI has significantly lowered the barriers to entry for high-quality creative production. Historically, producing professional-grade visual art, music, or video required specialized training, expensive equipment, or access to professional studios. Now, a smartphone user with access to AI-powered applications can produce competitive content that stands alongside professionally produced works. This democratization has profound implications for social media:

Diversification of Voices allows more individuals from diverse backgrounds can participate in creative expression.

Expansion of Micro-Creator Economies, as niche creators, can now build audiences and monetize their work without needing major institutional backing.

Acceleration of Trend Cycles should be mentioned, as with easier access to creative tools, the rate at which new trends and formats emerge has accelerated dramatically.

The implications of forming more diverse and actual sources are evident in this way.

5.3. New Models of Co-Creation and Remix Culture

Social media is evolving into a space where human and AI co-creation is becoming the norm rather than the exception. Connected to this, we can mention:

Remixable AI Content: AI-generated templates, beats, designs, and storyboards are remixed and reinterpreted by human creators, fostering dynamic innovation.

Interactive Tools: TikTok's AI green screen effects, Snapchat's Lens Studio, and Instagram's AI-generated filters allow users to easily create derivative works based on pre-trained AI models.

Such a participatory environment blurs traditional notions of "authorship" and challenges the idea of fully original work, replacing it with a model based on continuous collaboration and iteration.

6. Challenges and Ethical Considerations

While the integration of AI into social media crowdsourcing offers remarkable opportunities for enhanced creativity and innovation, it also introduces significant ethical challenges. Beyond the others, one of the most pressing ethical concerns is the question of ownership. When AI contributes substantially to a creative work, it becomes difficult to determine who—or what—owns the final product. Existing intellectual property laws were designed with human creators in mind. Legal frameworks are currently ill-equipped to address the nuances of content that is co-produced with or entirely generated by AI systems (Samuelson, 2020). The next task can also be algorithmic opacity. Despite the security vulnerabilities, the open-source AI governance can improve the alignment of ethical principles, regulatory issues, and societal principles. The development process can be made transparent and understandable in such a case.

6.1. Authenticity and Trust Issues

AI's growing role in content creation raises critical concerns about the authenticity of material on social media platforms:

Fake News and Synthetic Media: AI tools capable of generating realistic images, videos, and text (e.g., deepfakes) can be used maliciously to spread misinformation.

Erosion of Trust: As audiences become aware that content may be AI-generated or heavily AI-assisted, skepticism about the credibility and authenticity of online material may increase (West, 2019).

Platforms are beginning to explore labeling AI-generated content to promote transparency, but standards are inconsistent, and adoption is still limited.

6.2. Bias and Representation in AI-Created Content

AI systems trained on biased data can perpetuate stereotypes and reinforce systemic inequalities:

Cultural Biases: Image generators and writing tools may reflect racial, gender, or cultural biases embedded in their training data.

Lack of Diversity: AI models often favor dominant cultural narratives, limiting the diversity of creative expression unless intentionally designed to be inclusive (Noble, 2018).

Addressing bias requires careful curation of training datasets, regular auditing of AI outputs, and active efforts to promote equitable representation in AI-assisted media production.

6.3. Platform Responsibility and Regulation

Finally, platforms themselves bear responsibility for ensuring the ethical integration of AI:

Policy Development: Clear guidelines on content ownership, data privacy, and ethical AI usage are needed.

Moderation and Oversight: Automated moderation tools must be balanced with human oversight to avoid reinforcing bias or suppressing legitimate expression.

Global Regulation Efforts: Governments and international organizations are beginning to propose regulations for AI use (e.g., the EU's AI Act), but harmonizing these frameworks across jurisdictions remains a complex challenge.

7. Future Directions

As social media continues to evolve alongside advancements in artificial intelligence, the relationship between crowdsourcing, creativity, and technology will likely become even more complex and dynamic. Understanding the future trajectory of AI-assisted creativity on social platforms is crucial not only for researchers but also for creators, companies, and policymakers. This chapter outlines key future trends and opportunities, as well as potential risks that warrant close attention. The goal will not be to replace human imagination but to amplify it in ways that feel natural and empowering.

7.1. Regulation, Standards, and Ethical Frameworks

The growing role of AI in creativity will likely lead to more comprehensive regulation:

Mandatory Disclosure: Future regulations may require clear labeling of AI-generated or AI-assisted content.

Fair Use Reinterpretation: Legal frameworks around fair use, derivative works, and intellectual property will need to adapt to the new realities of human–AI collaboration.

Ethical AI Development Standards: Policymakers and industry leaders are already working toward defining principles for transparent, fair, and accountable AI development (Floridi & Cowls, 2019).

Balancing innovation with the protection of human rights and cultural diversity will be a key challenge in regulatory efforts.

7.2. Evolving Audience Expectations

As audiences become increasingly aware of the role of AI in content creation, their expectations will evolve as follows:

Demand for Authenticity: Human originality, emotional resonance, and transparent communication about the creative process may become even more valued.

Rise of "Human-First" Movements: Countertrends emphasizing purely human-made, "AI-free" creative works could emerge, offering new market opportunities and cultural movements.

Social media creators who understand and adapt to these shifts will likely be better positioned to build loyal audiences.

AI echo chambers connected to recommendation systems, responsible for reinforcing pre-existing beliefs by continuously sharing similar content, deserve more attention. Note that this is a potential source of misinformation, radicalization, and digital polarization.

8. Conclusion

The evolution of crowdsourcing within social media reflects a broader transformation in the digital age: the shift from purely human-driven collaboration to increasingly sophisticated forms of human–AI co-creation. Artificial intelligence tools enhance human creativity by democratizing access to professional-grade production capabilities, enabling faster and broader content generation, and offering new modes of expression. However, these advancements also bring significant ethical and regulatory challenges. Issues of ownership, authenticity, bias, and transparency must be carefully navigated to ensure that technological progress does not erode trust, diversity in traditions and cultures, or human thinking. Looking forward, the future of social media creativity lies in fostering symbiotic relationships between humans and machines, developing decentralized models that protect creators' rights, and crafting regulations that balance innovation with ethical responsibility.

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AI IN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

THE POTENTIAL OF SOCIAL ENTERPRISES IN SLOVAK PUBLIC PROCUREMENT: DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS AND AI-DRIVEN MATCHING FRAMEWORK

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Abstract

Despite legislative frameworks promoting social procurement in Slovakia, the integration of Registered Social Enterprises (RSEs) into public procurement remains limited. This study offers a descriptive statistical analysis of RSE participation from 2019 to 2025, revealing gradual growth in engagement but persistent challenges in contract acquisition and market share. Analysis of CPV classifications and supplier concentration highlights structural asymmetries and the dominance of a few RSEs, pointing to untapped potential across the sector.

To address these challenges, the paper introduces the concept of a data- and AI-powered Social Marketplace designed to improve matchmaking between public buyers and RSEs. The platform leverages national procurement data, CPV classifications, and institutional registries to increase supplier visibility, automate social value verification, and deliver intelligent recommendations through AI-driven processes such as predictive ranking, semantic matching, and personalized alerts.

This technological framework not only supports compliance with legal targets (e.g., the 6% procurement share for RSEs) but also aims to foster transparency, inclusion, and efficiency in public spending. The paper concludes by outlining implementation considerations and the transformative potential of such systems for building socially responsible public supply chains.

1. Introduction

The role of social enterprises (SEs) in building inclusive and sustainable economies has gained increasing attention across Europe. Social enterprises, which prioritize social and community benefits over profit maximization, are recognized as key actors in promoting social innovation, job creation, and local development. However, their integration into public procurement systems remains limited, often due to structural barriers and low awareness among procurers.

In Slovakia, the importance of supporting social enterprises is emphasized not only through national strategies but also through legislative frameworks that mandate public procurers to allocate a minimum proportion of their budgets - around 6% - to social enterprises. Despite these efforts, data-driven insights reveal that social enterprises still represent only a marginal share of public procurement contracts, indicating a substantial untapped potential.

This study provides a descriptive statistical overview of the participation of social enterprises in Slovak public procurement, based on national procurement data. Furthermore, it explores the possible application of AI-driven matching frameworks that could enhance the connection between public buyers and social enterprises. By facilitating better alignment between demand and supply, such technological innovations could significantly improve the effectiveness of public spending in achieving social policy objectives and contribute to the long-term sustainability of social enterprises.

2. Literature research

The integration of social enterprises into public procurement and commercial supply chains has become a key strategy to enhance social and environmental sustainability across Europe. Social procurement, defined as the use of purchasing power to achieve social outcomes, provides a unique opportunity to strengthen the social economy and foster inclusive economic growth (European Commission, 2021).

Role of Social Enterprises in Procurement

Social enterprises play a vital role in delivering societal value through economic activities (Bernal et al., 2019). They contribute to social inclusion, job creation for disadvantaged groups, and regional development (OECD/EU, 2017). In public procurement, their involvement can promote socially responsible purchasing, stimulate innovation, and support the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (European Commission, 2021). However, despite these recognized benefits, the integration of social enterprises into public procurement processes remains limited.

Challenges include administrative burdens, limited capacity to respond to tenders, and a lack of awareness among public buyers regarding the added value offered by social enterprises (OECD, 2018; European Commission, 2021, Troje, 2021). Moreover, procurement regulations often prioritize cost-efficiency over social impact, which can disadvantage social enterprises in competitive processes (Háček & Villahoz, 2020).

Strategic Use of Public Procurement

Strategic public procurement has been increasingly promoted as a policy tool to drive social and environmental outcomes (European Commission, 2015). Initiatives such as socially responsible public procurement (SRPP) and green public procurement (GPP) encourage public buyers to include social and environmental criteria in tendering processes. These initiatives align with the EU's broader agenda to create an economy that works for people and the planet.

The European Commission's "Buying Social" guide (2010, updated in 2021) provides practical advice to contracting authorities on how to incorporate social considerations into public procurement. It emphasizes that social procurement is not only permissible under EU law but encouraged as a way to achieve better societal outcomes without compromising efficiency (European Commission, 2021).

Slovak Context: Legal Framework and Practice

In Slovakia, the legal environment supports the inclusion of social enterprises in public procurement. Amendments to the Slovak Act on Public Procurement (Act No. 343/2015 Coll.) introduced reserved contracts for sheltered workshops and social enterprises, allowing contracting authorities to reserve participation in certain tenders exclusively for these organizations.

Additionally, Slovak legislation encourages public buyers to allocate a percentage of their procurement spending—reportedly around 6%—to social enterprises. However, practical implementation lags behind legislative ambition. Studies reveal that awareness among contracting authorities is still low, and procedural complexities deter many social enterprises from participating in public tenders (European Commission, 2021; OECD, 2018, B'anda & Urbančíková, 2020).

Barriers and Opportunities for Social Enterprises

Multiple studies identify barriers that inhibit the effective participation of social enterprises in public procurement (Bernal et al., 2019; Troje, 2021). These include:

- Limited internal capacity to prepare bids (OECD, 2018),
- Insufficient financial resources to handle large contracts (European Commission, 2021),
- Inadequate knowledge of procurement processes.

On the other hand, successful initiatives, such as pre-commercial procurement programs and socially responsible purchasing pilots in Western Europe, demonstrate that when supported adequately, social enterprises can compete effectively and deliver significant social value (European Commission, 2015; OECD/EU, 2017).

Potential of AI in Enhancing Social Procurement

Emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) offer promising solutions to overcome some of these barriers. AI can support:

- Better matching between public sector demand and social enterprise supply,
- Automated classification of tenders based on social criteria,
- Tailored notifications and recommendations for social enterprises about suitable opportunities.

In the Slovak context, where social enterprises are still struggling to achieve substantial market penetration in public procurement, an AI-driven matching framework could bridge critical gaps. Such a system would not only facilitate higher compliance with legislative targets but also contribute to building a more resilient and socially inclusive supply chain ecosystem.

The literature strongly suggests that while policy frameworks supporting social procurement exist both at the EU and national levels, practical implementation remains challenging. To fully realize the potential of social enterprises in public procurement, systemic changes are needed — including regulatory simplification, capacity-building support for social enterprises, and the deployment of advanced digital tools like AI-based matchmaking platforms. These steps can significantly enhance the ability of social enterprises to access public procurement opportunities and thus contribute more robustly to social innovation and inclusive economic growth.

3. Descriptive analysis of social enterprises and the activity in public tenders

An analysis of Slovak public procurement data from 2019 to 2025 gathered from Electronic contractual system API, reveals a gradual increase in the participation of Registered Social Enterprises (RSEs) in tendering procedures. As shown in Figure 1, the number of participating RSEs was negligible in 2019, which aligns with the relatively recent introduction of the legal framework supporting social enterprises. A notable rise occurred from 2020 onwards, peaking in 2023 with more than 18 unique RSEs submitting bids. However, the corresponding volume of tenders involving RSEs did not mirror this upward trend. Although participation increased, the total value of tenders plateaued in 2022 and declined thereafter, suggesting potential limitations in the competitiveness or capacity of RSEs in the procurement market.

Figure 1. Number of contracts awarded to RSEs **Figure 2. Total value of contracts awarded to RSEs**
Source: (author)

Figure 2 illustrates the number and total value of contracts awarded to RSEs. Despite growing engagement, awarded volumes remained relatively low. The highest number of successful tenders occurred in 2024, with over 125 contracts awarded. Yet, these represented only a modest fraction of overall public procurement spending, highlighting a disconnect between policy objectives—such as the 6% target for RSE inclusion—and actual implementation.

Figure 3 demonstrates the evolution of contracting authorities (CAs) engaging with RSEs. The number of unique CAs increased steadily through 2024, reflecting a positive shift in institutional awareness and willingness to contract socially responsible suppliers. Nonetheless, the steep drop in awarded volumes in 2025 may point to institutional or financial constraints, including potential discontinuation of subsidy schemes or limited supply capacities on the part of RSEs.

Figure 3 The evolution of the number of contracting authorities (CAs) inviting RSEs with total volume
Source: (author)

In summary, while the presence of RSEs in public procurement has improved over time, their ability to secure contracts and access significant financial volumes remains limited. These findings underscore an untapped potential that could be addressed through data-driven tools—such as AI-based recommendation systems—to better align public sector demand with RSE supply capabilities.

Figure 4 Top 10 CPV divisions by RSE participation

Figure 5 Top 10 CPV divisions by RSE wins

Source: (author)

A detailed analysis of tender categories based on the CPV2 classification reveals specific domains where Registered Social Enterprises (RSEs) are most active and most successful in Slovak public procurement. In the CPV structure, the first two digits (CPV2) represent a division-level category, offering insight into broader sectors of economic activity.

As shown in the figure 4, RSEs most frequently participated in tenders falling under CPV2 79 – Business services: law, marketing, consulting, recruitment, printing, and security, which accounted for more than €2.5 million in total tender volume and approximately 140 contracts. This was followed by CPV2 98 – Other community, social and personal services and CPV2 30 – Office and computing machinery, equipment and supplies, each with substantial volumes (above €1 million) and high contract counts (ca. 120 and 90, respectively).

These categories are highly aligned with the operational characteristics of many social enterprises. They tend to be labor-intensive, service-based sectors with relatively low capital entry barriers, which enables RSEs—especially those focused on employing disadvantaged or vulnerable groups—to participate competitively. Business and community services often include cleaning, facility management, low-skill administrative support, and social assistance—activities where RSEs can generate significant social value while meeting procurement requirements.

The figure 5 focuses on contract awards won by RSEs. Again, CPV2 79 dominates, confirming not only frequent participation but also high competitiveness in this domain. The volume of contracts won in this category exceeded €2.5 million, consistent with their overall participation levels. Other top-performing divisions mirrored the participation chart, reinforcing the idea that RSEs are successful primarily in the same sectors in which they are most active.

This alignment suggests a specialization of RSEs in lower-barrier, service-oriented segments of the public procurement market. However, the concentration of RSE activity in a limited number of CPV2 categories also indicates potential missed opportunities in more diversified or capital-intensive sectors. For policymakers and procurement professionals, this presents both a challenge and an opportunity: to support RSEs in building capacity to compete in a broader range of procurement categories, and to adapt procurement practices to better accommodate the characteristics of social enterprise supply.

Figure 8. ABC analysis of RSE dominance

Source: (author)

The concentration of public procurement success among a small number of Registered Social Enterprises (RSEs) is further reinforced by the ABC analysis shown in Figure 8. This cumulative distribution reveals that just the top 1 RSE account for over 40% of the total awarded contract value. Expanding to the top 5 RSEs covers more than 80%.

Such a sharply skewed distribution confirms that public procurement contracts involving RSEs are not broadly dispersed across the sector, but rather captured by a narrow group of dominant actors. While these leading RSEs likely possess higher operational capacity, administrative readiness, or sectoral specialization, this also highlights a systemic underutilization of the broader RSE base.

This imbalance underlines the need for targeted interventions, such as AI-driven matchmaking and recommendation systems, to better distribute opportunities and assist emerging or less visible RSEs. Enhancing transparency, segment-specific supplier profiling, and capacity diagnostics could help unlock the remaining RSE sector’s potential—currently marginalized from impactful public market engagement.

4. Data-Driven Social Procurement: A Strategy for an AI-Supported Social Marketplace for Registered Social Enterprises in Slovakia

Analysis of public procurement involving Registered Social Enterprises (RSEs) in Slovakia has revealed a critical gap between policy objectives and practical outcomes. Although legislation requires public buyers to allocate at least 6% of their procurement expenditures to RSEs, participation rates remain low, highly concentrated among a few suppliers, and largely fragmented across sectors and regions. This underperformance indicates systemic challenges on both the demand and supply sides: public buyers struggle to identify eligible RSEs and verify their social value, while many RSEs are unable to access opportunities due to complexity, lack of information, and administrative overload.

To address this gap, Slovak national strategy for digital transformation of social economy (Delina et al, 2022) includes the use of structured public data, interoperable registries, and artificial intelligence (AI) which offers a promising solution. A dedicated digital platform—a Social Marketplace—can optimize and automate the matching of demand and supply by increasing visibility, streamlining verification processes, and supporting strategic decision-making based on social impact criteria.

Such a system would strengthen the transparency of social enterprises, enhance their sustainability by improving their access to public funding opportunities, and embed social value more firmly into

procurement practices. It would also provide public buyers with smarter, more efficient tools for fulfilling their legal and policy obligations.

The concept of the Social Marketplace builds on the following pillars:

- **Visibility:** Centralized cataloging of RSEs and their offerings using CPV classifications and regional mapping,
- **Verification:** Automated validation of social impact indicators (e.g., employment of disadvantaged groups) via data linkages to national institutions,
- **Intelligent Matching:** AI-driven recommendation of RSEs based on buyer needs, geography, capacity, and social value,
- **Monitoring:** Ongoing compliance tracking and performance analysis to support continuous improvement and transparency.

The platform follows a workflow that can be structured into three interconnected phases:

Registration and Cataloging

Registered social enterprises submit detailed profiles into a centralized catalog, specifying their legal status, social mission, CPV-classified goods and services, and operational capacities. This enables:

- Filtering and structured search by buyers,
- Geographic visualization of supplier availability,
- Industry and specialization-based discovery.

Verification of Social Criteria

Through system integrations with the Social Insurance Agency, Labour Offices, and other registries, the platform verifies:

- Employment of disadvantaged groups,
- Legal compliance and tax status,
- Certification of social enterprise status. This verification supports awarding "social labels" that buyers can rely on during procurement evaluations.

Automated Matchmaking and Tender Support

When a public buyer initiates a procurement process, the system activates several smart functionalities:

- CPV, location, and criteria-based matching to suggest eligible RSEs,
- Template generation for tenders including social responsibility clauses,
- Ranking and filtering of RSEs based on readiness, previous performance, and impact metrics,
- Integration of outcomes to continuously enrich supplier profiles and compliance records.

The core technological engine of the Social Marketplace relies on a set of AI-driven services:

- **Recommendation Algorithms:** Match buyers with suppliers based on CPV similarity (cosine matching), geographic proximity (GIS-based clustering), past performance (historical data weighting), and verified social value.

- Alert Systems and Auto-Notifications: Inform RSEs about relevant tenders in real-time, prioritizing based on tender fit and competition density.
- Natural Language Processing (NLP): Interpret unstructured tender texts to extract requirements even when CPV codes are missing or misclassified.
- Continuous Learning Models: Refine matchmaking over time by analyzing outcomes (e.g., tenders won, bidder feedback) to adjust recommendations and identify systemic gaps in RSE supply.

Additional functionalities include a procurement analytics dashboard for buyers and policymakers. This component monitors progress toward meeting the 6% RSE procurement target, sectoral and regional distribution of awarded contracts, trends, gaps and potential in RSE participation and win rates, aggregated metrics (based on data driven methodology) on social value generated (e.g., jobs created for marginalized groups).

By integrating these AI-driven processes into the procurement workflow, the Social Marketplace shifts public procurement from a compliance-based exercise into a proactive, strategic tool for fostering social impact. It helps diversify supplier bases, lowers entry barriers for emerging RSEs, and makes public spending more accountable and socially oriented.

Nevertheless, several challenges must be managed carefully:

- Avoiding algorithmic bias that might favor already dominant suppliers,
- Ensuring data privacy and ethical use of sensitive social information (like type of disability),
- Providing capacity-building support for RSEs to effectively engage with digital procurement processes,
- Ensuring interoperability with existing national procurement platforms.

A phased pilot deployment—starting with selected sectors or regions—would allow for controlled testing, adjustment, and scaling. Ultimately, the Social Marketplace represents a blueprint for building resilient, transparent, and socially responsible public supply chains, with the potential for replication across Europe.

5. Conclusion

This paper has shown that Registered Social Enterprises in Slovakia face both opportunity and constraint in the public procurement ecosystem. While legal frameworks mandate inclusion, and participation has increased over time, descriptive evidence points to a highly concentrated market, limited sectoral diversity, and inconsistent access to public contracts. These inefficiencies undermine the potential of social procurement as a lever for economic inclusion and sustainability.

The proposed Social Marketplace addresses this gap by offering a unified, intelligent, and transparent system to bridge the divide between RSE supply and public sector demand. By combining open procurement data, registry integration, and AI-driven functionalities—such as semantic search, predictive scoring, and continuous learning—the platform offers public buyers a powerful tool to fulfill their social obligations while unlocking new opportunities for underrepresented RSEs.

Beyond technical efficiency, this system enables a strategic shift toward proactive, impact-oriented procurement. To be successful, it must be embedded within a supportive governance structure, ensure ethical data use, and be implemented with stakeholder buy-in across public and social sectors.

While this paper focuses on the conceptual and technical design of the platform, important implementation aspects—such as governance models, stakeholder adoption, and cost-benefit evaluation—remain open questions for future research. Comparative studies and pilot testing in other EU contexts and countries, could also help validate and refine the proposed model.

Ultimately, the Social Marketplace represents not only a digital innovation but a policy enabler, offering a replicable model for other EU member states seeking to build more inclusive and socially accountable supply chains.

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CLUSTERING GLOBAL INNOVATION ACTIVITY IN LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS VIA PATENT DATA

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Abstract

The rapid development of Large Language Models (LLMs) has triggered a surge in global patenting activity, reflecting both technological innovation and strategic positioning across industries and nations. This study investigates the landscape of LLM-related patents by analyzing a dataset of 32,685 patent documents filed across multiple jurisdictions. Using a structured Natural Language Processing (NLP) pipeline combined with heuristic clustering, key technological directions were extracted from patent abstracts, and patents were grouped into thematic clusters such as Fine-Tuning Techniques, Prompt Engineering, Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), Safety and Bias Mitigation, and Multimodal Model Development.

The findings provide a structured view of emerging trends, dominant innovation pathways, and the evolving strategic interests shaping the future of large language models. This cluster-based analysis offers valuable insights for researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders aiming to navigate and influence the evolving landscape of LLM technologies

1. Introduction

The rapid proliferation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies marks a pivotal moment in technological evolution, fundamentally reshaping industries, economies, and the very nature of innovation itself (Parteka & Kordalska, 2023; Rahman et al., 2024). AI, encompassing a spectrum of capabilities from machine learning and deep learning to natural language processing and computer vision, is no longer confined to theoretical research but is actively driving tangible advancements across diverse sectors including healthcare, finance, manufacturing, transportation, and climate change mitigation (Zhu et al., 2024; Zhang & Ming, 2023a; Ajithkumar et al., 2025; Wang et al., 2023; Podrecca et al., 2024). As AI systems demonstrate increasing autonomy, capable not only of processing information but also of generating novel solutions and potentially inventive outputs (Thiruvani & Brinda, 2025; Banerjee, 2025), they present unprecedented challenges and opportunities for the intellectual property (IP) system, particularly patent law. Patents serve as a cornerstone of the innovation ecosystem, providing inventors with exclusive rights in exchange for disclosing their

inventions, thereby incentivizing R&D investment and promoting technological progress (Banerjee, 2025; Yordy, 2021). However, the integration of AI into the inventive process strains traditional patent doctrines related to inventorship, patentable subject matter, disclosure, and liability, prompting a global re-evaluation of existing legal frameworks (Kunda, 2024; Matulionyte, 2024; Owoye & Ajayi, 2024). Understanding the dynamics of AI patenting – how companies strategize, which technologies are trending, who the key global players are, and how legal systems are adapting – is crucial for policymakers, innovators, legal practitioners, and researchers navigating this complex and rapidly evolving landscape. This introduction synthesizes insights drawn from a comprehensive analysis of recent patent literature, focusing on the multifaceted interplay between AI and the patent system.

1.1 Corporate Strategies and the Value Proposition of AI Patents

For corporations, AI represents a significant strategic frontier, offering transformative potential for business models, operational processes, and market offerings (Teli et al., 2024). Consequently, securing IP rights through patents has become a critical component of corporate strategy in the AI domain. Companies are actively investing in AI R&D and seeking patent protection not only to safeguard their innovations but also to gain competitive advantages, attract investment, and generate value (Rahman et al., 2024; Jiang & Fang, 2024; Li et al., 2025b). The strategic importance of AI patents is underscored by the significant financial implications associated with them. Research indicates that patent infringement litigation involving AI patents (AI-PILs) can have a more pronounced negative impact on a firm's short-term abnormal returns compared to non-AI PILs, suggesting that the market perceives higher stakes or greater uncertainty surrounding AI-related IP disputes (Teli et al., 2024). The nature of the plaintiff (practicing vs. non-practicing entities) and the type of AI technology (expertise-driven vs. data-driven) further moderate these market reactions, highlighting the complex valuation dynamics at play (Teli et al., 2024).

The concept of "high-value patents" is particularly pertinent in the AI field. These are patents that not only protect specific innovations but also possess significant technological importance, market potential, and legal robustness, thereby contributing substantially to a firm's competitive positioning and overall value (Jiang & Fang, 2024; Zhang & Ming, 2023a). Cultivating such high-value patents requires strategic foresight, focusing R&D efforts on foundational or breakthrough AI technologies and ensuring comprehensive legal protection (Jiang & Fang, 2024). The transformer architecture serves as a case study illustrating the successful cultivation and impact of high-value patents in driving the widespread application and commercialization of generative AI (Jiang & Fang, 2024). Evaluating patent assets from a portfolio perspective, rather than individually, is increasingly recognized as crucial for effective IP management (Zhang & Ming, 2023a; Dong et al., 2021). Methods integrating quantitative analyses, such as intuitionistic fuzzy sets or technology proximity networks, are being developed to assess the value of AI patent portfolios, particularly within specific industrial clusters like AI for healthcare (Zhang & Ming, 2023a; Zhang & Ming, 2023b). Such evaluations help decision-makers plan industrial patent layouts, devise licensing strategies oriented towards open innovation, and understand the impact of technological proximity on patent value (Zhang & Ming, 2023a; Zhang & Ming, 2023b).

Corporate investment in AI is influenced by various macroeconomic and firm-specific factors. Studies indicate a positive correlation between GDP growth, ICT goods exports, AI patent applications, and corporate AI investments, suggesting that broader economic health and technological advancement foster greater AI funding (Rahman et al., 2024). Conversely, the role of regulatory quality appears more ambiguous, with some research finding no statistically significant relationship or even a negative one, perhaps indicating that overly stringent or unclear regulations might hinder investment (Rahman et al., 2024). The stock market's reaction to AI patent approvals

further reflects the nuances of perceived value. While patents related to AI machine learning are often viewed positively, especially those demonstrating higher radicalness, patents concerning AI planning/control may receive a negative reaction, potentially due to perceived uncertainties or displacement effects (Patel & Sahi, 2025). AI hardware patents, meanwhile, might elicit an insignificant market reaction on average (Patel & Sahi, 2025). These differential responses underscore the importance of the specific type and perceived impact of the AI innovation being patented. Furthermore, factors like the firm's temporal depth in AI and patent pedigree can moderate market reactions, indicating that established AI capability and strong prior IP influence investor perception (Patel & Sahi, 2025). The strategic management of AI patent portfolios, considering factors like diversity, size, and technological proximity, is thus essential for maximizing innovation performance and market valuation (Dong et al., 2021; Zhang & Ming, 2023b). The decision to pursue patent protection versus relying on trade secrets also presents a critical tradeoff, particularly in fields like AI for personalized medicine where data access and algorithm transparency are key considerations (Lee, 2020).

The literature reviewed confirms the growing importance of intellectual property in the context of artificial intelligence. As identified, companies operating in this domain are currently facing the following key challenges:

- The increasing pace of patent application filings, which complicates strategic planning and the effective management of intellectual property portfolios.
- The necessity to redefine invention and innovation protection strategies to account for components involving artificial intelligence.
- The intensification of competitive pressure in the intellectual property domain, highlighting the critical need to implement early warning systems.

This study addresses the last of these challenges by utilizing published data on patent applications filed in 2024. It introduces a method for monitoring and analyzing of potentially patentable AI solutions.

2. Methodology

2.1 Data Collection

The dataset used in this study was obtained through patent database export (via a structured query using the WIPO Patentscope platform) with a focus on inventions related to Artificial Intelligence, particularly those describing or applying large language models (LLMs) and foundational AI architectures. To ensure relevance and currency, the dataset was filtered by publication date, limiting results to patent application published in 2024.

The query syntax employed in the search included combinations such as:

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(DP:[20240101 TO 20241231]) AND EN_ALL:("large language model" OR "foundation model" OR "transformer model" OR "language generation" OR "pretrained model" OR "prompt engineering" OR "prompt injection" OR "context window" OR "fine-tuning" OR "token embedding" OR "decoder-only transformer")
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Additional filters based on International Patent Classification (IPC) codes were applied, specifically within G06F (Electric Digital Data Processing), G06N (Computer Systems Based on Specific Computational Models), and G06V (Image or Video Recognition/Understanding).

To uncover dominant innovation directions and emerging trends in LLM-related patenting, a structured natural language processing (NLP)-based pipeline and rule-based clustering methodology were implemented, composed of the following stages:

1. Text Cleaning: Patent abstracts were cleaned by removing noise, lowercasing text, and ensuring consistency across entries.

2. Keyword and Pattern Extraction: A keyword-based extraction method was used to detect significant technological terms in each document. Common LLM-related expressions such as "fine-tuning," "prompt engineering," "retrieval-augmented generation," and "alignment techniques" were identified through pattern matching.

3. Heuristic Clustering and Technology Mapping: Rather than unsupervised machine learning clustering, a heuristic (expert-driven) method was applied to map abstracts into approximately 10–15 meaningful innovation clusters. Each cluster represented a distinct area of LLM technological development.

4. Purpose Tagging and Industry Classification: Using a rule-based mapping of keywords to societal applications, each patent was categorized into broader industries, such as Information Technology (IT), Security and Compliance, Healthcare, or Automotive sectors.

5. Temporal and Geographic Analysis: Application dates and country codes were extracted from the metadata, allowing a decomposition of innovation trends over time and a comparative analysis across countries.

6. IPC Code Analysis: International Patent Classification (IPC) codes were parsed, normalized, and analyzed to understand technological depth and concentration within various clusters.

2.2 Tools and Platforms

All data processing and analysis were conducted using Python, with the following libraries:

- Pandas and NumPy for data handling,
- Regex (re) for text pattern matching,
- Matplotlib for visualizations,
- Custom Python functions for keyword extraction and heuristic classification.

Interpretation of clusters, summarization, and formatting—were tested using two generative AI platforms: OpenAI’s ChatGPT and Google Gemini 2.5. These tools were used to cross-validate thematic interpretations of the clusters, generate summaries, and assess reproducibility of findings using AI-supported reasoning.

3. Results

The patent analysis focusing on large language models (LLMs) and related technologies reveals a dynamic and accelerating landscape. As of this analysis, a total of 338,041 patents have been identified across various jurisdictions and fields, underscoring robust global innovation and interest. The United States leads significantly with 171,843 patents, followed by international applications under the Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) with 61,333 entries, and the European Patent Office (EPO) accounting for 31,079 patents. Major industry players driving this innovation include International Business Machines Corporation (IBM) with 4,086 patents, Microsoft Technology Licensing with 2,985, Intel Corporation with 2,943, and Google with 2,342. Inventor activity also

provides insights into influential individuals, notably Kia Silverbrook with 408 patents and Yeong-Ming Chang with 261. The dominant International Patent Classification (IPC) codes, notably G06F (58,898 patents), G06N (29,040 patents), and A61K (22,836 patents), illustrate a strong interdisciplinary approach linking computer technology with healthcare and biotechnology sectors. Publication dates reveal steady growth, peaking dramatically in 2024 with 32,539 patents, indicating a surge in technological advancements and strategic patenting in recent times.

A closer examination of the 2024 dataset, comprising 32,685 patents, highlights several important trends and developments within the LLM and foundational AI space. The United States remains the primary source of innovation with 16,165 filings, followed by China with 7,783 and PCT filings accounting for 5,603. Leading applicants include Google (780 patents), Microsoft Technology Licensing (748), and NVIDIA (374), indicating significant involvement from key technology giants. Google and Microsoft's prominence reflects their expansive investment in AI infrastructure and foundational model research.

In terms of technological focus, the IPC classifications further clarify key areas of innovation. G06F (electrical digital data processing) and G06N (computer systems based on specific computational models such as neural networks) dominate with 10,943 and 8,218 filings respectively. The presence of G06V (image or video recognition) and G06T (image data processing or generation) codes suggests a growing convergence between LLM capabilities and multimodal processing technologies. Additional classifications such as A61B and A61K indicate LLM-related applications in healthcare diagnostics and pharmaceutical formulations.

The CPC codes reinforce these observations, with g06n 20/00 (machine learning) and g06n 3/08 (neural networks) leading the list. Monthly publication trends show heightened activity in the second and third quarters of 2024, particularly in May (3,027), August (4,951), and October (3,503), suggesting increased strategic patent submissions mid-year. The data not only marks the maturation of large-scale LLM applications but also highlights the expanding role of AI in intersecting domains such as computer vision, health tech, and autonomous systems.

The clustering analysis revealed that General LLM Development dominated the landscape, accounting for over 74% of all patents, followed by specialized areas such as Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), Fine-tuning LLMs, and Prompt Engineering. Innovations in Architecture (Transformers and Attention Mechanisms) also formed a significant thematic group.

From an industry perspective, the majority of patents aligned with the General IT and Multi-Industry sector, supported by strong presence in Information Technology (IT) and Data Services. Specialized fields such as Security and Compliance and Healthcare, Automotive, and Multimedia were smaller but emerging areas of interest.

Geographical analysis showed that the United States was the leading contributor to LLM-related patent filings, followed by China, WIPO international filings, Europe (EP), and Australia. The key players driving innovation in this space included major technology companies such as Google, Microsoft Technology Licensing, LLC, NVIDIA Corporation, Intel Corporation, and Qualcomm Incorporated.

4. Conclusion

Patent data represent a unique tool for monitoring market-relevant technologies, including technological advancements and emerging trends. Although patent applications do not automatically confer protection rights, they can significantly contribute to corporate processes related to innovation management, competitive and business intelligence, and intellectual property strategy.

In this paper, we focused on analyzing the current state of the art in the context of large language models as reflected in patent literature. Such analysis serves both researchers and business decision-makers by helping them understand their position within the market and enabling them to anticipate future developments—despite the inherent delay in the publication of patent applications.

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Ethics declaration

The authors declare the study does not include any personal or sensitive data.

AI declaration

The use of AI in this paper, particularly large language models, is fully documented in the Methodology section. Furthermore, Claude Sonnet 3.7 and ChatGPT 4o assisted the author in various stages of writing, including proofreading, language refinement, and bibliography formatting. All content was critically reviewed and edited by the authors, who takes full responsibility for the final version of the manuscript.

STRUCTURED INSIGHTS INTO GREEN PROCUREMENT: THE LITHUANIAN CASE

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Abstract

Green public procurement (GPP) represents a key policy instrument for promoting environmental sustainability through public sector spending. This study conducts a data-driven assessment of green procurement practices in Lithuania using publicly available procurement data accessed through the national Power BI dashboard. The analysis distinguishes between high-value and low-value green contracts (above and below € 60,000, respectively), exploring the distribution of procurement by contract type (works, services, goods), CPV (Common Procurement Vocabulary) categories, and the application of specific environmental clauses. A Pareto analysis identifies the CPV categories that dominate the volume of green tenders, while a clause-level breakdown reveals how environmental criteria are most frequently integrated into procurement documentation (e.g., technical specifications, supplier qualifications, and contract performance conditions). The findings show that in high-value contracts, the top CPV categories account for over 80% of green procurement volume, with environmental management requirements and self-determined environmental criteria being the most widely used clauses, particularly in works and services contracts.

1. Introduction

Across the European Union, Green public procurement (GPP) became a frequently used instrument for advancing environmental sustainability within the public sector, enabling governments to align their purchasing decisions with broader climate and resource-efficiency goals. GPP is increasingly encouraged through European policy frameworks and directives, but its practical implementation is still difficult to assess due to inconsistent data availability (Karnabos et al., 2022). In most countries, identifying green procurement practices requires labour-intensive textual analysis or AI-driven classification of unstructured documents. For several years, Lithuania offered a rare opportunity in this context: one of their previous national procurement platforms included a structured variable that explicitly labelled green procurements, allowing researchers and policymakers to conduct detailed, clause-level analyses based on official data. This study takes advantage of that structured data to explore the characteristics of Lithuania's green procurement market from October 2022 to October 2024. Specifically, it examines (1) the distribution of green contracts across CPV categories, (2) the

most frequently used types of environmental clauses, and (3) the sections of procurement documentation in which these clauses are typically applied.

The GPP represents a strategic tool for any organization that seeks to improve its environmental performance while contributing to sustainable development. It is a process that considers not only economic but also environmental criteria, such as carbon footprint, energy consumption, recyclability of materials, or eco-certifications, when selecting goods, services, or works. (Rebej et al., 2023). In their study, Carter, Kale, and Grimm (2000) point out that the implementation of environmental initiatives in procurement has the potential to increase not only environmental but also social sustainability. It enables purchasing managers to actively influence behaviour not only within their organisation but also with their suppliers and partners throughout the supply chain. In this way, knock-on effects are created - positive environmental practices are spread across the market, reinforcing the overall push for environmental responsibility (Preda, and Popescu, 2019). Given the growing need for sustainable procurement policies, it is clear that green procurement is not just an adjunct to environmentally responsible supply chain management, but an essential driver in the fight against climate change and the promotion of circular economy principles. (Rebej et al. ,2024; Rebej and Appollon, 2022). Green public procurement allows institutions to consider environmental and social impacts alongside price, supporting climate goals and sustainable development. At the same time, as Rebej et al. (2024) point out, green procurement is an effective way for public institutions to influence broader changes in the business sphere, as its introduction puts pressure on business partners within supply chains, ensuring greater environmental responsibility across the market.

The legal framework for public procurement in the European Union is established in the Consolidated Version of the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (2012/C 326/01), as well as in the relevant Directives of the European Parliament and of the Council, in particular Directive 2014/24/EU on public procurement and Directive 2014/25/EU, which covers procurement in the water, energy, transport, and postal services sectors. These directives enable contracting authorities and entities to apply Green Public Procurement (GPP) throughout the entire procurement process. The integration of environmental characteristics into contracts is increasingly recognized as essential, but challenges remain. The uptake of environmental supply chain management in the construction sector is limited and fragmented, indicating a need for more systematic approaches (Balasubramanian and Shukla, 2018). To meet the commitments and goals set for 2030, international cooperation must play a key role in shaping energy policies and facilitating the exchange of knowledge and best practices. The public sector plays a significant part in this process, as it can provide access to EU funds, incentives, and subsidies. In doing so, it effectively supports private sector initiatives aimed at ensuring access to affordable and clean energy (Megyesiova, Duřová Spiřáková, Gontkovičová, 2023).

2. Methodology

This study seeks to provide insight into green public procurement environment in Lithuania as one of the EU countries. The research addresses three primary questions. First, which CPV categories are most associated with green procurement in Lithuania? Second, which environmental clauses are most frequently used in green procurement contracts across works, services, and goods? Third, in which types of procurement documents are these clauses most often embedded? The answers to these questions provide a detailed view of how green procurement is implemented in practice and which sectors lead in sustainability-related contracting. The empirical analysis is based on publicly available historical data from the Lithuanian national public procurement platform, accessed through a Power BI dashboard. (Public Procurement Office of the Republic of Lithuania, 2022). This dataset was compiled from procurement notice forms submitted by contracting authorities and included a

structured indication of whether a procurement met the criteria for green procurement, as defined by national regulations. It contains detailed information on CPV codes, types of environmental criteria applied, contract values, and procurement types. The research sample covers both high-value contracts (above € 60,000) and low-value contracts (below € 60,000), enabling a comparative analysis of green procurement practices across different segments of the public procurement market. In this study, environmental clauses are defined according to the Lithuanian regulation on green procurement. Clause 4.1 refers to products listed in the official catalogue with minimum environmental criteria. Clause 4.2 covers Type I eco-labels, and Clause 4.3 involves environmental management systems like ISO 14001 or EMAS. Clause 4.4 includes self-determined criteria by contracting authorities, further divided into: products listed in eco-catalogues (4.4.1), innovative solutions (4.4.2), non-discriminatory criteria (4.4.3), and custom environmental requirements (4.4.4).

3. Results

Identifying dominant sectors in Green Public Procurement (GPP) is key to assessing the impact of environmental policies on public spending. This analysis focuses on high-value competitions exceeding € 60,000 that qualify as green procurements. Using Pareto analysis, we examine the most frequently procured green goods, services, and works by two-digit CPV categories. The results are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Pareto Analysis – High-value GPP by CPV category

Source: Author

The data show a highly concentrated distribution of high-value green procurements across CPV categories. Construction works (CPV 45) and Medical equipment and pharmaceuticals (CPV 33) together account for over 38 % of all competitions, indicating a strong sectoral focus. Although other categories, such as IT services, transport equipment, and maintenance, contribute, they do so to a much lesser extent. The top 13 CPV categories make up 80 % of the total green procurement competitions. This suggests that while GPP is present across various fields, it remains predominantly

focused on infrastructure and healthcare, with limited uptake in sectors like education, culture, and social services.

Following the analysis of high-value competitions, we will now focus on low-value green competitions, i.e., competitions with a value less than € 60,000. The aim is to see whether similar sectoral concentration patterns also occur in the lower-value segment of green public procurement (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Pareto Analysis – Low-value GPP by CPV category

Source: Author

The distribution of small-value green procurements largely reflects that of high-value ones, with Construction works (CPV 45) again leading, followed by Medical equipment and pharmaceuticals (CPV 33). Other notable categories include Repair and maintenance services (CPV 50) and Furniture (CPV 39), reflecting frequent, lower-value operational purchases. The top 17 CPV categories account for 80 % of procedures, indicating a slightly broader distribution than in high-value competitions. While concentration persists, small-value green procurement appears more diversified across sectors.

The second research question focuses on understanding which environmental clauses are most frequently used in green public procurement procedures. This is essential to identify not only the sectors where GPP is prevalent, but also how environmental sustainability is implemented contractually, whether through eco-labels, environmental management standards, or customized requirements. The Figure 3 presents a breakdown of environmental clauses by procurement type, works, services, and goods using high-value contract data. The variable shown is the percentage of green procurement procedures within each category that include a given clause. The following figure helps reveal whether different types of procurement rely on standardized, third-party criteria or customized in-house environmental goals.

Figure 3. Percentual representation of High-value GPP by clause and category Source: Author

The analysis of environmental clauses applied within green public procurement across various contract types (works, services, and goods) reveals significant variation in their implementation. Clause 4.3, referring to requirements related to environmental management systems, is predominantly utilized in works contracts, accounting for 62 % of cases in this category. Clause 4.4.4, which permits the use of self-defined environmental protection criteria, is most frequently applied in the procurement of goods (51 %) and also features prominently in services (22 %). In the domain of services, Clause 4.4.3, addressing non-material or intellectual deliverables, is notably represented, constituting 24 % of cases. By contrast, the use of Type I eco-labels (Clause 4.2) and provisions promoting innovative environmental solutions (Clause 4.4.2) remains marginal across all procurement types. These findings suggest a differentiated approach to the application of environmental criteria, with a preference for either standardized management-based requirements or flexible, self-determined measures, contingent upon the nature of the procured subject matter.

The following Figure 4 continues in this type of the analysis but for low-value green procurement contracts (below € 60,000). The goal is to determine whether the use of environmental clauses varies by contract value.

Figure 4. Percentual representation of Low-value GPP by clause and category Source: Author

The overall patterns observed in high-value contracts are replicated in the low-value segment, though with some shifts in intensity. Clause 4.3, referring to environmental management requirements, is the most frequently used in works contracts, accounting for 47 % of cases. In contrast, self-determined environmental protection criteria (Clause 4.4.4) are most dominant in the procurement of goods (35 %) and services (33 %), suggesting a preference for flexible, contracting authority-defined requirements in these categories. Services procurement also shows a substantial reliance on Clause 4.4.3, concerning non-material or intellectual items (e.g., software, licenses), which accounts for 27 %. The use of minimum environmental criteria (Clause 4.1) remains relatively high in goods (21 %) and works (17 %). Meanwhile, the use of Type I eco-labels (Clause 4.2) and provisions for innovative or eco-friendly listed products (Clause 4.4.1, 4.4.2) remains marginal.

The third and final research question seeks to determine where within procurement documentation environmental clauses are most frequently applied. Understanding this helps clarify how environmental objectives are operationalized in practice, whether during technical specification, bidder selection, contract performance, or evaluation. Each cell in Table 2 represents the proportion of high-value green procurements that include the respective clause type in that specific part of the tender documentation. This cross-sectional view allows us to assess both horizontal variation (by clause type) and vertical variation (by document type).

Table 2. Percentual representation of Environmental Clauses in Procurement Documents – High-value GPP

Where in procurement	C4.1	C4.2	C4.3	C4.4	C4.4.1	C4.4.2	C4.4.3	C4.4.4
In the technical specifications	22,55	2,06	12,06	9,80	11,65	0,19	11,97	29,73
In the contract performance conditions	15,25	0,67	6,53	11,19	9,41	0,17	11,46	45,31
In other supplier requirements	18,43	0,54	64,02	3,02	3,02	0,09	3,20	7,67
In supplier qualification requirements	18,86	1,08	58,55	3,83	3,83	0,20	2,26	11,39
In bid evaluation criteria	16,09	3,80	22,28	13,48	13,48	0,43	3,48	26,96
In supplier pre-qualification criteria	17,43	3,67	43,12	8,26	8,26	0,92	4,59	13,76

Source: Author

The analysis of high-value green public procurement shows that environmental management requirements (Clause 4.3) are most frequently applied in supplier evaluation documents, in other supplier requirements (64 %) and qualification requirements (58 %), underlining the importance of certified systems such as ISO or EMAS. Clause 4.4.4 (self-determined criteria) is most frequently used in the performance of the contract (45.31 %) and the technical specifications (29.73 %), indicating a preference for flexible, contract-specific sustainability measures. Clause 4.1 (minimum criteria) is used consistently in all documents (15 - 23 %), reflecting its essential role. Clause 4.2 (eco-labels) has been rarely used so far. Clauses dealing with innovative or intangible solutions (4.4.1 - 4.4.3) appear moderately, mainly in technical specifications and terms of performance. Overall, the data reveals a twofold strategy: reliance on standardised environmental rating systems for suppliers, and at the same time, the use of flexible criteria in the performance of contracts to promote sustainability.

To complete the analysis of where environmental clauses are applied in procurement documents, the Table 3 focuses on low-value green contracts (below € 60,000). It uses the same structure as Table 2, analysing the distribution of clause types across six parts of the procurement documentation.

Table 3. Percentual representation of Environmental Clauses in Procurement Documents – Low-value GPP

Where in procurement	C4.1	C4.2	C4.3	C4.4	C4.4.1	C4.4.2	C4.4.3	C4.4.4
In the technical specifications	25,58	1,54	5,98	5,27	3,58	0,34	9,15	48,56
In the contract performance conditions	19,73	1,17	12,53	11,38	3,64	0,23	12,35	38,97
In other supplier requirements	37,98	1,78	17,55	5,74	3,55	0,61	6,90	25,89
In supplier qualification requirements	24,72	2,12	46,79	2,25	2,45	0,53	5,09	16,06
In bid evaluation criteria	30,93	2,44	13,45	8,58	1,59	0,00	4,45	38,56
In supplier pre-qualification criteria	30,00	1,54	32,31	3,85	2,31	0,00	10,00	20,00

Source: Author

In the context of low-value green public procurements, Clause 4.4.4, referring to self-determined environmental protection criteria, was most frequently applied across documentation types, particularly in technical specifications (48 %) and contract performance conditions (38 %). Clause 4.1, which sets minimum environmental protection criteria, also showed notable representation, especially in bid evaluation criteria (30.93%) and supplier pre-qualification criteria (30 %). Environmental management requirements (Clause 4.3) were predominantly used in supplier qualification requirements (46 %) and in other supplier-related documents (17 %). The application of Clauses 4.2 (Type I eco-label), 4.4.1 (eco-labelled products), and 4.4.2 (innovative products) was considerably lower across all documentation categories. These findings highlight the dominant reliance on flexible, self-defined environmental standards and basic environmental requirements in low-value green procurements, with a comparatively limited use of certified or innovation-based criteria.

4. Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive empirical assessment of Green Public Procurement (GPP) practices in Lithuania, focusing on the concentration of GPP activities based on CPV categories, the frequency and types of environmental clauses used, and their distribution within the documentation in the procurement process. The analysis is based on structured data from the national procurement system of Lithuania. The findings show that green procurement in Lithuania is concentrated in a small number of CPV categories, mainly in the areas of construction works (CPV 45) and medical equipment and pharmaceuticals (CPV 33), with 10 - 20 categories accounting for more than 80% of the total volume of high/low-value competitions. This shows the lack of extension of GPP to less-represented areas such as education, culture, or social services. The analysis also identifies a dual approach to the application of environmental criteria: standardised requirements such as environmental management systems (clause 4.3) dominate in works contracts, while self-determined criteria (clause 4.4.4) predominate in goods and services. The clauses themselves are not tied to a single procurement phase but are spread throughout the documents required across the entire life cycle of the contracts, demonstrating the integration of sustainability. The research highlights the need for the creation or introduction of a uniform label for public procurement that would allow to clearly identify whether a particular contract meets environmental criteria and can be classified as green public procurement. The introduction of such a label would contribute to increasing transparency and clarity in the public procurement process.

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AN EMPIRICAL SURVEY OF SKILLS AND COMPETENCY EXPECTATIONS AMONG STUDENTS

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Procurement education; competencies; skills; survey research; student expectations

Abstract

The field of procurement has undergone significant evolution, particularly in understanding the skills and competencies required for effective performance. University students preparing for careers in procurement face a dynamic landscape where both technical and soft skills play a pivotal role. The aim of the conference paper is to analyze the key skills, competencies, and expectations of students specializing in procurement at a selected faculty of a university in the Czech Republic. The research focuses on identifying the competencies students consider most important for the role of a procurement professional, while also examining their perceptions of the procurement function within the business environment. The empirical part is based on an online questionnaire survey conducted among 174 respondents who studied the relevant program during the years 2022–2024. The findings provide valuable insights for optimizing academic curricula and supporting the professional development of future procurement specialists.

1. Introduction

Literature review section reviews some of the studies to contextualize the skills necessary for modern procurement professionals.

The analysis of procurement professionals' skills and competencies represents an essential tool for the systematic management of procurement processes and the strengthening of organizations' competitive advantage. It enables the precise definition of required competencies, more effective planning of professional development, and the optimization of recruitment processes. At the same time, it is advisable to gather feedback from potential candidates or students of procurement, particularly regarding their expectations and motivations. This approach not only facilitates the

alignment of educational and professional objectives but also provides valuable insights into further innovation in procurement strategies and the development of job roles.

The objective of the paper is to analyze the key skills, competencies, and expectations of students specializing in procurement at a Faculty of Economics, VSB-technical University of Ostrava. The research sample comprises 174 respondents who pursued studies in a business-oriented discipline at the designated faculty. Data collection was conducted over a three-year span, covering the period from 2022 to 2024. The collected data are described using descriptive statistics, and advanced statistical methods will also be employed to provide deeper insights. Furthermore, a comparative analysis of the results across individual years will be conducted to identify potential trends and differences over time.

2. Literature review

Procurement roles have been increasingly influenced by digitalization and globalization, as highlighted by Delke, Schiele, and Buchholz (2022). Their study utilized the World Café methodology with 81 professionals to identify how Industry 4.0 shapes procurement roles. Direct procurement was found to require greater responsibility for innovation, while indirect procurement emphasizes cultural awareness, flexibility, and communication skills. These findings underscore the necessity for educational programs that cater to the distinct demands of these procurement types.

A complementary perspective is offered by Klezl et al. (2022), who analyzed job advertisements to map the skills and personality traits demanded across managerial and operational roles in procurement and supply chain management. Their content analysis revealed that managerial roles prioritize leadership and strategic thinking, while operational positions demand technical expertise and precision. These insights point to a divergence in skill requirements and the need for tailored curricula that align with these differing roles.

Managerial competencies in procurement were further examined by Changalima and Ismail (2019), who used structural equation modeling to study public procurement in Tanzania. Their research demonstrated that networking and leadership skills significantly influence cost reduction and compliance. Additionally, technical and communication skills play a crucial role in enhancing procurement efficiency. These findings align with Changalima and Mdee's (2022) subsequent study, which emphasized procurement planning as a mediating factor in the relationship between procurement skills and organizational performance. Analytical thinking, negotiation, and financial planning were highlighted as essential for translating skills into actionable outcomes.

Despite their varied contexts, these studies converge on the importance of integrating technical, managerial, and soft skills to address the demands of modern procurement environments. Technical skills, such as cost management and contract administration, remain foundational. However, increasing emphasis on strategic thinking, adaptability, and leadership reflects the evolving role of procurement professionals. For university students, bridging the gap between academic preparation and industry expectations is vital. Addressing these skill gaps through targeted educational programs will equip future procurement professionals to navigate complexities effectively and contribute to organizational success and innovation.

3. Research design

This section presents the methodological framework of research. It outlines the fundamental conditions related to data collection and provides a brief overview of the methods employed.

3.1 Data collection

This study adopts a quantitative research approach, utilizing primary data obtained through an online survey administered to university students who completed courses related to purchasing. The data were collected over the period from 2022 to 2024 and include responses from three distinct cohorts of students enrolled in marketing and business programs with a focus on procurement-related subjects. In total, 174 valid questionnaires were gathered for analysis.

The research instrument consisted of a questionnaire comprising 23 distinct questions, formulated to align with the objectives of the study. Data collection results were processed using IBM SPSS Statistics. The analysis involved not only basic frequency distributions but also the application of advanced statistical techniques. Most of the collected data are of a nominal or ordinal nature, with respondents assessing specified factors on a five-point Likert scale (where 1 denotes the most favorable response and 5 the least favorable), see Boone and Boone 2012; Joshi et al. 2015. The questionnaire items are systematically categorized by type into closed, semi-closed, and open-ended questions, and by focus into factual and identification-oriented questions. One of the main limitations of the presented article is the relatively small sample size.

3.2 Applied methods

The methods applied in this study are aligned with the nature of the research, the defined objectives, and the characteristics of the dataset. Given the limitations of the article, only selected results are presented. The analysis began with the application of standard descriptive statistics, followed by an assessment of data distribution. Subsequently, relationships between selected variables were examined using non-parametric tests. All hypotheses were tested at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The methodological procedure consisted of three fundamental steps: (a) descriptive statistical analysis, (b) testing for normality, and (c) Mann-Whitney U test.

4. Results

The results are structured into two sections. The first section presents basic descriptive characteristics, while the second section focuses on the analysis of the relationships between gender and preferred employment benefits, as well as personality traits (abilities).

4.1 Descriptive statistics

A total of 174 students participated in the survey, of whom 68% were women and 32% men. Despite this gender imbalance, the sample is considered representative, as all students responded, and the gender distribution reflects the actual composition of the student population in the program.

The results show that most students expect their starting gross monthly salary to fall within the middle range of the scale. The most frequent response was the 30,000–35,000 CZK category (35.6%), followed by 35,000–40,000 CZK (22.4%) and 20,000–25,000 CZK (21.8%). This suggests that students have relatively realistic expectations, with the majority aiming for a mid to slightly above-average income range. Expectations of extremely low or high salaries are rare. However, it is worth noting that the 20,000–25,000 CZK gross monthly salary range represents a relatively low level of expectation given current wage trends in the labor market.

The data show that most students (35.1%) prefer an employer regardless of company size, which may indicate that other factors play a more important role for them – such as company culture, industry, job content, or benefits. The second most common choice (27%) is working for a medium-sized

company, which is often perceived as a balance between stability and flexibility. A large company is attractive to 10.3% of respondents, while 12.6% prefer a small company. Interestingly, 14.4% of students are considering self-employment. This result suggests a slight shift toward a greater willingness to work independently.

	N	Mean
Career growth opportunities	174	1,53
Flexible working hours	174	1,76
Remote work option (home office)	174	1,80
Opportunity for further education	174	1,93
Vacation beyond statutory minimum (more than 25 days)	174	2,14
Sick days (3-5 days)	174	2,18
Contribution to sports/culture activities	174	2,30
Contribution to pension plan	174	2,38
Laptop	174	2,60
Free refreshments at the workplace (drinks, coffee, fruit, etc.)	174	2,63
Cell phone	174	3,21
A company car	174	3,38
Valid N (listwise)	174	

Figure 1. Preferred employment benefits Source: (author)

The results indicate which employee benefits are most important to students when choosing an employer. The highest levels of agreement (i.e., lowest mean scores) were given to developmental and flexible working conditions, specifically, career growth opportunities, flexible working hours, and the option to work remotely. These findings reflect the preferences of the younger generation, which values professional development, work-life balance, and modern forms of work. On the other hand, material benefits such as a company phone or car were rated as less important, receiving the highest mean scores (indicating lower agreement). Other benefits, such as contributions to sports and cultural activities, pension plans, or free refreshments at the workplace, fall into a medium range of importance. Overall, the results suggest that students prioritize intangible and development-oriented benefits over traditional material perks, reflecting the values of today’s young workforce.

	N	Mean
I am goal-oriented	174	2,0
Career is important to me	174	2,1
I like to communicate with people indirectly	174	2,4
I can work well under pressure	174	2,5
I am fluent in English	174	2,6
I like to communicate with people directly	174	2,7
I handle stressful situations well	174	2,7
I'm an extrovert	174	2,8
I enjoy working with data	174	2,9
I enjoy working with IT systems	174	3,0
Valid N (listwise)	174	

Figure 2. Personality characteristics (abilities) Source: (author)

The results of the descriptive statistics show that students generally agree most strongly with statements reflecting their goal orientation and the importance of career, indicating a high level of intrinsic motivation and professional focus. Conversely, lower levels of agreement were observed in statements related to working with data, information technologies, and extroversion, which may suggest lower preferences or confidence in these areas. Other examined characteristics, such as

working under pressure, communication, and stress management, show moderate levels of agreement. Overall, the findings suggest that students are ambitious, but there are areas, particularly technical and interpersonal skills, where further development could be beneficial.

4.2 Difference in the evaluation of employment benefits between men and women

First, we verified the assumption of normal data distribution. A normality test is used to assess whether the data follow a normal distribution. Given the nature of our data, we applied the Shapiro-Wilk test. The resulting p-values ($p \leq 0.05$) indicated that the distribution in our sample significantly deviates from normality. Since the assumptions for parametric tests were not met, we opted for a non-parametric statistical method. For this type of comparison, the Mann-Whitney U test is a suitable method (see Mann and Whitney, 1947), which works with ordinal data. The null hypothesis (H0) assumes that both groups come from the same population, i.e., they are homogeneous and share the same distribution (Nachar, 2008). Median values are recommended to describe the basic characteristics of the data. It can thus be concluded that the respondents answered the questions in a relatively similar manner. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine whether employment benefits differ by gender and whether personality traits (abilities) vary between men and women. The null hypothesis assumes that the median values are equal across groups, whereas the alternative hypothesis suggests that the medians gradually increase or decrease between groups.

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig. ^{a,b}	Decision
1	The distribution of A company car. is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,011	Reject the null hypothesis.
2	The distribution of Phone is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,626	Retain the null hypothesis.
3	The distribution of Laptop. is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,433	Retain the null hypothesis.
4	The distribution of Contribution to pension plan is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,382	Retain the null hypothesis.
5	The distribution of Flexible working hours. is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,693	Retain the null hypothesis.
6	The distribution of Remote work option (home office) is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,296	Retain the null hypothesis.
7	The distribution of Sick days (3-5 days). is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,064	Retain the null hypothesis.
8	The distribution of Vacation beyond statutory minimum (more than 25 days) is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,419	Retain the null hypothesis.
9	The distribution of Free refreshments at the workplace (drinks, coffee, fruit, etc.) is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,966	Retain the null hypothesis.
10	The distribution of Contribution to sports/culture activities is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,483	Retain the null hypothesis.
11	The distribution of Opportunity for further education is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,209	Retain the null hypothesis.
12	The distribution of Career growth opportunities is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,633	Retain the null hypothesis.

a. The significance level is ,050.

b. Asymptotic significance is displayed.

Figure 3. Statistically significant difference in the evaluation of employment benefits between men and women
Source: (author)

The test revealed that a gender difference was statistically significant only in the evaluation of the company car benefit. For all other benefits and working conditions, no significant differences in evaluation between men and women were found. These results indicate generally equal evaluations across genders, except for one specific benefit.

4.3 Difference in the evaluation of personality characteristics (abilities) between men and women

Hypothesis Test Summary				
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig. ^{a,b}	Decision
1	The distribution of I'm an extrovert is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,656	Retain the null hypothesis.
2	The distribution of I like to communicate with people directly is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,705	Retain the null hypothesis.
3	The distribution of I like to communicate with people indirectly is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,981	Retain the null hypothesis.
4	The distribution of I enjoy working with IT systems is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,065	Retain the null hypothesis.
5	The distribution of I can work well under pressure is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,015	Reject the null hypothesis.
6	The distribution of I enjoy working with data is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,042	Reject the null hypothesis.
7	The distribution of I handle stressful situations well is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,026	Reject the null hypothesis.
8	The distribution of I am goal-oriented is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,273	Retain the null hypothesis.
9	The distribution of Career is important to me is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,543	Retain the null hypothesis.
10	The distribution of I am fluent in English is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	,265	Retain the null hypothesis.

a. The significance level is ,050.

b. Asymptotic significance is displayed.

Figure 4. Statistically significant difference in the evaluation of personality characteristics (abilities) between men and women Source: (author)

Significant gender differences in evaluation were found for these three characteristics. Men and women differ notably in how they assess their ability to work under pressure, their relationship to working with data, and their ability to handle stressful situations. This may suggest differences in self-perception of these abilities between genders. Overall, the results support general equality in personality profiles, but they also indicate specific areas where gender may play a role.

Looking at the results of the contingency tables, we can conclude that there is a statistically significant difference between the evaluation of three personality traits and gender. Specifically, men reported that they handle stress better than women, cope more effectively with working under pressure, and prefer working with data. Of course, these results may indicate certain differences; however, for more general conclusions, it is necessary to work with a representative sample of respondents or to follow up with qualitative research, which can help explore the depth of these evaluations and their underlying causes.

5. Conclusion

The results suggest that students hold relatively realistic salary expectations, with most aiming for a gross monthly income in the mid-range category. Extremely low or high expectations are rare, though some students still report expectations that may fall below current market averages.

When choosing an employer, students tend to prioritize factors beyond company size, placing the greatest emphasis on career growth opportunities, flexible working hours, and the option to work remotely. These preferences highlight the importance of professional development, work-life balance, and modern working conditions to the younger generation. Material benefits, such as a company car or phone, were rated as less important, suggesting a shift in values toward non-material and growth-oriented incentives.

In terms of personality traits, students showed strong agreement with statements indicating goal orientation and career ambition, reflecting high intrinsic motivation. Conversely, lower levels of agreement were noted in areas related to data handling, information technologies, and extroversion. Moderate responses were observed in domains such as communication, stress management, and working under pressure, pointing to potential areas for further development, especially in technical and interpersonal skills.

Gender differences were minimal across most benefit evaluations and working condition preferences, except for the company car, where men and women differed significantly. However, statistically significant gender-based differences emerged in the self-assessment of three personality traits: handling stress, working under pressure, and working with data. Men reported higher confidence in these areas than women, which may suggest differences in self-perception. While these findings point to specific areas where gender may play a role, broader conclusions would require a larger, representative sample or complementary qualitative research to further explore the underlying causes.

Overall, the study indicates that today's students are career-focused, value flexibility and development over traditional benefits, and perceive themselves as motivated and ambitious—with some variability by gender in how they assess certain competencies.

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AI-SUPPORTED DECISION-MAKING IN THE OUTSOURCING OF INTERNAL LOGISTICS PROCESSES

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Abstract

This paper examines how artificial intelligence (AI) can support decision-making in the outsourcing of internal logistics services. Based on a case study of Ford Trans Slovakia, the research compares traditional supplier evaluation methods with AI-enhanced multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) models. The study specifically integrates predictive analytics with the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AI-AHP) and a Forced Decision-Making Matrix (AI-FDMM) to assess potential logistics providers. Findings highlight improved accuracy in supplier ranking, early risk detection, and better alignment with strategic goals. The results demonstrate that AI tools significantly reduce managerial subjectivity and enhance the predictive quality of decisions. The paper concludes by recommending the adoption of hybrid decision-making models that combine AI capabilities with expert insights, as well as investments in data infrastructure to ensure long-term competitiveness.

1. Introduction

Outsourcing has become a key strategic approach for companies striving to optimize processes, enhance flexibility, and improve cost-efficiency. In the fields of logistics and warehousing, outsourcing decisions are often driven by the need to streamline operations, refocus internal resources on core activities, and gain a competitive advantage through specialized service providers. However, identifying optimal outsourcing opportunities and selecting appropriate logistics partners remains a complex, multidimensional challenge for management teams.

This paper examines the application and effectiveness of artificial intelligence (AI)-enhanced multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods in the context of logistics outsourcing—specifically in warehousing and internal logistics services within a selected enterprise. Using the example of Ford Trans Slovakia (FTS), the authors compare traditional outsourcing decision-making methods with those supported by AI technologies. The aim of this research is to demonstrate how AI-assisted decision-making can improve conventional outsourcing practices.

2. Literature review

Outsourcing is regarded as a strategic component of modern logistics management, with the potential to incorporate external resources into core business operations. It involves the transfer of responsibility for internal activities to third-party providers, under the expectation that outsourced tasks will be performed at a quality level sufficient to meet the company's predefined objectives (Csikosova et al., 2022). Originally derived from the concept of "outside resource using," outsourcing has evolved into a widely adopted managerial strategy across various corporate functions. According to Akbari et al. (2018), logistics outsourcing entails delegating selected operational tasks—such as transportation, warehousing, inventory management, and distribution—to specialized external providers. These providers are expected to deliver services more efficiently due to economies of scale, domain expertise, and targeted resource allocation.

Strategic decisions to outsource logistics functions are typically motivated by goals such as increasing organizational flexibility, reducing costs, accessing advanced technologies, and concentrating internal efforts on core competencies (Murphy & Knemeyer, 2017). It is essential for managers to determine which activities should be outsourced and which should remain in-house. Commonly outsourced functions include customer service, human resource management, accounting, transportation, warehousing, and related services. Logistics outsourcing enables companies to convert fixed operational costs into variable ones, thereby improving responsiveness to market fluctuations (Rushton et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, outsourcing decisions inherently carry risks, such as dependence on external providers, potential quality control issues, and the loss of direct operational oversight (Christopher, 2022). Therefore, the selection of a suitable logistics partner is a critical task that typically requires a complex decision-making process.

Traditional approaches to selecting logistics partners often rely on manual analysis, expert judgment, and basic decision-making frameworks. While these methods provide general guidance, they may struggle to address the dynamic complexity of modern supply chains. In contrast, rapidly evolving technologies particularly artificial intelligence (AI) offer innovative solutions to enhance the precision, speed, and predictive power of decision-making. AI-supported decision-making processes can significantly improve traditional multi-criteria evaluation methods by incorporating advanced predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms. These technologies enable deeper insights into potential risks, cost savings, and supplier performance, thereby facilitating more informed and strategic decisions.

Selecting a logistics outsourcing partner requires multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM), which involves evaluating numerous critical factors such as cost, service quality, reliability, technological advancement, and innovation potential (Uygun et al., 2023). Traditionally, companies have addressed the complexity of such evaluations through techniques like the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), forced decision-making matrices (FDMM), or various ratio-based approaches (Saaty & Vargas, 2012).

Although these frameworks are effective, they are limited by their reliance on expert input and static evaluation criteria. Recent research suggests that integrating artificial intelligence (AI) can greatly enhance these methods—boosting accuracy, predictive capacity, and adaptability to dynamic environments (Andaloussi, 2024). Artificial intelligence, particularly machine learning (ML) and predictive analytics, is beginning to transform logistics and supply chain management. AI technologies provide powerful tools for analysing large datasets, detecting hidden patterns, forecasting future scenarios, and enabling data-informed strategic decisions (Goodfellow et al., 2016; Russell & Norvig, 2022).

AI-powered predictive analytics allow logistics managers to anticipate demand shifts, predict supply chain disruptions, and dynamically assess supplier performance (Fedorko et al., 2023). Notably, AI-augmented MCDM methods have proven effective in complex supplier selection tasks, where human evaluators may struggle to consider interdependencies among multiple criteria (Tate et al., 2019).

Advanced AI algorithms—such as supervised learning models and deep neural networks—are increasingly used in logistics applications to deliver real-time insights and recommendations that go beyond traditional human-centered decision frameworks (Marr, 2017). AI implementation not only improves current decision-making but also learns from ongoing data inputs, enabling continuous optimization of logistics operations. Overall, AI technologies represent a transformative leap for decision-making in logistics. Their integration with traditional MCDM methods enhances accuracy, predictive power, and strategic value, enabling organizations to thrive in increasingly complex and competitive environments.

3. Methodology

The appropriate selection of a supplier is a crucial step in business logistics, involving a complex and multi-layered process aimed at identifying the most suitable service provider. This decision-making process is further complicated by the large number of suppliers available on the market.

To support supplier evaluation and selection, managers may choose from several methodological approaches, which can be broadly categorized into three types:

- *Empirical methods.* These are based on the subjective judgment of the evaluator, often derived from practical experience and expertise (e.g., Brainstorming, Delphi, Syntetics).
- *Exact methods.* These rely on mathematical and statistical techniques and operations research (e.g., probability theory, network analysis, queuing models).
- *Heuristic methods.* These combine elements of empirical and exact approaches (e.g., preference theory, decision trees, decision matrices) (Janoskova et al., 2018).

AI-Supported Decision-Making

To address the challenges associated with logistics outsourcing in the selected company, some multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) framework was applied. The outcomes of traditional methods were compared to those generated using an AI-supported approach (ChatGPT). This hybrid model combines machine learning algorithms and predictive analytics with established decision-making tools such as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and the Forced Decision-Making Matrix (FDMM).

AHP and AI-AHP: Augmented Analytic Hierarchy Process

The model incorporates Random Forest and Gradient Boosting algorithms to process historical data, including delivery accuracy, responsiveness to scheduling changes, and supplier reliability. The process consists of three main steps:

- Criteria definition and integration of historical data
- Predictive analytics and dynamic weighting of criteria
- Pairwise comparison of suppliers and ranking generation

AI-FDMM: AI-Enhanced Forced Decision Matrix Method

This model offers an alternative approach to supplier evaluation based on simulations of future scenarios. The results obtained through AI-FDMM were used to verify and complement the outputs of the AI-AHP model.

Implementation of Predictive Analytics Models

The models were trained using five years of historical data. Random Forest produced the most accurate predictions for delivery precision and cost deviations, while Gradient Boosting was better suited to handling extreme events.

Neural networks were applied in an exploratory manner, primarily to test their potential for identifying hidden relationships within a dataset. However, given their limited interpretability, their role remained complementary. The outputs were triangulated with data from more transparent models (e.g., random forest, gradient boosting, increasing robustness without compromising clarity).

The methodology applied to ensure model reliability supports reproducibility. The AI-based models were trained on a dataset comprising five years of operational data from Ford Trans Slovakia. The training set contained more than 1,200 data points encompassing supplier performance metrics such as delivery accuracy, lead time variability, cost variance, response to change requests, and compliance with technical standards. The selection of features was done using correlation analysis and validation by experts in the field. The indicators with the highest relevance to logistics performance were prioritized.

4. Case Study: Ford Trans Slovakia

Ford Trans Slovakia (FTS), a member of the global network of automotive suppliers, primarily focuses on the production of advanced transmission systems. The company's strategic priority is the continuous optimization of internal processes in order to ensure operational efficiency and sustain long-term competitive advantage. One area under regular assessment is internal logistics, particularly warehousing and related services.

Current Logistics Operations at FTS

The company's logistics framework involves comprehensive management of raw materials, semi-finished products, and finished goods. The Logistics Service Center at the plant coordinates these processes, including material handling, inventory control, and storage. Internal logistics is divided into two main categories:

- *Warehouse logistics*: covering goods receipt, storage, packaging, and dispatch. The warehouse operates with standards such as KLT containers and uses the SAP system for inventory tracking and transaction processing.
- *Production logistics*: supporting production lines through material replenishment (Kanban), material flow management, and handling between the warehouse and manufacturing lines. Accurate timing is critical in this process.

Historically, these logistics operations have been managed internally. However, recent analyses have revealed inefficiencies, particularly in terms of flexibility and responsiveness to demand fluctuations and external disruptions.

Assessment of Identified Shortcomings

- *Cost inefficiencies*: high fixed costs related to infrastructure and labor remain a challenge.
- *Lack of flexibility*: internal processes respond slowly to changes in production schedules and logistical disturbances.
- *Technological limitations*: the introduction of innovations is hindered by complex internal approval procedures.

These findings point to potential benefits from partial outsourcing, especially in the area of warehousing.

Identified Outsourcing Opportunities

GFT evaluated warehousing and related services as the most suitable candidates for outsourcing. The selection criteria for logistics partners included not only cost but also technological maturity, flexibility, innovation capability, and strategic alignment with GFT's goals. Given the complexity of the decision-making process, the company opted to implement AI tools to support the evaluation and selection of a suitable partner.

5. Results and Discussion

The implementation of AI-based multi-criteria decision-making (AI-MCDM) at GFT led to significantly more efficient supplier evaluation processes when compared to traditional approaches. A key indicator in this comparison was the accuracy and reliability of the final supplier rankings. Traditional methods relied on static historical data and subjective managerial assessments. In contrast, AI models introduced dynamic predictive analytics, enriching the evaluation process with insights into future performance scenarios.

Results according to AI-AHP

The AI-AHP model revealed discrepancies between suppliers' historical performance and their predicted future potential. It identified suppliers whose performance may decline due to market shocks or technological lag, as well as those with untapped potential. For example, Supplier A, previously considered average, was identified through predictive analytics as highly flexible and innovative, with strong growth potential over the next three years. Conversely, Supplier C, traditionally viewed as reliable, was flagged as high-risk in scenarios involving technological changes.

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was enhanced with AI-powered predictive analytics. Historical logistics data was analysed using Random Forest and Gradient Boosting algorithms, enabling dynamic weighting of criteria and improving accuracy in supplier evaluations (Table 1).

Table 1: AI-AHP Evaluation Criteria and Weights

Criterion	Weight (%)
Cost efficiency	25
Delivery reliability	20
Operational flexibility	15

Criterion	Weight (%)
Technological capability	15
Scalability	15
Innovation Potential	10

Source: authors

The repositioning of Supplier A demonstrates the added value of predictive insights offered by AI technologies (Table 2).

Table 2: Comparison of Supplier Rankings: Traditional vs AI-AHP

Supplier	Traditional Ranking	AI-AHP Ranking
A	4	1
B	1	2
C	2	4
D	3	3

Source: authors

Results according to AI-FDMM

The results from the AI-supported Forced Decision Matrix Method (AI-FDMM) complemented and validated the outcomes of the AI-AHP model. Scenario-based analyses highlighted performance risks that would likely have been overlooked using traditional methods. Some suppliers were re-evaluated in terms of scalability and adaptability, which affected their final rankings.

AI-FDMM Risk Evaluation

Table 3: AI-Based Risk Assessment of Suppliers

Supplier	Traditional Risk	AI-based Risk	Recommendation
A	Moderate	Low	Preferred
B	Low	Low	Preferred
C	Low	High	Avoid
D	Low	Moderate	Monitor

Source: authors

While Supplier C was traditionally perceived as low-risk, AI-based evaluation revealed significant vulnerabilities due to projected technological stagnation and limited adaptability (Table 3).

Managerial Feedback on AI Integration

Feedback from management indicated a high level of satisfaction with the integration of AI tools, emphasizing enhanced strategic clarity, improved understanding of supplier relationships, and reduced decision-making bias.

Table 4: Managerial Evaluation of AI Benefits

Evaluation Criteria	Score (1-5)
Decision Objectivity	4.8
Predictive Accuracy	4.7
Strategic Decision Support	4.9
Ease of Use	4.2
Risk Mitigation	4.6

Source: authors

Benefits of AI implementation in Logistics Decision-Making

The implementation of AI in outsourcing decision-making brought not only higher accuracy of assessment, but also the possibility of strategic foresight. Predictive models allowed management to respond in a timely manner to risks that would otherwise remain unidentified. Moreover, these tools also created space for a more qualified discussion across decision-making levels and reduced dependence on subjective inputs.

Stakeholder feedback focused on interviews with logistics managers and decision-makers, who confirmed a high level of satisfaction with AI tools. Their main benefits were identified as:

- better understanding of complex supplier relationships,
- increased confidence in decisions,
- ability to model uncertainty and respond to changes.

Managerial interpretability

While the predictive accuracy of AI models can be considered a key advantage, their adoption in managerial practice is conditioned by interpretability. To address this issue, the authors of the study propose to introduce the principles of explainable artificial intelligence (XAI), especially in relation to supplier selection. XAI frameworks such as SHAP (SHapley Additive ExPlanations) can be used to visualize important elements and clarify how individual factors influenced supplier evaluation. This transparency can significantly improve managers' confidence and support the integration of AI-generated insights into strategic decision-making processes.

6. Conclusion

This study focused on the strategic application of AI in decision-making related to the outsourcing of warehousing and internal logistics services, using a case study of Ford Trans Slovakia. The integration of AI—particularly predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms—into traditional multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods such as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and the Forced Decision-Making Matrix (FDMM) resulted in significant advantages.

Key Findings:

- AI-enhanced methods improved the accuracy of supplier evaluation and selection.
- Predictive analytics enabled the identification of supplier risks and strengths that would have otherwise remained undiscovered.

- Decision-making became less dependent on subjective managerial judgment and more grounded in data-driven analysis.

The authors urge GFT's management to invest in high-quality data collection and management systems, as these are essential for precise AI-driven analysis. Building an internal analytics team is recommended to ensure competency in handling critical business decisions. Furthermore, it is advisable to combine AI-generated outputs with expert managerial judgment—hybrid decision models have proven to be the most effective.

Benefits of AI Integration in Decision-Making:

- **Increased Objectivity:** AI reduces cognitive bias and subjective influence in decision-making.
- **Improved decision-making accuracy.**
- **Proactive Risk Management:** Early identification of vulnerabilities within the supply chain.
- **Adaptability:** Dynamic modelling allows companies to respond to changing market conditions.
- **Strategic Alignment:** Decisions are better aligned with the organization's long-term goals.

The pace of technological progress also requires companies to regularly update and validate their predictive models using fresh data inputs. The study concludes that the strategic integration of AI into logistics decision-making is not merely a technological innovation, it is a key enabler of efficiency, adaptability, and sustainable competitive advantage in today's complex business environment.

Although this study is based on the context of Ford Trans Slovakia, the methodology has been designed to allow for adaptability. Future research should focus on validating the proposed approach across multiple cases and various sectors, such as retail or e-commerce. This would enable further refinement of model parameters and an assessment of robustness in heterogeneous logistics environments. Moreover, broadening the scope to include demand forecasting, inventory optimisation, and transport planning will enhance the practical utility of the framework. The integration of artificial intelligence into logistics outsourcing decision-making not only improves accuracy and objectivity but also marks a shift towards data-driven strategic formulation. Nonetheless, transparency remains essential. This can be achieved through the application of explainable AI techniques and detailed documentation of model architecture and functioning.

The authors intend to expand this research by exploring the use of AI in inventory management, demand forecasting, and transport planning. Special attention will be given to explainable AI (XAI) as a potential way to improve the interpretability and managerial acceptance of AI-generated outputs.

The strategic integration of artificial intelligence into logistics decision-making processes is more than a technological innovation; it is a key prerequisite for achieving higher efficiency, adaptability, and sustainable competitive advantage in today's complex business environment. In addition to reviewing international literature, this study offers a practical model for managerial implementation. Future research should not only deepen the integration of AI tools into operational processes and the strategic logistics management, but also on cross-sectoral verification.

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UNIVERSITY-INDUSTRY COLLABORATION

ROLE OF ACADEMIA IN SEMICONDUCTOR INNOVATIONS: BETWEEN FREEDOM AND RESILIENCE

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Semiconductor industry; integrated circuits; supply chain resilience; national semiconductor strategies; institutional innovation models

Abstract

The goal is to provide a comprehensive overview of semiconductor products, production processes, and strategic positioning of Central Europe, and the policies and institutional frameworks that shape global competitiveness in this critical industry. It examines national and regional strategies from major global players including the US, EU, China, Japan, Korea, and Taiwan. Finally, it identifies institutional models facilitating the transition from research to innovation and the significance of university-led contributions to talent and innovation. The ultimate goal is to provide advices what study programs are vital for further scalable development of this industry and its applications, and what institutional instruments can the policymakers use to foster the semiconductor industry and innovation growth in Czechia and Europe.

1. Introduction

Semiconductors are essential components that drive modern technology. Their importance extends beyond computing into other strategic sectors such as energy industry, defense, where they enable sophisticated systems for surveillance, data processing, and autonomous control. They also

increasingly shape the globalization (Lamsal, Devkota, & Bhusal, 2023). In this setting, academia plays a dual role – as a source of foundational research and as a partner in innovation ecosystems.

1.1 Goal and Structure of the Paper

Chapter 2 brings an overview of semiconductor products and production processes, followed by Chapter 3 describing strategic positioning of Central Europe. Then in 4, it analyses the R&D intensity, Chapter 5 examines of national and regional strategies from major players such as the US, EU, China, Japan, Korea, and Taiwan. Finally, it identifies institutional models – such as ITRI, IMEC, and KAIST – that facilitate the transition from research to industrial innovation.

2. Semiconductor Products

2.1 What are Semiconductor Elements?

Semiconductor elements primarily refer to “chips” – that is, integrated circuits (ICs) composed of up to billions of transistors. These chips are found in a wide variety of applications, such as central processing units (CPUs), graphics processing units (GPUs), and other processors used across computing and communication systems. A specialized category includes *ASICs (Application-Specific Integrated Circuits)*, which are designed for specific tasks in fields like automotive systems, military hardware, and consumer electronics. Semiconductor chips serve essential roles in both *computational processing* and *data storage*.

2.2 Logic and Memory Semiconductor Devices

They are what we mostly colloquially understand as chips – integrated circuits of high complexity serving as the “hearts and brains” of today’s computers, smartphones, and drive the global online services running in large datacenters, as well as banking, governments, telcos, and many more. They are by far the most complex semiconductor devices manufactured using high-tech production processes in a limited number of fabs. The most advanced manufacturers are Samsung (memory chips) and TSMC (logic chips). Apart of final production, there is a strong position of so-called fabless industries based on chip-design rather than manufacturing, such as NVIDIA or Apple that not only design their custom chips but also deliver products to end customers.

2.3 Power Semiconductor Devices

Power semiconductor devices are crucial for transmission, distribution, and conversion of electrical energy. They are commonly used in *photovoltaic systems* and *distributed energy resources (DER)* to control and optimize energy flow. In transportation, they are central to *traction systems* such as those in electric vehicles, locomotives, and e-bikes. Power semiconductors also play a vital role in *high-voltage direct current (HVDC)* power transmission and are based on wide-band gap materials such as silicon carbide (SiC). OnSemi and Infineon belong to the top vendors.

2.4 Analog-Digital Chips

Analog-digital chips (Martins et al, 2021) are fundamental for *telecommunications devices*, including *transmitters and receivers* for various RF (Radio Frequency) purposes. These chips are also included in *positioning system receivers*, such as GPS, Baidou, or Glonass, where they receive satellite signals to determine location. Analog-digital chips are frequently used as *amplifiers*. They are also vital for

medical devices as sensors. In general, these chips are indispensable in systems where analog input must be converted to digital form or vice versa.

2.5 Special Semiconductor Devices

Notably, the current era opens the future for quantum communication and computing employing completely different physical principles such as silicon spin qubits, donor qubits, or quantum dots, and allowing quantum computing as a new paradigm. Other classes of special devices include organic semiconductors where some of them are already in use, such as organic LED (OLED) in displays. Organic photovoltaics is another promising field, capable of producing flexible, light, and cheap photovoltaic cells.

3. Position of Semiconductor Industry

3.1 Semiconductors in Central Europe

Central European countries – particularly CZ, DE, SK, and PL – are recognized for their diverse contributions to the semiconductor value chain, especially since the *EU Chips Act*. The next table provides an overview of semiconductor sector share of GDP as a proxy for its economic significance.

Table 1. Estimated Share of Semiconductor Industry GDP for Selected Central European Countries

Country	Estimated Share of GDP	Context / Notes
Czech Republic	0.5% – 1%	Established microelectronics sector with design and manufacturing presence. OnSemi and South Moravia are notable contributors, see Czech Strategy (2024).
Germany	1% – 1.5%	Leading European semiconductor producer with focus on automotive and industrial chips (Infineon, Bosch). Major investments in scaling production (new fab in Dresden), see (German Trade and Invest, 2024).
Slovakia	0.5% – 1%	Electronics sector closely tied to automotive industry. Notable contribution to GDP through sensors and microelectronics, see Statista (2025).
Poland	0.2% – 0.5%	Emerging player focused on semiconductor design and software. Increasing investments in packaging capabilities as of Grzegorzcyk (2024)

3.2 Semiconductors in Czech Economy

For further analysis, five sectors and three key technologies that can benefit from the development of integrated circuit design in the Czech Republic were identified in the *National Semiconductor Strategy* (Czech Strategy, 2024) based on the *National RIS3 Strategy*:

- *Industries*: 1. Automotive, namely electric vehicles; 2. Railways and rolling stock; 3. Aerospace, in particular the space sector; 4. Energy; 5. Electronics and Electrical Engineering.

- *Key technologies under the Czech National Semiconductor Strategy are:* 1) *Cybersecurity* (thematic area Digital Technologies and Electrical Engineering, key technology Digital Security and Connectivity); 2) *Artificial Intelligence* (thematic area Digital Technologies and Electrical Engineering, key technology Artificial Intelligence); 3) *Photonics and Micro/Nanoelectronics* (thematic area Digital Technologies and Electrical Engineering, key technology Photonics and Micro/Nanoelectronics). 4) *Innovations in Semiconductor Production Key Steps*

Innovations in semiconductor production reflects the R&D intensity in each phase. As a prerequisite, qualified personnel must be trained in specific study programs.

4.1 R&D Intensity

Design: its goal is to create custom systems on chips (SoCs), HW accelerators, analog-digital devices. This phase requires complex EDA tools featuring formal verification, simulations, high-level abstraction, logical complexity, and increasing integration of AI methods. Vendors like Synopsys, Cadence, or Codaip develop highly advanced tools while Apple, NVIDIA, Qualcomm, and others construct their own designs, such as Apple Silicon Mx SoC series. The R&D intensity is very high, with innovation focusing on design automation, HW-SW optimization, and RISC-V adoption.

Raw Materials. The initial stage of materials acquisition centers on obtaining and conditioning critical substances like ultra-pure silicon, rare-earth metals, and specialized gases integral to semiconductor manufacturing (Piotrowski, 2023; Mei, 2024). Research and development efforts in this phase are generally moderate to limited with gradual, stepwise enhancements.

Instrumentation: This phase involves the development of cutting-edge equipment such as photolithography machines including leading-edge Extreme Ultraviolet (EUV) lithography, and wafer inspection tools based on advanced (light- and electron) microscopy being essential to the manufacturing process. Companies like ASML and ThermoFisher lead in delivering tools capable of operating up to the atomic-scale precision. R&D intensity is very high.

Chemicals: Semiconductor materials are developed in steps encompassing ingot growth, wafer slicing, cleaning, and chemical-mechanical polishing. It requires ultra-high-purity chemicals and formulations. It needs medium to high R&D intensity, particularly in refining materials that support next-generation lithography and minimizing contamination at nanoscales.

Wafer Fabrication: is the key step in semiconductor production, where chips are manufactured in fabs operated by companies like TSMC, Samsung, OnSemi, Infineon and others. This phase includes photolithography, etching, deposition, and doping. The R&D intensity is very high, as this area drives process scaling to 3 nm and beyond, enabling advanced device architectures such as FinFETs.

Assembly & Packaging involve physically inserting chips into final packages using techniques that become increasingly complex through use of 2.5D/3D stacking and chiplets. Traditional outlet for packaging where cheaper yet nearshore to production facilities. However, this phase has grown increasingly strategic. The R&D intensity is medium to high, with a strong focus on thermal management, signal integrity, and miniaturization to meet performance and size demands.

Distribution: the finished semiconductor devices must be handed over to OEMs and integrators which involves logistics and warehousing. This stage typically involves low R&D intensity, as it focuses more on operational efficiency through modern logistics tools and supply chain optimization, rather than technological innovation.

Integration: the previous steps would miss a purpose unless the integration phase follows: using semiconductor components into final products such as cars, smartphones, machinery, or telecommunication devices. It involves design and manufacturing of hardware devices using chips and typically requiring some firmware and/or its adaptation. The R&D intensity is medium, as it enables performance tuning, energy efficiency enhancements, and differentiation of products through system-level innovation.

4.2 Skills and Study Programs

Table 2 depicts relevant skills and study programs for each semiconductor production step.

Table 2. Study Programs and Skills in Semiconductor Production

Stage	Relevant Study Programs
1. Design	Computer Engineering, Chip Design, Embedded Systems, EDA Tools, SoC Architecture, Analog-Digital Systems
2. Raw Materials	Materials Engineering, Chemistry, Geology, Environmental Engineering
3. Instrumentation	Applied Physics, Optoelectronics, Instrumentation & Control, Mechatronics
4. Chemicals	Chemical Engineering, Physical Chemistry, Surface Chemistry, Nano-chemistry
5. Wafer Fabrication	Microelectronics, Nanotechnology, Semiconductor Physics, Cleanroom Technology, Optics
6. Packaging	Mechanical Engineering, Packaging, Thermal Simulation, Microsystems
7. Distribution	Supply Chain Management, Industrial Engineering, ERP Systems, Logistics
8. Integration	Systems Engineering, Embedded Systems, Automotive, IoT Systems

Source: (author)

5. Strategies for Innovations

We used a bottom-up approach to find semiconductor production phases with their respective R&D intensity. The strategies to achieve and maintain competitiveness in research and industry are often underpinned by national/EU policy documents, see also (Diamond, 2023).

5.1 Policy Documents

United States CHIPS and Science Act (2022) aims to foster the domestic manufacturing and R&D by \$52.7 billion in semiconductor incentives, including \$39 billion for manufacturing. The National Semiconductor Technology Center (Natcast) was founded and the program stimulated private investment in semiconductor facilities.

European Chips Act (2023) wants the EU semiconductor market share to reach 20% by 2030. The policy seeks to enhance supply chain resilience and promote technological sovereignty through public and private investments of over €43 billion. However, the latest report from the EC Court of Auditors does not see the original targets as achievable without major changes, see Inside EU (2025).

China Semiconductor Self-Sufficiency Strategy focuses on technological self-sufficiency even under foreign export controls and geopolitical limitations, see (Lee & Malerba, 2022). The government commits large subsidies to Chinese firms such as SMIC and Huawei.

Japan Semiconductor Revitalization Strategy strives to regain competitiveness on the global scale. A major tool is the establishment of Rapidus Corporation, which tries to create next-generation chips in an international collaboration.

Korea K-Chips Act and Strategic Industry Support provides significant tax incentives and government support for semiconductor companies. The country aims to maintain its dominance in memory chips while expanding into non-memory and AI-related semiconductor markets.

Taiwan Semiconductor Strategic Policy 2025 is aimed to ensure the country's global leadership in semiconductor manufacturing. Taiwan seeks to bolster its technological sovereignty and protect against geopolitical disruptions.

5.2 Institutional Instruments

A successful semiconductor strategy does not rely solely on large-scale financial subsidies also an establishment of specialized institutions as mediators between scientific innovation and commercial application:

Rapidus Corporation in Japan (see Rapidus, 2025) is a Japanese semiconductor initiative established in 2022 to develop next-generation logic semiconductors, including the 2nm scale and lower. It collaborates with international partners, including IBM and Europe, to adoption the cutting-edge chip architectures being supported by the Japanese government and leading domestic firms.

Semiconductor Research Institutions in China are combination of state-directed initiatives and the emergence of specialized research institutions. Among the most prominent is the Institute of Microelectronics of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (IMECAS, 2025).

Semiconductor Research Institutions in Korea contribute to the strong collaborative model of industry, academia, and government sectors. Namely, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology, is famous in semiconductor materials, nanoscale electronics, and AI-focused hardware (KAIST, 2025), and the Electronics and Telecommunications Research Institute (ETRI) plays a key role in memory systems, logic chip development, and foundry-related technologies. The government facilitates programs by the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Energy and by directing targeted R&D investments that align with the K-Semiconductor Strategy.

Taiwan semiconductor research institutions are dominated by the National Institutes of Applied Research (NIAR, 2025), this organization is Taiwan's central point for publicly funded national laboratories. Its role is critical in supporting academia—industry collaboration, particularly in pre-commercial experimentation including semiconductors in Taiwan Semiconductor Research Institute (TSRI). Industrial Technology Research Institute (ITRI) supports both established firms and startups in semiconductor design, packaging, and AI chip development.

Fraunhofer in Germany focuses on *incremental innovation* with *direct industrial application*. Its typical project cycles range from 6 to 24 months, allowing for rapid, industry-relevant outcomes. The institute's strength lies in achieving cumulative small advances that gradually build national technological capability. (Fraunhofer, 2025)

IMEC in Belgium concentrates on exploring fundamental scientific themes that maintain strong industrial relevance, as recently shown in its participation in IPCEI projects (IMEC, 2024). Its

primary goal is to sustain long-term research excellence and readiness for future technology scaling, making it a critical part of Europe’s semiconductor R&D infrastructure.

5.3 University-Led Innovation in Asia

China between 2018 to 2023 published approximately 160,000 studies related to chip technology, accounting for 34% of all global research in the field, according to recent reports from ETO (MSN, 2025). University-linked research platforms such as University of Chinese Academy of Sciences (UCAS) and Tsinghua University’s School of Integrated Circuits are central to China’s research and talent cultivation.

Korean top universities such as KAIST, POSTECH, and Seoul National University operate advanced semiconductor labs that produce world-class research and skilled engineers, particularly in 3D integration, EUV lithography, and process automation, see KAIST(2025).

Taiwan top universities – namely National Taiwan University (NTU), National Tsing Hua University (NTHU), and National Chiao Tung University (NCTU) – operate advanced semiconductor research centers that produce skilled engineers and generate foundational research in device physics, system-on-chip (SoC) architecture, and power electronics. These academic institutions often collaborate with ITRI and NIAR and participate in national programs such as the Semiconductor Moonshot Project, which aligns research objectives with national industrial policy and talent development strategies.

6. Conclusion

We could see several necessary preconditions for establishing robust innovative ecosystem for semiconductors in regions, countries, and beyond. These findings can serve as both overview and high-level advice for policy-making and strategic considerations.

Alignment of Interests: Success is maximized when public funding and private capability align—through co-investment, shared infrastructure, and policy.

Institutional Diversity: Breakthroughs come from both short-term applied research (Fraunhofer) and long-horizon exploration (ARPA-E, imec).

Ecosystem Building: Ecosystems (e.g., Hsinchu Science Park in Taiwan) amplify innovation via talent clustering, shared infrastructure, and SME integration.

Geopolitical Adaptability: Shocks (e.g., Covid or U.S. sanctions on China) can catalyze restructuring and convergence of innovation actors. However, recent EU analysis on advancement in EU Chips Act do not give convincing evidence that the EU fills the gap (IEM, 2025).

Strategic Sovereignty: Nations are increasingly pursuing “technology sovereignty” reducing reliance on foreign sourcing: raw materials, IP, and production capacities while integrating into global supply chains.

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INTEGRATION OF EDUCATION AIMED AT DEVELOPING THE KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS OF THE STUDENT REFLECTING THE REQUIREMENTS OF THE 21ST CENTURY.

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Abstract

The paper points to future trends in skills needed for individuals in order to successfully find employment in the labor market among competitors. The aim of the paper is to give, if possible, an overview of the basic development areas of education, which have been published by experts in important studies and surveys published so far and which can facilitate the entry of graduates into the labor market. The skills and abilities of students needed for practice help develop activities such as graduate internships and team projects organized in cooperation between universities and businesses. The basics of project and process management give students valuable experience and skills to practice within a safe academic space what they will use in their future lives. Working on projects requires teamwork, analytical thinking and a sense of innovation, a comprehensive assessment of the issue, analysis and critical thinking, creativity and originality, knowledge of the use of technology, reasoning, problem-solving and imagination, as well as resilience, stress tolerance and flexibility, empathy. These are all qualities that employers require from employees not only today, but also in the foreseeable future.

1. Introduction

The preparation of students and graduates of universities and high schools must respond flexibly to external influences. Here, the training unit is required to adapt quickly to changing market conditions and job offers in the territory and sector. The purpose of the paper is to point out the importance of the adaptability of students to practice and school graduates for the labor market, in a period when we need graduates who will be able to apply themselves in the global labor market as qualified experts for practice, but above all also as independently operating business entities.

The application of innovative forms of education helps students develop creativity, adaptability, resilience and also allows them to take risks. These skills are essential for entrepreneurs and can be valuable in any business environment. Many innovative learning approaches include collaborative

projects and team learning – collaborating with industry and business partners through which students are confronted with current business trends, challenges, and best practices. Engaging students in practice helps to bridge the gap between academia and the business world, making them more aware of needs and expectations in practical life, while guiding students to make responsible decisions and understand the impact of their decisions on stakeholders and society. At the same time, they expose them to a dynamic and evolving learning environment that fosters adaptability and a growth mindset. Participation in student projects provides opportunities for students to network with industry experts, entrepreneurs and alumni, expanding their contacts and potential opportunities in practice.

2. Target and methodology of the research

The described research focuses on the issue of increasing the employment of graduates and the creation of a reasoned strategic model for the quality of education of the workforce in key sectors of the national economy, therefore it assumes the degree of originality and innovativeness resulting from the need for an urgent solution to the current and acutely arising situation of the lack of quality workforce in individual sectors and regions of Slovakia. The paper points to future trends in skills needed for individuals in order to successfully succeed in the labor market among the competition in the 21st century. The aim of the paper is to give, if possible, an overview of the basic development areas of education, which have been published by experts in important studies and surveys published so far and which can make it easier for graduates to enter the labor market. The presented paper summarizes domestic and foreign knowledge, documents dealing with the issue of employability of graduates in the labor market and subsequently identifying skills that will be in demand in the coming years. Students need to learn more consistently to work effectively in different groups, understand the importance of collaboration, and use different skills and perspectives to achieve common goals, critical thinking, and problem-solving.

The presented publication output used several scientific methods of research and was processed mainly by the following methodological procedure:

- Study of domestic and foreign scientific and professional literature and other sources in the field of the education system.
- Identification of theoretical-methodological needs to support the labour market.
- A proposal to support the labour market through skills and basic development areas of education.

The method of acquiring knowledge and data used not only internet and web documents, study of domestic and foreign scientific and professional literature, analysis and statistical data, scientific and professional journals, but also the knowledge and practical experience of the authors. The mentioned scientific method is used mainly in the processing of data aimed at obtaining sufficient information and specifying the problems and potentials of the current state of the described issue.

The skills needed for the future are illustrated by a survey by the National Union of Employers in the Slovak Republic, which focused on the expected most important skills by 2030. Figure 1 ranks skills in order of importance (the more points, the more important the skill) and this representation reflects the necessity of human resources to have a combination of hard and soft skills, not only for the present, but especially for the next 5 years (Lednárová Dítětová et al. 2021).

Figure 1. Skills in order of importance by 2030

(Source: Lednárová Dítětová et al., 2021)

In general, the most easily automated work is routine manual work, the worst automatable work is non-routine knowledge work (Kotíková et al., 2019; Reljic et al., 2023). Therefore, in order to avoid a situation where automated systems replace us in the labor market, it is essential to know the trends and requirements that are in demand and have a low level of automation risk. In 2019, the Business Alliance of Slovakia conducted a survey from which we were interested in the areas in which graduates come least prepared (Figure 2). According to the findings, graduates in the areas of so-called soft skills are the least prepared (Business Alliance of Slovakia, 2019).

Figure 2. Areas where graduates enter practice least prepared

(Source: Business Alliance of Slovakia, 2019)

According to the World Economic Forum (2020), a combination of soft skills and digital skills can be included in the list of the 10 most important skills of the future:

- Analytical thinking and innovation.
- Active learning and learning strategies.
- Comprehensive problem solving.
- Critical thinking and analysis.
- Creativity, originality and initiative.
- Leadership and social influence.
- Use, monitoring and control of technology.
- Technology design and programming.
- Resilience, stress tolerance and flexibility.
- Reasoning, problem-solving, and imagination

The OECD also complements self-regulation, empathy, the ability to cooperate (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2023).

Study on the Impact of Digitalisation on Employment and Social Security of Employees (Kohout, 2017) similarly states that an individual who has more comprehensive knowledge and skills, is able to think and make decisions in a broader context and is willing to constantly educate himself will be more successful on the labour market. Narrow specialization in a single field will give way to the demand for “T-shaped professionals”, i.e. they will have both deep and broad knowledge - deep expertise in one field, and broad knowledge across many disciplines (Figure 3) (Kršák and Závodný, 2018), but also the ability to communicate, think critically, etc. The ability to think interdisciplinary is a prerequisite for innovation. Given the interconnectedness of technologies, production processes and the entire value chain, it will be essential for an individual to navigate the entire system.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the requirements for a system worker (Source: Kršák a Závodný, 2018)

3. From theory to practice

In the field of higher education, cooperation between colleges and universities and companies is particularly emphasized (Kešelová et al. 2022). Examples of basic forms and selected types of cooperation, including their penetration into practice, are as follows.

3.1 Graduate practice

Graduate practice in Slovakia is one of the specific measures of active labour market policy aimed at reducing the unemployment rate of young graduates. The specific objective of this intervention is to provide young jobseekers with their first contact with the labour market, their first work experience and work habits that can be attractive to potential employers. Graduate practice is specific to Slovakia, it can serve as an inspiration for other countries (Švábová et al., 2021).

Graduate employability activities are used around the world. In Australia, for example, supervision of young graduates in practice has proven successful. This facilitates skills development and improves the quality of services to clients. (Melman, 2016). Poland research findings proved that the internship program, developed and implemented in close cooperation with local companies, may increase employment opportunities after graduation. There is, therefore, a clear need for further cooperation between education and business in order to facilitate the transition of graduates from education to employment, as well as to satisfy labor market needs (Puda, 2017). The study, published in the journal *Science & Justice*, analyzes a three-year pilot program in which older students mentored younger colleagues in forensic science and police education. The results showed that mentoring contributed significantly to the development of self-confidence, communication skills and the ability to identify professional competencies. The study also proposes a framework to link mentors' skills to employers' requirements (Bolton-King, 2022). Research published in *The British Journal of Social Work* analyzed the impact of supervision during internships on the employment intentions of social work students in China. Quality supervision and collaboration between schools and organizations have been found to positively influence students' interest in working in the field (Zhensong et al., 2024). In response to the high turnover among new graduates in healthcare, a large public health organization in Sweden has implemented a mentoring program. A program aimed at promoting learning, socialization, and a sense of belonging has helped reduce the departure of new employees and encouraged them to stay in the profession (Wikström et al., 2023). Also a 10-week field-oriented training programme for new graduate nurses in South Korea significantly improved their clinical knowledge and competencies, though it was associated with decreased job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The study highlights the need for future transition programmes to incorporate organizational socialization to enhance retention and engagement. (Kim, 2025). A study published in the *Papers on Postsecondary Learning and Teaching* examined the perception of hospitality undergraduate students on the role of mentoring during internships. Students emphasized the importance of both formal and informal mentoring by supervisors and its contribution to their professional development. Mentoring is thus one of the workplace practices that offers opportunities to improve psychosocial and career development support. (McDonald, M., & Wilson-Mah, 2022). The London School of Economics and Political Science develops students' skills in effective collaboration, particularly as a member of a diverse and interdisciplinary team, is a critical area of interest in higher education. Students bring their own disciplinary expertise to the project, and are expected to work collaboratively with their team to synthesise insights from across the social sciences to deliver a presentation and digital report (Terry, 2024).

A survey by the Centre of Scientific and Technical Information of the Slovak Republic (Filčák, 2022) (also CVTI) investigated the extent to which graduate practice is used by employers. The data show that about a third (29.9%) of the employers involved in the survey used graduate practice. A more detailed look at which employers use the graduate practice tool by industry, it is clear that these are mainly employers operating in the sectors of public administration (57.4%), real estate (42.9%), healthcare (39.8%) and professional scientific and technical activities (38.9%) (Filčák, 2022).

In the survey, employers had the opportunity to express their opinion on the graduate practice tool. These opinions were thoroughly analysed and, for better clarity of CVTI's findings, employers' responses were categorised into three options (positive, negative and neutral). According to the data, more than half of employers (55.7%) have a positive opinion of graduate practice. The strengths of graduate practice were most often considered by employers to be the fact that the graduate can get acquainted with the work process and organization in practice, gain an overview of individual activities and working life, and the employer can also verify the graduate's abilities. Almost a third (29.8%) of employers stated that they had no opinion or neutral opinion on graduate practice.

Employers most often stated that they did not have enough information about this tool. A smaller share of employers (14.5%) expressed a negative opinion about graduate practice. The most common justification was that this tool is associated with a large bureaucratic burden and also that it is problematic to obtain graduates with adequate qualifications (field) for the job. Furthermore, employers expressed the opinion that there is no motivation among graduates to use this tool due to low financial remuneration, graduate practice is more advantageous for the employer than for the graduate (Filčák, 2022).

3.2 Project cooperation at the University of Banská Bystrica

For example, the Faculty of Economics of Matej Bel University in Banská Bystrica has experience in connecting industry and academia (Kormancová, 2018). Matej Bel University actively cooperates with practice, especially in the following areas:

- Lectures by experts from practice at the university: including the participation of representatives of practice in state exams, offer of scholarships by companies, practical internships, organization of joint management forums or joint activities on social networks (group "School and Practice" – publication of offers for students by employers), lectures (e.g. KIA Motors Slovakia, Amazon, PwC and many others).
- Research activities for businesses: research projects for practice.
- Cooperation with representatives of the region: joint participation in various associations or chambers together with businesses, volunteer activities, joint conferences or consulting for small and medium-sized enterprises.

Cooperation between universities and businesses promotes the exchange of knowledge, with positive effects for both parties. Practically conceived project cooperation with local companies within the subject of Project Management takes the form of, for example, projects implemented by students for selected companies. Groups of 4-6 students have the opportunity to improve some of their skills, such as teamwork, problem solving, flexibility or creativity on projects such as: organizing a Christmas event for the children of hotel employees, marketing research, activities to increase the number of visitors to the sports center, updating business processes, etc (Kormancová, 2018).

The top skills of graduates identified by employers (79 companies surveyed) included language skills, a high level of independence, the completion of tasks on time, as well as the high quality of the results delivered. One of the ways to offer students more practical experience during their studies are projects that are designed in cooperation with various types of entities (Kormancová, 2018).

3.3 Team project and team assignments at universities in Bratislava

From personal experience, we present three examples of using the basics of project management in order to acquire these skills in life and thus increase readiness for the labor market.

For a long time, the subject of Team Project has been taught in the first year of engineering studies at the Faculty of Informatics and Information Technology of the Slovak University of Technology. Students in groups of 6-7 people prepare assignments necessary for the university or from partners (cooperating companies). Under the supervision of pedagogical leaders, they develop and implement solutions such as: a university library system, intelligent chatbots for partners or e-learning platforms for the university. The pedagogical leader is a university employee with a PhD, Doc., or a dedicated employee from a partner. At the end of the year, students present their outputs in front of an evaluation committee consisting of selected representatives of technology companies.

Likewise, students of the first year of master's studies at the Faculty of Management of Comenius University learn the basics of projects and processes and practice teamwork. By developing an assignment – a process design of the company's information system within the subject of Information Systems Management. Students in groups of 3-4 members define and design the organizational structure of the company, a diagram of functional dependencies, workflows, use cases, functional requirements for the system, as well as the graphic design of the screen / window in a special graphic program.

For high schools, the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering of the Slovak University of Technology organizes specialized lectures on the topic of programming CNC machines, robots, mathematics or industrial automation. Interactive workshops at university professional workplaces, professional internships and various projects are also prepared for high school students. The Faculty of Mechanical Engineering of STU offers high school student's topics of technical projects that can serve for high school activities or as Class Projects at vocational schools. The projects offered are in the fields of automation, programming, additive manufacturing, automotive, design, manufacturing technologies, robotics, energy, mechanics, mechatronics, materials, measurement, and more. Each offered topic has its own consultant from the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering. To solve the project, each student has access to the relevant specialized laboratories, access to technology, equipment as well as all necessary software. Depending on the nature of the projects, some can also be solved as team projects.

All of the above activities at universities in Bratislava require an analysis of the situation, to come up with and design a solution, to assess its difficulty, efficiency and feasibility, to select a suitable solution, to implement it taking into account not only technical parameters, but also in terms of design and aesthetics, and at the same time to reach a consensus with other project members within the project. The final presentation also represents an experience where students have to overcome stage fright and appear in front of the committee, the teacher and classmates and also manage various questions, objections and arguments.

4. Conclusion

Graduate practice is not very attractive and used, perhaps it is the projects – one/two semester collaborations with companies – that are suitable tools to bring students closer to practice and at the same time gain universal experience.

Collaboration and teamwork are two important skills for employers, and by gaining experience working with others, students can practice professionalism, mutual respect, and communication (Soemarno, 2025).

The basics of project and process management at Slovak Universities give students valuable experience and skills, where they can practice within a safe academic space what they will use in their future lives. Working on projects requires teamwork, analytical thinking and a sense of innovation, a comprehensive assessment of the issue, analysis and critical thinking, creativity and originality, knowledge of the use of technology, reasoning, problem-solving and imagination, as well as resilience, stress tolerance and flexibility, the ability to self-regulate, empathy.

These are all qualities that employers require from employees not only today, but also in the foreseeable future. As experts with more than 15 years of experience in the field of project management, we support teaching and exercises in project management in schools. We also identify the versatility of the application of project management across all sectors of the economy and for individuals not only in working life, but also in various areas of personal life. Not only for students,

but also for people who are looking for inspiration for lifelong learning. A survey of schools over the past five years generalizes that based on the results obtained from questionnaires from university and secondary school students, interesting facts have been obtained that students evaluate the connection between practice and theory on average to above average well. Most students think that the knowledge from the theory is better usable in practice this way. At the same time, project work allows students to broaden their horizons and test their knowledge and knowledge in practice, which will greatly facilitate the search for future employment.

Student and team project activities have their advantages, but also barriers that hinder their success. The biggest barriers to the development of the connection between theory and practice in some specializations here in Slovakia are mainly the lack of willingness of companies to cooperate, which we understand given their workload, but some do not even feel like it. In the medium and long term, there is a need to develop digital and universal skills in schools. It is important to develop skills not only according to the current need, but also regarding the forecast of the development of the demand for skills on the labour market in the future. The development of soft skills must be a priority across all groups of employees, the specific form and content of trainings should be adapted to the target group. It is also necessary to consider the plans of employers and set up education regarding their needs of the 21st century.

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LABOUR MARKET EVOLUTION IN LIGHT OF DEMOGRAPHIC CHANGE

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Abstract

The demographic development of society is one of the current megatrends that have a potentially large impact on the labour market. It is not only that the age structure is changing, and unevenly so from a global perspective, but also that emerging generations have different expectations with which they enter the labour market. HR professionals and business owners should prepare for an early increase in the proportion of Gen Z employees, the first generation that grew up with the internet and digital technology. This text presents a closer look at the expectations and characteristics of Generation Z, based on a questionnaire survey conducted at the economic study program of a technical university. It showed that members of Generation Z have no problem with common means of communication and that they spend long hours in front of computers and smartphones. Many use them for private purposes, especially for communicating on social networks and playing games. On the positive side, their declared interest in travel shows that they are still interested in the real world for the time being. HR professionals and business owners will need to prepare for a generation that wants to succeed quickly at work, be independent, and apply their entrepreneurial skills.

1. Introduction

As the new millennium dawns, changes in the world economy, and indeed in the global community, are continuing, perhaps accelerating. Over the last two decades, they have been concentrated in a few areas that are significant, long-term, and usually global in nature and are often referred to as megatrends. Although there is not full agreement in professional circles on their definition, usually megatrends include globalisation, shifts in technology and technology, demographic changes, and the consequent changes in the world of work (sometimes changes in the world of work are considered a separate megatrend), environmental protection and digitalisation, all linked by a specific megatrend known as instability, uncertainty, and change. Contemporary management is faced with the challenge of not ignoring the current megatrends and either adopting a defensive strategy, monitoring and responding to the possible risks that arise from them, or choosing an aggressive strategy, to identify the opportunities that megatrends offer and to try to exploit them in the conditions of the organization, probably the most promising is the third approach, preferring a combination of the two previous ones.

The following text is devoted to contemporary shifts in the demographic development of society and their impact on the world of work: changes in the content of work, the structure of workers, the organization of work, but also workplaces, working conditions, and activities with the search for workers, especially talent, the requirements for their stabilization, maintaining and developing their skills and abilities of managers and executive employees. It confronts many of these changes with the views of representatives of the Z and Alpha generations.

2. Key Contemporary Demographic Changes

At the outset, it should be noted that there is no uniformity in the demographic situation: the continents differ in terms of their numbers or share of the world population: Asia about 58 per cent, Africa 19, Europe 10, Latin America 8, North 5 and 0.6 per cent is accounted for by Australia and Oceania (Worldometer (b), n.d.). Understandably, the human population varies from country to country, and the period over which the global population has increased by a billion has also evolved: from one to two billion took 123 years (1804-1927), but from seven to eight billion in just ten years (2012-2022) (Worldometer (a), n.d.). Perhaps even more interesting, but still in the position of expert estimates, are the predictions of the population in forty years (between 2012-2050) (Worldometer (a), n.d.), when the largest increase (more than double) is expected in Africa, the population in Asia should increase by about a quarter, while in Europe there should be a decrease of about 15 percent. Although the rate of population growth is slowing down, realistic scenarios predict that by the end of this century, there will be about 10 billion inhabitants on Earth, the planet will be subjected to additional demands on their livelihoods, livelihoods, and living standards, the production of food of animal origin will become a certain problem, already requiring considerable demands on arable land and pastures, cattle already account for 15% of greenhouse gas emissions. However, there is no shortage of opinions that population growth will stop sometime after the middle of this century: stagnation or even decline in developed countries will be due to changes in lifestyle and values, higher rates of female education, and further expansion of contraception.

The European Union is realistic about the impact of demographic change in a number of ways. With the growing number of elderly people in the population structure, the share of the 65+ category is expected to increase from the current 21.6% (end of 2024) to 59.7% in 2100 (Eurostat 2025), which is related, among other things, to the following feature:

- life expectancy is increasing - life expectancy in 2021 was 82.8 years for women and 77.2 years for men (EC, n.d.),
- unfortunately, according to Eurostat data (2025), the share of the young generation (aged 15-29) in the population structure is falling: in 2014 it was 11.1%, in 2024 it was already 10.7%; the share of the 0-14 generation was 14.6% at the end of 2024 (compared with 15.3% in 2014); the share of the productive component (15-64) was 63.8% of the EU population (65.9% in 2014).
- declining birth rates, the latest data (Eurostat, 2025) are for 2023, when the average number of births per woman is 1.38 (1.54 in 2014), well below the 2.1 needed to maintain a stable population.

The other impact is smaller households. Although the number of households in the EU is growing, their size is shrinking, in 2024 the number of single-person households was over 75 million, which is 16.9 % more than in 2015 (Eurostat, 2025).

The development in the Czech Republic follows to some extent the above-mentioned European trends. The child component of the population (0-14 years old) accounted for 15.9% of the population in 2024 (compared to 15% in 2014) (Eurostat, 2025). The productive component of the population (15-64 years old) accounted for 63.6% of the population in 2024 (67.6% in 2014, the senior component has been growing steadily since the mid-1980s. It is worth mentioning the comparison of the five-year age group (45-49) of 946 thousand persons, against 516 thousand persons in the 20-24 age group at the end of 2023 (CSO, n.d.). At the end of 2023, the population of the country will be 10.9 million people. The growth in recent years has been driven by migration from Ukraine.

Even the natality does not deviate from European borders, with a decline to 1.46 children per woman in the Czech Republic in 2023, compared to 1.53 in 2014 (Eurostat, 2025). There is an obvious shift in the number of children born to older women: the average age of mothers at birth shifted to 30.4 years in 2023. (CSO, 2023).

The EU and the Czech Republic do not differ much in the fact that there are about 3 persons of working age for every one person of senior age. If we consider that working-age people have more or less responsibilities towards the youngest generation (0-14), we end up with two working-age people on whom the youngest and the elderly depend. If we consider the increasing share of the elderly category, the share of working-age persons on whose shoulders the fate of the youngest and oldest age groups of the population will depend will logically decrease. These working-age people will be members of the Z and Alpha generations. With more than two billion members in the world population, Gen Z is expected to account for 30% of the global workforce by 2050 (Chomařowska et al., 2022).

Although there is no absolute consensus on their definition, or perhaps even their labels, the terms Gen Z (born 1996-2010) and Gen Alpha (2011-2025) can be considered prevalent (Amrit, 2020; dos Reis, 2018; McCrindle & Wolfinger, 2014).

Both generations were born into the digital age (dos Reis, 2018), and they feel they have to be online all the time, they are not very interested in reading books, newspapers, or watching TV, everything is replaced by digital news and findings from social media. Already Gen Z has some doubts about classical forms of learning (they do not need to remember key knowledge, after all, they can find everything on the Internet or other digital mediums), representative surveys of Gen Alpha signal that its oldest members spend up to 4 hours a day on tablets, mobile phones, computers, and most of their time is spent on entertainment and discussions on social networks in the evening from 6-11 pm. Kabaja et al. (2023) report that according to the Pew Research Center, Gen Z students spend approximately 9 hours per day on their mobile phones. Their average attention span has decreased to 8 seconds (compared to 12 seconds for millennials) (Shatto & Erwin, 2016).

Gen Z in the near future will make up one-fifth of the Czech population, its members often feel that they are excluded from debates by members of older generations, they are able to cope with digital applications, but unfortunately, they are quite dependent on digitalization, with the realization that some metrics (their own apartment) are unavailable to them, they focus on enjoying life, they postpone their own children to a later time, they do not like alcohol too much, they are often unclear whether their chosen field of study or work is the right one. This leads to a certain instability in their working relationship, they prefer more sustainability, and the media world (social networks, individual viewing of news and cultural programmes) distances them from their peers, thus reinforcing their individualism, the female population may be more active than the male population, but both prefer a greater degree of independence, they are interested in meaningfulness and satisfaction at work, valuing work results, but also in the length of holidays and the possibility of working from home.

The establishment of the first job(s) is far from a “marriage with the company, no divorce,” more like a stopover on a round-the-world trip. Members of the younger generation are used to finding everything on the internet and they expect to be able to use Information and Communication Technologies as a matter of course, even from members of older generations; they expect their superiors to be open and to discuss, especially short-term goals; the younger generation is very ambitious.

A big problem across all generations, but especially among the young, is the use of mobile phones and computers for personal purposes during working hours. Firstly, there is the danger of cyber-attacks being recorded this way, and secondly, there is a considerable loss of time. Expert studies report that for the young generation, the urge to look at mobile or private sites on the computer has now been reduced to about 20 minutes, with the total time lost at work averaging one and a quarter hours, and up to two more hours during the rest of the day (BusinessInfo, 2018). Even more ominous is information from research in 2022 stating that greater or lesser dependence on mobile phones and other digital means of communication affects half a million of the Czech population, especially young people over 15 (Baroch, 2022). This condition has a number of negative consequences: neglect of restful eating, eyestrain, back fatigue, limitation of face-to-face social contact and thus loss of physical friends, and limitation of leisure activities. Mobile phone viewing in the evening before sleeping leads to poor quality sleep, and subsequently, in the longer term, to various neurotic conditions (Baroch, 2022). The limitation of face-to-face contact is also aided by the fact that social media provides a channel for young people to talk about their health conditions, and students have reported that they prefer to post on social media when they feel happy, whereas when they feel bored or isolated they browse social media for humorous content to help improve their mood (An, Vesty, & Cheong, 2023). Loneliness, anxiety, and depression are symptoms of digital addiction (Peper & Harvey, 2018). Many people try to reduce digital overuse by using well-being apps. In particular, these provide the user with information about time spent online, send alerts, and allow them to set up blocking of selected apps where appropriate (Roffarello & Russis, 2023; Almourad et al, 2021).

3. Realized survey

In our research, we decided to respond to the claims most often made about the Z and Alpha generations in the literature and compare them to the reality of college students.

Gen Z's expectations of working life differ from those of previous generations. They are motivated not only by profit, but personal development (Tidhar, 2022) and the opportunity to apply their entrepreneurial skills is key (Yilmaz, Ksactutan, & Karatepe, 2024; Cirstea & Anagnoste, 2023). Other authors confirm their preference for independent work and self-sufficiency (Vitelear, 2019) and high self-confidence (Bencsik, Horváth-Csikós, & Juhász, 2016), their desire to become CEOs (Arar and Oneren, 2018) or to achieve professional success quickly (Ozturk & Yildirim, 2023; Bencsik, Horváth-Csikós, & Juhász, 2016). In contrast, other sources report that members of Generation Z prefer to work together to achieve corporate goals and tend to cultivate friendly relationships with colleagues (Ozturk & Yildirim, 2023).

Members of Gen Z are also more hesitant to make decisions about the future (Yulianto, 2012 in Ozturk & Yildirim, 2023). Many are apprehensive about taking a call from an unknown number.

The fact that they were born into the world of social networking has shaped them to form social relationships without physical proximity and yet interact online with many people for many hours a day (Apaydin & Kaya, 2020). In doing so, they are more concerned with asserting themselves against the group rather than communicating, making them a very individualistic generation (Soriano & Ortega, 2021). Gaidhani, Arora, & Sharma (2019), on the other hand, find that despite being a digital

native generation, they prefer face-to-face communication. Thus, they use social networks for entertainment rather than communication (Mude & Undale, 2023), but also as a channel to talk about their health status if they feel happy (An, Vesty, & Cheong, 2023). In doing so, most of the current generation interacts with them (Marugán & Critikián, 2023). They use their digital devices frequently and for a long time. Ayhun (2013 in Ozturk & Yildirim, 2023) argues that they show a greater propensity to use digital technologies than any previous generation, Kabaja et al. (2023) cite research by the Pew Research Center that found that Gen Z spend up to 9 hours a day on mobile devices. Meanwhile, the average attention span for Gen Z individuals has decreased to 8 seconds compared to 12 seconds for Gen Y (Shatto & Erwin, 2016).

3.1 Survey of the younger generation on their lifestyle, work, and personal preferences

The chosen methodology is based on a simple comparative comparison, where on the one hand opinions based on secondary information - current professional world literature on a given topic - are assessed and on the other hand they are compared with primary findings - these were obtained from surveys among students of the Zet generation, with the aim of confirming or in some ways refuting opinions from secondary research.

Conclusions from various expert texts about the young generation bring some new insights into the lifestyles and preferences of the young generation. The authors of this article wanted to test these views, although admittedly in an easier way, by interviewing their university students. This, of course, narrows the focus to one segment of the young generation, but the findings are still interesting and informative. The questionnaire developed had fifteen questions, three related to age (the dominant group was respondents aged 21-23 years 65%, under twenty years 20% of the age group 24-26 years it was 11%, the remaining percent belonged to respondents aged 27-29 years), gender (although the questionnaire allowed for multiple genders, only a binary distribution with a majority of women, 64%) and nationality (in this case, 27% of respondents were foreigners living in the Czech Republic for less than five years, the rest were Czechs or Slovaks), the remaining questions mapped work and personal preferences, partly also changes in lifestyle.

3.2 Results

The following findings emerge from the approximately eighty responses:

- After graduation, about 45% of the respondents intend to enter practice, 27% are considering doctoral studies, and the rest are not sure or are considering looking for longer-term employment abroad.
- After completing their studies, about half of the respondents expect to enter employment in the Czech Republic or Slovakia (56% of them in the business sector, about 29% in the financial services or social services, culture, non-profit organizations), 16% are considering private business outside the Czech Republic and Slovakia, a similar proportion do not have an idea about their job orientation yet, others, already individuals are considering private business in the country, work for non-profit organizations abroad, etc.
- In the time horizon of 5 years or more, more than one-quarter of the respondents are considering buying a flat even with the help of a mortgage, 13% are considering buying a cheaper property even in the form of a prefabricated house, 45% are considering subletting with the expectation that they will see it in time, about 10% have no idea, the rest are not yet deciding.

- In the time horizon of 10-15 years, more than two-thirds of the respondents consider entering into a legitimate marriage and eventually having one or two children, about 20% admit the possibility of having more than two children, about 12% have no idea about marriage and children yet and will solve everything in time, about three or four percent of the respondents want to enter into a marriage without children yet or, on the contrary, they want children but in a free relationship without marriage.
- The overwhelming majority of respondents said that they play recreational sports; perhaps surprising is the finding that almost a tenth of respondents admitted that they do not play sports. Similarly, most respondents are interested in travel and the photography often associated with it. Approximately 5-10 respondents listed playing a musical instrument, watching streaming movies learning foreign languages, or attending (fan) sporting events among other hobbies.
- An interesting finding is that almost a third of respondents admit to not having many friends.

A more detailed block of questions concerned the relationship of the young generation to digitalisation:

- The answers to the control of modern technologies were about half and half. Half of them admitted that they know the common functions of a mobile phone, tablet, and computer, and can handle standard MS Office and MS Teams programs. The other half presented more advanced knowledge of mobile phone control or their encounters with various application programs during work brigades, etc.
- More than two-thirds of the respondents spend 4 or more hours a day at the computer on weekdays for their work, study needs, the rest 2-3 hours or did not dare to specify their time spent at the computer.
- The overwhelming majority, in terms of using mobile phones or other means of digital communication, use them in their personal life to communicate on social networks, play various games, surfing to see what new products are on offer (in clothing, consumer items, etc.), the subject of interest (albeit marginally) is what is happening at home and in the world.
- On average, 40% of respondents spend on their mobile phones, etc. on personal (non-work or study) activities every day 4 hours or more, almost a fifth spend 3 hours on average per day, and a fifth spend two hours per day. The rest one hour or did not dare to estimate their time.

As far as a healthy lifestyle is concerned, 12 respondents said that their interest is still rather theoretical, but most of them chose one of the other options offered. The most frequently chosen alternatives were eating a balanced diet (about 60%) and trying to follow the rules for sleep and rest (almost 60%). About 50% of the respondents stated that they do not drink too much alcohol and that they either exercise at home or run, cycle, do yoga, etc. Just under a quarter of respondents have a smartwatch and regularly monitor their key life indicators.

3.3 Discussion

There is no doubt that the younger generation will gradually gain a share in the structure of the working-population. Different views on their behaviour and preferences are emerging in the literature, which will sooner or later be reflected in their working life and, ultimately, in their everyday life. Our research, although targeted only at the segment of university students, has confirmed some of the conclusions, some of which we cannot fully agree with.

What was confirmed: Undoubtedly, the fact that the younger generation has no problem with common means of communication (mobile phone, tablet, computer), can handle common programs and some advanced ones. However, the respondents did not claim to have mastered superstructure office programs such as MS Planner, Designer, Project, etc.). It was also confirmed that the younger generation spends many hours on the computer while studying (or working), but also in their free time. In this case, communication on social networks and gaming are of particular interest. This may to some extent be related to the fact that many members of this generation complain about the lack of friends or admit that they do not play sports. The interest of the younger generation in traveling is also clearly confirmed. The high proportion of those who want to enter employment in the business sector after their studies (more than half) and the unusually high interest in private enterprise (about 16%) confirm the prevailing view that members of Generation Z prefer to work independently, want to achieve success quickly and apply their entrepreneurial skills.

What was not confirmed, and in a way is a pleasant finding, is the fact that the majority of respondents subscribed to the classic model of marriage and raising two or more children, which corresponds to the consideration of getting their own apartment or even a smaller property. A perhaps surprising finding is the relatively high proportion of those (more than a quarter) who are considering a PhD.

As mentioned, the survey was directed only at the category of university students (mainly bachelors in economics and management). The authors are aware that the Generation Zet segment is much broader, so it will be useful in the next survey to focus on other groups: high school students, apprentices, and young employees, to assess whether technicians or more humanities-oriented individuals have different interests or preferences.

4. Conclusion

It turns out that members of Generation Z are digital natives, which means that they are fluent in common digital communication tools, but they are not IT specialists, and although they spend long hours on computers and smartphones, they will have to learn to work with more complex ICT. Frequent interaction with mobile devices, coupled with low attention span, can be a challenge to work efficiency, especially in work positions where long periods of routine work are required.

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This article was independently developed; Grammarly and DeepL applications were consulted for phrasing improvements and stylistic edits.

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EARLY CAREER & STUDENT SHOWCASE

GENDER EQUALITY IN HIGH-TECH SECTORS: ANALYSIS OF WOMEN'S REPRESENTATION IN TECHNOLOGY INDUSTRIES IN THE VISEGRÁD GROUP COUNTRIES

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Gender equality; gender pay gap; employment; high technology

Abstract

This study explores gender equality within the high-tech sectors of the Visegrád Four (V4) countries, with a focus on gender disparities in employment, the unadjusted gender pay gap, and the representation of women in technologically and knowledge-intensive industries at the supranational level. The findings indicate that, despite increasing demand for specialized professionals, the proportion of women employed in these sectors remains low, with notable differences observed between individual countries. Key contributing factors to inequality include educational and career entry barriers, wage gaps, and limited work-life balance support.

1. Introduction

In the last decade, research on gender equality in the Visegrád Four (V4) countries has primarily focused on disparities in employment, remuneration, and the representation of women in the IT and high-tech sectors. Numerous studies (e.g., Anderson et al., 2022; Harman & Bartůšková, 2024) have demonstrated that gender inequality remains prevalent, even though its extent varies across the selected countries. It has also been shown that political and institutional factors, as well as historical developments, significantly influence women's position in the labor market. Despite this extensive

research, many aspects of gender inequality in the region remain unclear. The reasons why certain V4 countries experience faster progress in gender equality, while others face stagnation or even regression, have not been sufficiently explored. Why is it so challenging for women to succeed in the IT sector? What are the measures countries are implementing to ease this process for women? How are countries progressing in this area? These are also the questions we address in this study. The objective of this study was to analyze gender equality disparities in employment and remuneration across the V4 countries and to examine the representation of women in high-tech sectors. The paper is structured into several sections. After the introduction, an overview of the current state of the issue is presented, followed by the research design and methodology used in the analysis. The main section is dedicated to presenting the results and their discussion, where the findings are compared with existing studies. The conclusion summarizes the key findings, their practical implications, and suggestions for future research.

2. National and international context of gender equality in technology fields

The Visegrád Group countries share not only geographical proximity but also historical experiences that have shaped their approaches to gender equality. Following their accession to the European Union, gender equality emerged as a significant challenge for all V4 countries, manifesting across political, economic, and technological spheres. While some positive developments are visible, especially in terms of increased awareness, the overall progress in women's representation remains slow, with signs of stagnation or even regression in certain areas. This trend has implications not only for gender relations and the societal position of women but also for their access to high value-added sectors, such as information technology and high-tech industries (Jędrzejczak & Trzcińska, 2023; Barteková & Janikovičová, 2025). Although historically these countries have followed divergent development paths, clear progress in gender equality is evident. This is also reflected in the IT and high-tech industries. While some countries are advancing more rapidly and witnessing growing numbers of women in these sectors, the V4 nations continue to lag due to various barriers, such as the lack of female mentors and the persistence of gender stereotypes (Bolibok et al., 2025). While recent efforts have shaped the current landscape, it is also important to consider the long-term effects of past policies. For example, reforms introduced over a decade ago, such as educational campaigns to increase female interest in STEM fields, early-stage career support, and institutional commitments to equal opportunity, have gradually influenced the pipeline of female professionals entering the high-tech workforce. However, empirical data directly linking these historical interventions to current outcomes remain limited and require further study. As available sources indicate, the V4 countries have adopted a variety of measures—both legislative and institutional—within the framework of gender mainstreaming. However, the effectiveness of these initiatives varies significantly across regions, particularly when it comes to supporting women in technological fields. Among the most frequent challenges faced by women are the reconciliation of family and professional life, gender-based pay gaps, and underrepresentation in decision-making positions. Systematic support for girls in STEM education is often lacking, as are mentoring programs that would facilitate their career advancement in the IT sector (Maďarová, 2015; Anderson et al., 2022). Dorčák, Štrach, and Pollák (2015) highlight that the effective use of digital communication tools and innovative promotional strategies can enhance engagement and visibility, which may be particularly beneficial in encouraging women's participation in technologically oriented fields. Existing research underscores the fact that countries with higher levels of digitalization and developed ecosystems for technological innovation are also those where gender equality in IT is more strongly supported. This correlation provides a crucial impetus for strategic changes within the V4 region (Küfeoğlu, 2022). Despite numerous studies mapping gender equality trends, many lack a focused quantitative comparison across all V4

countries within high-tech employment. Moreover, few offer a direct assessment of the impact of gender representation on SDG 5 progress, highlighting the necessity of this study.

3. Methodology

The objective of this paper is to explore the issue of gender equality within the context of the Visegrád Four (V4) countries and to assess their progress in fulfilling Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 5. The data used in this study are secondary and were sourced from the Eurostat database. Within this database, we selected the EU policy category and proceeded to the section on Sustainable Development Indicators, where we identified Goal 5 as relevant to our research. From this goal, we selected three key indicators for analysis: a) The gender employment gap; b) The unadjusted gender pay gap; c) Employment in high technology sectors at the supranational level, disaggregated by gender. For each of these indicators, we retrieved data for the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, and Slovakia, covering the most recent five-year period available—2019 to 2023.

As a next step, we formulated two research questions:

1. What are the differences in gender inequality in employment and pay among the V4 countries?

How does the representation of women in the high-tech sector impact gender equality in the V4 region?

In addition to visualizing the trends through graphs, the study also applies comparative percentage analysis to assess relative changes over time. The indicators are interpreted in the context of broader labor market structures to reveal deeper patterns of gender disparities. Though descriptive in nature, the analysis identifies country-specific gaps and progress markers relevant for further policy implications.

4. Research results

4.1 Gender Employment Gap

This indicator focuses on the difference in employment rates between men and women aged 20 to 64. The 20–64 age group is used in accordance with Eurostat’s definition of working age population, ensuring comparability across indicators. The employment rate is calculated by dividing the number of employed individuals within this age group by the total population of the same group. The indicator is based on data from the European Union Labour Force Survey. Figure 1 illustrates the gender employment gap among individuals aged 20 to 64 in the V4 countries during the period from 2019 to 2023. The data show that the Czech Republic maintained the highest gap throughout the observed period, peaking at 15.4% in 2021 before gradually declining to 13.9% in 2023. This decline may indicate an improvement in labor market conditions and more effective gender equality policies. Poland demonstrates a more stable trend, with the gender gap decreasing from 14.6% in 2019 to 11.8% in 2023. This progress could be attributed to improved policies supporting women in the workforce and increasing their participation in the economy. Hungary consistently recorded the lowest gender employment gap among all V4 countries, with a decrease from 11.1% to 9.1% over the same period. This development may be related to effective family policies and flexible working conditions that enable women to better balance work and private life. However, while these family policies may improve women's access to the labor market, they may also reinforce traditional gender roles. In the Hungarian context, such measures often support women primarily in combining paid

employment with caregiving responsibilities, rather than promoting equal career opportunities. As a result, although more women may enter or remain in the workforce, they often do so in part-time or lower-ranking positions. This raises questions about whether improved employment indicators truly reflect progress in gender equality or rather the continuation of role-based expectations under updated policy frameworks.

Figure 1. Gender Employment Gap

Source: own processing based on Eurostat data (2025)

Slovakia, which also shows a relatively low gap, experienced slight fluctuations – from 7.3% in 2020 to 8.5% in 2021 – before returning to 7.7% in 2023. This relatively stable trend may reflect the lower representation of women in technical and managerial positions, as well as the persistence of traditional gender roles. Overall, the decreasing gender employment gap across all V4 countries suggests a positive trend. Nevertheless, the remaining disparities continue to be shaped by sociocultural factors, labor market policies, and the availability of family-supporting infrastructure. It is also important to consider whether the reduction in the gender employment gap corresponds to actual growth in employment among women, or whether it results from an overall contraction in male employment. Without evaluating the absolute size of the labor force, observed trends may misrepresent progress toward equality.

4.2 Unadjusted Gender Pay Gap

This indicator reflects the difference between the average gross hourly earnings of male and female employees, expressed as a percentage of the average gross hourly earnings of male employees. It is referred to as “unadjusted” because it provides an overall picture of gender-based pay inequality without accounting for variables such as education, occupation, or working hours. The indicator includes all employees working in enterprises with ten or more employees, regardless of age or number of hours worked. However, this approach may underestimate the gender pay gap, particularly in high-tech sectors where women may be more active in micro-enterprises, start-ups, or freelance work—entities typically employing fewer than ten people. These smaller firms, while statistically less visible, can represent a significant portion of women’s economic activity in the digital and innovation economy. Figure 2 illustrates the unadjusted gender pay gap, meaning the difference is measured regardless of sector, in the V4 countries over the period from 2019 to 2023. The data show that the Czech Republic consistently maintained the highest gender pay gap throughout the observed years, reaching a peak of 19.3% in 2019, and decreasing to 18% in 2023. This decline may be

associated with improved equal opportunity policies and increasing transparency in wage structures. Hungary displays relatively stable values around 17%, indicating persistent inequalities in the labor market, which may be influenced by traditional gender roles and the underrepresentation of women in managerial positions. Poland shows the lowest pay disparities among the V4 countries.

Figure 2. Unadjusted Gender Pay Gap

Source: own processing based on Eurostat data (2025)

In 2020, the gap dropped to a minimum of 4.5% but increased again to 7.8% in 2022 and 2023. This upward trend may suggest uneven wage growth in male-dominated sectors. Slovakia demonstrates a relatively stable trend, with the gender pay gap decreasing from 18.2% in 2019 to 7.7% in 2023. This reduction may be the result of legislative measures and policies aimed at promoting pay equity. Overall, the developments indicate that although the V4 countries have made progress in reducing the gender pay gap, structural factors and gender stereotypes continue to influence wage disparities between men and women.

4.3 Employment in high-tech sectors at the national level by gender

This indicator represents the percentage share of women and men employed in the high-tech sector during the period from 2019 to 2023. According to Eurostat, high-tech sectors include industries with high R&D intensity, such as pharmaceuticals, aerospace, computer programming, and scientific research services.

Figure 3. Women employed in High-Tech Sectors*

Source: own processing based on Eurostat data (2025)

*Note: Only the female share is visualized; male employment is approximately 1.5 to 2 times higher in all countries, as detailed in the discussion.

Figure 3 illustrates the share of women employed in high-tech sectors across the V4 countries from 2019 to 2023. Hungary consistently reported the highest proportion of women in these sectors, with values ranging from 4.4% in 2019 to 5.2% in 2023, showing a steady upward trend since 2021. In contrast, Poland recorded the lowest levels, with the share of women remaining around 2.6% between 2019 and 2022, followed by a slight increase to 3.1% in 2023. The Czech Republic and Slovakia fall between these two extremes. The Czech Republic shows a stable, slightly increasing trend, from 3.4% in 2019 to 3.7% in both 2021 and 2022, with a minor decline to 3.6% in 2023. Slovakia reported a 3.3% share in 2019, followed by a noticeable jump to 4.2% in 2020—the highest figure among its neighboring countries, excluding Hungary. However, from 2021 onward, the share declined to 3.7%, before rising slightly again to 3.5% in 2023. Overall, Hungary demonstrates the most consistent and highest participation of women in high-tech sectors, while Poland continues to lag. Slovakia and the Czech Republic display similar trends with minor fluctuations, although Slovakia recorded a notable spike in 2020 before returning to average levels. Despite these developments, women continue to be underrepresented in high-tech sectors across the V4 region. In all observed countries, men hold a dominant position, consistently making up most of the workforce in this field. For instance, in 2023, male representation in Hungary stood at 7.1%, significantly higher than the 5.2% for women, and similar disparities are evident in the Czech Republic, Slovakia, and Poland. These findings underscore the persistent gender imbalance in high-tech employment, which has remained largely unchanged over time. While fewer women are employed overall (Figure 1), their underrepresentation in high-tech sectors is even more pronounced, suggesting specific barriers within these industries rather than just general employment inequality.

5. Discussion

5.1 Discussion to the first research question

"What are the differences in gender inequality in employment and pay among the V4 countries?"

The analysis indicates that gender disparities in employment persist across the V4 countries. The Czech Republic had the highest employment gap, at 15.4% in 2021, dropping to 13.9% in 2023. Slovakia showed the lowest, ranging between 7.3% and 8.5%. These differences may stem from factors such as family policies, flexible work options, and cultural norms. For instance, the Czech Republic's gap may reflect the dominance of male-oriented industries and limited family support. Anderson et al. (2022) note that stronger family policies and better work-life balance are linked to smaller gaps, helping explain better outcomes in Slovakia and Hungary. The COVID-19 pandemic further affected labor participation, especially for women. Lockdowns and school closures disproportionately impacted female employment due to caregiving responsibilities, while increased digitalization created opportunities that were not equally accessible, potentially masking deeper gender barriers. Regarding the gender pay gap, the Czech Republic again led with 19.3% in 2019 and 18% in 2023. Poland had the lowest, narrowing to 4.5% in 2020 before rising to 7.8%. This may be due to legislative efforts and Poland's larger share of women in public sector jobs, where wage transparency is stronger. The pandemic also accelerated digital transformation, shifting employment dynamics and affecting demand for digital skills, with mixed impacts on women (Markovič et al., 2022). Harman and Bartůšková (2024) argue that pay transparency and more women in leadership can reduce pay gaps. Slovakia's sharp drop—from 18.2% to 7.7%—may reflect such policies, along with a smaller presence of high-paying, male-dominated sectors. Overall, Slovakia and Poland appear

to have more effective equality policies, while the Czech Republic's persistent gaps may result from more rigid labor structures. The comparison underscores the importance of national contexts over regional trends.

5.2 Discussion to the second research question

"What is the impact of women's representation in the high-tech sector on gender equality in the V4 countries?"

Women's representation in the high-tech sector across the V4 countries significantly affects gender equality, with persistent disparities evident from 2019 to 2023. In all countries, women remain consistently underrepresented compared to men, limiting the sector's diversity and innovation potential. Encouraging more women to enter high-tech fields is crucial, as they offer unique perspectives that can drive added value. Paetsch et al. (2017) emphasize that inclusive digital infrastructure is key to economic and technological progress, reinforcing the need for diverse talent. Hungary had the highest female share in high-tech (5.2% in 2023), yet still below the male share (7.1%). In the Czech Republic, women made up 3.6% versus 6.9% for men. Poland consistently reported the lowest female presence, rising slightly to 3.1% in 2023, compared to 5.3% for men. Slovakia saw a brief rise to 4.2% in 2020, but stagnated at 3.5% afterward, with men at 6.2%. These gaps suggest structural barriers, including occupational stereotypes, insufficient STEM support, and limited advancement opportunities (Tardos & Paksi, 2021). Greater female participation in high-tech could improve income equity, career prospects, and decision-making roles, but this potential remains unrealized (Perin et al., 2022). The underrepresentation reflects not just general employment inequality, but deeper systemic issues. Hungary's relative progress may result from targeted programs, while Poland's lag highlights the need for more effective strategies.

6. Conclusion

This study offers a detailed overview of gender equality in the V4 countries, focusing on disparities in employment, pay, and representation in high-tech sectors. The findings may inform policymaking to improve conditions for women pursuing careers in IT and tech industries. Notably, the Czech Republic shows the highest gender disparities in employment and pay, while Poland reports the lowest. A key issue is the continued underrepresentation of women in tech, despite gradual increases; men still dominate the field across all V4 countries. The study has limitations. It relies on secondary data from Eurostat, which, while useful, may miss qualitative aspects like workplace discrimination or cultural attitudes. It also focuses on selected indicators without fully exploring the sociocultural factors behind gender inequality. To promote equality in high-tech sectors, V4 countries should adopt stronger policy tools. These include STEM education for girls, targeted mentorships, pay transparency laws, and family-friendly policies like accessible childcare and flexible work. Future research should delve deeper into the structural and cultural roots of gender gaps and examine women's specific experiences in tech, especially regarding career advancement. Hungary illustrates a potentially positive link between family policies and lower gender employment gaps. While such policies may help reduce work-life conflict and enable women to remain active in the labor market, they may also reinforce traditional gender roles by encouraging dual responsibilities in both paid work and domestic care. As a result, progress in employment numbers does not necessarily equate to broader gender equality in terms of autonomy or career advancement. Moreover, the feasibility of implementing family-focused policies depends on each country's economic capacity and political context. These variables must be considered when evaluating or replicating policy models. Therefore,

further research is needed to assess not only the effectiveness but also the long-term sustainability and socio-economic impact of such interventions.

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PUBLICLY AVAILABLE IT KPIS FOR BUSINESS PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

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Information Technology KPIS; Business Performance Evaluation; Management

Abstract

The paper deals with the topics of business performance evaluation with a focus on how the information technology (IT) aspects of companies might reveal information about the business health. The primary aim of this study is to provide a structured approach to evaluating IT performance through publicly available key performance indicators (KPIs), ensuring that IT investments align with business objectives and drive sustainable growth. The author of this study systematically researched eight KPIs: cybersecurity incidents, IT-related fines from regulators, open-source intelligence (OSINT), compliance with IT standards, technology partnerships, technology patents, usage of emerging IT technologies, and research and development expenditures. These indicators were identified through a comprehensive academic literature review and industry reports. Each KPI offers unique insights into various aspects of IT performance, from security and compliance to innovation and technological adaptability. By evaluating these KPIs, organizations can ensure their IT investments effectively contribute to business objectives, drive better outcomes, and foster sustainable growth.

1. Introduction

Information Technology (IT) is crucial for enhancing business performance in a competitive business environment. IT systems are crucial in optimizing operations, improving productivity, and enabling strategic decision-making. As businesses strive to achieve their performance goals, evaluating the effectiveness of IT systems becomes essential. This evaluation ensures that IT investments are aligned with business objectives, driving better outcomes and fostering sustainable growth. By systematically assessing IT performance, organizations can identify strengths, address weaknesses, and make informed decisions that enhance overall business performance.

The study of IT performance evaluation has evolved through multiple perspectives, from early works on IT's strategic role in business competitiveness to recent discussions on digital transformation and governance frameworks. Since the 1980s, IT has been recognized as a transformative force in business strategy. Porter and Millar (1985) introduced the concept of IT as a source of competitive advantage, highlighting its role in redefining industry structures and enhancing operational efficiency.

Brynjolfsson and Hitt (1996) later provided empirical evidence demonstrating the positive impact of IT investments on productivity. These findings were further expanded by Melville, Kraemer, and Gurbaxani (2004), who proposed an integrative model linking IT investments to firm performance, incorporating factors such as IT infrastructure, business processes, and organizational performance.

More recent research has examined IT's contribution to firm agility and innovation. Aral and Weill (2007) emphasized that firms with superior IT governance structures achieve higher profitability, while Mithas et al. (2011) found that IT capabilities significantly influence customer satisfaction and business value. Furthermore, Vial (2019) explored the role of digital transformation in business performance, stressing the importance of technology-driven innovation and organizational change. The positive impact of IT on innovations, as well as IT shaping business success, emphasizing its impact on productivity and financial performance, was also identified by Melville et al. (2004).

In the context of digital innovation, Westerman, Bonnet, and McAfee (2014) examined the factors driving digital leadership, linking IT investments to firm agility and innovation. Similarly, McKinsey & Company (Isenberg et al., 2021) highlighted the importance of IT resilience, emphasizing cybersecurity, regulatory compliance, and emerging technologies as key performance indicators.

Publicly available IT performance indicators provide a standardized means of assessing organizations' technological capabilities. Several studies have explored the use of patent activity (Criscuolo & Verspagen, 2008), cybersecurity incidents (Anderson & Moore, 2006; Gordon & Loeb, 2002), and research & development (R&D) expenditures (Bloom et al., 2012; Hall & Lerner, 2010) as measures of IT performance.

Various frameworks have been developed to assess IT's impact on business performance. One of the reasons behind this is that the digital transformation of industries has accelerated the need for standardized IT performance indicators, allowing for cross-industry comparisons and benchmarking (Vial, 2019). Particularly, Weill and Ross (2004) introduced IT governance frameworks that align IT strategy with business objectives. Besides, Van Grembergen and De Haes (2009) engaged with IT Governance Implementations and their Impact on Business, while Weill & Ross (Weill & Ross, 2004) highlighted the importance of integrating IT-specific metrics into corporate assessments as part of their research dedicated to IT governance models.

Based on the literature research, the author identified that no paper exists that summarizes all key performance indicators (KPIs) that are IT-relevant and that might serve for evaluation of business performance. Therefore, this study provides a structured approach to evaluating IT-driven business performance by consolidating academic research with publicly available data sources. The findings aim to support both researchers and practitioners in assessing IT's role in corporate competitiveness, risk management, and long-term sustainability.

2. Methodology

The paper is part of the researcher's broader doctoral research that focuses on establishing a controlling mechanism through which it is possible to evaluate companies' business performance based on publicly available information. The author has already researched and identified different categories of publicly available indicators that support the business performance evaluation of companies. The identified KPI categories are Customer, Employee, Environment, Financial, Innovation, Learning, Product and Sales.

To identify and research the publicly available IT KPIs, the author leveraged, especially, the recent academic studies and industry reports. The primary inquiries were conducted, especially regarding

the Web of Science and Scopus databases. The secondary search was then performed over the digital database of the Czech National Library of Technology. This database has access to 106 electronic resources (other databases), among which are, e.g., Scopus, Web of Science, Springer Compact, Wiley Online Library, or ScienceDirect. This database of the Czech National Library of Technology enabled the author to do more complex and extensive searches than going through individual databases. The tertiary exploration was executed over the public internet to identify industrial reports.

The research results are presented in Chapter 3, where the public IT KPIs are presented. For each KPI, the author provided a description with an explanation of how it supports the business valuation and the potential public source from which the KPI might be taken. The final selection was based on three main criteria: (1) the indicator's relevance to IT performance and business value, (2) its availability through public sources, and (3) its recurrence in academic and professional literature. This approach ensured that the chosen KPIs are not only theoretically grounded but also practically observable and comparable across firms. The author continually went through the analysed studies and reports up to the point where there was no new information based on which an additional IT KPI might have been identified.

3. Research

In the rapidly evolving landscape of information technology, evaluating organizations' performance requires reliable and publicly available indicators. Businesses are increasingly dependent on IT-driven strategies to maintain a competitive edge, innovate, and ensure security and compliance. Therefore, defining robust IT performance indicators is crucial for both academic research and business management (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014).

The identified publicly available IT KPIs are presented in the subsequent paragraphs.

3.1 Cybersecurity Incidents

The frequency and severity of cybersecurity incidents serve as negative KPIs, highlighting security vulnerabilities in an organization's IT infrastructure and overall cybersecurity measures. Such incidents can lead to significant financial losses, reputational damage, and operational disruptions (Kamiya et al., 2021). The security incidents might have many forms of impact on the organizations as well as on external parties, e.g., data leakage of customers' personal data, the ability to provide contracted services (such as the provision of an e-shop), or the value of a company on the stock market. The fundamental metric of this indicator is the number of security incidents, which, however, might be extended by additional metrics such as time to detect/respond/remediate, which might be shared, e.g., press releases or during the presentation of lessons learned (Perera et al., 2022).

Exemplary sources of public information:

- News website – especially IT/cyber-related media
- Company press releases / published lessons learned on e.g. conferences
- Information on dark webs published by the attackers themselves

3.2. IT-Related Fines from Regulators

The occurrence and size of IT-related fines imposed by regulatory bodies serve as critical KPIs for assessing an organization's compliance with legal and regulatory standards. Frequent or substantial fines may indicate deficiencies in IT governance and compliance frameworks, potentially leading to

financial penalties and reputational harm. One type of fines also touches the previous indicators, since selected companies are mandatory to disclose cybersecurity incidents to the determined national authorities. Monitoring these fines helps evaluate the effectiveness of an organization's security governance, risk management and compliance strategies (Achuthan et al., 2024; Quach et al., 2022).

Exemplary sources of public information:

- News websites
- Regulatory bodies' websites
- Industry reports

3.3. Data from Open-source Intelligence

Open-source intelligence (OSINT) is a method that describes the collection and analysis of publicly available information on a certain party (company, person, etc.). Organizations leverage OSINT practices to proactively identify and mitigate potential threats, understand market trends, and gain insights into competitor strategies. Monitoring the scope and effectiveness of OSINT activities can measure an organization's situational awareness and strategic preparedness. Exactly as companies leverage OSINT for their own protection or detect information on their competitors, the external parties might apply the same approach to evaluated companies. Since OSINT is only a mean to gather data, assessors/organizations still need to determine what information they will seek and monitor – e.g. number of company accounts (based on domains in email addresses) with leaked credentials. Overall, the data from OSINT might indicate how much companies protect their assets against cyber threats (Böhm & Lolagar, 2021; Yadav et al., 2023).

Exemplary sources of public information:

- OSINT tools and platforms
- Information on dark webs

3.4. Compliance with IT Standards

Adherence to established IT standards is an essential KPIs indicating robust IT governance and risk management practices. Compliance with standards or regulations such as ISO/IEC 27001, GDPR, or coming NIS2 demonstrates an organization's commitment to maintaining high information security and data protection standards. Regular compliance assessments help identify areas for improvement and ensure ongoing adherence to regulatory requirements (Huygh et al., 2022). Except for some exceptions, organizations naturally do not allow external parties to analyze the current state of IT. Therefore, an organization might publish a “certification” that they are compliant with a certain standard and that they successfully passed the certification process.

Exemplary sources of public information:

- Publicly proclaimed information – e.g. on company web, conferences, LinkedIn, webinars
- Company annual reports

3.5. Technology Partnerships

Technology partnerships are a key KPI reflecting a firm's commitment to innovation through external collaboration. By engaging with research institutions, startups, or technology firms, organizations gain access to specialized knowledge, accelerate innovation, and strengthen digital capabilities. The

number and impact of such partnerships indicate how effectively a company leverages external expertise to enhance competitiveness and support strategic IT objectives (Kilubi, 2015; Zhang et al., 2024). The technology partnership brings valuable information to external parties that the technological vendors see potential in the particular company and that such companies passed checks of the technological vendors which are a natural part of each partnership establishment.

Exemplary sources of public information:

- Publicly proclaimed partnership activities – e.g. on company web, conferences, LinkedIn, webinars, hackathons
- Technology news websites

3.6. Patent Activity

Patent activity is a critical KPI reflecting a company's innovation and commitment to research and development. The quantity and quality of patents filed and granted indicate efforts to protect intellectual property, enhancing market position and competitive advantage. Studies have shown that patents are valuable indicators of inventive activity and can positively influence a firm's market valuation. Moreover, patent citations are often used to assess innovations' technological impact and economic value. From a finance perspective, the patents usually bring certain financial income for the registered company, which is a positive indicator for the external parties as well (Marchesini & Valentini, 2022). This indicator is, however, affected by the fact that usually only specialized or large companies in the IT field undergo the patent process, which results in limited usability of the indicator.

Exemplary sources of public information:

- Patent offices and databases
- Company annual reports
- Publicly proclaimer patents - e.g. on company web, conferences

3.1.7. Usage of Emerging IT Technologies / IT Trends

The extent to which an organization adopts emerging IT trends, such as artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, and cloud computing, serves as a KPI, reflecting its commitment to digital transformation and innovation. Proactively adopting these technologies can lead to improved operational efficiency, enhanced customer experiences, and the development of new business models. Tracking the integration of emerging technologies provides insights into an organization's strategic direction and adaptability in a rapidly evolving digital landscape (Akter et al., 2022; Fineberg, 2025). Investment and onboarding of the emerging technologies might potentially also indicate the financial stability of the company. The reason is that if companies are short on a budget, they would cut the potential investments that do not bring direct value to the business.

Exemplary sources of public information:

- Publicly proclaimed innovations – e.g. on company web, conferences, LinkedIn, webinars
- Descriptions of technologies in public job descriptions
- Technology news websites
- Industry reports

3.8. Research and Development Expenditures

Investment in research and development is a pivotal KPI indicating a firm's dedication to innovation and future growth. Higher research and development spending is typically associated with developing new products and services, enhancing competitive positioning. From the metrics perspective, organizations do not commonly reveal the amount of money invested in the entire research. However, companies might publish spending on specific projects or at least describe the specific research, which might indicate its size even without the provision of specific costs. For external parties, this indicator might again advise on the financial and technological health of the company (Pereira & Mohiya, 2021).

Exemplary sources of public information:

- Publicly proclaimed information – e.g. on company web, conferences, LinkedIn, webinars
- Descriptions in public job descriptions
- Company annual reports

3.3. Subsequent Research Activities

As the research is part of the broader doctoral research, the subsequent activities will focus on determining the weights of the various KPI categories using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method. This approach aims to provide an additional understanding of the relative importance of each KPI category in evaluating business performance. By leveraging AHP, the weights of KPI categories will be determined, which will result in the establishment of a complex scoring method applied within the comprehensive framework for assessing the business performance based on publicly available data.

Another important area of the subsequent steps is quantification of the indicators. To ensure practical applicability, each KPI shall be accompanied by clear guidance on how it can be measured. For instance, patent activity may be quantified through the number of patent applications, granted patents, citations, or revenue generated from licensing. Similarly, the “Use of Emerging IT Technologies” can be assessed by tracking public mentions of specific technologies (e.g., AI, blockchain) in company reports, job postings, or technology partnerships.

Moreover, the author’s strong assumption is that not all indicators will always be possible to gather, and thus, only a subset of indicators will always be used for the business performance evaluation. This is relevant for the IT KPIs as well as all other categories of KPIs.

After completion of the above-mentioned steps – weights calculation, quantification, exceptions handling – the author will apply the mechanism on selected companies to validate and fine-tune it. Since the mechanism calculates only with publicly available data, there is no need to request any information from the evaluated companies. The author will select more companies to ensure that the mechanism providing sufficiently comparable results.

4. Conclusion

Integration of IT into business strategies is not just about operational efficiency but also about fostering innovation and maintaining a competitive edge, which has then implications for business performance. Therefore, it would be unwise to leave the IT perspective out when evaluation the performance or business health. The author of this research identified in total eight KPIs that might

be publicly available and that might be leveraged for the evaluation. Among these identified KPIs are cybersecurity incidents, IT-related fines from regulators, open-source intelligence (OSINT), compliance with IT standards, technology partnerships, technology patents, usage of emerging IT technologies, and research and development expenditures.

These indicators offer a window into the organization's technological health and impact on business success. Cybersecurity incidents reveal how well a company protects its digital assets, while IT-related fines highlight the cost of non-compliance. OSINT showcases the firm's engagement with open-source technologies, and compliance with IT standards reflects its adherence to best practices. Technology partnerships can drive innovation, and patents are committed to protecting intellectual property. The use of emerging technologies indicates adaptability and R&D expenditures demonstrate a focus on long-term growth.

While the identified IT KPIs offer valuable insights into technological performance and innovation, they also present several limitations. These include inconsistent data availability, lack of standard definitions, and sensitivity to industry or company context. Some indicators may be misinterpreted without proper background, while others, like R&D spending, may only show impact over time. Additionally, companies may selectively disclose favourable data, and the focus on quantitative metrics can overlook important qualitative factors such as IT culture or leadership. These challenges highlight the need for careful interpretation and complementary analysis when using these KPIs for business evaluation.

As a next step, the author will apply the AHP method on the identified IT KPIs which will lead to identification of weights of the IT KPIs.

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USING ARCHIMATE TO ALIGN AGILE SOFTWARE PRODUCT MANAGEMENT WITH ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE

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Enterprise architecture; software product management; agile; modeling; ArchiMate; metamodel

Abstract

In today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, Software Product Managers (SPMs) increasingly rely on agile methodologies to drive software product development. However, the dynamic nature of agile practices can sometimes lead to a misalignment between tactical product initiatives and an organization's long-term strategic objectives. Enterprise Architecture (EA) can offer guidance to bridge this gap. This paper aims to (i) investigate the role of Enterprise Architecture in Agile Software Product Management, and (ii) design a model that supports Software Product Management tasks and activities within the broader Enterprise Architecture of a company. A research method based on Conceptual modeling, Ontological mapping, and ArchiMate modeling, was employed. The paper presents an SPM Metamodel, provides its translation into ArchiMate language, and introduces an SPM ArchiMate Model that serves as a blueprint for integrating SPM into standard EA practices. Ultimately, this research argues that Agile Software Product Management is not only a distinct discipline but also an essential component of Enterprise Architecture.

1. Introduction

Over the past few decades, Agile methodologies have transformed the software development process. Principles such as collaboration, customer-centrism, and the ability to adapt to changes have gradually found their way into all aspects of what was previously very rigid environment (Hoda et al., 2018). However, the unpredictability that can accompany agile practices sometimes results in product roadmaps that do not fully align with an organization's strategic objectives (Trieflinger et al., 2021). This may be problematic for Software Product Management (SPM) professionals who aim to deliver high-quality software products designed with a company's business goals in mind (Prisca Amajuoyi et al., 2024; Tkalich et al., 2022). In such cases, a robust framework is needed to harmonize agile execution with long-term strategic planning.

In this context, Enterprise Architecture (EA) could offer guidance. Enterprise Architecture is recognized as a strategic discipline that provides holistic blueprints encompassing an organization's

business strategy, processes, and IT infrastructure (Greefhorst & Proper, 2011). By integrating Agile SPM with the company's strategic goals through EA, it should be possible to ensure that a software product does not deviate from the organization's strategic direction.

Since no research papers related to the area of interest were identified, we can assume that the relationship between Enterprise Architecture and Software Product Management is unexplored. To address this gap in knowledge, this paper investigates the role of Enterprise Architecture in Agile SPM. The main focus is on bridging the gap between strategic planning done at the organizational level and technical execution achieved through agile software development processes. The aim is to design a model that supports Software Product Management tasks and activities within the broader Enterprise Architecture of a company.

To guide this investigation, this paper proposes the following research questions (RQs):

- RQ1: What is the relationship between Enterprise Architecture and Agile Software Product Management?
- RQ2: How can the gap between strategic planning and technical execution be closed?

The remainder of this paper is organized in the following way. Section 2 describes research method. Sections 3, 4, and 5 research the relation between EA and Agile SPM. The study's key findings, contributions, threats to validity, and conclusions are contained in Section 6.

2. Research Method

A specific methodology was needed to achieve the objectives of this study. The methodology utilized (see Table 1) was developed by Buchalcevova (2019) for the purposes of her research.

Table 1. Research method

Order	Activity	Method	Output
1	Problem identification	Literature review	Problem definition
2	SPM metamodel development	Conceptual modelling	SPM metamodel
3	Mapping definition of SPM metamodel elements to ArchiMate language	Ontological mapping	SPM metamodel to ArchiMate Mapping
4	SPM ArchiMate model development	ArchiMate modelling	SPM ArchiMate model

Source: (author), (Buchalcevova, 2019)

Four sequential activities are proposed, and for each activity, used method and expected output were defined. Firstly, the problem was identified. The literature review process revealed a knowledge gap in the area of interest. Specifically, no scientific literature that would explore the relationship between Enterprise Architecture and Agile Software Product Management was identified. Secondly, the SPM metamodel was developed using Conceptual modelling. Thirdly, the mapping of the SPM metamodel to the ArchiMate language was defined. Lastly, the SPM ArchiMate model was constructed.

The individual activities are described in detail in the following sections.

3. SPM Metamodel Development

In order to align SPM with the Enterprise Architecture, it was necessary for these two distinct concepts to be described, mapped, and integrated. ArchiMate was utilized for this purpose. ArchiMate is a well-known language that is used for Enterprise Architecture modelling (Buchalcevova, 2019). No definition, however, that would describe the SPM in this language exists. For this reason, it was necessary to create a metamodel of the SPM in the ArchiMate.

ArchiMate language differentiates several layers (Buchalcevova, 2019). These are Business, Application, Technology, Strategy, Physical, Implementation, and Migration. For the purposes of this paper, only the Business layer was required, as the research focused on aligning SPM tasks and activities – which predominantly lie in the business domain – with EA.

As a first step in modelling SPM with ArchiMate, a general description of the SPM needed to be considered. The ISPMA's (Kittlaus, 2022) Software Product Management Body of Knowledge (SPMBoK) provides a well-established SPM framework that consists of activities, tasks, responsibilities, methods, tools, and artifacts relevant to software product management. This framework is frequently referenced in other studies (e.g. Springer & Miler, 2022; Maglyas et al., 2017; Adenuga et al., 2015) and, due to its comprehensive nature, was chosen as a foundation for this research.

Tasks and activities are primary concepts in SPMBoK. Some of these tasks and activities are directly performed by software product managers (i.e., they are responsible for them), while others are carried out by different stakeholders, with product managers being either accountable or consulted. For the purpose of the metamodel creation, the following concepts were defined based on the SPMBoK:

- **Outcome.** A result that is achieved by executing a specific task, or activity.
- **Task.** An action that needs to be done in order to achieve one or more outcomes.
- **Activity.** A structured set of tasks performed to achieve a specific outcome.
- **Role.** A set of responsibilities and expectations associated with a specific position or function.
- **Artifact.** An output, document, or tool resulting from an activity.
- **Tool.** A resource, software, or method used to support tasks or activities.

As per Buchalcevova (Buchalcevova, 2019), the initial metamodel was developed using classical UML class diagram notation. Figure 1 showcases the SPM metamodel build based on information gathered from SPMBoK. The metamodel describes the basic relations between different SPM concepts (and their multiplicity).

Figure 1. SPM metamodel

Source: (author)

4. Mapping the SPM Metamodel Elements to ArchiMate Language

The mapping of the SPM metamodel elements to ArchiMate was done using version 3.2.0 of the language. After the initial analysis of the SPM metamodel, it became clear that an unmodified version of the language could be used. The majority of the components were modelled using Business layer elements of the ArchiMate. One component was modelled using the Motivation element. These are coloured yellow, and violet, respectively.

Table 2 describes the translation of the SPM metamodel elements into the ArchiMate language. Additionally, Table 3 describes relationship mapping.

Table 2. Mapping of the SPM metamodel elements to ArchiMate

SPM metamodel element	ArchiMate element name
Task	Business Function
Activity	Business Process
Role	Business Role
Artifact	Business Object
Tool	Business Function
Outcome	Outcome

Source: (author), (Buchalcevova, 2019)

It is worth noting that both Tool and Task were mapped to the ArchiMate element Business Function. While this may seem redundant, Task represents the action performed, whereas Tool denotes what supports that action. Their shared representation aligns with ArchiMate semantics, with context and relationships clarifying their distinct roles.

Table 3. Relationship mapping

Relationship name in SPM metamodel	From SPM metamodel element	To SPM metamodel element	ArchiMate relation	ArchiMate relation notation
performs	Role	Activity	Assignment	
performs	Role	Task	Assignment	

Relationship name in SPM metamodel	From SPM metamodel element	To SPM metamodel element	ArchiMate relation	ArchiMate relation notation
consists of	Activity	Task	Composition	
produces	Activity	Artifact	Access	
achieves	Activity	Outcome	Realization	
produces	Task	Artifact	Access	
achieves	Task	Outcome	Realization	
supports	Tool	Activity	Serving	
supports	Tool	Task	Serving	

Source: (author), (Buchalcevoa, 2019)

No issues or limitations were encountered during the mapping process. The elements of the SPM metamodel were fully mapped to their counterparts in the ArchiMate language. Additionally, the relationships of the SPM metamodel were translated into ArchiMate relationship notation. As a result, it was possible to depict the entire SPM metamodel using the ArchiMate, as showcased in Figure 2.

Figure 2. SPM metamodel modelled in ArchiMate

Source: (author)

5. SPM ArchiMate Model Development

The instantiation of the SPM ArchiMate Model was done based on the knowledge contained in the ISPMA's (Kittlaus, 2022) SPMBok. In total, SPMBok identifies 15 core activities, divided into three groups, that fall under the responsibility of software product managers. These activities cover the primary business responsibilities software product managers hold concerning both the product and the organization. Figures 3, 4, and 5 showcase the aforementioned activities and all their relations, divided according to their groups.

Figure 3. SPM Strategic Management activities modelled in ArchiMate

Source: (author)

Figure 4. SPM Product Planning activities modelled in ArchiMate

Source: (author)

Figure 5. SPM Product Strategy activities modelled in ArchiMate Source: (author)

As established by the SPM metamodel, each SPM activity is composed of one or more tasks. These are illustrated in Figures 6, 7, and 8, which contain tasks related to Strategic Management, Product Planning, and Product Strategy, respectively. Tasks are modelled as ArchiMate Business Functions. No other elements are depicted in these figures – the Outcomes, Roles, Tools, and Artifacts are usually related to the entire group of tasks and, therefore, are only showcased in Figures 3, 4, and 5.

Figure 6. SPM Strategic Management tasks modelled in ArchiMate

Source: (author)

Figure 7. SPM Product Planning tasks modelled in ArchiMate Source: (author)

Figure 8. SPM Product Strategy tasks modelled in ArchiMate Source: (author)

6. Discussion and Conclusion

6.1. Discussion

The motivation for this research was to describe the relationship between Enterprise Architecture and Agile Software Product Management. To achieve the stated goal, there was a need to translate SPM into a language that would be compatible with an EA. ArchiMate was chosen for this task.

As part of the research, an SPM metamodel was developed based on the ISPMA's (Kittlaus, 2022) SPMBok using classical UML class diagram notation. This metamodel was then translated into ArchiMate elements, forming the basis for the SPM ArchiMate model. The resulting model consists of 15 activities, 71 tasks, 17 artifacts, 17 outcomes, 9 tools, and 1 role, all modelled using either Business layer or Motivation elements. The model demonstrates that SPM components can be effectively represented and organized within the EA framework using ArchiMate.

Based on the SPM ArchiMate model, we can conclude that Agile Software Product Management is a specific component of an Enterprise Architecture. This conclusion follows from how the model embeds SPM practices into standard EA constructs. Activities are modelled as Business Processes, tasks as Business Functions, and roles and outcomes are explicitly linked, mirroring the actor → process → value pattern common in EA. For illustration, a strategic goal such as “Expand into the SME market” can be linked via the model to *Market Analysis* activity and *Market Segmentation* task, which produce outcomes that inform product decisions. These structural correspondences ensure traceability from enterprise capabilities to product-level tasks. As such, the model not only aligns Agile SPM with EA but confirms that it constitutes an integral part of it.

6.2. Threats to Validity

Framework by Wohlin et al. (2012) was utilized to assess the validity of this study. **Internal Validity:** The entire research process, from its inception to the SPM ArchiMate model development, was conducted by only two researchers. Further independent evaluation of this work is necessary. **External validity:** This study translated a concrete SPM definition into ArchiMate elements and developed an SPM model grounded in the ArchiMate language. The conclusions drawn are context-specific and may not be applicable to all organizations. **Conclusion validity, Construct validity:** The SPM ArchiMate model was built using the knowledge contained in the ISPMA's SPMBok. The use of a single source of knowledge about SPM could introduce bias and affect both the conclusion and construct validity.

6.3. Conclusion

This research has determined that there is a strong relationship between Enterprise Architecture and Agile Software Product Management. By integrating SPM into EA using the SPM ArchiMate model developed in this study, organizations can better align their strategic objectives with their software product development efforts, as elaborated in Section 6.1.

Future research in this area should focus on validating the model in real-world settings. This could be done using case studies or other research methods. Doing so should make it possible to identify potential areas for improvement and indicate which parts of the model need adjustment.

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ANNEX

STATEMENT OF THE PUBLICATION ETHICS AND PUBLICATION MALPRACTICE

IDIMT's Publication Ethics and Publication Malpractice Statement is based, in large part, on the guidelines and standards developed by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE).

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Authors must notify us of any conflicts of interest.

Authors must identify all sources used in the creation of their manuscript.

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